

Locally tested interventions

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Summary

Task 2.4, led by CES, focuses on the development and testing of interventions within the nine BIOTraCes case studies. It involves evaluating existing strategies operating in transformative niches, particularly in their capacity to address indirect drivers of biodiversity loss within multisectoral and multi-stakeholder contexts. The task explores enablers and disruptors identified across the cases and reflects on how they can be leveraged or mitigated. It also examines successful and failed practices implemented by partners and stakeholders. A central component of the task is the co-learning process, which includes critical reflection on the capacity to pluralise, politicise, embed, and empower interventions - especially in relation to indirect drivers of change. These reflections are grounded in workshops conducted with societal partners and stakeholders. Furthermore, the interventions are tested on the ground through collaborative experimentation, monitoring, and evaluation in regional events involving a broad array of actors, such as local authorities, practitioners, activists, associations, grassroots initiatives, producers, consumers, researchers, and enterprises. The key output of this task is Deliverable D2.4: Analysis of locally tested interventions.

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1 How this Deliverable was created

Task 2.4 of the BIOTraCes project focuses on *locally tested interventions* - intentional, place-based actions or processes that aim to address the structural and institutional barriers ("lock-ins") hindering biodiversity regeneration. These interventions are not understood as isolated events or technical outputs, but as co-created and embedded strategies, designed and implemented by societal partners - sometimes in collaboration with, and sometimes observed by research teams - to challenge dominant ecological imaginaries, governance arrangements, and development models.

Deliverable 2.4 represents a collective synthesis of these locally grounded interventions. Coordinated by the Centre for Social Studies of the University of Coimbra (CES-UC), this deliverable pursues two complementary objectives: (1) to understand the transformative potential of these interventions in shifting institutional trajectories related to biodiversity regeneration; and (2) to identify enablers and lock-ins that affect their replicability, scalability, and long-term impact.

Task 2.4 was grounded in the recognition that transformative interventions emerge not from abstract models but from situated knowledge, relational processes, and long-term engagements with local actors. This understanding guided both the analytical focus and the collaborative process behind deliverable 2.4.

In this sense, Deliverable 2.4 is also an exercise in reflexive documentation - not only recording the interventions and their outcomes, but also reflecting on the processes, collaborations, and methodological learnings that shaped them. To construct the deliverable, CES followed a participatory and multi-layered pathway that unfolded in several stages, explained below.

1.1 The process

To support the implementation of Task 2.4, CES designed a methodological pathway to assist research partners in evaluating and testing strategies conducted by the societal partners or designed in partnership with them. This pathway included:

- **workshops** to establish a shared understanding of key concepts and to reflect on common challenges through cross-case discussions (M27–M30);
- **focus groups** or other qualitative moments with societal partners and stakeholders to identify possible lock-ins in each case study (M29–M30);
- **bilateral meetings** between the CES team and the research partners to address sensitive points and prepare for feedback workshops (M30–M31);
- **feedback workshops** (M32–M33) for sharing with societal partners and stakeholders the main findings from the focus groups;
- **systematisation of collective discussions** among research partners (M28–M31), aimed at synthesising cross-case insights, identifying common trends and challenges.

This methodological pathway - particularly the sequence of focus groups, bilateral meetings and feedback workshops - was not prescriptive but rather offered a shared structure that could be adapted to each case's specific dynamics. The premise was that testing interventions required not only observing activities in the field, but also engaging

in qualitative, dialogical moments of reflection with both local actors and consortium research partners.

The main methodological tools applied throughout this process are presented below:

1.2 Workshops on key concepts

After a series of preliminary meetings to outline how the deliverable would be developed, CES convened a **first workshop** (M27) - **Workshop on Intervention** - with all research partners to explore the conceptual and methodological implications of testing interventions. These methodological discussions were crucial, since the definitions of “intervention” and “testing” would directly shape methodological choices for case analysis, action plan design, and the overall evaluation framework. This collective session was a space to refine the shared understanding of what it means to “test” an intervention in the context of BIOTraCes - not in a laboratory sense, but as a relational process of learning and evaluation, co-produced with those directly involved in implementing change. The shared framework that emerged from this workshop provided the foundation for the following activities.

Figure 1 Miro Board of the First Workshop

Source: CES Team, 2025

A **second workshop** (M28) - ***Alignment, focus group & feasible scripts*** - built directly upon the previous Intervention Workshop (M27) and focused on the methodological preparation for the qualitative phase of Task 2.4. This session aimed to collectively assess the feasibility of applying focus groups in different local contexts and to identify needs for adaptation. During the workshop, participants discussed the objectives of the focus groups, tested the draft script, and reviewed the relevance of the proposed questions for their specific cases. This exercise helped clarify the methodological flexibility of Task 2.4, confirming that while focus groups were the suggested format, other qualitative approaches could also be adopted when better suited to each context.

A third key moment was the *Workshop on Development and Testing of Interventions* (M30, Live Consortium Meeting in Hungary), which focused on the collective systematisation of insights emerging from all case studies. During this session, research partners jointly reflected on the patterns observed across contexts, identifying common shortcomings, recurrent trends, and innovative strategies. The discussion also contributed to consolidating methodological learning within the consortium, refining shared analytical lenses and strengthening collective understanding of how interventions functioned across diverse territorial and institutional settings. While these reflections helped inform the feedback workshops regarding common lock-ins at the European level, their primary aim was to capture transversal lessons and build a comparative view of the testing process within BIOTraCes.

Intervention workshop: collective perceptions on testing

The conclusions drawn from this first moment of discussion - the *Workshop on Intervention* - confirmed that across cases, interventions were collectively perceived as strategies sometimes pre-existing, sometimes co-designed – initiated by societal partners, or co-implemented together with research partners –, and always situated within territorial realities. These processes, while diverse, consistently foregrounded collaboration, stakeholder engagement, and systemic transformation as foundational principles. Partners adopted mainly the Participatory Action Research (PAR) approach, emphasising interventions as material, relational, and symbolic acts aimed at challenging dominant paradigms and fostering long-term structural change.

Testing interventions in Task 2.4 was broadly understood as an iterative, participatory and reflexive process that seeks to observe, adapt and learn from interventions in real time - rather than applying a rigid evaluation of success or failure. Testing is seen as part of a long-term process of co-creation, embedded in dialogue with societal actors, and attentive to the situated nature of change in each territorial context.

The collective reflection that emerged during the Intervention Workshop allowed the consortium to articulate a nuanced understanding of what interventions signify within the framework of Task 2.4. Far from being seen as isolated acts or externally imposed

solutions, interventions were understood as situated, relational, and deeply embedded in the social-ecological realities of each territory. From this process, six interconnected dimensions of intervention were identified as central across the cases.

First, **co-creation and collaboration (1)** emerged as a foundational principle, with interventions taking shape through horizontal partnerships between academic and non-academic actors. This mode of engagement ensures not only the contextual relevance of the strategies but also fosters shared ownership of the change process. Interventions were also recognised for their **transformative ambition (2)**, aiming not simply to resolve immediate problems but to unsettle entrenched power dynamics, reconfigure governance structures, and shift dominant ecological imaginaries. Equally important was the emphasis on **multi-stakeholder engagement and dialogue (3)**, with interventions serving as entry points for broader conversations among diverse actors, including those traditionally excluded from decision-making processes.

Another key dimension was the recognition of **flexibility and unpredictability (4)** as inherent qualities of the intervention process. Interventions are not linear or predefined; rather, they unfold iteratively, adapting to shifting dynamics, feedback, and the emergence of new alliances. In this sense, interventions were not only about action but also about cultivating the conditions for action—opening space for collective reflection, repositioning, and mutual learning. **Knowledge production and framing (5)** was also highlighted as a crucial element: interventions do not merely apply knowledge but actively generate it, giving rise to new vocabularies, imaginaries, and ways of understanding and navigating socio-ecological transformation.

Finally, interventions were consistently grounded in **action-oriented strategies (6)** - practical, place-based experiments such as community workshops, land practices, and artistic performances that allowed for concrete testing and observation of their effects. These initiatives were not ends in themselves but acted as catalysts for dialogue, learning, and future possibilities. Together, these six dimensions reflect the rich diversity of approaches taken by partners, and the shared conviction that transformative change must be enacted through a combination of material practices, symbolic gestures, and political imagination.

Towards a Shared Understanding of Testing

The Intervention Workshop also contributed to developing a shared understanding of what it means to “test” an intervention within this framework. Rejecting narrow notions of impact measurement or binary success/failure, partners adopted a view of testing as a qualitative and relational process, where researchers and societal actors together reflect on the relevance, effects, and potential of interventions.

When research partners reflected on what kind of change was expected from the interventions, both pragmatic goals and transformative hopes were identified. On the one hand, partners aimed to improve governance relations, support local actors, and embed new practices. On the other hand, many hoped to challenge dominant imaginaries, shift institutional norms, or create space for systemic alternatives.

When asked what exactly they were testing in their interventions, partners highlighted a combination of practical and strategic dimensions. Rather than evaluating predefined outcomes, most cases sought to observe how interventions could broaden participation, engage more diverse groups, and resonate with community needs and aspirations. A strong focus was placed on the capacity of interventions to foster trust, dialogue, and new alliances — whether through formal governance changes or more subtle shifts in perception, relationships, and institutional practices. Signs of transformation were therefore not limited to policy outcomes but extended to qualitative indicators such as the appropriation of regenerative practices, the emergence of alternative imaginaries about land and biodiversity, and the continuation or scaling-up of ideas by the community itself.

The workshop also helped consolidate shared approaches to testing. Across the cases, partners adopted iterative and relational methods that emphasised dialogue, adaptability, and reflection. These included participatory workshops and focus groups as spaces for co-analysis, pilot actions to explore interventions in situ, and process-based evaluations that focused less on measuring results and more on understanding enabling conditions, emerging barriers, and the affective or symbolic impact of interventions. Ultimately, testing was seen as a collective exercise in learning and adjustment — an opportunity to make visible what works, what doesn't, and what might still be possible. This orientation towards reflective experimentation, rather than rigid assessment, was key to shaping the understanding of intervention that informs Deliverable 2.4.

Partners also collectively recognised that subjectivity and unpredictability are inherent in this type of testing: some impacts may only become visible over time or in unexpected ways. Rather than seeing this as a weakness, partners embraced it as part of the reality of working with complex social-ecological systems.

Ultimately, the workshop reaffirmed that testing interventions is a social and political process, centred on reflection, learning, and adaptation. This understanding has shaped the way Deliverable 2.4 was constructed: not as a catalogue of finished successes, but as a composite portrait of transformative experimentation across territories.

Focus Groups

As part of the methodological framework for Task 2.4, research partners implemented qualitative moments — most commonly focus groups or participatory workshops — to support the testing of interventions through dialogue and joint reflection with societal actors. To assist with this process, CES shared a proposed script, offering a structured yet adaptable framework. The guiding questions were conceived to explore three interrelated dimensions: local understandings of transformative change, the indirect drivers of biodiversity loss, and the alignment between territorial strategies and broader policy frameworks. Together, these orientations ensured that each case could critically examine its own intervention in relation to both contextual specificities and overarching governance dynamics.

The focus group discussions invited stakeholders to articulate their own understandings of change and to assess how their practices and collaborations were contributing to transformation within their territories. Exchanges unfolded around the collective efforts

undertaken for biodiversity regeneration and the ways in which local organisations, institutions, and communities had worked together to shape these processes. Stakeholders were also asked to trace the roots of current environmental challenges, identifying how historical, social, and economic dynamics had deepened pressures on local ecosystems and discussing how institutions had sought to address such constraints. Finally, attention turned to the policy landscape, as participants considered whether existing regional, national, and European frameworks were enabling or constraining regenerative strategies, and how local actors were navigating these tensions in practice.

The questions proposed in the script encouraged reflection on stakeholder engagement, knowledge co-production, governance shifts, community-level changes, and broader transformative potential. Beyond gathering perspectives, these discussions enabled societal partners to explore how interventions interacted with regional or national policy frameworks, how socio-economic and cultural dynamics influenced biodiversity outcomes, and how enabling or disruptive conditions emerged during implementation. Collectively, these discussions generated valuable qualitative insights into both the transformative aspirations and the practical constraints shaping each case.

This qualitative approach was designed to enable each case to reflect in-depth on its intervention strategies, not just through internal project dynamics but in conversation with local stakeholders, ensuring that the testing phase remained grounded, situated, and open to adjustment.

Bilateral Meetings

CES offered **bilateral meetings** (M30-31) to help partners design and plan the qualitative component of their testing process with societal partners - particularly in view of organising focus groups and preparing subsequent feedback workshops. These sessions included discussion of focus group methodology, question framing, and strategies for fostering honest, critical, and constructive dialogue with societal actors in the context of the feedback phase.

These preparatory meetings were instrumental in enabling each team to adapt the suggested approach to their territorial realities while maintaining overall methodological coherence across Task 2.4.

A **second round of bilateral meetings** was offered to research partners (M31–M32), building on the outcomes of the focus groups. These optional sessions provided tailored support for refining the interpretation of focus group results and preparing for the upcoming feedback workshops. Beyond synthesising key insights, the meetings served as a space to revisit sensitive or complex issues that had not been fully addressed in the focus group. They also allowed teams to reflect more strategically on how to frame and facilitate their feedback workshops, focusing on surfacing shortcomings in local strategies and identifying actionable pathways for improvement.

Feedback Workshops

Building on the bilateral exchanges with the CES team, research partners were encouraged to translate the insights from focus groups into participatory feedback

workshops with societal partners. These workshops were conceived as opportunities for societal and research partners to reflect jointly on preliminary findings and to identify, in a collaborative manner, areas where strategies could be adjusted or strengthened.

Beyond validating the information gathered, the workshops aimed to provide a constructive space for refining local work plans - particularly by addressing shortcomings or tensions revealed during the process. The extent to which partners implemented these suggestions varied, as feedback workshops remained voluntary and context-specific. Where carried out, partners reported that these dialogues proved highly valuable - not only for enriching the content of the deliverable, but also for reinforcing alliances, addressing latent disagreements, and opening up new avenues for co-learning and shared strategy-making within their territories. Ultimately, they also contributed to the refinement of prospective co-designed action plans.

1.3 Systematisation of collective discussions: a cross-case analysis

This session marked the culmination of the iterative learning cycle within Task 2.4, bringing together the threads from the previous focus groups and bilateral meetings to collectively identify patterns and shared lessons across cases.

A strategic milestone for Task 2.4 was the consortium workshop held in Hungary (May 2025), which served as both a space for shared learning and a pivotal step toward consolidating the project's collective findings. Beyond exchanging updates, the workshop's purpose was to generate cross-case insights that could inform not only the individual case reports but also the integrated conclusions of Deliverable 2.4, particularly the synthesis' section.

By bringing together diverse case teams in a structured, interactive format, the workshop aimed to identify patterns, tensions, and transferable practices across very different territorial contexts. This cross-case analysis was essential for grounding the discussion sections of each case study in a wider analytical framework, ensuring that local reflections were positioned within the project's overall narrative on the enablers, disruptors, and practical realities of implementing regenerative governance.

The workshop was structured as an **interactive, three-part exercise** designed to foster reflection on the first three key themes of D2.4, namely:

- (1) evaluation of strategies in action,
- (2) enablers and disruptors,
- (3) failed and successful practices.

Partners first engaged in **individual reflection** on their own case experiences. Then, in mixed small groups, they discussed the following guiding questions:

- What trends can we identify across the cases?
- What are the key shortcomings or limitations observed?
- Which innovative or inspiring strategies stand out?

The plenary session brought together these reflections through **visual mapping** (see below) and synthesis, producing a collective map of trends, shortcomings, and

strategies - with the explicit purpose of supporting the writing of the “conclusion” section of D2.4.

Some of the **main cross-case trends** highlight the persistence of structural and procedural barriers that continue to limit the transformative potential of biodiversity governance. Among the main cross-case tendencies identified were:

- **Persistent underrepresentation of marginalised groups in biodiversity governance.** Despite ongoing efforts to create inclusive spaces, dominant groups remain overrepresented in participatory arenas, while those most affected by environmental degradation continue to have limited influence over decision-making processes.
- **Tension between policy commitments and the operational constraints of implementation.** While case strategies were often well aligned with stated governmental or EU priorities, bureaucratic and systemic barriers limited their expansion - revealing a persistent gap between the political rhetoric of support and the institutional capacity to deliver it.
- **Entrenched procedural obstacles.** Across contexts, partners pointed to the weight of administrative routines and regulatory procedures that hinder experimentation and slow down the integration or scaling of local innovations. These procedural constraints are closely linked to top-down and opaque governance structures.
- **Predominance of top-down and opaque governance structures.** Across several contexts, decision-making remains centralised within public institutions, with limited transparency and few mechanisms for downward accountability. This reinforces hierarchical relations and undermines community trust and ownership.
- **Value of variety across cases.** The range of contexts and approaches was seen as a productive basis for shared learning, generating richer comparative insights and a stronger collective understanding.

These trends underline a central paradox of regenerative governance: while there is broad rhetorical commitment to inclusivity and innovation, the structural and procedural realities across cases make such goals difficult to realise in practice. The persistence of marginalised groups’ underrepresentation is not simply a participation gap but a reflection of systemic inequalities in access to time, resources, and influence.

Moreover, the disconnect between supportive policy language and its operationalisation exposes a critical need to address the “implementation gap” that stalls change at the territorial level.

As for **key shortcomings**, partners particularly mentioned:

- **Structural and procedural barriers that continued to block innovation.** Administrative hurdles and entrenched systems prevented innovative practices — particularly those associated with environmental and community-based approaches — from flourishing or expanding. These obstacles are not only operational but cultural, reflecting long-standing governance routines that prioritise economically oriented initiatives over ecological or social experimentation, and that value control and compliance more than trust and learning.

- **Prevalent centralisation in public governance.** Decision-making by public bodies remains predominantly opaque and top-down, with limited downward accountability. This lack of transparency reduces local ownership and hinders collaboration with community actors.
- **Contradictions in biodiversity governance.** Policies that support community action in theory often undermine it through restrictive or fragmented implementation. This exposes a disconnect between the normative ambitions of biodiversity policy and its practical enactment on the ground, creating an “implementation gap” that weakens trust and continuity in local initiatives.
- **Difficulty for marginalised actors to engage meaningfully.** Participation barriers were often attributed to lack of time or resources, yet such explanations risk oversimplifying a deeper issue: the limited recognition of underrepresented actors’ agency and legitimacy by public bodies and organisations. The persistence of these asymmetries drains representativeness and reinforces power hierarchies in local decision-making on regenerative strategies.
- **Disconnection between biodiversity goals and social justice concerns.** Environmental objectives are frequently pursued without acknowledging the social dimensions of biodiversity loss — particularly how inequality, gender relations, and power asymmetries shape both its causes and its impacts. As a result, regeneration efforts risk reproducing existing exclusions rather than challenging the social, political, and cultural lock-ins that continue to block transformative change.
- **Gender and intersectionality gaps.** Gender was frequently perceived as an external requirement associated with EU agendas rather than as a locally embedded concern. Women’s and minorities’ contributions to biodiversity regeneration remained undervalued, and intersectionality was rarely used as an analytical framework for understanding how social inequalities may shape environmental processes and trajectories.
- **Fragility of community-led initiatives.** While community-led strategies are recognised as vital for regenerative governance, they remain highly dependent on project-based funding, lacking consistent institutional support or long-term sustainability mechanisms.
- **Limited impact of individual research roles.** Researchers expressed concerns about their isolated capacity to influence systemic change, pointing to the need for collective advocacy, coalition-building, and closer alignment between research, policy, and community practice.
- **Knowledge and data gaps on gender equity.** In many contexts, gender-related information was not considered relevant for biodiversity governance. The absence of gender-sensitive data limits both the visibility of women’s contributions to adaptation and mitigation strategies and the evaluation of how regenerative strategies align with gender equity frameworks.

The shortcomings identified are tightly interlinked, painting a picture of change processes that are heavily constrained by the interplay between structural inequalities and occasional institutional inertia. Barriers to innovation are not only technical or financial, but embedded in governance routines that resist deviation from established patterns. This dynamic also limits the engagement of marginalised actors, as their exclusion is perpetuated by the same material constraints and lack of institutional recognition that regenerative strategies have seldom managed to address. The contradictions between enabling policy narratives and restrictive practice highlight the fragility of relying on

policy alignment as a lever for transformation. Finally, the recognition that systemic change exceeds the influence of individual researchers underscores the importance of collective learning spaces and advocacy, long-term institutional commitments, and cross-sectoral alliances as key conditions for transformative governance.

Finally, the workshop surfaced some **innovative strategies**:

- **Creative and inclusive engagement approaches.** Partners emphasised the importance of developing participatory methods capable of reaching actors who are usually distant from institutional processes. Artistic, narrative, and experiential formats were seen as effective ways to lower barriers to participation and diversify the types of knowledge recognised in decision-making.
- **Co-governance models.** Emerging partnerships between public institutions and civil society actors are experimenting with more horizontal forms of governance. These arrangements seek to distribute responsibility and decision-making more evenly across sectors, challenging the persistence of top-down procedures and stimulating new forms of collaboration grounded in shared goals and mutual accountability.
- **Proposal for basic income.** The proposal of a basic income was discussed as a provocative idea to address structural inequalities that affect participation, though such economic solutions only partially respond to the deeper issue of recognition and agency. It would be a means to give people - especially those in more precarious situations - more time and stability to engage in governance and community-building efforts. It also reflects a growing awareness that participation in regenerative governance depends not only on material resources but also on the social and institutional conditions that allow people to act as recognised agents of change.
- **Recognition of multiple forms of knowledge and agency.** Several discussions underscored the need to expand what counts as legitimate expertise in biodiversity governance — including local, practical, and gendered knowledges that have often been marginalised. This shift implies valuing co-learning processes and translating community experiences into actionable insights.
- **Translocal collaboration.** Innovative connections emerged between community actors, researchers, and public institutions, as well as among territories facing similar challenges. These collaborations have been crucial for identifying transferable practices and building solidarity-based networks that transcend administrative and geographical boundaries.
- **Transformative research practice.** Researchers increasingly recognised themselves not merely as observers but as participants in co-producing transformative practices. This evolving stance signals a shift toward approaches that blend knowledge generation with facilitation, dialogue, and strategic engagement for systemic change.
- **Networks of mutual learning.** Collaborative platforms connecting community actors, researchers, and institutions have shown potential to build shared understanding, peer learning across territories, and concerted actions. Although still emerging, these networks help generate collective proposals and reinforce solidarity among actors navigating similar challenges.
- **Commitment to social cohesion and collective learning.** Strengthening community participation and cohesion has been identified as a key condition for long-term regenerative change. These processes foster trust, mutual recognition,

and incremental shifts in social imaginaries — outcomes that are essential for embedding regeneration within local cultures.

- **Ecological literacy and intergenerational learning.** Educational and community initiatives have begun to promote ecological literacy across generations, fostering a sense of care for local ecosystems. By strengthening people’s connection to land and biodiversity, these actions contribute to the social foundations of regenerative transitions.

The strategies identified point to a gradual shift from reactive adaptation to proactive systemic intervention. These emerging tendencies underscore that regeneration relies as much on new governance relationships and learning processes as on technical or financial solutions. Together, they signal a move toward more participatory, reflexive, and interconnected forms of transformative practice across the consortium.

Collective key points on cross-case analysis

Figure 2 Summary of collective key points

Source: Lucas dos Santos and Belizário, 2025

Overall, the in-person workshop in Hungary provided an important shared space for reflection, confirming many of the challenges and opportunities already emerging in individual cases, and reinforcing the importance of **iterative, participatory learning processes** within the BIOTraCes project.

The following section presents the case-specific contributions submitted by each research partner, following a shared analytical structure. These contributions describe the interventions examined in each territory, as well as reflections on their transformative potential, enabling and constraining factors, co-learning processes, and remaining challenges.

Each case-study contribution is presented as submitted by the respective partner institution, which retains full responsibility for the accuracy and analytical coherence of its content. CES has provided feedback to support alignment with the expected analytical scope of D2.4; however, the decision to integrate suggested revisions remains entirely with each partner.

Together, these analyses form the empirical and conceptual foundation of Deliverable 2.4, offering a collective portrait of transformative experimentation across the consortium.

2 Locally tested interventions

2.1 BC3 Case Study: Spain

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2.1.1 Short presentation of the case

This case study is about schoolyard greening in public pre- and primary schools in Vitoria-Gasteiz, Basque Country, Spain. In concretely, it follows the implementation of a municipal schoolyard greening pilot program initiated in 2022 as a response to a manifesto of the municipal associations of parents demanding healthier and greener school environments a year earlier. Administrated by the city hall and funded by different public grants, as of 2025 14 schoolyards have been renaturalized through replacing hard with permeable, natural surfaces such as sand and soil and the adding of plants, trees, and lawn areas, nature-based play equipment and garden elements. The process was implemented through a collaboration of different municipal entities and, in various degrees, together with the educational communities of the different schools.

We zoom on to the various challenges derived from a combination of complex administrative structures and responsibilities scattered across different institutional entities, plural imaginaries attached to the role of schoolyards in education and urban planning, and a diversity of actors involved and needed to make the schoolyard interventions successful. Concretely, we disentangle the various challenges, but also potentials of the current program structure together with multiple actors to envision a schoolyard greening program in future, where biodiversity and equity are at center of the design, use, and narrative of the schoolyard.

The overarching research objective is to explore to what extent green schoolyards can be part of a wider transformative change towards a (bio)diverse society. For this end, we applied a participatory action research approach in close collaboration with BIOTraCes societal partner, the Environmental Studies Center of Vitoria-Gasteiz, and the municipal Department of Education leading the program. We further collaborated with representatives of the local educational communities, the main recipients of the schoolyard transformations.

We draw on document and archival data as well as field- and workshop-based data. We found that the municipal schoolyard greening pilot program in its current state of governance, regulations, and broader paradigms contains both barriers and opportunities for transformative, nature-inclusive change in the social-ecological system. The multi-level governance embedded in two high impact sectors of urbanism and education with their past and current dominating paradigms is still based on unequal (power) relations resulting from rigid and complex top-down structures and furthering human disconnection from nature. However, as actors active in schoolyard transformations navigate these barriers, their initiatives can be considered challengers to current lock-ins.

Overall, we encountered throughout our research a relational narrative shift. This can be seen, e.g., in a variety of actors' stronger emphasis on care as being learned and practiced in the schoolyards towards other peers and nature. This shift implies longer participatory processes potentially enabling a deeper integration of educational communities into the decision-making process in a way that their concrete needs are at the heart of the schoolyard transformations. The process of learning between institutional and educational community actors has already led to an adaptation of processes to overcome previous shortcomings, leverage current program successes and respond to the educational communities' feedback. This shows potential for an adaptive co-governance form in future of municipal schoolyard greening.

This document examines locally tested interventions, by evaluating strategies in action, identifying enablers and disruptors and failed and successful practices, and examining the process of co-learning and testing of interventions.

2.1.2 Evaluation of strategies in action

Introduction

The case study of a municipal schoolyard greening program in Vitoria-Gasteiz results from a demand from the city's diverse educational communities to improve local school environments that got translated into a municipal pilot program run by different city hall departments. The case study hence offers multiple insights into strategies that are both bottom-up and top-down driven and that resulted in an increasing degree of learning between institutional and educational actors. Many of the strategies aim to navigate institutional dynamics, including inertias, to allow a continuation and stabilization of the biodiversity innovation over the long term. The case study's institutional focus results from its embeddedness into public sectors of education and urban planning and the strong involvement of the local administration - also in the form of BIOTraCes societal partner.

Current strategies in action

Current strategies in action can be clustered in (i) bottom-up strategies implemented by the educational communities themselves and (ii) top-down strategies implemented by institutional actors, mainly municipal, involved in the public education system. This distinction results from the governance structure of schools in which local administrations are holding most of the decision-making power over transformations of the school environments. Bottom-up strategies have then been put in place when institutional processes are blocked by institutional inertias or inaction. Most of those aim for changes at the scale of the respective educational community. Top-down strategies refer to those actions taken by institutional actors trying to steer change from the inside. Lastly, (iii) refers to strategies that are targeting educational paradigms, such as top-down and classroom-based teaching, and offer tools for a better integration of the biodiversity innovation into the school day-to-day.

1. *Bottom-up strategies to improve local school environments*

Strategies initiated by the municipal educational communities included a collective demand in the form of a manifesto in 2020 to the city hall that called for an improvement of the municipal public schools in the context of the covid-19 pandemic. This was accompanied by different initiatives at the school level, such as fundraising campaigns (e.g. through crowd funding or selling products) to carry out diagnostics of the schoolyards by specialized companies or to employ architects to make new designs for improving the school environment. Some schools further implemented their own projects, e.g., school gardens or nature-based play equipment. These interventions, while contributing to a biodiversity increase in the schoolyards, were mostly framed towards new ways of environmental education (e.g. nature-inclusive and project-based learning), to increase inclusivity and gender equality, and to achieve higher agency of the local schools regarding the governance of their own schoolyards. While the manifesto has been taken up by the city hall in the form of a municipal pilot schoolyard greening program, individual efforts of educational communities have not received sufficient support from the municipal administration. For instance, many of the schoolyard plans drafted by architects hired and financed through the schools were not taken into consideration for the interventions implemented under the municipal pilot program.

2. Top-down strategies targeting institutional dynamics and governance

The creation of the schoolyard greening pilot program was driven by two municipal entities: the CEA (BIOTraCes' societal partner) and the Department of Education. Strategies for program implementation employed by technical and administrative staff of those two entities involved the setting of criteria for the concrete schoolyard interventions (e.g., allowing only nature-based interventions and prioritizing marginalized public schools through the selection of a vulnerability criteria). As the pilot program is approaching its end (as of 2026), current strategies are targeted towards achieving a city hall decision regarding the transformation of the pilot into a long-lasting program through dedicating a fixed annual budget. This includes creating a systematic strategy for greening all schoolyards in Vitoria-Gasteiz, which can be presented to the next municipal government after the elections in June 2027. Until then, concrete strategies involve a bricolage approach to funding to enable a stabilization of the program, i.e. funding is derived from different grants and organizations across different policy scales, often also with differing requirements. It further includes scientific accompaniment, studies, and results for generating evidence of the program importance (through collaborations with research projects, e.g. BIOTraCes, and research groups of the local university). Collaborations between the CEA and the University of the Basque Country also extend to offering training programs for teachers that address the lack of knowledge about how to integrate nature into teaching and summer schools aimed at a wider audience interested in schoolyard greening. Institutional actors are further adapting the program structure and implementing a first test in a school between 2026-28 in which a whole academic year will be dedicated to the participatory process with the respective educational community. Funding has so far been only secured for the participatory process (and the design). However, having a ready to implement design will also add pressure to local policy makers to vote in favor of a prolongation of the schoolyard greening program.

3. Strategies addressing the use of schoolyards in day-to-day education

This set of strategies aims to provide concrete tools to integrate renaturalized schoolyards into curricular and extracurricular activities. Consequently, these strategies aim to generate both awareness and knowledge of how to make better use of the transformed schoolyards, so that the biodiversity innovation can unfold its full potential. This is driven by various actors, such as the city hall, the local university, and different

societal organizations working around issues of environmental education. The aim here is to overcome top-down and nature-disconnecting ways of teaching, moving towards a whole-school approach. The university, for instance, is organizing an accredited course for teachers on how to use schoolyards in natural science teaching. The city hall organized various conferences bringing together a broad range of actors to exchange knowledge with other school renaturalization programs and teaching. And lastly, local environmental organizations prepare and share teaching materials and activities for teachers to implement in curricular activities.

Transformative potential

Both bottom-up strategies and those aiming for a better integration of schoolyards in the day-to-day learning are responding to dominant education paradigms that follow a top-down and classroom-based learning model, furthering social inequity (e.g. through gender-exclusive schoolyard design). These strategies aim for shifting this paradigm towards a learning approach that enables all children to interact and engage with nature - fostering relational values (Lange 2018). Here, schoolyards should be understood as both outdoor classrooms and social-ecological relational spaces. Over the long run, this holds the promise to create stronger ties between the younger generations and nature needed to advance towards a nature-inclusive society. The manifesto written by the local educational communities further exemplifies an intent to achieve a higher degree of agency over decisions regarding the urban school environments, envisioning a co-governance of the schoolyards that more closely involves the educational communities.

Strategies by institutional actors, while not specifically targeting dominant paradigms, are used to navigate lock-ins and barriers resulting from institutional governance structures and current dominant paradigms. As those strategies are a response to a social demand, they can be seen as a process of trust and alliance building by engaging, collaborating and learning from the educational communities. One of the overarching aims of these strategies is to create green schoolyards especially for marginalized schools and to achieve a full embedding of the biodiversity innovation in the municipal governance context by forging a political decision of a fixed annual budget. Political support for schoolyard greening, although only a small factor, can contribute over the long term to fighting educational segregation by putting more attention on the public schooling system. It further contributes to generating more social-ecologically nurtured spaces and processes that are deepening human-nature relationships.

Indirect drivers

The structural conditions these strategies are responding to concern, first, the privatization of education driving educational segregation in the Basque and Spanish context and resulting from an increasingly underfunded public education system. By targeting those public schools that are most marginalized, one goal is to increase attractiveness of public schools by improving public educational infrastructure. Especially those top-down implemented strategies aim to generate more awareness of local policymakers regarding the importance of green and healthy school environments, also with the goal to put public education locally as a priority in urban planning.

Second, some strategies are targeting cultural resistance towards new modes of teaching that results in part from an increasing domination over and disconnection from nature, also driven by an extinction of experience that attests a decrease of opportunities

allowing for close contact and interactions with nature, especially for younger generations (Soga & Gaston, 2016). For instance, resistance towards more project-based and embodied learning is coming from a culturally deeply embedded neoliberal, i.e. competition-based, paradigm that sees education as a way to increase human capital and following economic growth. In that paradigm, project-based learning is seen as a barrier to successfully compete in standard-based international assessments, such as PISA (Delaune, 2019). Cultural resistance can also be found in the narrative of urban nature that sees nature as something aesthetic, ordered, and instrumental to human well-being (Angelo, 2021). In this narrative, engaging with nature, e.g. playing with soil or plants, climbing on trees, observing insects attracted by flowers, is perceived as dirty or risky. Daily interactions with nature may hence overcome this nature-detached paradigm.

Despite the pilot program's specific focus on vulnerable schools, social inequalities nonetheless currently limit the success of the biodiversity innovation. This is due to the fact that a big responsibility of implementing further action, using, and maintaining the schoolyard falls on the educational communities, and specifically the parents' associations. Consequently, schools with a high percentage of marginalized children tend to have a less active parents' association as parents face many structural barriers, such as socio-economic pressures, time constraints, and limited institutional support, that exclude them from engaging in schoolyards greening and other educational activities. Consequently, those most profiting from the schoolyard transformation in the program's current governance context are those schools where parents act as driving agents. Over the long run, this risks an increase of the gap between marginalized educational communities and those attended by families with a higher socio-economic profile.

Scalability

A main factor for the municipal schoolyard greening pilot program to arise in Vitoria-Gasteiz is the policy exchange with other cities, including the learning from other initiatives. Barcelona's *patis x clima* (schoolyards for climate)^[1] with a project framing focusing on heat vulnerability, initiated in 2017, has often been mentioned as a reference point by various actors. Following, Vitoria-Gasteiz' schoolyard program can already be seen through the lens of *policy mobilities* (see e.g. Temenos and McCann), that is, a replication of best practices implemented elsewhere adapted to the local context. Schoolyard-specific funding schemes on the regional (Basque) level were further supportive of this policy exchange, as they enabled the city to implement their own initiatives. The city has thereby been always connected to other practitioners or experts, e.g., through the organization of conferences or the participation in Spanish and international city networks.

The pilot program's processes of scalability can also be found in the municipal context of Vitoria-Gasteiz: First, over the course of the pilot program more educational communities have been participating in the schoolyard transformation than initially planned. Second, schools participating later on in the program were or are looking for inspiration at those schoolyards already implemented, hence enabling an exchange of experiences locally. Third, some schools are developing and implementing initiatives bottom-up where possible, e.g., by adding more nature-elements to the schoolyard or by drafting programs and projects, such as the care program in which children take care over the schoolyard and the younger ones. Fourth, technical administrative staff has been able to continuously prolong the pilot program beyond its initially set end date, by finding and

securing more funding sources through a bricolage approach that builds on a scattered funding approach through diverse funding bodies (Neidig et al., 2024).

The scaling of the biodiversity innovation at the municipal level contributed to an increasing communication between institutional and educational community actors, e.g., in the form of feedback sessions, which allowed for an adaptation of the pilot program to its earlier successes and shortcomings, indicating an improved partnership between top-down and bottom-up actors. As a result of this, a long-term participatory process is in preparation that aims for a co-creation of a roadmap for future action together with educational communities that will be presented to local policymakers.

Symbolic framing

In all these strategies discussed above, we observed throughout the research an increasing emphasis on the relationality of schoolyards, e.g. through fostering care, stewardship, and inclusivity. This relationality can be seen in demands from educational communities, specifically parents, for more embodied and nature-inclusive learning approaches in the public education system, but also in goals formulated by the societal partner CEA to increase ecological literacy through e.g. a citizen science program aiming to bring urban resident closer to their surrounding biodiversity. Strengthening relational values in the broader discourse and narrative attached to schoolyard greening holds one of the biggest transformative potentials, as it helps generate over the long-term deeper human-nature relationships (also through alliances between diverse social and ecological communities). For instance, the first harvest of apples in one of the renaturalized schoolyards generated a visual image of children engaging with “newly discovered” biodiversity - through harvesting fruits. This image was shared across local media outlets^[2].

Conclusion

Strategies applied in this case study entail to different degrees potential for transformative change. Bottom-up strategies, such as the collective manifesto, were the initiating driver of this biodiversity innovation. It was successful in kickstarting a municipal pilot program, however, over time the driving actors shifted towards institutional actors. With this shift, bottom-up processes lost some momentum, and as for now, are less active in pushing forward new transformative ideas. Consequently, the rapid institutionalization of the social demand for improved learning environments then translated into a top-down managed program. Nonetheless, there is an ongoing process of co-learning that leads to a better understanding of educational communities’ needs and following an adaptation of the pilot program structure. It now depends on the city hall decision to prolong the municipal schoolyard greening program to fully embed the biodiversity innovation in the municipal governance context. Over the course of BIOTraCes, a relational turn in the overall schoolyard greening narrative could be observed, which indicates an opening up that may lead to an increasing pluralization within the biodiversity innovation.

2.1.3 Enablers and disruptors

Introduction

The municipal schoolyard greening program is an initiative by the municipality. In its current governance configuration, different city hall departments are responsible for its design, implementation, and maintenance. The biodiversity innovation hence shows a high degree of institutionalization which allows us to gain deep insights into barriers, such as institutional inertia, but also opportunities resulting from a long-established institutional awareness and support of nature-inclusive initiatives in the urban and peri-urban areas (Neidig et al., 2022, 2024).

Enablers

The municipal schoolyard greening program is embedded into broader governance frameworks that have been favorable for the program design and implementation. At the national level, the new Spanish education law introduced in 2022 has for the first time put sustainability at the center stage, recognizing in its preamble that “given that the education system cannot be oblivious to the challenges posed by global climate change, schools must become a place of stewardship and care for our environment”^[3]. It openly invites experimentation with the curriculum and encourages innovative practices such as community service learning. The legal framework in the education system has therefore opened up unprecedented space for pedagogical innovations such as learning in nature in green schoolyards and recognizes community service learning (such as for instance maintaining urban green spaces or growing food for the community in community gardens) as equally important to passive learning in the classroom (Ó Riada et al. forthcoming).

This policy change on the national level has further been accompanied by schoolyard-specific grants released through the regional government, that funded most of the schoolyard greening pilot program at the municipal level. While in the Basque context these grants mainly aim at promoting physical activity in an inclusive way, there is a recognition that greening schoolyards can be a way to achieve this, by offering more diverse opportunities for play than the competitive sports played on paved schoolyards. This context of “schoolyard greening-favorable” governance enabled other municipalities to implement holistic programs, such as Barcelona’s patios for the climate program. These “best practices” from other cities served then as an inspiration in the local context and delivered assurance to local policymakers for the concrete program implementation.

These favorable political visions on the European, Spanish and Basque level certainly factored into the local city hall decision to implement a pilot program which proves at least political awareness, here in form of a political consensus, for the importance of improved school environments and willingness to dedicate municipal budget for a pilot program. This momentum opened up by multi-scale policy visions has been used by niche innovators inside local administration that know how to navigate the inner-institutional dynamics (with its barrier and lock-ins). This enabled the creation of the pilot program, also through garnering local political support and is now aiming to prolong the pilot in order to renaturalize more schoolyards (see above). Through participation in research projects, university campaigns, and conferences institutional actors further increase visibility for the program which may lead to a broader public supporting the biodiversity innovation.

Disruptors

Structural disruptors challenging the schoolyard greening can be found in the highly privatized education system that enhances educational segregation. Public schools are more vulnerable, also due to the lack of resources, and have to cater to a broader range of needs of marginalized children. Often, they also lack the resources to implement “extra” initiatives such as school gardens, as those initiatives tend to be driven by parents or individual teachers. While the societal partner, through the establishment of a vulnerability criteria for the school selection, is aiming to increase attractiveness of those schools, the renaturalization of their schoolyard is not sufficient to overcome educational segregation as this requires political willingness across the regional and national scale to tackle the shortcomings of the educational system in a holistic manner. In some of the schools that participated in the pilot program, the educational communities are lacking knowledge and resources to fully integrate the transformed schoolyard into the day-to-day activities and to provide the maintenance needed. This generated frustrations, e.g., for a more marginalized school, where the schoolyard renaturalization has been perceived yet another burden added to the many responsibilities of teachers at underfinanced schools (interviews fieldtrip, May 2023).

Additionally, complex administrative structures of the municipal public schools make bottom-up initiated actions difficult as the administration of those schools is scattered across different institutional entities. To be able to enact change, educational communities must have the knowledge and resources to navigate these complex administrative structures. Often, the bureaucratic hurdles are too big to overcome. This strengthens a rigid top-down approach, in which the administration is the only decision-making actor as can be seen, e.g., in the way criteria for the schoolyard greening program were set, the strict (and too short) timelines and in the implementation of the actual greening effort that is scarce of real participation of schools. The societal partner has not been able to overcome this barrier yet, also due to their embeddedness into the institutional structures being a municipal entity. While small aspects of the pilot program have been adapted, such as more planned meetings with schools throughout the schoolyard design phase, it is not yet sufficient to create a real co-governance of the schoolyards. This may risk long-term societal acceptance and support of the biodiversity innovation currently implemented top-down.

Cultural disruptors can be found in the imaginaries attached to urban biodiversity that visualize nature as clean, ordered, structured, and aesthetically appealing and as instrumental to human well-being. This can be seen in technical concepts dominating urban planning language, such as nature-based solutions (Kotsila et al., 2021), and in how urban landscaping is understood, namely often focusing on ornamental plants or cut lawns. These imaginaries attached to urban nature result from an increasing disconnection from and domination over nature (Muradian & Pascual, 2018). While this biodiversity imaginary can also be found in the schoolyard greening program, e.g. in the choice of plants, there are increasing intentions to overcome this cultural disruptor. Those include, e.g., a citizen science program to monitor and learn from urban biodiversity or nature-based activities offered to families, such as those organized by the societal partner CEA^[4].

Policy Attunement and Mismatch

This case study is embedded into the governance framework of two broader public sectors, namely the education and urban planning sector. At the European level, the

tendency of both sectors to frame guiding visions under the overarching banner of sustainability aligns well with the local schoolyard greening objectives and overall narrative. Education falls under the responsibility of the Member States, European strategies regarding education are only guidance. Nonetheless, several research partners have been referring to them to help ground local action in higher-scale policies. The GreenComp, the European reference framework for sustainability competences, for example offers support for education and training programs for lifelong learning around sustainability^[5]. As for urban planning, the schoolyard greening program fits well within the various European green strategies and visions, such as the European mission for 100 climate neutral cities, EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and the EU Green Deal, as it promotes urban planning based on low-carbon and green infrastructures, e.g. through the implementation of urban nature-based solutions. However, those urban sustainability strategies have also been criticized in previous literature for proposing rather shallow, technocratic solutions that are often claimed to be universal while neglecting local needs, histories and realities (Neidig et al., 2022). Consequently, a too close alignment with higher scale policy vision may enable the embedding of transformative action locally - however, it also challenges a pluralization of narratives attached to the biodiversity innovation by being detached from place-based notions.

At the national level, the most recent education law from 2022 integrates sustainability and project-based learning in the national education policy (Ó Riada et al. forthcoming). While this has opened up possibilities at the discursive level, teachers participating in the BIOTraCes February and April workshops^[6] reported on the difficulties and structural barriers to integrate these new policy visions in day-to-day teaching and learning activities - also because a neoliberal education paradigm has been the guiding paradigm over several decades and is still so much embedded in teaching practices and the management of schools. That is, for the national policy shift to permeate day-to-day teaching practices, a paradigm shift needs to occur throughout the many aspects influencing educational practices. Research participants mentioned the need to adapt university programs of education and to restructure the school administration, shifting from a school management approach borrowed from private companies towards one that understands schools as public democratic institutions. The new education policy promoting embodied, project-based learning experiences in nature furthermore needs to be followed up with improvements in teaching conditions for teachers, such as reducing student-teacher ratios and overall teaching hours, since these approaches require more resources from teachers and are hard to carry out with large class sizes.

In Spain, the autonomous regions have control over a large part of the curriculum content and provide funds for the local action. The government of the Basque Country has released important funding schemes that enabled the municipality to implement some of the schoolyard greening initiatives. Those funding schemes aimed for example for more inclusive schoolyards. At the same time, standards or minimum requirements for green schoolyards are still missing. Even more, some policies, such as the requirement of football and basketball pitches in every schoolyard, work against their own inclusive schoolyard funding schemes as they make it more difficult to renaturalize schoolyards through gender- and nature-inclusive design.

Conclusion

The societal partner organization is due to its institutional nature very connected to multi-level policy visions and strategies and holds the capacity to navigate and use them to enact change locally and to advance schoolyard greening. It can be said that the local biodiversity innovation has been in parts driven by its connectedness to those higher scale sustainability policies, including their overarching narratives, which ultimately also factored in for local policymakers to consent to the pilot program. However, the links to dominant sustainability imaginaries challenge locally the implementation of new, alternative imaginaries much more rooted in local needs and perspectives.

2.1.4 Failed and successful practices

Successful practices

1. Bottom-up schoolyard transformation

One of the most successful practices has been a bottom-up schoolyard transformation implemented by a local educational community in 2021-24 drawing on a close collaboration of the school community, the parents' association, and a local architecture firm. The educational community presented the idea of a schoolyard transformation to the annual municipal participatory budget contest in 2021, an initiative run by the city hall to which every resident can vote for one project presented. The project with the most votes will be realized, with (financial) support from the city hall. After a strong campaign in the neighborhood, the schoolyard initiative received most votes and became realized in 2024 after a two-year long participatory process with children, parents and teachers to co-design the new patio. The schoolyard transformation has been finished in 2024 and is now open for use for the broader neighborhood after school hours.

Many research participants referred to this project as it is considered locally a success story of creating a beautiful green schoolyard that is supported by and contributes to the creation of social cohesion within the wider neighborhood. Parts of this success story result from the project not being bound to strict and narrow nature-based requirements, like those guiding the municipal pilot program. This gave the educational community leverage to implement a holistic approach responding to the specific needs of the educational community, creating a multifunctional schoolyard with both natural elements and new play equipment. The slower paced participatory process that was stretched over two years further enabled a deep involvement of children in the collaborative designing of the schoolyard. However, it also caused quite some frustrations for those schools participating in the municipal pilot program as they expected a similar outcome. Yet funds and time dedicated to the municipal program are much more restrictive and not sufficient to generate a schoolyard transformation of the same scale as this specific initiative.

2. Spaces of dialogue

Successful practices are also those that aim to generate an improved flow of information and communication, e.g. through shared spaces of dialogue. This includes increased feedback loops and evaluations of the implemented schoolyards, e.g., in form of surveys and direct communication with the educational communities, but also research activities implemented through BIOTraCes, such as the February and April 2025 multi-actor workshops (for more details, see footnote 6).

Based on the direct feedback channel between institutional and educational community actors and on the internal evaluations by institutional actors, many aspects of the program structure have been continuously adapted. For instance, more activities with children are being implemented, such as painting the schoolyard during the design phase or crafting small models with the desired schoolyard design. This has helped to increase children's ownership over the schoolyard transformation. Further, an extra session to contrast schoolyard design with educational communities has been added, i.e., one-on-one sessions with the educational communities have been increased from two to three. Knowing that this is still not sufficient, the technical institutional staff is now piloting a new process that dedicates two years to the schoolyard renaturalization. A new schoolyard is planned for 2026-28, that involves a whole year of participatory process and trust building. While funding has been secured for the participatory process, more funds need to be found for the actual project implementation. However, having a longer participatory process with the school is hoped to exert some pressure on local policymakers to provide funds for the actual implementation.

The multi-actor workshops implemented through BIOTraCes created a space of dialogue for people to meet and discuss the current program objectives and visions, its barriers and potentials and concrete future action points. The process brought together a broad range of actors involved in the schoolyard greening, that have not interacted before (such as city councilors, technical administrative staff, teachers, parents, school employees, and researchers). Participants really appreciated having the chance to exchange and learn from other actors' perspectives. As facilitators, we often encountered the challenge to steer conversations away from things not working well towards identifying concrete action points for positive futures. Participants asked for more of those spaces of dialogue beyond BIOTraCes, especially between those that are main recipients of the biodiversity innovation - the educational communities - and those responsible for its governance - institutional actors. These spaces also helped to bring narratives of schoolyards as relational places more to the fore, as many participants emphasized the relational aspects.

Failed or less effective practices

Too holistic framing of objectives led to frustrations

The overarching pilot program's objectives have been framed very holistically – namely through a contribution of the schoolyards renaturalization to achieving inclusivity, co-education, and sustainability. While this holistic framing has been useful to connect a municipal pilot program to broader policy visions (see Section 2.2), locally this practice has contributed to generating frustrations on the site of the educational communities. This results from an unrealistic expectation of restricted funds and limited possibilities of actual schoolyard transformations' contribution to those ambitious goals stated above. The broad framing of the program as a practice of generating a positive narrative surrounding the schoolyard greening program also for public and political support hence had the opposite impact on the ground as it raised expectations of those educational communities participating the pilot program that were in part disappointed by the rather small scale of actual interventions in the schoolyards, e.g. reduced to the replacement of hard surfaces with permeable soils and the adding of trees and lawn areas. Based on past frustrations resulting from too high expectations, communication channels have been improved, also to be on the same page from the first contact with the selected educational communities until the schoolyard's opening for use. Further, the February

2025 multi-actor workshops was used to disentangle and reduce the multiple objectives attached to schoolyard transformations based on renaturalization efforts.

Critical Gaps and Missed Opportunities

The following points, among others, were raised during the BIOTraCes multi-actor workshops, when discussing the current pilot program's challenges (see below, Co-learning during the D2.4 preparation).

Lacking municipal minimum standards for green schoolyards: the creation and implementation of a municipal schoolyard greening program would have been the perfect opportunity to decide on the political level on a long-term strategy for improved school environments, by setting some minimum standards for each municipal schoolyard, including e.g. minimum percentage of green coverage and of permeable soils or a minimum number of nature-based play equipment. Having these minimum standards signed by local policymakers could have acted as a long-term commitment to the educational communities. This list of minimum standards to be fulfilled by all schoolyards is needed to fully embed the biodiversity innovation in the local context.

Too little time dedicated to participatory process: More meetings with schools would have been needed to better communicate expectations and limitations, and to enable a trust building between educational communities and institutional actors, especially with marginalized communities, such as those with a high percentage of foreign-born children. To facilitate the participation of marginalized families in the schoolyard co-design and -implementation, participatory processes must counter concrete barriers of participation, e.g., by using translators to communicate project details in different languages, and to facilitate workshop-based activities. Lacking participation of marginalized families challenges a full-on pluralization and empowerment through the biodiversity innovation.

Too narrow framing of nature-based interventions: The mere focus of schoolyard transformations through nature-based elements led to an exclusion of specific needs stated by some educational communities. For instance, some schools asked for smaller, shaded amphitheaters that could be used as outdoor classrooms. Those would have needed structures built from non-natural materials, which fell outside the nature-based requirements for materials. Having the infrastructure of an outdoor classroom, however, would still bring children closer to their surrounding biodiversity. As for now, too little shade is available in the schoolyards, as planted trees still need to grow. That is, more flexibility in terms of concrete schoolyard elements could have led to better and quicker usable outcomes, generating hence broader acceptance of the biodiversity innovation.

Closing these critical gaps could contribute significantly to transformative change by, first, embedding the innovation in the municipal agenda through enforcing minimum requirements for renaturalizing all municipal schoolyards. This will counter some of the structural barriers as it assures similar interventions in both marginalized and more advantaged educational communities, closing the gap of school segregation. Second, it enables a pluralisation and empowerment of the educational communities through implementing a longer participatory process that assures that the school's needs are really heard and taken into account. Widening the criteria for concrete interventions would further allow to better respond to specific needs and plural perspectives.

Conclusion: Lessons and Future directions

Reflection on those strategies listed above have led to an adaptation of those aspects of the pilot program's structure that could more easily be tackled. That is, in a first intent, there has been an increase in feedback sessions to contrast schoolyard designs and accompanying activities with children. While these program adaptations show good will of institutional actors, they were not sufficient to allow for full and real participation of the educational communities. Hence, the decision was made to prolong the schoolyard greening process from one to two years – starting with a participatory process for one schoolyard in the academic term of 2026/27 reaching over a full year. Here, funds are only secured for the participatory process, not for its implementation in 2027/28, which raises many risks.

The most recent decision to co-create a roadmap for schoolyard greening together with educational actors is a big step towards overcoming many of the challenges stated above. The creation of this roadmap is planned for next years and will build on BIOTraCes' efforts in creating spaces of dialogue and concrete content discussed there. This process is open to all the research participants and educational actors, with the hope to develop a concrete action plan for the "universalization" of the pilot program locally. That is, BIOTraCes' societal partners are hoping to achieve through this process the commitment of the city hall to renaturalize schoolyards of every municipal public school.

2.1.5 Co-learning

Introduction

Co-learning in the case study of a municipal schoolyard greening program happened through continuous shared reflections and interactions between the societal partner CEA, the researchers, and other relevant actors, such as other relevant institutional actors, and most importantly, actors representing the educational communities. The spaces for co-learning were those that enabled a deep listening and exchange of perspectives, such as in one-on-one meetings and interview settings, collective spaces in form of regular meetings and discussion sessions between researchers and societal partner, and in multi-actor workshops.

Co-learning as a principle and method

Co-learning has been at the heart of this case study. Informal moments of sharing experiences, impressions, and personal understandings of transformative change have thereby been the starting point to understand each other's positionality, including one's guiding values. Moments of co-learning were most inspiring when actors were able to leave their predefined roles (e.g. city hall technician, city councilors, or even the one of a researcher) and were able to speak from personal points of view. Following this observation, our aim as researchers was to create informal spaces that enabled a safe sharing of one's own worldviews and paradigms. Often, meetings in more formal settings, such as municipal office spaces, followed more formal structures – where participants spoke from the perspectives of their professional/ institutional roles. Workshops hence were conducted in a classroom of one of the schools participating in the municipal schoolyard greening pilot program. We also noticed the effects of trust building over the project duration. That is, getting to know each other on a personal level improved levels of communication and flow of information, hence an important pre-condition for co-learning.

A final observation, over the course of the BIOTraCes, initially diverging perspectives from researchers and societal and research partners became more aligned. This also results from an increased understanding of each other's perspectives, and the challenges they encounter in their day-to-day. This approximation towards each other has been essential to understand the current biodiversity innovation's potential and shortcomings. Beneficial to this process was a mixture of one-on-one interactions, smaller group conversations with a few actors and bigger group discussions, e.g. in the workshops. The conversations in smaller groups were essential for trust building between the diverse actors and researchers. This again was needed to effectively facilitate workshops and to create safe enough spaces of dialogue.

Co-learning during the D2.4 preparation

This deliverable was created based on two of the multi-actor workshops implemented under BIOTraCes, and several meetings with the societal partner CEA to directly discuss topics relevant for this deliverable. In the workshops, we implemented different methodologies to discuss the following research questions with actors representing institutional entities, other researchers and educational communities, i.e., teachers, parents and school staff. Concretely, we zoomed onto (i) Overarching objectives and visions of schoolyard greening, including their contribution to transformative change, (ii) Current program successes: How have they been achieved (e.g. strategies, actions taken)? Which factors were helpful for the objectives to be achieved (e.g. institutional support, creative freedom, social demand)? Who has been driving the success? (e.g. collaboration between different actors)? (iii) Current program challenges: Why is it considered a challenge? Which factors are blocking the objective from being achieved (e.g. lack of institutional support, of creative freedom, of political frameworks, etc.)? Who and how are actors currently working towards overcoming those challenges (e.g. concrete strategies or actions)?

The workshops were further used for scenario development, including a strategy at the individual school level and a structural change, identifying actions that can realistically be implemented to achieve the common vision and resources needed for the actions (such as (i) money, collaborations, spaces, education or training, policies and programs and (ii) actors who hold these resources and are needed to implement the action, e.g. key community partners, organizations, or experts). Then, we discussed facilitators and barriers of each scenario. We raised the following questions: Do the scenarios privilege a specific outcome at the expense of others within the vision, i.e. are there any trade-offs between the scenarios? More specifically, how do the actions consider the different profiles of the schools (with emphasis on existing inequalities between the different educational communities)? The workshops findings were further complemented with reflections from researchers' participation in internal cross-departmental meetings of local institutional actors regarding the municipal schoolyard greening program, and specific discussions that took place in regular meetings between the researchers and the societal partner. The workshops, however, were the most important space for the creation of this deliverable, as they brought together actors that would usually not meet, to reflect on successful and less effective strategies and actions currently applied, and to learn from those reflection for future interventions – under the lens of just transformative change. As facilitators of those spaces, it was sometimes difficult to lead the conversation towards identifying positive future pathways, including concrete (and realistic) actions. Because this was the first time representatives of educational communities and institutional actors had a dedicated discussion space, conversations tended to circle

around challenges and failures. As a result, one major takeaway was to understand the necessity to provide spaces to discuss negative processes to be able to advance from there towards positive futures. Those moments were also needed for trust building between the different actors participating which ultimately also enabled the emergence of new perspectives, such as one of relational schoolyards.

Based on these discussions, the societal partner is currently preparing a participatory process for next year (2026) to co-create a roadmap for a municipal schoolyard greening program together with multiple actors involved in this biodiversity innovations. The process is supposed to build on and continue BIOTraCes efforts.

Figure 3 Building a collective vision of schoolyard greening for transformative change (Multi-actor workshop, February 2025).

Co-learning dynamics in the case study

Concrete examples of co-learning that can be found in this case study include, first, interdepartmental meetings between various institutional entities involved in the schoolyard greening program to some BIOTraCes researchers were invited to. In those meetings, institutional actors shared the program updates but also challenges they were encountering in their day-to-day responsibilities in this program. Second, co-learning happened in those feedback sessions between institutional actors and educational communities in the design phase and post schoolyard transformation to understand educational actors' perspectives. Third, BIOTraCes workshop served as a pilot for a longer participatory process currently in the planning to co-develop a joint action plan in form of a roadmap for future schoolyard greening initiatives.

Moments of co-learning were supportive of aligning in part diverging visions (especially across the different city hall departments involved in the schoolyard greening pilot program). However, more spaces would have been needed from the beginning of the pilot program to dedicate time specifically to the exchange and alignment of expectations. This would have been needed also to counteract frustrations resulting from a mismatch of expectations and actual implemented schoolyard transformation. Over the course of the pilot program, and through the constructive discussions during BIOTraCes workshops, more importance has been given to the creation of those spaces. This becomes visible in the planned schoolyard intervention that dedicates a full year to a

participatory design process and through the collective process planned for the creation of the roadmap.

Despite the intentions to create more participatory spaces and improve communication between institutional and educational community actors, decision-making and overall governance settings are still organized in a top-down manner. To move towards a co-governance of urban schoolyards, decision-making power must be shifted to those actors most impacted by the biodiversity innovation. This includes the creation of more spaces facilitating the participation of vulnerable families which is needed to be able to fully pluralize imaginaries and policies related to schoolyard greening. Disagreements remain regarding the scale of the concrete renaturalization efforts, weighing up increased maintenance costs vs. actual improvements of the schoolyards, and more broadly, to what extent educational community actors should be “granted” more agency to enact change locally – considering schools being embedded into a public schooling system and hence subject to political shifts on different policy scales.

Conclusion

Over the course of BIOTraCes, more spaces of dialogue were created. These are the first steps for trust building between diverse actor groups whose relationship is also marked by power imbalances. For instance, decision-making power falls on institutional actors, educational communities are often excluded from those rigid top-down spaces. Since the initiation of the pilot program, more spaces and processes for co-learning have been implemented, first, between those institutional actors responsible for the program implementation, and second, between institutional and educational community actors to improve communication channels and share feedback. BIOTraCes workshops have helped to draw importance to those spaces of exchange of visions. While there are still power imbalances prevalent, future initiatives are aiming for a better integration of the educational communities in the governance process.

2.1.6 Testing of interventions

Introduction

This case study tested the current administrative structure of the municipal schoolyard greening pilot program and its resulting narratives, including its overarching vision and objectives and the success and barriers of current actions. Testing the “governance” intervention is needed, as the current overarching municipal pilot program structure severely impacts the state of the biodiversity innovation, namely the through renaturalization measures transformed schoolyards. Adapting the governance structure hence can help to overcome current lock-ins and injustices holding the biodiversity innovation from unfolding its full potential, including institutional inertias and social exclusion. This may support specifically processes of pluralization and empowering.

Description of the testing process

Testing happened through an iterative process. Interviews and field trips to the schools were conducted with the societal partner and educational communities. The interviews were used to identify diverging perspectives in respect to the municipal pilot program and to understand the first challenges encountered by diverse actors. Based on these interviews and other field interactions, the workshops were designed to discuss in a

multi-actor setting the shortcomings, but also potentials of the current structure of the municipal schoolyard greening pilot program (see section 6.5 “co-learning”). Several meetings with the societal partner were used to discuss in-depth perceptions and learnings from the evolution of the pilot program and the research process under the lens of transformative change.

In this process, two key questions arose: (i) What role can schoolyard greening really play in improving a highly neglected public schooling system? (ii) What are the justice and social equity implications for marginalized communities, if much of the transformative potential of renaturalized schoolyards depends on efforts of local educational communities, and especially on support from the families? Those questions were open questions that guided reflections throughout the research process yet remain in big parts unresolved. It needs to be stated that the societal partner of this case study is the Center of Environmental Studies, a municipal entity, that holds some of the decision-making power over the schoolyard governance, including the schoolyard design, the criteria used for the schoolyard transformation, the selection of participating schools, and the implementation of the participatory processes. Following, the societal partner represents one that holds power over the biodiversity innovation and its relevant actors.

Results

Stakeholder engagement and participatory processes

The municipal schoolyard greening pilot program entails from its beginning a so-called participatory process with the aim that educational communities can state their needs and wishes regarding a schoolyard transformation. Over the course of the program, and through increasing feedback from educational communities, also in the BIOTraCes workshops and field activities, an incremental adaptation of this process has happened. The first schoolyard transformations involved a participatory process with the educational communities of only two one-hour sessions, in schoolyard transformations implemented since autumn 2024 an additional session was added. Following, while the participatory process so far implemented has by no means the form of a full and real participation that was able to include more marginal educational communities sufficiently, the institutional program coordinators are showing increasing awareness. As an outcome of co-learning (especially through feedback from the ground), the whole process of schoolyards transformations is now being prolonged from one to two years. More time and resources dedicated to the participatory process is also hoped to, first, set and manage educational communities’ expectations from the beginning, and second, achieve a better involvement of schools in the design, implementation, and maintenance of the schoolyard. This will help to generate a feeling of ownership over the schoolyard – needed for transformed human-nature relationships over the long run.

Impact on policy and decision-making

While political commitment of the city hall is pending to fully embed the pilot program as a long-term initiative in the local municipal budget, with the goal of renaturalizing all the city’s schoolyards, institutional technical staff is applying diverse strategies aiming for a prolongation of the program. The fact that smaller aspects of the program have already been adjusted based on internal and external feedback shows that governance arrangements are flexible enough to be shifted. The most important sign for shifts in

institutional practices is the abovementioned co-creation of a roadmap for future schoolyard greening, together with educational actors.

Community-level changes and social perceptions

Overall, throughout our interactions with research participants, we noticed an emerging emphasis on the relationality of schoolyards, i.e., to understand them as spaces where closer human-human and human-nature-relationships are formed and nurtured. While relationality does not play a significant role in the program's current framing, it has been increasingly the center of conversations surrounding a redefinition of program objectives, such as enhancing children's caring relationships with each other and with biodiversity. It can also be hypothesized that with an increasing number of schoolyards being renaturalized, social perceptions of the biodiversity innovation increase. First biodiversity monitoring efforts through a citizen science program, in which 12 volunteers and some schools participated to observe birds and pollinators, showed a (visible) increase in urban biodiversity. This can have a positive impact on e.g. the neighborhood's perception of the program that is directly affected by the biodiversity increase.

Reflections on the intervention's transformative potential.

The question of whether schoolyard greening is indeed a step towards transforming the way we think, interact and relate with our social-ecological environments, remains contested. Some parents demand greener and healthier school environments for their children to create early-on memories in nature, while other parents still see renaturalized schoolyards as dirty and risky. Local policymakers emphasize its contributions to overcoming educational segregation and to increase urban biodiversity. Most revealing of the more structural challenges the biodiversity innovation is encountering were conversations with teachers critical of the municipal schoolyard greening program: they see schoolyards first and foremost as places of play and recreation. They shared experiences of how trees and lawns that are closed for the use of children due to needed growth periods are taking away necessary spaces for children to run. According to them, the current form of the schoolyard greening program is only a small drop on a highly neglected public schooling system that needs much more attention in many other areas than an additional tree in its yard, opening many questions around the justice implications of the biodiversity innovation in question.

Observing the evolution of this biodiversity innovation, a key transformative moment can be found in its initiation where social mobilization led to the formulation of key demands presented to policymakers. This was then taken up in a municipal pilot program for schoolyard renaturalization. However, its initial governance structure can be understood as a set-back from transformative change. Here, rigid administrative structures, top-down decision-making and lack of real participation of educational communities reinforced common lock-ins of institutional practices of local climate actions. The co-learning through ongoing reflections and feedback, however, shows promising avenues for an opening up of the governance structure to become more inclusive of those actors the biodiversity innovation is targeted to.

Open questions for future strategies

The future of this biodiversity innovation depends on the political decisions to prolong the municipal program by dedicating a fixed annual budget to enable the renaturalization of

all public municipal schoolyards. Future strategies will depend on this decision. If there is no political consensus in favor of the improvement of educational environments, strategies will need to aim for an increasing politicizing and embedding of the biodiversity innovation by achieving political awareness and commitment. There would further be the need to develop strategies that allow for actions and initiatives merely driven bottom-up by the educational communities. If the city hall decides to fully embed schoolyard greening into the municipal budget, the most urgent future strategies should aim for achieving a pluralization and a better empowerment of marginalized educational communities. Guiding questions concern here how to increase and facilitate participation of marginalized families in the schoolyard greening and its use? How to open up the overarching program narrative to become more nature-inclusive?

2.1.7 Discussion

Introduction

This case study of a municipal schoolyard greening pilot program gave deep insights into the institutional functioning, its resulting barriers and opportunities, and the multiple factors influencing its implementation on the ground. Through accompanying the program over the last three years and observation of its evolution in response to feedback and changing conditions it can be said that while there is a potential to foment and nurture deep human-nature relationships from an early age, structural barriers, such as top-down governance, lacking political commitment, connections to higher scale political discourses are still constraining transformative change. The case study drew importance to the trust-building through continuous dialogue, evaluation and learning processes and could show that local governance frameworks are flexible and can be adapted if supported by institutional niche innovators and policymakers.

Main insights from testing the interventions

Shifts in governance frameworks can occur, but they occur slowly. Especially on the local scale, institutional actors hold a certain agency to enact changes, e.g., through incrementally adapting program structures as a response to processes of learning. These small shifts can be understood as levers to exert pressures on policymakers to enact further change – if supported by a social demand and embedded into institutionalized knowledge (e.g. through participation in research projects, collaboration with the university, or through technical knowledge exchange). Examples encountered in this case study include, e.g. the manifesto turned into a pilot program, and the many ways institutional, technical staff find to prolong the program, e.g. through a bricolage funding approach or through participation in research programs. However, adapting rigid top-down governance structure towards overcoming the lack of real participation and the exclusion of historically locally rooted needs takes time and requires deep efforts of trust building and the safe sharing of one's perspectives, values, and knowledges in relation to the biodiversity innovation. It further requires honesty and transparency in formulating reachable objectives and expectations regarding the impacts, both positive and negative, a renaturalized schoolyard can have. This includes openly recognizing that schoolyard greening at the scale implied in this case study is not enough to address the many shortcomings of a neglected public schooling system. If program goals are not communicated rightly, this will lead to frustration and decreasing support from the educational communities to take part, and even more, ownership over changes of their school environments.

Aspects that showed promise or traction

The creation of spaces of dialogue through BIOTraCes research activity consisted of a first space for the multiple actors involved in this schoolyard greening program to come together and share and discuss the overarching vision attached to the schoolyard greening. This was a necessary step to understand actors' divergencies and align expectations while being realistic of current barriers. This step was further needed to start a process of trust building between institutional and educational community actors. It has now been taken up by institutional actors with the idea to create a participatory process with diverse educational actors, to define a future roadmap for municipal schoolyard greening. Again, this is an indication of a willingness to adapt, to make changes. Trust building takes time but allows for new perspectives to emerge. Those new perspectives need to be communicated effectively and convincingly to policymakers and be integrated in a framing of the biodiversity innovation, so its narrative is mirroring the plural perspectives attached to it. That is, if the relational narrative of schoolyard greening will permeate into its overarching program structure and framing remains to be seen.

Remaining challenges and areas for further work

Although the latest Spanish education law from 2022 indicates a policy shift on the national level and hence opened up a window of opportunity for shifting overarching education paradigms towards a whole school approach, there are still many barriers for its practical implications locally – also resulting from educational segregation marking the Spanish education system. Currently, educational communities are lacking the resources to adapt to and implement those changes in the day-to-day learning activities. That is, for the policy changes to effectively trickle down to the local level, concrete strategies and action plans need to be formulated and pushed forward by policy makers across the different scales, overcoming rigid administrative structures. As for now, the lacking political commitment to prolong the municipal schoolyard greening program is a barrier to the full-on integration of the national policy shift locally. It is further challenging a full-on pluralization of the biodiversity innovation locally as it undermines local perspectives and needs and challenges the implementation of the new relational education paradigm in day-to-day activities. Structural barriers to embedding a co-governance of the schoolyard and to overcome educational inequalities, as encountered and discussed in this case study, are currently the biggest constraints to transformative change.

Final messages and perspectives for future strategies

To move this biodiversity innovation of schoolyard greening to one that is fully politized, empowering, embedded and pluralized, and nature-inclusive, concrete actions must be implemented that adhere to the ambitiously framed goals of achieving co-education, inclusivity and sustainability through a schoolyard transformation. This requires, first, a political decision to provide sufficient resources needed for a long-term sustainable implementation, use and maintenance of the biodiversity innovation. It requires, second, the full-on integration of the educational communities into the decision-making process in a way that this attentive to their capacities and that allows them to enact change in their day-to-day activities without facing too many administrative barriers. For this, regular spaces of dialogues need to be created that allow for both sharing of experiences, but also for having a real voice in the final decision-making. This is needed to remake

and democratize the current schooling system towards one that puts needs of children first and foremost.

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[⁶] Workshop February 2025: with 15 local institutional and educational community actors active in the schoolyard greening program to identify program visions with a

prioritization of concrete objectives and current challenges hindering the objectives from being met.

Workshop April 2025: with 10 local institutional and educational community actors active in the schoolyard greening program to identify concrete actions and pathways to overcome current program challenges.

2.2 CER Case Study: Hungary

Authors: Bálint Sándor, Zsolt Molnár

2.2.1 Short presentation of the case

We are working together with numerous actors involved in our research topic and main goals. The Hungarian case study is about the traditional ecological knowledge of Hungarian herders, which contributes both directly and indirectly to the maintenance of biodiversity in natural and semi-natural grassland areas. For historical and cultural reasons, the Hungarian herders are a marginalised social group, whose social presence, professional recognition and needs have not been properly addressed. For this reason, the number of stakeholders included in our case study and influencing our work is higher than if we were to focus solely on a single natural or environmental issue. (2)

The basic problem of our case study is the disregard of the traditional ecological knowledge of local communities and the irresponsible and thoughtless destruction of biodiversity (in urban, rural and natural environments) at almost state level. The general trend across Europe is that the behavioural and spatial reorganisation of our society has distanced people very strongly from the knowledge of natural values and processes, and from the opportunities and needs to conserve and maintain ecosystem services essential for human life. Changes must be attempted on several levels, with external and internal restructuring having an equally important role to play in saving the herders profession. It was therefore necessary to create the herders' own demand for internal change within their society. On the other hand, the social, economic, and regulatory environment — including the dynamics of all areas of policy in general — which is largely responsible for the current situation, must be transformed. As the survival of herders' knowledge, jobs and farms is extremely fragile due to a number of negative factors, it is in our vital interest to collect and document knowledge for future generations. We conclude that we must not only work for today.

Generally speaking, in the context of our case study, political impotence and disinterest is high at both national and EU level. The herders' problems are ultimately also the problems of humanity as a whole, since, for example, the processes of drought and desertification and semi-desertification are generating pressing issues for all in terms of drinking water supply and food security. This is likely to lead to the emergence of allies and stakeholders in the future that we did not expect in the past, but which we can nevertheless count on to represent common interests.

In this chapter, we will present the strategies, enablers, disruptors, failed and successful practices, and co-learning processes that we have implemented, experimented with, or assessed in our case study so far.

2.2.2 Evaluation of strategies in action

In our case study, we are working for maintaining the biodiversity of grasslands, and other areas in the landscape, which are suitable for environmentally friendly form of livestock keeping (mainly herding) in the hole area of Hungary. Due to accelerating climate change, the natural environment changed dramatically. However, the outdated system of regulations and subsidies in nature conservation, agriculture and the general economic sector is causing increasing damage to the biodiversity of the areas we are examining. The competent decision-making sphere and the institutions entrusted with the implementation/enforcement of the regulations are doing nothing to monitor and follow the changes. The increasing drying of the landscape, the destruction of the condition of the soils, and the dramatic decrease in biodiversity no longer allow the continuous success of the agricultural technologies that have been widely used to date. Pastoralism, on the other hand, may be able to survive in these circumstances, given its methods, while also playing a role in maintaining biodiversity and reversing the current situation. Moreover, the traditional ecological knowledge of traditional herders can help to map and understand in detail the processes to which humanity must respond about nature and environmental issues. At the same time, the social background created by human society, as well as the nature conservation and agricultural regulatory environment makes it impossible for the herders lifestyle to continue. The situation threatens the loss of traditional ecological knowledge represented by pastoralists, which we absolutely need to preserve the biodiversity and health of grasslands.

We are working together with our main stakeholders, the Hungarian herders to develop the strategies presented in our case study. Although they are naturally our most prominent stakeholders in the majority of cases, numerous other actors are also involved in joint consultations with the herders and us, as well as in the development of national and regional strategies. We are working together with various researchers and research partner organizations about collecting and systematize traditional ecological knowledge, land use practices, water management methods, ecological impacts, etc. They have mainly a scientific role about data management and communication within society, and among herders. There are members of the nature conservation ranger service, other staff of National Park Directorates and other nature conservation experts working together with us and the herders. They have a strong, direct impact on pastoralism through the different type of knowledge about nature conservation grassland areas, climate change issues, and through conservation regulations to humans, livestock keeping and grassland management. They have a very important role in the life of pastoralists, but they can have quite different attitudes about herding (good or bad opinions about the herders knowledge and role in grassland management. The representatives of regulatory and animal husbandry-related infrastructure and institutions has also a very important role through requirements, bureaucracy and registration in animal husbandry, but they basically are not concerned especially about herders. We have to take into count animal health experts, as allies in the formation of hybrid animal healthcare knowledge in the future, and the preventers of dangerous livestock diseases that are emerging more and more frequently nowadays. The breeder organizations are also important to our work. The different institutions have a different role in the case study, because the herders are keeping different breeds in different numbers. Moreover, the role of those breeds are also important, which are not kept by herders, because they might have an influence to the economic background of livestock keeping. In this aspect, they have a very important, but partly indirect role in the life of herders. (1.;2.;7.)

The Hungarian case study is about the traditional ecological knowledge of Hungarian herders, which contributes both directly and indirectly to the maintenance of biodiversity in natural and semi-natural grassland areas. For historical and cultural reasons, the Hungarian herders are a marginalised social group, whose social presence, professional recognition and needs have not been properly addressed. Local, national and international regulations in the areas of land ownership, land use, animal

husbandry standards and market outlets have created a strong vulnerability in the lives of herders, which they have never tried to change due to a lack of advocacy, and which has not been recognised by policy makers and society. We are trying to use a range of instruments to launch the professional and social innovations needed to save herders' knowledge, to preserve their way of life and to reverse marginalising decision-making.

Our central aim is to maintain the knowledge and society of herders who help to conserve and partially restore biodiversity. Accordingly, our first and most important strategy is to shape herders' societies from within so that they are willing and able to recognise and influence the processes that affect them in their ecological, social and regulatory environments. We do this by strengthening their societies, building relationships and social networks, and developing target groups (eg. the women herders, young herders, herder communities with specific needs in direct areas, connecting herders with same breeds of livestock, etc.) In accordance with these efforts, the informal network of contacts with a national coverage is constantly expanding. An excellent example of social transformation is the Women Herders Group, which has been set up to represent the interests, contacts and professional opinions of women working in pastoralism. The series of Forum of Hungarian Herders (2.;4.), which aims to bring together active herders with a nationwide coverage, was launched by our research group. The aim is to inform herders on a wide range of issues, to discuss their views and to set up their own strategies on professional and social issues that concern them, including occasional involvement of external partners - other stakeholders and decision-makers. The Forums also provide an opportunity for individual organisation, as we try to invite specific target groups by topic, age, etc. The members of these specific target groups can connect among themselves in professional or social meaning much more easily, so they can experiment and explore the opportunities created among them individually. This will hopefully lead to the formation of a self-organising group of young herders in the future. Seeing positive examples, herders in many regions will start to organise themselves effectively, strengthening the representation of the profession towards the civil and professional world. The herders' community is now beginning to open up to society, and is increasingly actively seeking opportunities to build useful professional links and contacts at individual or community level.

The second step is to make the regulatory environment more professionally and economically acceptable, even beneficial for herders. This, of course, requires that decision-makers and individuals who are currently completely uninformed about the needs and importance of herders' expertise are given a thorough understanding of the current processes and situation affecting herders. The Forum of Hungarian Herders (2.;4.) provides an opportunity to invite and inform decision-makers and representatives of the bodies and institutions involved in decision-making on specific issues. In addition, we try to initiate face-to-face discussions in various other professional and social forums and conferences to bring the views of the profession and decision-makers closer together. For these occasions, we have initially invited herders to represent their professional interests and demonstrate their knowledge and its relevance, with our guidance and supportive presence. The method is proving to work, as more and more herders are being asked to participate in such events or to make a professional presentation. The general awareness and motivation of the decision-makers towards herders is still low and further long-term efforts will be needed in this respect.

A key task for the future is to inform society as widely as possible about the importance and value of the work of herders. In parallel with promoting change in the decision-making environment, it is also worthwhile to influence the immediate economic and occupational environment of herders. In addition, raising the awareness of the broader civilian community is equally important to ensure the supply of new generations of herders, as it would create the right regulatory and employment

environment to attract new herders into the profession. The educational environment in Hungary currently seems unsuitable for training herders, so this is likely to be a long-term process of planning and implementation. (2.;4.)

As the survival of herders' knowledge, jobs and farms are extremely fragile due to a number of negative factors –like ecological changes, the occupational environment, economical factors, regulation background in conservation and livestock keeping, global social disinterest, etc. -, it is in our vital interest to collect and document knowledge for future generations. We conclude that we must not only work for today. A collection of knowledge that archives both the traditional and innovative knowledge of herders can ensure the survival of the profession even if the current economic and societal environment does not allow for the straight lineage of the Hungarian herding profession. For this reason, a wide-ranging collection of details of the practical work of herders in relation to livestock and the natural environment is being carried out at national level. In this respect, it is entirely up to the herders themselves to share with us and to record and pass on to their descendants. (4)

Generally speaking, in the context of our case study, political impotence and disinterest is high at both national and EU level. The herders' problems are ultimately also the problems of humanity as a whole, since, for example, the processes of drought and desertification and semi-desertification are generating pressing issues for all in terms of drinking water supply and food security. This is likely to lead to the emergence of allies and stakeholders in the future that we did not expect in the past, but which we can nevertheless count on to represent common interests. The identification of partners is slow because we need to continuously map the interest groups that are immediately emerging to address the problems that are becoming more and more socially recognised. What seems encouraging is that a number of stakeholders representing other sectors and interests are seeking to bring solutions similar to our own research, with some overlap, into the public regulatory and implementation sphere.

In fact, our activity is trying to prepare for several different possibilities for the future. We seek to influence herding communities, society, the agricultural sector and the policy environment in ways that mitigate negative impacts on biodiversity. On the other hand, we will prepare as far as possible for the long-term problems that are bound to arise as biodiversity and climate change. In this way, a society undergoing radical change will have access to the knowledge that can help it survive in the face of adaptation challenges, regardless of our current achievements.

2.2.3 Enablers and disruptors

The basic problem of our case study is the disregard of the traditional ecological knowledge of local communities and the irresponsible and thoughtless destruction of biodiversity (in urban, rural and natural environments) at almost state level. The general trend across Europe is that the behavioural and spatial reorganisation of our society has distanced people very strongly from the knowledge of natural values and processes, and from the opportunities and needs to conserve and maintain ecosystem services essential for human life. Traditional or innovative local communities capable of restoring and maintaining biodiversity have become marginalised groups. There are no such local policies or initiatives that actively support the recognition of these local societies (such as Hungarian herders) and their traditional ecological knowledge. EU-level initiatives are typically unsuitable for specifically helping the marginalized society of Hungarian herders in this regard. The legal harmonization of Hungary in this regard has not occurred, and there is currently no political will to do so. In addition, governments do not attach importance to maintaining biodiversity or even ecosystem services and basic human needs. It has now reached the point where the country's food insecurity is looming, the problem of drinking water supply is becoming increasingly serious, and the rapid acceleration of human made 'desertification' through subsidised agriculture and other activities is increasing. About the

identified structural constraints, land-based support schemes, the out of date conservation regulatory frameworks and subsidies, and general land use subsidies have the most direct affect in the destruction of biodiversity in our country during use of the landscape.

It can be concluded that the traditional and innovative strategies of local communities are not taken into account by trends and decisions at regional, national and EU level. The regulatory system is extremely inflexible and slow, and is unable to absorb proposals and solutions from the local community level. It cannot of course support them for the same reason. The supporting system in agriculture and conservation is a very good example for these cases. The dates of grassland management regulations and subsidies in conservation areas urge that kind of land use, what can directly contribute to destroying grassland areas and damage soil conditions. Although local herders have many ideas and suggestions for reasonable changes in local or national level, these suggestions do not even reach the local decision-making levels. Inclusion in policies or international proposals is not provided in any form for local communities. In addition, it would be impossible to make meaningful interventions for biodiversity in the face of the complete contradictions in the support systems. The interests and trends of the economic sectors are not in line with local needs and public interests. In addition, the lack of public awareness would make certain necessary decisions unpopular and thus exclude them from the decision-making process.

Many international examples show that among the different agricultural sectors, pastoral grazing is the one that can adapt even in increasingly extreme weather conditions. However, they are also finding it difficult to adapt to trends in agriculture, forestry, water management or urbanisation at national and EU level and have become extremely vulnerable. Unfavourable land ownership restructuring, land conversion and land-based support schemes have opened up loopholes that have created conditions that have made the livelihoods of the large majority of herders impossible. Positive examples have been observed mostly only in personal reconciliations and local cases (eg. we know about some cases in the country, when local herders are allowed to use other farmers land out of agricultural plant cultivation season due to unique relationship with farmers), but the long-term positive effects and the survival of traditional communities are not really solved or generated by these initiatives. Herders and extensive livestock farmers could potentially implement different or identical approaches to biodiversity and food security. But they are not given the necessary territorial and regulatory opportunities to do so. As a result, their spot interventions generally fail to achieve the effects that researchers generally agree are attributed to herders' activities. Thus, the technological potential for ecological change is available, but the social, economic and regulatory environment largely prevents its realisation. Herders and other relevant stakeholders are unable to address these constraints with their influence and currently available power.

Local policies and strategies that need to be renewed are not constrained by the European directives in the sense that the Hungarian government does not currently pay attention to such issues, but rather approaches the issue in terms of economic funding opportunities. In fact, there is no real will at the top level of the country to address the issue in a meaningful way. Moreover, the decisions that are taken are typically not technically grounded. Further questions are raised by the fact that EU directives do not leave sufficient room for the maintenance of useful and workable local practices as a result of the implementation of funding schemes. Regulations that focus on environmental and nature conservation rather than exclusively economic (agricultural) ones may also contribute to biodiversity loss and the disappearance of local practices that can mitigate extreme climatic factors, due to dramatically changing climatic conditions. In summary, inflexibility at EU level and political and social indifference at national level are barriers to the implementation of beneficial local practices. At the same time, the economic and supportive context tends to neglect the use of scientifically sound methods that are in the interests of biodiversity. This is in large part due to a system and approach that is unable to respond to rapid change and that continues to perpetuate the practices of the last century as a tradition. The partial passivity of cultural and local

communities thus repressed, combined with the predominant reliance on subsidy-based management represents a major threat to the future sustainability of the areas. The knowledge needed to do so are held by the marginalised groups they would otherwise support, will be lost in the near future. The reduction of constraints is not strongly perceived, but the willingness of middle-level decision-makers and executives to compromise on some minor issues is a positive development.

The herders themselves have so far not formulated a public, unified opinion on the processes that affect them and society as a whole. Their attitudes are changing dramatically as we work, but they do not yet have the real power to bring about real change. The social partners are thus developing theoretical strategies to mitigate the disturbing factors, but they are still powerless to implement them and to transform the barriers. The problem is that they have no insight into the national and EU regulations and decision-making environment, next to its connectivity and infrastructure. They are therefore best placed to assist in the implementation and design of local practices, and in the collection of scientific and technical data and opinions. The former are important in the sense that the regulatory and support environment in which they operate is in need of change at all levels of decision making and implementation, and harmonisation is almost impossible to ensure in the short term. (2)

2.2.4 Failed and successful practices

The basic problem in Hungary is that biodiversity conservation as a fundamental issue is only stated and effectively considered in the context of nature conservation. Although some local communities, such as herders, have a special and basic interest, they do not frame the problem in this way. Moreover, due to the heavily agricultural sector dominated Hungarian nature conservation, a very significant proportion of farmers do not base their livelihoods on actual production activities, but on the subsidies provided by a dysfunctional system, while they are not really interested in positively influencing their environment (agricultural and natural). State nature protection in our country now plays more of an executive role and cannot intervene to resolve these financial and regulatory contradictions. Today, the changes in climatic conditions (especially drought and water supply problems) and the drastic loss of biodiversity are tangible to almost everyone, but there is no comprehensive movement for change at either social or political level. The problems have probably not yet reached the critical level where society needs to address these issues with discernment and compulsion. In fact, there are no political factors that actively support the goals and results of our case study, and the public sector is not helping biodiversity conservation in any way due to the failures of the system (regulations and subsidies) and the lack of interest (sometimes willful damage to nature) of the current government.

From a societal perspective, we expect to discover double effects. The civil society (traditionalists, festivals, folk art organisations, local communities, etc.), which respects the diversity of Hungarian culture, sees pastoralism as a unique curiosity. Consequently, sharing the experience gained in our case study with a specific layer of the civil society could be quite effective. On the other hand, these communities are not moved by the technical and technological issues of herding, nor by their social, economic and cultural problems. Most of them seek only to examine and visualise the herders' cultural heritage in the form of externalities (eg. traditional clothing, carvings, typical tools and other fancy equipments, songs and dances, etc.), in many cases in a way that is distinctly unethical towards them. So, in some respects, there is also a great receptivity to our own work on herders, but so far we have not found allies and stakeholders who can technically benefit herders. However, in the civil society sector, with the increasing climate and drought situation over the last few years, civil organisations have emerged that are completely unaware of the presence and needs of pastoralism, but which represent public interests that are closely linked to herders. One example is the issue of ecological water resupply, which is becoming an increasing problem for herders every minute. The sudden emergence of these civil organisations should be seen as a new

potential ally, but we need to examine their precise background and intentions to see if cooperation is possible. Although the actual role of these opportunities is still unfolding, perhaps in the future, professional representatives of the civil society can be powerful allies in the technical promotion of herders' issues.

In terms of successful practices, the internal processes in the Hungarian herding community are worth mentioning. Thanks to the networking activities of our research group, increased communication between small and large communities of herders and the ever-increasing exchange of knowledge between groups and age groups have been initiated (1.;2.;3.;4.;7.). By knowledge, we do not only mean the methods for the maintenance and regeneration of biodiversity that are found in the practical work of herders. It can include the various ways of adapting to the diverse set of rules that human society has created today. The latter form of knowledge contributes indirectly to biodiversity conservation by facilitating the survival and retention in the profession of those communities and individuals most skilled in biodiversity conservation and regeneration, and thus their traditional biodiversity-related ecological knowledge. We cannot, of course, claim that this will stop biodiversity loss, it will simply enable us to professionally gather the methods and needs to advocate to decision-makers in the interests of biodiversity and herding communities. It is important to highlight the increasing trust-building between the herders' community and the representatives of the relevant disciplines and institutions (e.g. during the Forum of Hungarian Herders organised by our research group - (2.;4.)). This is clearly successful in the sense that the stakeholders and sometimes decision-makers in their negotiations with us treat the herders we bring into the negotiation process as partners in the negotiations. This has never been done before, so the herders themselves can start to build their own advocacy and representation.

Attempts over the last two decades to get real help from the top level decision and policy making community have proved to be unsuccessful or less effective. To this point no progress has been made. While many decision-makers and political leaders agree or even support our efforts in principle, no practical efforts have been made to provide substantive assistance. While it would be inappropriate to give up trying to move in this direction, we must acknowledge the lack of interest and infrastructural powerlessness at system level. For the time being, we do not have a concrete, developed method for breaking through these barriers, and we need to keep working on our approaches.

One of the shortcomings of our activities is the lack of communication channels that could inform the profession and the civil society on a very broad scale about the results and priorities of our research and the objectives and solutions we are seeking to achieve. The publication of technical material in scientific and agricultural journals is also of course a value and can be seen as an essential first step in informing the professional community. However, they have not been followed up by further progress in the field of communication. At the same time, the research community typically lacks the insight - and in many cases the skill and sensitivity - to use these media opportunities ethically and professionally to achieve their objectives. So, in fact, our own research team needs to develop its professional manifestations. In this respect, development together with herders cannot be considered the same as the research team's own state of being.

The lesson to be drawn from our achievements so far is that we should not continue to push the same methods and communication lines to achieve the same goals, solely because of the powerlessness and disinterest of the state and international governmental and infrastructural background. Change must not only be considered from the perspective of biodiversity and the stakeholders that sustain it - in our case the herders - but also the case study workers must make continuous adaptations between different static and highly variable environmental elements. Otherwise, the long-term objectives to be achieved could easily be stalled by a single inhibiting factor, which could be avoided in several places by innovative solutions. In this respect, the herding sector among the stakeholders of our case study provided us with a number of reinforcing feedbacks.

Although no workshop has yet been held specifically on this topic, it will be necessary to hold one in the future.

Among the practices and specific interventions that support the conservation and restoration of biodiversity, we can highlight those that we have made possible for shepherds at an individual level, or in some cases regionally and nationally. We tried to promote the national or local legalization of useful practices, or we provided information to herders about the circumstances and effects of implementation that were invisible to them. The basis for this is therefore to ensure the flow of information among herders, between herders, researchers and conservationists, and between competent decision-makers and local stakeholders. Concrete examples of successful practices include adjusting the timing of fox rabies immunization at the beginning of grazing seasons; ad hoc agreements on stubble grazing, which both improve the condition of agricultural land and protect grasslands; resolving individual conflicts between conservationists and herders regarding specific economic activities and conservation issues; etc. This mostly includes practices that herders are basically familiar with and perform (with or without permission). However, it is worth further refining these practices with knowledge from other fields, sciences and aspects. Moreover, it is very important to communicate them properly between the stakeholders involved, as the perceived conflicts of interest in the legal sense actually represent mutual benefits to the parties during practical implementation. For example, the practice of stubble grazing was active among Hungarian pastoralists until the second half of the last century. However, with the redrawing of property relations and agricultural regulations, the majority of herders and their livestock were forced to move to protected grasslands. When grazing stubble and fallow lands, livestock benefit both landowners and herders: the livestock can access an additional feed base, for which the herder does not have to pay any costs. Grazing removes weeds that farmers are required to remove with herbicides. The vegetation on the remaining (i.e. unrolled) stubble covers the soil, protecting it from further drying out. The trampling and droppings of livestock can improve the condition of the soils. In summary, we are talking about an ecologically and economically rewarding practice for everyone, which we must once again widely introduce in the country. The successes so far have only started with a compromise between a few shepherds and farmers, but we are launching further lobbying activities to legalize and financially support successful practices.

2.2.5 Co-learning

Our work with Hungarian herders began years before the BioTraCes project began. It is a difficult task to ethically and effectively approach a marginalized and traditionally closed community due to its social past. Gaining social trust was based on joint fieldwork and participatory action research over the long term. The most effective way to learn and exchange information emerged from this fieldwork was through this kind of physical cooperation. The herders understood the researchers' perspectives and goals, while revealing more and more information from their traditional ecological knowledge and social processes. Community-level knowledge exchange and co-learning developed from this, to which our personal networking activities within the BioTraCes project and the meetings and workshops we organized contributed greatly. As our research team conducts fieldwork with national coverage, herders from different backgrounds and regions have begun to connect more closely, both personally and professionally. A new network of relationships began to emerge, and an increased flow of knowledge began within the pastoralist society, as well as between the pastoralist society and stakeholders directly or indirectly involved in their work.

At the conference at Olaszfalu (19-20.05.2023), at the international meeting among herders and between herders and researchers working with pastoralists, the herders recognized and made aware that in many places in the world, there are separate interest groups, educational and training solutions and economic partners about herding. Through their example, it is worth examining Hungarian herders' society, then determining their goals and developing their community life and groups according to their own needs and

culture. At the first Forum of Hungarian Herders held on September 27, 2023, the gathered pastors specifically consulted with decision-makers and representatives of the institutions affecting them regarding the current situation and needs of the pastoral community. The meeting had three main results: informing decision-makers about the situation of herders; the herders were able to see the opportunities and barriers provided by the state infrastructure; together with the herders, we were able to define long-term goals for the survival of the herding profession. The Second Forum of Hungarian Herders was organized on February 20, 2024. The event provided an opportunity for herders to discuss their own ideas in detail regarding the main issues affecting their own communities. Some plans were accepted, others were rejected on the spot, thus determining the further work of our research group. The First National Meeting of Hungarian Womenherders Group took place in March 2024. The meeting established the representation of a special group – women working in pastoralism. The members of the group could discuss their personal situations and ask each other for advice on their internal affairs. In 2024 and the second half of 2025, we participated in several professional conferences and consultations (organized by others) that provided information for our work together with herders on topics related to regenerative farming, grassland management, and water management. On the other hand, with these occasions herders and researchers had the opportunity to represent their own positions on issues affecting them.

The year 2025 was not at all favorable for mutual knowledge exchange and personal consultations with the participation of stakeholders from different areas. We had to postpone face-to-face meetings and group workshops due to the emergence of the foot-and-mouth disease virus, as the meetings we organized for livestock farmers would have created a potential risk of spreading the disease. Stricter animal health and livestock farm regulations, as well as research ethics required us to temporarily cancel or postpone the meetings, field visits, and trips abroad that we had organized. As a result, for a longer period of time, we were only able to hold consultations in a smaller circle, online, or in person (1-on-1 meetings) under secure conditions. This plays a role in that, herders are best at personal consultations among themselves in bigger numbers, if they need to coordinate their views on a national scale. At the same time, it is important to note that in the case of the Hungarian case study, mutual knowledge exchange and learning are the result of longer-term cooperation that goes beyond the time frame of the BioTraCes project (as we have already explained in several places). Therefore, the temporary suspension of personal consultations and the learning of conclusion did not cause as much of a problem in terms of the results of our case study as it would have if we had to produce our results within the specified deadlines during the four-year duration of the project.

Discussions about the indirect causes of biodiversity loss have been ongoing in recent years. The learning processes between research partners vary in terms of methods and intensity between different regions of the country. Our main research partners in this regard are participants from the research sector who share our interest in some form in grassland wildlife and biodiversity (e.g., experts in grassland entomology, forestry, ornithology, etc.), herders and livestock farmers themselves, as well as nature conservation experts, with particular emphasis on certain members of the ranger service working under the National Park Directorates. In addition, our work brings us into contact with numerous experts from the civil, public, and other sectors who could potentially be involved, and with whom the exchange of knowledge and joint position statements could provide extremely important additions to our own research group's work and thinking on the topic. (1.;2.;5.;6.)

As a result of the co-learning processes, we reached the following conclusions regarding biodiversity in our case study: Since different regions of Hungary have completely different characteristics (e.g., saline and sandy landscapes, forested areas, hills and mountains, floodplains, nature reserves and agricultural landscapes, centuries-old cultural landscapes, etc.), the various stages of biodiversity development are influenced by anthropomorphic and natural factors, and biodiversity processes are at different

stages even in areas with different or identical characteristics within the same region. It is worth working with our stakeholders to assess and solve local, regional, and national problems at the same time. Our partners generally identify the extremely harmful water management practices of the last 150 years as the main cause of biodiversity loss, and in our opinion, the severe droughts that have developed as a result of bad water management practices over the last two decades in particular. The impact of droughts is significant in that our native natural environment is slowly becoming unable to regenerate. The environment has been able to absorb the effects of numerous processes causing biodiversity loss, most of which are man-made, for a very long time. However, with the onset of increasingly extreme droughts, our natural environment is unable to regenerate adequately. Opinions are divided on the vision for the future and the processes that need to be implemented to secure it. From the perspective of farmers and the agricultural sector (including herders and livestock farmers), droughts threaten the existence of agricultural sectors. From a nature conservation perspective, alarm bells have been ringing for intervention, but despite this, there is a high degree of infrastructural inertia and institutional passivity. Most interventions are small-scale and ad hoc, serving mainly to influence public opinion. Research perspectives may vary depending on the areas and topics studied. Based on our own perspective, the droughts that have occurred over the past two decades and are intensifying year by year are part of a major transformation process. The legal and regulatory protection of native flora and fauna has not adapted to the current ecological and climatic conditions. A significant proportion of native grassland species are becoming less and less tolerant of severe droughts, including atmospheric drought, and we can therefore expect to see the decline and disappearance of many species in the near future. Despite previously effective landscape conservation activities, we will not be able to maintain the survival of these species at the local level in the absence of the conditions that are essential for them. The appearance and spread of invasive and non-native species is obviously not in the interests of nature conservation, nor is it an ecological goal. At the same time, a drastic decline in the species composition of grasslands and grassland-related biotic communities is to be expected, as well as a transformation parallel to this decline, possibly accompanied by the spread of non-native species. These species are generally undesirable from a nature conservation point of view, but – alongside local biotic communities that are unable to adapt to the changing conditions – we can and must find ways to use them successfully in the future. There are already numerous examples of this in Hungary. For example, grazing on invasive and non-native *Asclepias syriaca* in the Kiskunság region ensures the survival of flocks and their herders. Although livestock are generally unwilling to graze on this plant, it still serves as fodder for them in times of shortages. The foliage of *Robinia pseudoacacia* can also be used as feed for livestock, but its reputation and status are mixed: in the lowlands, these trees are drying up, and fewer and fewer tree species are able to withstand droughts. In the much rainier areas of the west part of Hungary (the part of Hungary west of the Danube), these tree is considered an invasive species that needs to be reduced, but it can also be a significant source of feed for livestock in some cases. The few examples listed above demonstrate that diverse and often extreme conditions can elicit diverse responses from farmers, researchers, and conservationists. Reconciling comparable problems and disseminating possible solutions requires continuous work. The meetings we organize (the international Conference at Olaszfalu, the first and second Forum of Hungarian Herders, and other occasions) and the events organized (sometimes spontaneously) among stakeholders provide a suitable environment for the co-learning processes, clarify the results of co-learning processes.

Numerous solutions have already been developed for certain biodiversity issues, which could bring about change across the country under the right circumstances and when applied appropriately. In disseminating these solutions, we not only engage in professional consultations and personal exchanges of experience, but also strive to publicize the methods in ways agreed upon with our partners, e.g., by publishing articles in professional journals, giving presentations at conferences, and holding roundtable discussions, both in Hungary and abroad. However, most of these methods are successful when they can be implemented at the level of individual farms and individuals.

We base the importance of the former statement on the fact that individual commitments to certain methods lead to changes in practice more quickly. The policy and regulatory environment, as well as the inertia of decision-making and infrastructure related to agriculture and nature conservation, the regulations which are subject to little change, do not allow for a rapid and effective response to rapidly changing ecological conditions. Of course, regardless of this, it is necessary to continue with the guiding professional activities in this field, but at the same time, it is not possible to rely solely on these in the future.

2.2.6 Testing of interventions

On-site testing of local interventions in the Hungarian case study is ongoing, but it is also encountering difficulties. We have already discussed the cultural composition and processes (and, in some cases, tensions) of the herders' society, as well as the differences in their natural and social environments. During our work, among other things we were working on the field of the herding methods of different regions, animal healthcare, grassland management strategies, water retention possibilities of different regions, the nature conservation procedures, cooperation, or even conflicts of the competent National Park Directorates, the difficulties of the bureaucracy related to livestock farming, the social and cultural barriers and opportunities, the necessary professional and social reactions in critical animal health situations, etc. Accordingly, beyond establishing ecological guidelines, it is not possible to generalize specific interventions among Hungarian herders and livestock farmers in order to maintain biodiversity. Every herder has his own innovative interventions on his own fields and socio-cultural sphere, to which we ourselves have tried to contribute to the best of our knowledge we have gathered and transferred. The social, economic, natural, and other conditions of the different regions are far from uniform, making it impossible to plan uniform interventions for all areas. The exchange of knowledge and experience is therefore justified, but the synthesis of knowledge and the development and implementation of intervention proposals require smaller-scale consultations. Accordingly, when discussing the results, special attention should be given to the different circumstances of the negotiating parties and to gathering information that is useful to them. Furthermore, we strongly urge that the knowledge of local communities be supplemented not only by national and international research, but also by the involvement of other local experts on the subject. For practical and cultural reasons, the development and testing of action plans should not be carried out exclusively in cooperation with experts who come from radically different parts of the country or who specialize in those areas. When establishing national principles, the situation is naturally reversed, as it may be worthwhile to involve as many experts as possible from as many regions as possible (local stakeholders with different knowledge; local and international researchers, etc.) in the consultations so that all potential circumstances can be taken into account in the decision-making process.

Action plans can be categorized according to their individual level or their community character. Developments that directly impact biodiversity at the local level are largely due to the personal exchange of knowledge between herders. Our primary social partners, herders and livestock farmers, are constantly working individually on their own interventions to improve their natural environment, economy, and social environment. We can help them in this process in two ways. On the one hand, we establish connections with their colleagues and other professionals, thus enabling the exchange of experiences and the resulting personal innovations. The other option is to create a community space (which can be physical, intellectual, or virtual) and community events where collective experience sharing can take place. Of course, these community events can be organized on an ad hoc or regular basis (an excellent example of this is the series of Forum of Hungarian Herders we organize - (2.;4.)). In this regard, it is a huge advantage that Hungarian pastoralists within their profession specifically like to meet personally and exchange stories and ideas. The events we coordinate or organize have expanded the topics they discuss among themselves. So they are starting to

communicate more broadly and openly with different groups and members of their own community, and they are also willing to pass on different and deeper knowledge to each other in order to help their communities. The exchange of experiences between communities and sectors can on the one hand generate personal innovations, and on the other hand define the basic principles and necessary interventions that the research sphere needs to further develop, explore, propose, and communicate to the relevant policy-making and decision-making organizations and interest groups. Similar to the development of action plans, these interventions can be monitored on two levels. Individual interventions can be monitored through on-site inspections and consultations (about the grasslands, animals, and other parts of biodiversity at place). The experiences of personal innovations can go through great distances between regions by personal communication of herders and through our intermediary role, and can reach different professional circles among livestock keepers, researchers and conservationists. Thus, the innovations generated by the initial small scale knowledge exchange return to the community and create new innovations through repeated knowledge exchange, starting a self-exciting process between the community and its individual members. This requires the personal experiences of herders and livestock owners, as well as the involvement of external parties with the necessary expertise (researchers, various experts), which is expected to be followed by the development of a new action plan. Community action plans can be monitored in several ways, depending on their nature. On the one hand, we can gather information on social processes by specifically seeking out community members, and we can also discuss results, mistakes, shortcomings, and proven or unsuitable methods during meetings. Measuring the results of the goals set in policy and decision-making processes is much simpler, as it is easy to track the start, halt, or completion of processes, which is communicated to our stakeholders through national and regional communication channels, and stakeholders directly feel the effects of decisions that affect them. It is definitely worthwhile to gather information about new decisions and changes as soon as possible, regardless of whether they were made on our own initiative or for reasons beyond our control.

Action plans can be classified into two types according to their nature: those implemented by stakeholders in the areas they manage, and those we wish to achieve at the local, national, and international levels in the policy, regulatory, and decision-making environment. Due to the large number of cases, we are unable to present the implementation of local practices in detail in this report. However, it can be stated with certainty that the professional exchanges and knowledge transfer (primarily related to livestock and land management) that arise through the network of relationships built up between stakeholders and various stakeholder groups often yield results in the everyday practical work of local farmers and herders. Of course, this applies to all groups of herders and livestock owners, regardless of region, age, origin, family background, and gender. These results are also discussed during formal and informal occasions organized during our work or related to our work as participants. Consultations with stakeholders other than practitioners are a much greater challenge. We have not yet found an effective method to break the policy deadlock in our work. In terms of the regulatory environment, policies, and economic background, we are unable to involve some of the stakeholders related to our case study in the consultations; at most, we can ask for their opinion on certain issues (e.g., commercial organizations involved in the trade of live animals from abroad). The lack of infrastructure is so severe that in many cases the requests we make and the bottom-up initiatives we launch get stuck at the lower and middle levels, so we can only maintain contact with regional representatives with limited authority. A further difficulty is that the herders and livestock farmers we represent do not have any significant connections in this area, so they can only provide effective assistance in planning initiatives (and of course, the practical interventions would fall to them at a later stage). They have no authority in the infrastructural launch and intellectual-regulatory implementation of interventions, and can only rely on the authority of our own research group. Therefore, we can provide very few examples where the results of the procedures initiated could be evaluated. We discuss these on an individual level with certain directly affected herders, but they are always mentioned at

community meetings, and we communicate our results in this area in professional journals for the purpose of providing general information. We are aware of most of the shortcomings arising from policy, decision-making, and infrastructure conditions, and we continuously list newly emerging needs in our individual work and during various meetings and consultations.

The involvement and participation of stakeholders in the processes we plan and initiate creates an intellectual and knowledge system intersection that has never occurred before in the history of Hungarian pastoralism. A new form of dialogue is emerging, as herders are increasingly willing to be involved in certain discussions that affect them personally or professionally. Although we still devote significant energy to supporting herders in this area, more and more organizations are paying attention to them in this regard. For example, they are invited to cultural events where they can present their knowledge and culture according to their own needs and ethics. In an increasing number of cases, scientific and cultural materials created in their connection are published with their contribution and presence (e.g. scientific works, photo contests, film productions, ethnographic lectures, etc.). Our own efforts are most strongly trying to strengthen their professional presence in the issues of grassland management, landscape use, nature conservation and agricultural subsidies. Our research group is invited to numerous consultations and conferences, where we arrive representing the professional opinion of herders and, in most cases, together with herders in person. This raises the professional dialogue about pastoralism to a higher level. We also try to achieve results in decision-making with similar methods, but at the same time, our possibilities and actual influence on decision-making processes in this area are currently very limited. It is encouraging that the First Forum of Hungarian Herders, organized by us, has already provided an opportunity to bring the decision-making sphere closer to the practice and presence of herders.

All meetings we organize contributed to mutual learning and shared reflection among herders themselves, between herders and the research team, and between herders and other organisations, policy-makers, or groups of interest. The dialogues held at the location of the meetings can also have a significant impact on the thinking of Community-level changes and social perceptions of the pastoral communities, as the knowledge exchange influenced how herders researchers and other actors perceive biodiversity, land use, participation, and regeneration practices. Moreover, specific consultations have already taken place on some decision-making issues. These occasions provide opportunities for mutual learning not only on site. After each meeting, we collect both the personal and collective opinions of the participating parties, further helping the development and perfection of ideas. Regardless, unfortunately we cannot report on a larger decision-making process generated by our activities, what made a shift of formal or informal rules, institutional practices, or interactions with local or regional authorities. They were more about information exchange and knowledge co-production. Structural constraints are so strong in terms of policies and institutions (primarily agriculture and nature conservation), and institutional inertia and political disinterest are so great that the potential for future changes seems unpredictable.

2.2.7 Discussion

We are working together with our main stakeholders, the Hungarian herders to develop the strategies presented in our case study. Although they are naturally our most prominent stakeholders in the majority of cases, numerous other actors are also involved in joint consultations with the herders and us, as well as in the development of national and regional strategies. We are working together with various researchers and research partner organizations about collecting and systematize traditional ecological knowledge, land use practices, water management methods, ecological impacts, etc. They have mainly a scientific role about data management and communication within society, and among herders. There are members of the nature conservation ranger service, other staff of National Park Directorates and other nature conservation experts working

together with us and the herders. They have a strong, direct impact on pastoralism through the different type of knowledge about nature conservation grassland areas, climate change issues, and through conservation regulations to humans, livestock keeping and grassland management. They have a very important role in the life of pastoralists, but they can have quite different attitudes about herding (good or bad opinions about the herders knowledge and role in grassland management. The representatives of regulatory and animal husbandry-related infrastructure and institutions has also a very important role through requirements, bureaucracy and registration in animal husbandry, but they basically are not concerned especially about herders. We have to take into count animal health experts, as allies in the formation of hybrid animal healthcare knowledge in the future, and the preventers of dangerous livestock diseases that are emerging more and more frequently nowadays. The breeder organizations are also important to our work. The different institutions have a different role in the case study, because the herders are keeping different breeds in different numbers. Moreover, the role of those breeds are also important, which are not kept by herders, because they might have an influence to the economic background of livestock keeping. In this aspect, they have a very important, but partly indirect role in the life of herders. (1.;2.;7.)

Discussions about the indirect causes of biodiversity loss have been ongoing in recent years. The learning processes between research partners vary in terms of methods and intensity between different regions of the country. Our main research partners in this regard are participants from the research sector who share our interest in some form in grassland wildlife and biodiversity (e.g., experts in grassland entomology, forestry, ornithology, etc.), herders and livestock farmers themselves, as well as nature conservation experts, with particular emphasis on certain members of the ranger service working under the National Park Directorates. In addition, our work brings us into contact with numerous experts from the civil, public, and other sectors who could potentially be involved, and with whom the exchange of knowledge and joint position statements could provide extremely important additions to our own research group's work and thinking on the topic.

Numerous solutions have already been developed for certain biodiversity issues, which could bring about change across the country under the right circumstances and when applied appropriately. In disseminating these solutions, we not only engage in professional consultations and personal exchanges of experience, but also strive to publicize the methods in ways agreed upon with our partners, e.g., by publishing articles in professional journals, giving presentations at conferences, and holding roundtable discussions, both in Hungary and abroad. However, most of these methods are successful when they can be implemented at the level of individual farms and individuals. We base the importance of the former statement on the fact that individual commitments to certain methods lead to changes in practice more quickly. The policy and regulatory environment, as well as the inertia of decision-making and infrastructure related to agriculture and nature conservation, the regulations which are subject to little change, do not allow for a rapid and effective response to rapidly changing ecological conditions. Of course, regardless of this, it is necessary to continue with the guiding professional activities in this field, but at the same time, it is not possible to rely solely on these in the future.

On-site testing of local interventions in the Hungarian case study is ongoing, but it is also encountering difficulties. We have already discussed the cultural composition and processes (and, in some cases, tensions) of the herders' society, as well as the differences in their natural and social environments. Accordingly, beyond establishing ecological guidelines, it is not possible to generalize specific interventions among Hungarian herders and livestock farmers in order to maintain biodiversity. The social, economic, natural, and other conditions of the different regions are far from uniform, making it impossible to plan uniform interventions for all areas. Within pastoralist society, different groups (e.g. young and old herders, women working in pastoralism,

etc.) are able to help mitigate biodiversity loss with different methods and effectiveness depending on the region and local customs. The exchange of knowledge and experience is therefore justified, but the synthesis of knowledge and the development and implementation of intervention proposals require smaller-scale consultations.

Accordingly, when discussing the results, special attention should be given to the different circumstances of the negotiating parties and to gathering information that is useful to them. Furthermore, we strongly urge that the knowledge of local communities be supplemented not only by national and international research, but also by the involvement of other local experts on the subject. For practical and cultural reasons, the development and testing of action plans should not be carried out exclusively in cooperation with experts who come from radically different parts of the country or who specialize in those areas. When establishing national principles, the situation is naturally reversed, as it may be worthwhile to involve as many experts as possible from as many regions as possible (local stakeholders with different knowledge; local and international researchers, etc.) in the consultations so that all potential circumstances can be taken into account in the decision-making process.

The basic problem in Hungary is that biodiversity conservation as a fundamental issue is only stated and effectively considered in the context of nature conservation. Although some local communities, such as herders, have a vested interest, they do not frame the problem in this way. Moreover, due to the heavily agricultural sector dominated Hungarian nature conservation, a very significant proportion of farmers do not base their livelihoods on actual production activities, but on the subsidies provided by a dysfunctional system, while they are not really interested in positively influencing their environment (agricultural and natural). Public nature protection in our country now plays more of an executive role and cannot intervene to resolve these financial and regulatory contradictions. Today, the changes in climatic conditions (especially drought and water supply problems) and the drastic loss of biodiversity are tangible to almost everyone, but there is no comprehensive movement for change at either social or political level. The problems have probably not yet reached the critical level where society needs to address these issues with discernment and compulsion. In fact, there are no political factors that actively support the goals and results of our case study, and the public sector is not helping biodiversity conservation in any way due to the failures of the system (regulations and subsidies) and the lack of interest (sometimes willful damage to nature) of the current government.

One of our greatest challenges in our case study is the disregard of the traditional ecological knowledge of local communities and the irresponsible and thoughtless destruction of biodiversity (in urban, rural and natural environments) at almost state level. The general trend across Europe is that the behavioural and spatial reorganisation of our society has distanced people very strongly from the knowledge of natural values and processes, and from the opportunities and needs to conserve and maintain ecosystem services essential for human life. Traditional or innovative local communities capable of restoring and maintaining biodiversity have become marginalised groups. In addition, governments do not attach importance to maintaining biodiversity or even ecosystem services and basic human needs. It has now reached the point where the country's food insecurity is looming, the problem of drinking water supply is becoming increasingly serious, and the rapid acceleration of human made 'desertification' through subsidised agriculture and other activities is increasing.

2.3 CES Case Study: Portugal

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2.3.1 Short presentation of the case

Mértola, a semi-arid municipality in southern Portugal, faces a convergence of ecological fragility - water scarcity, soil degradation, desertification risks - alongside social and economic challenges such as demographic decline and limited diversification. Yet, these vulnerabilities, however, have also created conditions for innovation, positioning the territory as a site of experimentation for regenerative governance and biodiversity restoration.

The **Mértola case study in BIOTraCes, called Mértola Future Lab**, is anchored in a local strategy for agroecological transition, under which a diversity of projects have been developed. Rather than focusing on a single institutional actor, **this strategy has consolidated a co-governance architecture** that articulates efforts from municipal, associative, and grassroots levels. Within this distributed governance model, the Mértola City Council (MCC) plays a catalytic role, generating synergies and supporting collaboration with a wide network of territorial actors - including Terra Sintrópica Association, schools, civil society organisations, and community initiatives. These partnerships have helped establish biodiversity regeneration as a shared political and cultural objective.

Within this broader framework, five actors stand out for their strategic relevance to the BIOTraCes case: Terra Sintrópica Association, which leads experimentation in regenerative agriculture and territorial regeneration; ESDIME - the Agency for Local Development in the Southwest Alentejo, which fosters community-based development and social economy initiatives; ALSUD, a vocational school offering training in wildlife management and sustainable land use; Mértola Biological Station (MBS), a research and technology transfer hub focused on biodiversity and agroecology; and the Community House of Santana de Cambas, which serves as a cultural and social anchor in one of Mértola's parishes.

Equally important is the Mértola Food Network (MFN), a participatory network that brings together institutions, producers, educators, and local actors to rethink food systems. The MFN acts both as a space for experimentation and as a collective decision-making forum. It has advanced food literacy, shifting school canteens toward local and organic sourcing. The Council is one voice among many, as MFN values the integration of scientific, traditional, and experiential knowledge in shaping territorial regeneration.

Through this constellation of initiatives, including the Agroecology and Regeneration Centre for the Semi-Arid (CARES) and its experimental Malhadinha Vegetable Garden, Mértola illustrates how shared governance, cultural change, and inclusive participation can unlock regeneration. Rather than relying on top-down innovation, transformation here stems from an embedded culture of co-learning, experimentation, and territorial commitment - positioning rural areas as laboratories for just and regenerative transitions.

2.3.2 Evaluation of strategies in action

Strategies in action

Mértola is a rural municipality in the Baixo Alentejo region of southern Portugal, known for its semi-arid landscapes, rich cultural heritage, and low population density. It faces some of the most acute ecological and socio-economic pressures in the country: high susceptibility to desertification, chronic water scarcity, severe soil degradation, and the compounded impacts of decades of intensive monoculture, unsustainable grazing, and past mining activities. These environmental stresses compound demographic decline, an aging population, and limited economic diversification - conditions that make the territory both vulnerable and, paradoxically, fertile ground for pioneering approaches to regeneration and resilience.

In Mértola, the evaluation of biodiversity regeneration strategies reveals a layered and dynamic landscape of experimentation, shaped by a strong commitment to co-governance, ecological learning, and systemic transformation. A set of organisations has contributed to building an atmosphere of co-governance, consolidating a concerted action towards a regenerative process, with particular attention to the establishment of a locally-grown healthy food system.

Within this context, Mértola's societal partners in BIOTraCes - Terra Sintrópica Association (TSA) and the Mértola City Council (MCC) - have actively integrated and nurtured a governance model that is rooted in collaboration across a wide spectrum of actors. This includes local government, development agencies, educational institutions, grassroots associations, producers, local development associations, and community spaces. One of the key arenas where this articulation happens is the Mértola Food Network (MFN), a participatory governance platform that brings together diverse stakeholders around the shared goal of building a sustainable and inclusive local food system. The MFN functions both as a space for experimentation - such as testing local distribution schemes - and as a forum for shared decision-making that brings together scientific, traditional, and experiential knowledge.

This articulation goes beyond the MFN itself, linking to a broader constellation of projects aimed at climate adaptation, biodiversity regeneration, and social resilience that play a pivotal role within the Mértola Future Lab - a community strategy for territorial innovation linked to ecological transition. Whereas educational initiatives foster food sovereignty and ecological literacy into schools, regenerative grazing and syntropic agriculture projects seek to restore degraded soils. At the same time, intermunicipal collaborations are advancing the creation of a cross-border "food basin," designed to secure healthy and accessible food for regional residents. Funding for these initiatives comes from a diverse mix of local, national, and international sources, including EU structural funds, cross-border cooperation programmes, and philanthropic foundations.

In the context of Deliverable 2.4, the Mértola case provided an opportunity to test how these interconnected strategies perform when examined through the lens of regenerative governance. The focus was on assessing their capacity to address persistent lock-ins - such as geographic isolation, policy and procurement barriers, and the underrepresentation of certain social groups - while advancing the goals of ecological restoration, food sovereignty, and social cohesion.

To understand how strategies for biodiversity regeneration are unfolding in Mértola, it is essential to first map the network of actors, initiatives, and governance structures that give shape to the territory's regenerative efforts. What follows is not an exhaustive list of all organisations working in Mértola, but rather a focused introduction to the actors,

platforms, and projects that are central to the agroecological transition explored in the BIOTraCes case study. These actors have played a pivotal role in experimenting with and operationalising regenerative governance, and will be referenced throughout this deliverable as we analyse the strategies tested in the field. Rather than presenting them through isolated descriptions, we introduce each actor and initiative in context, highlighting their interconnections, areas of influence, and contributions to systemic change in the territory.

Key Organisations, networks and projects

a) Terra Sintrópica Association (TSA). Leads territorial experimentation in regenerative agriculture and food systems, catalysing new imaginaries of rural sustainability and interspecies cooperation. Together with Mértola City Council, TSA constitutes a central societal partner in BIOTraCes. Its projects promote agroecological literacy and strengthen social cohesion across the territory. Examples include **Forest Gardens at Schools**, which engage children in cultivating vegetable gardens, exploring interspecies collaboration, and enjoying the harvest - either at school or at home - and the **Shelter Land Programme**, which welcomes Afghan refugees for training in syntropic agriculture. Developed in partnership with Permaculture for Refugees, the High Commission for Migration (ACM), and Mértola City Council, this programme fosters agency and integration through regenerative work. At the heart of TSA's efforts is the **Centre of Agroecology and Regeneration for the Semi-Arid Region (CARES)**, based at the Malhadinha Vegetable Garden, a site for experimentation and demonstration in agroforestry and the principle of "regeneration through use." Its **Therapeutic Garden Project - "There is a Party in the Forest Garden"** exemplifies how conviviality and memory-sharing can foster community resilience, well-being, and new imaginaries of soil care, particularly among the elderly.

b) The Agroecology and Regeneration Center for the Semi-Arid (CARES). Constitutes one of the central strategies of the Terra Sintrópica Association and grounds on practical experimentation to inspire broader participation in regenerative practices. This includes engaging farmers in syntropic agriculture as a method not only for restoring degraded soils but for shifting paradigms - from competitive to cooperative inter- and intra-species relations. These techniques, rooted in the syntropic philosophy promoted by the Terra Sintrópica Association (TSA), are presented as viable alternatives to extractive agricultural models historically dominant in the region.

c) Mértola City Council (MCC). Acts as an institutional facilitator within the co-governance ecosystem, supporting coordination among actors without assuming a dominant role, and creating space for experimentation, dialogue, and power-sharing.

d) Mertola Future Lab (MFL). Has emerged as a local and collective strategy for ecological transition, climate adaptation, and the fight against desertification. It brings together diverse organisations with the multiple aims of regenerating soil and ecosystems, building a healthy and local food system, valuing local knowledge in shaping a transition strategy, and positioning Mértola as a site of experimentation for regenerative practices.

e) Mértola Biological Station (MBS). Provides practical services - including keyline plow access, game censuses, management plans, and soil analyses - while investing in

innovative research perspectives. Its transformative potential lies in countering perceptions of the region as a “landscape with no future,” attracting international research interest, and reshaping long-term imaginaries of adaptation and sustainability.

f) Mértola Food Network (MFN). Serves as a space for planning and implementing changes focused on building a local food system in Mértola and initiating a regional Food Basin. The MFN is one of the key initiatives developed under the broader umbrella of the Mértola Future Lab, embodying its vision of regenerative territorial governance through food systems transformation. One of the main initiatives of MFN is **The Night at the Market**, an innovative community event hosted in Mértola’s municipal markets, designed to foster social connection and promote sustainable practices. The event brings residents together around themed cooking sessions where food is shared alongside knowledge and experience. Each edition highlights a different theme and invites a special guest, creating space for informal learning, peer exchange, and the collective development of new ideas. By combining conviviality with meaningful discussion, the initiative strengthens community engagement, nurtures trust, and empowers participants to take part in shaping local responses to climate change, desertification, and food sustainability. Another noteworthy initiative is **Fresh on Wheels (Frescos sobre Rodas)**, a decarbonised delivery service for fresh products sold at the Mértola Municipal Market. Operating only in the town of Mértola, this project promotes low-emission logistics, electric mobility, and short supply chains, while reducing plastic packaging and raising awareness about sustainable food consumption. Developed as part of the MFN strategy and supported by the Environmental Fund, it involves the Mértola City Council, Terra Sintrópica Association, local producers, and the Guadiana Valley Business Association (AEVG).

g) Agency for Local Development in the Southwest Alentejo (ESDIME). Stimulates territorial development by supporting social economy initiatives, entrepreneurship, and community projects. ESDIME has played a pivotal role in fostering new farming practices and techniques in the Baixo Alentejo region. Some examples of innovative and ground-breaking projects are **Regenerative Pastures** and **TerrAlimenta (Land feeds)**. While the first one stimulates techniques of regenerative agriculture such as holistic grazing and use of key-line design, also creating funding for regenerative approaches, TerrAlimenta (Transition for a local food system) set the foundations for a regional Food Basin. This Food Basin has started through changes in collective catering canteens.

h) ALSUD – Vocational Training School. Offers a **Technical Course in Game and Wildlife Management** (*Curso Técnico de Gestão Cinegética*), which equips young people with specialised skills in sustainable land use, biodiversity monitoring, and ecological stewardship. The course includes training in the management of **red-legged partridge and other steppe birds**, directly addressing the ecological characteristics of the Baixo Alentejo region ([ALSUD, 2021](#)). Additionally, ALSUD hosts a Senior University (*Universidade Sénior*), promoting intergenerational learning and the inclusion of older adults in discussions on regeneration, land care, and rural resilience. Through these two educational arms, ALSUD fosters knowledge exchange between generations and strengthens local engagement in biodiversity protection.

i) Community House of Santana de Cambas. Anchors social and cultural engagement in a geographically isolated parish, contributing to decentralising participation and linking regeneration initiatives with the most remote communities. One of its most emblematic

initiatives is **the Grandma's Kitchen (Cozinha d'Avó)**, a community-led project that reinterprets traditional Alentejo recipes using seasonal, organic, and locally grown ingredients, while promoting sustainable water use and agroecological practices. Jointly led by the Parish Council of Santana de Cambas, the Community House, and the Mértola City Council, the project fosters intergenerational co-learning by involving elderly women and children in educational activities that encourage healthy eating habits, food autonomy, and the preservation of cultural heritage. Through workshops like the **Cooking Academy**, families are engaged in adopting better food practices, especially in children's school meals. Funded by the EU's Operational Programme for Social Innovation and Employment (POISE) between June 2020 and December 2021, and implemented by the *Casa do Povo de Santana de Cambas, Cozinha d'Avó* illustrates how food can become a strategic entry point for social innovation, sustainability, and regeneration.

In the field of agriculture, several concrete interventions have been developed in Mértola to support the transition toward agroecology and biodiversity regeneration. These initiatives not only focus on technical practices like soil restoration and sustainable grazing, but also on reshaping collective food systems and embedding regenerative principles. Below are some of the **key practices and approaches currently shaping the agricultural landscape in the territory:**

Key practices in Mértola

a) Syntropic agriculture. It has been introduced as a key regenerative strategy for soil restoration and the conversion of degraded lands, based on cooperative intra- and inter-species dynamics, promoted by the Terra Sintrópica Association (TSA).

b) Education for regeneration from childhood. Regenerative pedagogy is being implemented in local schools through forest gardens and participatory ecological learning - helping to foster multispecies awareness and new relationships with the land.

c) Transformation of collective food systems. Through coordinated work on procurement processes, menu planning, and food preparation in public canteens, the Mértola Food Network (MFN) has supported a progressive shift toward including more local and organic food in schools and eldercare centres. This has involved strategically adapting purchasing practices - for instance, issuing tenders for smaller lots - to better match local supply capacities, and create room for qualitative criteria beyond price alone, while remaining fully compliant with European public procurement directives. These efforts have contributed to shaping purchasing decisions and strengthening a culture of food that values proximity, seasonality, and sustainability.

d) Food Basin for the Baixo Alentejo Region. Regional efforts are underway to structure supply chains and local markets around agroecological production.

e) Regenerative pastures and agroecological practices. ESDIME (Agency for the local development of Southwest Alentejo) has actively encouraged the adoption of regenerative techniques - such as holistic grazing and keyline design - through projects and partnerships that promote learning and experimentation. While its overall funding framework has not fundamentally changed, there is a growing effort to integrate regeneration criteria into its support schemes and to inspire local actors to adopt soil-restoring and climate-resilient practices. The regeneration agenda in Mértola is sustained by evolving governance practices that aim to redistribute power, foster cross-sectoral collaboration, and introduce greater institutional flexibility.

f) Co-governance model. Through partnerships between Mértola City Council (MCC), Terra Sintropica Association and other actors, a horizontal governance culture has emerged. The Mértola Food Network (MFN) exemplifies this model, bringing together producers, cooks, technicians, and political representatives to deliberate collectively on food systems, land use, and regenerative strategies.

g) Transformative funding logic. Regional actors such as ESDIME have begun to experiment with ways of embedding regeneration principles into their support activities. While this does not yet amount to a systemic change in funding logic, these efforts demonstrate a willingness to test and promote approaches that link development funding more closely with biodiversity regeneration and soil restoration.

Transformative potential of the strategies

The strategies currently being tested in Mértola aim to promote structural and discursive shifts in how biodiversity, food systems, and land use are imagined, governed, and practiced.

At the structural level, they seek to move beyond the usual fragmentation of governance, toward a more horizontal and participatory model of decision-making that brings together public authorities, civil society, producers, and local institutions. The co-governance structure of the Mértola Food Network is a clear example of this, fostering spaces where regenerative practices and food system transitions are collectively discussed and implemented. Its transformative potential lies in enabling coordinated action that can address multiple, interconnected barriers to regeneration more effectively.

However, the transformative potential goes beyond the co-governance itself, manifesting in the very capacity for concerted action that it enables, allowing for the simultaneous transformation of multiple dimensions that constitute persistent lock-ins. When actors act in coordination across different fronts - policy, funding, knowledge systems, and everyday practices - the chances of unlocking structural constraints and advancing biodiversity regeneration become significantly greater.

Another key structural shift is the growing institutional adaptability emerging at the municipal level. Local actors are demonstrating how public food systems can be oriented toward biodiversity goals - remaining fully within the legal frameworks while revising entrenched bureaucratic routines and streamlining procedures, thereby creating space for innovation.

At the discursive level, the interventions in Mértola are actively contributing to a reframing of agricultural and ecological imaginaries. Moving away from the dominant vision of the Alentejo as a monocultural breadbasket destined for intensive, extractive production, local actors are promoting new narratives of the territory as a mosaic of regenerative systems - dynamic, multispecies, and community-embedded. This symbolic shift is reinforced through education, public events such as "Night at the Market," and initiatives like "Grandma's kitchen" (see section 2.1.2 Strategies in Action), which revalue traditional knowledge and cultural practices linked to biodiversity.

By combining practical interventions with new governance models and cultural reframing, the strategies underway in Mértola offer the potential to challenge entrenched paradigms

and to foster a more **inclusive, adaptive, and regenerative approach to biodiversity governance** in the region.

Responses to indirect drivers of biodiversity loss

The strategies underway in Mértola explicitly engage with several indirect drivers of biodiversity loss, particularly those related to **demographic decline, economic dependency, social isolation, political inertia, and cultural undervaluation of local knowledge**. The region's long-standing trends of aging population, depopulation of rural parishes, and limited economic diversification have created structural vulnerabilities that exacerbate both environmental degradation and the loss of community resilience.

In terms of addressing these indirect drivers, the strategies in Mértola directly tackle socio-economic and cultural conditions that typically hinder transformation. Initiatives such as the Shelter Land project (see section 2.1.2 Strategies in Action), which combines refugee integration with syntropic training, and Grandma's Kitchen (Cozinha d'Avó, description in section 2.1.2 Strategies in Action), which valorizes the culinary knowledge of elderly women, are examples of how regeneration is framed not only as an ecological need but as a social and cultural opportunity. These practices engage with drivers such as generational isolation, limited access to land, and undervaluation of local knowledge systems.

Educational initiatives - including forest garden projects (see section 2.1.2 Strategies in Action) - directly respond to the erosion of place-based ecological knowledge among younger generations. By fostering ecological literacy and multispecies awareness from an early age, these efforts seek to counteract the disconnection between youth and land, which is a key driver of biodiversity loss in depopulating rural contexts.

At the governance level, the emerging co-governance model within the Mértola Food Network addresses political inertia by promoting shared responsibility and horizontal participation, moving beyond hierarchical or sectoral decision-making that has historically failed to halt ecological degradation.

Nonetheless, challenges remain: geographic isolation, unequal access to transportation and information, and entrenched patterns of marginalisation continue to limit the participation of certain groups, especially in the most remote parishes. These constraints were clearly highlighted in focus group discussions and interviews with local actors. While practical measures such as mobile council meetings offer initial steps towards reducing these barriers, sustained efforts will be needed to ensure that biodiversity regeneration strategies truly reach and engage the most vulnerable and isolated populations in Mértola.

Scalability and replicability

The capacity to scale and replicate the strategies underway in Mértola is already visible in several dimensions. The Mértola Future Lab has established itself as a regional reference point, attracting researchers, practitioners, and public officials from other municipalities who are interested in learning from its regenerative approaches and developing

partnerships. Within this broader strategy, the Agroecology and Regeneration Center for the Semi-Arid (CARES, see section 2.1.2 Strategies in Action) has further amplified the reach of local experimentation. Beyond testing soil regeneration techniques, CARES hosts guided visits, short-term trainings and volunteer programmes, welcoming participants from Portugal and abroad. These activities not only disseminate agroecological knowledge and practices but also create a living laboratory that allows diverse publics to engage with regeneration in concrete, hands-on ways. In this sense, CARES plays a pivotal role in transforming Mértola's local innovations into experiences that can be replicated and adapted in other contexts.

At the institutional level, the policy adaptability and the strategy towards a local food system led by Mértola City Council is now serving as an inspiration for neighbouring municipalities. Several municipalities in the Baixo Alentejo region have shown interest in adopting approaches to prioritise local, organic, and seasonal products. This influence is not prescriptive but rather emerges from Mértola's practical experience in aligning procurement procedures with regenerative goals, demonstrating that creative, context-sensitive solutions can inspire others while working within the current legal framework. Yet the experience also shows that without adjustments to procurement legislation and to EU Directive 2014/24/EU, the potential for truly scalable change will remain constrained, as the existing framework does not adequately value or prioritise local production.

At the same time, ESDIME has been taking steps to integrate regenerative principles into its support initiatives, encouraging interest in regenerative pastures and agroecological systems across the region. In parallel, the ongoing work to build a regional Food Basin holds strong potential for scaling, as it promotes inter-municipal cooperation and strengthens agroecological supply chains that extend beyond Mértola. Still, partners recognise that for these innovations to be fully institutionalised and replicated at scale, further steps are needed to broaden participation and to secure more stable and long-term policy commitments.

Strategic framing and symbolic dimensions

The strategies underway in Mértola are not limited to technical solutions or policy adjustments - they also actively engage with the symbolic and cultural dimensions of biodiversity regeneration. One of the most important shifts is the reframing of agricultural imagination: local actors, especially Terra Sintrópica Association, are working to replace the image of Alentejo as a monocultural breadbasket with new narratives of the territory as a mosaic of regenerative systems, based on cooperation between species, healthy soils, and community well-being.

This symbolic shift is supported by multiple initiatives: events such as "Night at the Market" create public spaces for dialogue on healthy food, biodiversity, and regeneration, while the Cozinha d'Avó project revalorizes traditional culinary knowledge, linking food practices with biodiversity and cultural identity. The work of **PREC - Ongoing Regenerative Process (Processo Regenerativo em Curso)**, a self-managed space created by Terra Sintrópica that serves healthy, local, seasonal, and regenerative meals in Mértola, further contributes to transforming local food culture. More than just a kitchen, PREC acts as a living laboratory for food sovereignty, ecological transition, and community engagement. By focusing on the consumption side of the food system – connecting production to the plate – it offers everyday experiences that link dietary

habits with ecological awareness and demonstrate that regeneration is not only about how food is produced but also about how it is prepared, shared, and valued.

At the governance level, the very structure of the Mértola Food Network (MFN) - based on co-responsibility, collective decision-making, and multi-actor participation - models an alternative form of public action that counters top-down and technocratic governance. Through these cultural and institutional framings, the strategies in Mértola help reshape how biodiversity, land, and regeneration are valued - not only by policymakers but also by the broader community.

Taken together, all these initiatives show that Mértola's regenerative strategies are not confined to production but extend to everyday consumption practices, linking the field to the plate. This broader perspective reinforces the view of regeneration as a whole food system approach — one that integrates ecological, cultural, and social dimensions and makes biodiversity part of daily life.

2.3.3 Enablers and disruptors

Enablers

Among the most important enablers of biodiversity regeneration in Mértola is the positioning of the municipality as a "living laboratory" for sustainability - a political and symbolic choice actively promoted by the City Council together with a plethora of organisations. This positioning has helped attract resources, networks, and visibility at both national and international levels.

A strong participatory governance culture is another major enabler. One of the defining features of the Mértola case is its embedded **culture of co-governance**, which extends beyond formal participation mechanisms to foster deep-rooted collaboration among local institutions, producers, educators, associations, and researchers. Rather than centering on isolated platforms, this governance culture supports long-term relationships and trust-building processes that enable diverse actors to align around shared ecological goals. This collaborative ethos has provided fertile ground for experimentation and innovation, particularly in projects like **Regenerative Pastures**, led by ESDIME, which has stimulated the adoption of holistic grazing and keyline design techniques by local producers.

While the overall funding logic has not fundamentally changed, this initiative represents a significant step toward embedding regeneration criteria in local development strategies. Similarly, the **Mértola Biological Station (MBS)** plays a key role in transforming local imaginaries. Through practical services such as soil analysis, game census, and research in wild biodiversity, MBS challenges the perception of Mértola as a territory without prospects, positioning it instead as a knowledge hub for future-facing land stewardship. These efforts illustrate how the governance landscape in Mértola is not only about institutional flexibility, but about sustained co-responsibility and the gradual redefinition of what regeneration means in a semi-arid rural context.

Institutional adaptability and public procurement innovation. Institutional adaptability has proved pivotal - not only in legal terms, but also in the way procurement processes were used as a lever for change. Evidence from the TerrAlimenta project, one of the projects led and recently concluded by ESDIME, shows that local authorities

worked with producers, nutritionists, and canteen staff to map production capacity, analyse food consumption data from public schools, and align menus with seasonal availability ([Monteiro & CIMBAL, 2024](#)). In Mértola specifically, the MFN served as an important arena for these discussions, bringing together organisations and municipal representatives to deliberate on how to progressively increase the share of local and organic products in public canteens.

The baseline data for the Baixo Alentejo Region - where Mértola is located - revealed the scale of the challenge: only 3.8% of the monthly volume of vegetables and 3.6% of fruit consumed in public canteens came from local production, with the remaining volume supplied by distributors, most of them within the Baixo Alentejo. This diagnosis suggests that building a regional Food Basin is a natural next step, as it would allow these existing supply chains to be reorganised around agroecological production and scaled up through inter-municipal cooperation.

These findings informed a process of progressive menu reformulation and the issuing of smaller tenders, enabling the application of qualitative criteria - such as proximity and organic production - while remaining fully compliant with EU procurement directives. In Mértola, the participatory process strengthened trust among stakeholders and encouraged local producers to adjust their calendars to supply schools and social institutions as regular clients.

Visibility and external recognition. The Mértola Biological Station (MBS) contributes by attracting academic and public attention to Mértola's regenerative work, positioning it as a reference at national and international levels.

Funding innovation, regenerative criteria and community of practice. Funding innovation, driven by ESDIME, has been another important enabler of change. Programmes such as Regenerative Pastures (Pastagens Regenerativas) have piloted approaches to holistic grazing and syntropic practices, providing technical support to encourage experimentation among farmers ([Cortegano & Encarnação, 2024](#)). While these initiatives do not yet represent a complete transformation of funding logic, they demonstrate a clear movement towards integrating regeneration criteria into territorial development support. The experience has also highlighted the importance of linking financial incentives with capacity-building, so that producers can adopt regenerative techniques with lower risk and greater continuity. Building on this, a Community of Practice on Regenerative Agriculture was created, bringing together farmers, researchers and practitioners in a structured process of exchange. The group combined participatory workshops with study visits to farms in Portugal and Spain where regenerative techniques such as holistic grazing and keyline design were already in place, offering concrete examples of their potential. These visits were complemented by theoretical and practical training sessions on topics ranging from rotational grazing to *montado* regeneration and direct marketing of pasture-raised meat, further strengthening collective learning and confidence in applying regenerative methods (Cortegano & Encarnação, 2024).

Networks of mutual learning. Within the Mértola Food Network and through cross-case inspiration with other municipalities - they support the spread of innovative approaches. The **Food Basin** initiative is fostering regional scaling, while practices piloted in Mértola are already inspiring similar efforts in neighbouring municipalities.

Taken together, these enablers - participatory culture, institutional flexibility, leadership commitment, visibility, funding innovation, and networked learning - provide a fertile ground for scaling and replicating biodiversity regeneration efforts across Mértola and the wider Baixo Alentejo region.

Disruptors

Several structural, political, ecological, and cultural factors continue to hinder biodiversity regeneration in Mértola, even in the presence of strong enablers.

First, ecological vulnerability remains a persistent background condition. The territory faces high exposure to desertification, water scarcity, soil degradation, and declining fertility - much of it inherited from decades of intensive land use. These pressures are compounded by prevailing imaginaries of land and water management held by many actors in dominant economic sectors. Traditional views continue to privilege extensive livestock farming, “LEGO-style” landscape interventions (rigidly fragmented and engineered responses), and the conventional *montado* system as ideal land uses. In this view, solutions often focus on large-scale infrastructure such as dams or river transpositions, rather than regenerative strategies like forest succession or water retention through syntropic agriculture. As noted in interviews, these imaginaries can act as significant cultural lock-ins, shaping local expectations and limiting the perceived legitimacy of agroecological experimentation.

Economic lock-ins reinforce these imaginaries. Many farmers operate with very narrow profit margins and remain trapped in a **subsidy-dependent cycle** tied to CAP mechanisms that usually reward conventional, high-input systems. This amplifies risk aversion toward agroecological innovation. As a result, regenerative strategies like syntropic agriculture are still perceived as uncertain by many producers.

Institutional inertia also persists. Long-standing administrative routines - for example, in municipal maintenance - often ignore or resist regenerative practices (e.g., regenerative planting, soil care), requiring ongoing efforts to shift institutional culture and knowledge.

Geographical isolation further limits change. The **highly dispersed rural geography of Mértola** - with 106 villages spread across the seven parishes of Alcaria Ruiva, Corte do Pinto, Espírito Santo, Mértola (town), Santana de Cambas, São João dos Caldeireiros, and the Union of Parishes of São Pedro de Sólis, São Sebastião dos Carros and São Miguel do Pinheiro - makes communication, transport, and participation difficult, especially for marginalised groups. As focus groups have shown, this territorial disconnection results in “two Mértolas”: one, more networked and engaged in regenerative initiatives, and a second, composed of more isolated communities that remain peripheral to these processes.

Culturally, a **dominant political imagination** in the Alentejo region still favours infrastructure-heavy, productivist approaches over biodiversity-centred, regenerative models. Without adequate policy shifts, this mindset risks slowing the institutional embedding of regenerative innovation.

In response, actors in the territory are actively working to **mitigate these disruptors** through multiple strategies. The **Mértola Food Network** seeks to build an alternative

ecological imagination - fostering social learning through projects like the **Therapeutic Gardens, Grandmothers' Kitchen, Shelter Land, and Forest Gardens** in schools. These initiatives engage citizens in hands-on regenerative practices and help transform perceptions of land, food, and community (see section 2.1.2 for a description of the initiatives).

At the policy level, the Food Network and Future Lab are committed to long-term dialogue with institutional actors, aiming to shift local and regional funding logics and planning priorities toward agroecology and regeneration.

Finally, participatory efforts by the Municipality - such as rotating council meetings to outlying parishes - aim to address geographical isolation by fostering **greater inclusion** in decision-making.

Policy Attunement and mismatch

Mértola's local biodiversity agenda encounters both alignment and tension within national and EU policy frameworks. While national and EU policies increasingly highlight biodiversity regeneration and agroecological transitions, their implementation frameworks often remain misaligned with the realities of rural territories like Mértola. Although recent CAP reforms introduced tools such as eco-schemes and rural development measures, in practice, structural incentives continue to favour large-scale conventional agriculture. This limits access to support for small-scale regenerative farmers and community-led initiatives. Rather than focusing solely on legal constraints, local actors have responded by exploring creative pathways to align available instruments with local priorities - experimenting with targeted procurement adjustments and fostering new partnerships. Yet, a broader transformation of policy cultures and funding logics is needed to fully accommodate regenerative approaches that are place-based, socially inclusive, and ecologically ambitious. The experience in Mértola reveals that adaptability alone is not enough: enabling real alignment requires sustained support for experimentation, recognition of diverse value systems, and space for local governance actors to shape implementation on their own terms. Below are some examples.

CAP

The structure of the [Common Agricultural Policy \(CAP\) \(2023–27\)](#) has introduced important environmental measures - such as mandatory eco-schemes, which allocate at least 25% of direct payments to sustainable practices, and the Rural Development pillar ([FEADER](#)) dedicated to climate and biodiversity goals ([food.ec.europa.eu](#), [agriculture.ec.europa.eu](#)). However, as implemented in practice, the Portuguese CAP Strategic Plan favors larger landowners and conventional models, rendering it difficult for small-scale regenerative farmers to access consistent support. The result is a subsidy system that remains misaligned with Mértola's regenerative objectives, leading many farmers to remain locked into high-input systems.

National subsidy frameworks

National subsidy frameworks such as the **Programme of Support and Incentives for Agriculture** may technically support sustainable practices, but in reality often maintain a resource-intensive logic, highlighting a misalignment between policy and implementation ([Viegas, Wolf, Cordovil, 2023](#); [OECD, 2023](#)).

Farm to Fork Strategy

The European Green Deal's Farm to Fork strategy encourages sustainable food systems -

reducing pesticide use, supporting organic farming, and promoting local agri-food networks ([European Commission, 2023 may](#)). This aligns conceptually with Mértola's efforts to build a local food basin. Yet, progress remains uneven due to delays in legislation and resistance from entrenched interests.

Public Procurement Policy

EU Directive [2014/24/EU](#) (European Union, 2014) requires procurement based on cost and non-discrimination, which often creates a bottleneck for sourcing local, organic produce. In Mértola, local actors addressed this constraint by developing a participatory procurement model involving TSA, MCC, and others to restructure school and eldercare menus. By working within the existing legal framework — for instance, by opting for smaller lot sizes and aligning supply with seasonal availability — they created space for local producers to participate. This grassroots adaptation, now being considered in neighbouring municipalities, illustrates how local practice can innovate within restrictive procurement norms.

Policy Alignment Opportunities

Portugal's CAP Strategic Plan must include a minimum share for eco-schemes (~25% of direct payments) and strong rural development funding (~35%) ([agriculture.ec.europa.eu](#)). These open pathways for Mértola actors to secure structural support for regenerative agriculture.

The Farm to Fork strategy additionally supports local food initiatives - creating a favorable policy narrative for Mértola's food basin.

The prevalent imagery

Major economic sectors in the Baixo Alentejo region – agriculture, livestock, hunting and tourism – tend to hold conservative positions on the solutions proposed for addressing local challenges in the territory, such as desertification, water shortage, rising temperatures, depopulation, natural resource degradation, soil erosion, and fertility loss. For example, discussions on water management not rarely focus on river transportation, desalination, and small-scale irrigation systems, as well as subsidies and market-driven approaches on cattle stocking density, etc. This, therefore, leads to a considerable mismatch between major economic actors' interests and Mertola's agenda for biodiversity regeneration.

2.3.4 Failed and successful practices

Successful practices

A co-governance approach. One of the clearest successes in Mértola has been the establishment of a co-governance approach that integrates diverse local actors in the design and implementation of biodiversity regeneration strategies. Through the Mértola Food Network and the Future Lab, Mértola City Council, Terra Sintrópica Association and other stakeholders have created spaces for collaborative decision-making that go beyond isolated projects. This participatory structure has been effective in mitigating some local power imbalances and fostering transparency, contributing to a greater sense of shared ownership over biodiversity initiatives. The success of this model can be attributed to strong leadership from the Municipality, the trust-based relationships cultivated among

actors, and the stability of the initiatives such as MFN and Mértola Future Lab, which provide continuity beyond individual projects.

Planting seeds for future youth opportunities. Initiatives on the ground are creating conditions that may, over time, generate new opportunities. Visible pathways for engagement with biodiversity and land regeneration are being created. The Mértola Biological Station (MBS) promotes research opportunities and innovation in biodiversity-related fields, helping to position the territory as a dynamic and forward-looking space and offering continuity for young researchers who might otherwise need to leave. ALSUD's training programmes in agroecology and game management provide vocational routes at an age when many young people consider leaving the region. These programmes help counteract the perception of Mértola as a place of limited prospects and have started to spark new forms of youth engagement. These initiatives may not yet yield immediate outcomes, but they represent important steps towards building synergies between education, employment and land stewardship, laying the groundwork for future youth opportunities linked to the territory's ecological vocation.

Strengthening social cohesion through regeneration. An essential dimension of Mértola's approach is its investment in strategies that connect ecological goals with social cohesion. Public events such as "*Night at the Market*" offer inclusive spaces where food, culture, and biodiversity regeneration are brought together in everyday life, reinforcing a sense of community in a geographically dispersed municipality. Similarly, initiatives like PREC and Grandma's Kitchen promote positive framings of the territory as a regenerative space - strengthening cultural identification with biodiversity goals. The strength of these practices lies in their ability to combine symbolic and tangible experiences, amplifying awareness while fostering a stronger collective identification with regeneration — a necessary condition for broader adherence and mindset change.

Failed Practices

Absence of ordinary citizens and underrepresented groups in participation processes. The participatory process promoted through the co-governance approach animated by the public body in Mértola is still limited to some pivotal organizations in the village and municipality. As a result, broader segments of the community - particularly ordinary citizens in more remote areas - remain underrepresented in the governance spaces, and their potential contributions to shaping local mindsets and values around biodiversity regeneration are not yet fully realised. Residing minorities should be better included in Mértola's strategies for biodiversity regeneration. Minorities are not ignored by Mértola's case, although some underrepresented groups such as Roma people and immigrants could strongly benefit from their insertion and participation in regenerative strategies in the territory.

Youth sensibilisation is missing. Youngsters are leaving Mértola as soon as they can as they are taught to consider the village and the municipality as places with no credible future. The strategies for enhancing the visibility of opportunities available in the municipality of Mértola needs targeted communication and further efforts to delineate promising ideas engaging youth. At present, Mértola lacks a structured strategy for youth sensibilization and talent retention. A significant number of young people perceive the municipality as offering limited prospects for the future. This perception, while not universally shared, might be reinforced by certain local actors, including educators within the public school system. However, some promising avenues are beginning to take

shape. ALSUD's vocational training programmes - particularly in agroecology and game management - are generating interest among younger generations and helping to reframe local rural professions as viable and meaningful career paths. Additionally, the Mértola Biological Station (MBS) holds potential to become a future hub for youth employment in biodiversity and regeneration, offering concrete prospects for those seeking locally rooted professional engagement. Importantly, the complementary action plan developed by CES includes a specific focus on youth engagement and participation, recognising it as a key dimension of any long-term regenerative strategy in the territory.

Critical Gaps and Missed Opportunities

A persistent gap is the **uneven participation across the municipality's dispersed geography**. Despite efforts to rotate meetings to rural parishes and initiatives like "Night at the Market" to both promote social cohesion and enhance food literacy, there is still a clear divide between the central network of engaged actors in the town and the more peripheral, isolated communities. The highly dispersed nature of Mértola - with 106 villages spread across the seven parishes of Alcaria Ruiva, Corte do Pinto, Espírito Santo, Mértola (town), Santana de Cambas, São João dos Caldeireiros, and the Union of Parishes of São Pedro de Sólis, São Sebastião dos Carros and São Miguel do Pinheiro - continues to produce **territorial disconnection**. Without more systematic approaches to outreach and participation, regeneration efforts risk deepening this divide rather than overcoming it.

Another important gap is the **lack of sustained youth engagement**. While individual programmes (such as the technical course in wildlife management promoted by ALSUD) are beginning to create pathways, there is still no coherent, municipality-wide strategy to involve young people in biodiversity regeneration - either through education, governance, or employment opportunities. Without such a strategy, the risks of **youth out-migration** and **future disengagement** remain high.

Minority inclusion also remains underdeveloped. Groups such as **Roma people and migrants** are underrepresented in the Food Network and in regenerative practices more broadly. Their potential contributions - in terms of cultural knowledge, social perspectives, and alternative practices - are not yet fully integrated. This reflects both structural inequalities and a lack of targeted strategies for meaningful engagement.

Finally, there is an opportunity to strengthen **external communication** and storytelling around biodiversity regeneration - particularly to counter dominant narratives of productivity and infrastructural "solutions" that still shape much of the regional political imagination. While successful efforts exist within the Food Network, a broader communication strategy that reaches beyond existing circles would help consolidate public support for long-term change.

Lessons and future directions

The range of successful regenerative projects, and the way Mértola has gradually become an example of a resilient territory in tackling desertification and promoting biodiversity regeneration, demonstrate the potential for locally rooted, collaborative approaches to drive change. One of the most significant lessons lies in how these strategies have

gradually taken root: not through imposition, but through a process of social legitimisation, trust-building, and iterative adaptation.

A key element in this transition has been the **emphasis on social cohesion**. Rather than treating change as a technical matter alone, the Mértola case foregrounds the cultural and relational work required to foster transformation. Literacy around biodiversity and food systems is promoted not through external imposition but through recognition of local knowledge, traditions, and forms of care. This participatory approach has made it possible to build legitimacy around new practices and their underlying rationales, allowing regeneration to be anchored in the lived realities of the territory.

Another valuable lesson concerns the **ongoing strategies that encourage people to experiment** with new techniques in areas such as water and biomass production (e.g., syntropic agriculture), wildlife population control (e.g., game management), and interspecies collaboration for soil regeneration (e.g., successional agroforestry systems). Several methods have proven effective:

- Engaging local and elderly farmers to share their knowledge while testing innovative practices;
- Inviting farmers to visit successful, evidence-based regeneration initiatives, encouraging change through peer-to-peer exchange;
- Promoting the gradual incorporation of regeneration-related criteria into funding schemes to support experimentation;
- Building alliances with nearby municipalities and territories to scale impact and generate learning beyond Mértola itself.

This **invitation to experiment**, for those already engaged in agroecological transitions, has been complemented by efforts to reach out to neighbouring municipalities. These strategies suggest that transformation does not emerge from isolated interventions, but from the creation of social, institutional, and ecological bridges that connect diverse actors and foster mutual learning.

While much has been achieved, the **persistence of gaps in youth engagement, minority inclusion, and territorial participation** highlights the need for more targeted and systematic efforts. This includes more structured approaches to youth sensibilisation, by challenging perceptions that Mértola lacks a viable future and building pathways to retain local talent, such as those offered by ALSUD. In terms of minority inclusion, the **Shelter Land project** represents an important symbolic and practical opening. Despite limited visibility in public narratives, it demonstrated that regenerative work can serve as a powerful tool for integration and agency-building, particularly for refugee and migrant communities. These gains, although modest, point toward scalable practices for fostering a more inclusive regenerative strategy.

This leads to a final key lesson: the **importance of combining institutional innovation with cultural work** that reshapes public narratives and values around biodiversity. Technical success alone is insufficient unless it is accompanied by strategies that deliberately work against community isolation, as well as structural inequalities and entrenched exclusions. Mértola's experience underscores that deep social transformation requires not only policy alignment and institutional support, but also cultural shifts, sustained dialogue, and a commitment to building just and inclusive alliances across the social fabric of the territory.

2.3.5 Co-learning

In the context of the Mértola case study, co-learning was both a methodological strategy and a political stance. It guided how BIOTraCes researchers, particularly CES, approached the field: not as observers collecting information but as facilitators of horizontal dialogue, committed to recognizing and strengthening the existing regenerative efforts already in place. Mértola is a mature case with ongoing processes of socio-ecological transformation. Therefore, the challenge for CES was not to introduce new solutions but to support reflection and consolidation, co-designing complementary strategies with local partners that could help address remaining gaps.

Co-learning as a Principle and Method

Co-learning in Mértola was conceived from the beginning as a strategic, methodological, and political approach. For CES, it involved more than sharing knowledge - it meant cultivating the conditions for joint reflection and decision-making across different knowledge systems, roles, and positionalities. The aim was not to transfer solutions, but to collectively think through what regenerative transformation could look like in a territory already rich in experimentation.

Recognising the maturity of local governance practices, CES approached co-learning as a way to support and critically accompany existing regenerative efforts. Societal partners such as Terra Sintrópica Association (TSA) and the Mértola City Council (MCC) brought deep territorial and institutional experience to the table. Equally important were the contributions of the Mértola Food Network (MFN), which mobilizes local producers, associations, local government public staff, and the diverse knowledge holders embedded in the region's social fabric - such as elders, community gardeners, artisans, educators, and other informal actors. CES's role was to foster reflective dialogues that could surface blind spots, consolidate existing strengths, and generate shared strategies for action. By recognizing these different voices as active co-constructors of regenerative futures, the co-learning process was able to articulate not only institutional perspectives but also grounded, embodied knowledges often left at the margins of policy and planning.

CES's approach throughout the BIOTraCes project was shaped less by a structured co-learning methodology and more by an ongoing process of adaptation and responsiveness to field realities. The team maintained close engagement with societal partners and community actors, which enabled small mid-course adjustments and the introduction of context-sensitive ideas as the project evolved. Rather than following a rigid implementation plan, this flexible approach allowed CES to remain attuned to emerging dynamics in the territory and to contribute to the local regeneration process in a grounded and supportive manner.

Rather than relying on predefined roles, co-learning unfolded as a relational practice shaped by mutual invitations to participate in strategic and reflective spaces. This included, for example, TSA's invitation to CES to engage in discussions about the Shelter Land and regenerative tourism projects, as well as CES's own initiatives to convene focus groups and workshops designed around local knowledge exchange and scenario building.

Through these engagements, a co-learning ethos emerged based on trust, continuity, and mutual recognition. The creation of a dialogical atmosphere - rooted in the ethics of non-imposition and respect for lived experience - was central. CES maintained a sustained presence in the territory, participating in local events and informal exchanges that provided a deeper understanding of how social and ecological knowledge was being mobilised locally.

Co-learning thus became a mechanism not only for producing knowledge, but also for generating legitimacy and ownership of proposed interventions. It anchored the research within a horizontal framework where the analytical gaze of the researchers was just one among many situated perspectives, enabling a richer and more context-sensitive understanding of Mértola's regenerative ecosystem. CES was not there to test or validate a model but to reflect alongside partners on how their own models could evolve.

Co-learning During the Preparation of D2.4

Co-learning was central to how Deliverable 2.4 was produced. The main structured co-learning moments included:

- **Internal CES workshop (IW)** (May 2024, Miro facilitation): served to clarify field strategy, reflect on ethical considerations, and prepare for respectful engagement in a mature and complex field. It aimed at discussing how concepts such as transformative change and co-governance might be understood in Mértola, including ethical questions related to inclusive engagement. The workshop was attended by CES team members and the Terra Sintrópica Association (TSA).
- **Two focus groups (FG1 and FG2)**: one with the **Mértola Food Network (MFN)** in December 2024 (**FG1**) and another in February 2025 with **other organizations and community stakeholders (FG2)**, more specifically, with one representative from each of the following entities: Terra Sintropica, Mértola Business Association, ALSUD (vocational training school), the Mértola City Council, Mina de S. Domingo Business Association, one from Casa do Guizo (rural tourism business) de Santana de Cambas and one representative from the Union of Parishes. The two focus groups were held in a space provided by Mértola City Council. These moments prompted self-reflection among participants and introduced a broader diversity of perspectives into the analysis.
- **Feedback workshop (FBW)** (December 2025): to be organised as a collaborative review of preliminary findings and strategies. It is conceived as a moment of feedback, co-validation, and adjustment.
- **Cross-case co-learning workshop (CoIW)** (December 2025): the event called "Participation and the youth's role in regenerative processes: opportunities and challenges" will focus on youth and its participation in regenerative governance. The aim is to bring together experiences from Portugal and Brazil, more specifically with representatives from IRPAA (Instituto Regional da Pequena Agropecuária Apropriada/Regional Institute for Appropriate Small-Scale Agriculture). The focus of the discussion will be the presence of youth in the design and implementation of nature-based solutions as well as the innovative approaches to connect community-based change and semi-arid territories.

Additionally, several **informal and embedded co-learning opportunities** occurred:

- Networking with key stakeholders during a "Night at the Market" event.
- Field visits to TSA's projects and participation in spontaneous conversations, including a knowledge-sharing visit and exchange with Luciane Lucas dos Santos and Fernanda Petrus on January 31, 2023.
- TSA's invitation to CES to reflect strategically on the Shelter Land project (with Afghan refugees) to reflect upon possible changes and betterments.
- and later to participate in the launch of the regenerative tourism initiative ("**TUI Field to Fork – Alentejo Regenerativo**", October 2024), where the concept of regenerative territory was once again brought to the scene as a kind of *leitmotif*. In this event, we engaged in discussions on sustainable tourism practices.
- Pedro Nogueira's participation in CES's colloquium "**New Generations, Risks and Vulnerabilities**", representing TSA and leading a workshop on syntropy and regeneration through use. His workshop stimulated valuable knowledge exchange and fostered potential collaborations for further projects.
- An invitation by TSA for CES to contribute to internal reflections at TSA, as the organization prepared for a shift in funding strategy following the end of European institutional support.

These moments allowed CES to **immerse itself in the lived dynamics of the territory**, forging a deeper understanding of local logics, challenges, and opportunities.

Focus groups also created opportunities for dialogue between the CES team and organisations from the Mértola Food Network, as well as with other local organizations. Based on these exchanges, it was possible to co-design a complementary action plan for Mértola. This plan prioritises actions in four key areas: (I) targeted communication and awareness-raising to support experimentation with new productive, consumption, and community redistribution practices; (II) identification and increase the valorisation of local knowledge to foster community resilience and social cohesion (these activities were labeled as "viveiros de experiências"); (III) promotion of experience-sharing with other initiatives in Portugal and abroad related to community participation in governance; and (IV) stimulation of regenerative economy initiatives. We highlight point III in particular, as it focuses on promoting moments of exchange between organisations that have faced similar challenges.

In December 2024, we conducted a first focus group, **FG1**, with the Mértola Food Network, which allowed them to enter into a self-reflection exercise regarding successful initiatives and possible shortcomings. The use of collaborative mapping allowed participants to visualize and strategise the importance of different aspects of the role of the network and aspects of regenerative processes in Mértola, fostering a sense of ownership and commitment to sustainable initiatives. In February, 2025, we conducted the **FG2** with other organisations and individuals that were not involved directly in the strategies related to MFN. It was a way of learning about other demands and perspectives from different stakeholders in Mértola.

We have also planned **FBW** scheduled for December 2025, which will focus on collectively reviewing the preliminary findings, particularly those emerging from the two focus groups. The workshop is designed to detect, together with local stakeholders, potential shortcomings in the current regeneration strategy in Mértola. It will include feedback forms, interactive sessions, and group discussions aimed at identifying areas

that require refinement or adjustment. The ultimate goal is to use this collaborative reflection to enhance or revise elements of the existing work plan, ensuring it better aligns with the insights, concerns, and aspirations expressed by the community and societal partners.

The following table summarizes the formal co-learning activities.

Table 1 Formal Co-learning events

Event	Participants	Location and date	Identifier
IW	CES and TSA	Online, May 2024	IW_PT_05-24
FG1	MFN	Mértola, December 2024	FG1_PT_12-24
FG2	Entities indirectly linked to the MFN	Mértola, February 2025	FG2_PT_02-25
FBW	All participants	Online, December 2025	FBW_PT_12-25
CoIW	CES team, MFN, IRPAA (Brazil)	Online, December 2025	CoIW_PT_12-25

Co-learning Dynamics in the Case Study

The co-learning dynamics in Mértola culminated in the development of a complementary action plan intended to support ongoing regenerative efforts by identifying opportunities for improvement and innovation. This was not a matter of replacing existing strategies, but rather of creating space for dialogue that could reinforce what was already in motion. The plan was shaped through sustained interactions and shared reflections among CES, societal partners, and community actors.

A recurring theme throughout these exchanges was the difficulty of broadening participation beyond core organizations. Communication challenges emerged as a shared concern among local actors themselves. Mértola’s geographic dispersion - its vast territory composed of multiple small and relatively isolated communities - was identified as a major obstacle, especially when it comes to reaching residents who are not already involved in regeneration initiatives. Notably, several stakeholders emphasised the particular challenge of engaging with younger populations, who often do not follow the same communication channels as older generations and may feel disconnected from institutional or community processes. While this difficulty was not unexpected, the co-learning process helped to increase the reflexion over the need to develop more tailored,

age-sensitive, and accessible formats for communication and outreach. As a result, the action plan proposed by CES is informed by strategies aimed at stimulating dialogue, fostering intergenerational engagement, and lowering barriers to participation. These should be seen as experimental starting points rather than definitive solutions.

In the co-designed work plan, a space was thought for Mértola to exchange with initiatives beyond Mértola, in order to discuss issues such as youth engagement in transition or successful strategies to deal with the challenges in semi-arid areas. Drawing on existing networks, CES suggested the possibility of reflecting collectively with actors engaged in similar efforts in other territories. This was not meant as a prescriptive solution, but as an invitation to dialogue - offered with the intention of broadening perspectives, sharing experiences, and reinforcing mutual learning. The idea was well received, as it resonated with ongoing reflections among local actors about the value of peer-to-peer engagement. These exchanges have since become part of the action plan, contributing to the process in a supportive and non-directive way.

Challenges and Reflections

Despite its successes, the co-learning process faced limitations. One of the main challenges was the difficulty of directly engaging ordinary citizens.

While the team initially hoped to reach beyond institutionalised actors, logistical constraints and limited availability among the population made this difficult. In addition to these practical challenges, the fieldwork also suggested a prevailing tendency to prioritize engagement through institutional channels. Although social cohesion is an explicit concern in the local regeneration strategy, there appears to be an underlying assumption that institutions - rather than individuals or informal groups - should take the lead in shaping and implementing change. This does not imply a lack of interest in broader participation, but it does point to a structural orientation that may limit the emergence of more horizontal or community-driven forms of involvement. Recognising this pattern can help inform future strategies that aim to expand participation beyond organised actors.

Another challenge involved asymmetries in capacity and visibility: some organisations had more experience with funding, facilitation, or policy dialogue. CES had to be attentive to these dynamics, ensuring that proposals reflected the needs and contributions of less empowered actors as well.

A further point that deserves reflection is the tension between CES's commitment to social justice and the priorities identified by local actors. As part of its methodological and political orientation, CES consistently emphasised the importance of identifying and including underrepresented groups - such as racialised communities, migrants, and Roma populations- as part of the effort to foster truly inclusive regenerative governance. However, in Mértola, these concerns were not widely shared or prioritised by local partners. In some cases, it was not a matter of open resistance, but rather a lack of familiarity or tools to address these dimensions effectively.

Although the Shelter Land project, which supported Afghan refugees, was a powerful and commendable initiative, its continuity was paused to allow for a period of reflection on its

social and environmental impact and to explore new approaches to reception. The project represented an important step towards more inclusive participation in Mértola. Yet inclusivity in the territory requires further attention and deepening.

It is worth recalling that inclusion is grounded in local perceptions and continually shaped by how difference is interpreted and negotiated. Co-learning processes must therefore address not only mechanisms of participation, but also the underlying understandings of justice, diversity, and equity. The Mértola case reminds us that co-learning is not always fully consensual – it involves negotiating tensions, working with discomfort, and identifying spaces for gradual transformation.

2.3.6 Testing of interventions

The interventions analysed in Mértola cannot be understood as isolated actions. Rather, they are embedded within a complex landscape of pre-existing regenerative practices, ongoing experimentation, and participatory governance dynamics. These interventions were primarily led by local actors - including the Mértola Food Network (MFN), Terra Sintrópica Association (TSA), the Mértola City Council (MCC), and ESDIME.

What was tested was not a single product or policy, but a set of situated, co-created strategies designed to transform the structural conditions that contribute to biodiversity loss and social exclusion. It is also worth noting that a work plan was co-designed with the societal partners and is already under implementation. This plan focuses on areas previously underexplored or requiring greater attention - such as targeted communication to engage young people in regenerative processes, and intercultural dialogue with successful initiatives, both in regenerative strategies for semi-arid regions and in the engagement of women and youth. Several of the strategies resulting from this co-creation process - developed through focus groups and collective reflection - are already being tested, while others are scheduled for implementation throughout 2026.

Testing, in this context, referred to the social, political, and adaptive process through which interventions were designed, assessed, and adjusted. Through co-learning and co-reflection, CES and its partners aimed to understand to what extent these strategies were effective in addressing entrenched lock-ins.

The testing of interventions was conducted through a range of participatory methods: two focus groups (one with MFN and another with different actors of the community), a feedback workshop, participatory observations, internal strategy meetings, and planned co-learning exchanges (see *table 1*). Rather than a one-time assessment, this testing was embedded in the **relational flow of the project**. The action plan co-developed through this process served as both a mirror and a vehicle for evaluation: it reflected what had been learned and proposed ways to move forward.

Stakeholder Engagement and Participation

The participatory strategies fostered over time by the societal partners succeeded in opening space for new dialogues-particularly through the MFN, which have been bringing together, since its inception, institutional actors and individuals who might not otherwise

collaborate on a daily basis, including school nutritionists, cooks, producers, teachers, public health officials and municipal staff. This diversity of voices helped shape a more plural space for reflection, even though not all groups in the territory were equally represented. The process is expected to continue and deepen in the coming period, building on the trust already established.

Despite the undeniable engagement, important exclusions remained. Although the Shelter Land project with Afghan refugees demonstrated that inclusive work was both possible and welcome, its continuation is still expected, with hopes that it may inspire further inclusion efforts in the future. Greater attention to internally marginalised groups would be an important next step, helping to advance spatial justice in the territory.

So far, underrepresented groups -such as Roma communities or recent migrants - have neither been engaged nor prioritised. From CES's perspective, this represents a key limitation in the transformative potential of the interventions: by their continued underrepresentation, the social justice dimension of the work remains incomplete. CES has consistently highlighted the need to better integrate these perspectives, since current interventions have focused mainly on strengthening social cohesion, shifting mindsets towards a regenerative approach, and changing practices in agriculture and livestock systems. These are crucial steps, but insufficient on their own to achieve fully inclusive and systemic transformation.

As documented in European reports on environmental justice and climate equity, communities such as Roma, migrants, and racialised populations often live under higher environmental risks and have lower visibility in environmental decision-making ([Marin & European Environmental Bureau, 2024](#); [Civil Rights Defenders, 2023](#); [European Migration Network Inform, 2023](#)). This empirical evidence supports CES's observation that the underrepresentation of these groups undermines the justice dimension of regeneration and limits its transformative potential.

Looking ahead, the co-created work plan and participatory strategies already in motion - particularly those developed through the Mértola Food Network - offer promising avenues to address these gaps and ensure that future interventions are more inclusive and socially embedded.

Knowledge Co-production and Collaboration

Knowledge co-production has been a cornerstone of Mértola's regeneration strategy. It builds on the municipality's efforts to foster concertation and dialogue, and has become a defining feature of the partnership between CES and local actors within the BioTraCes project.

At the local level, Mértola has promoted knowledge exchange through diverse formats - from informal conversations to MFN assemblies and hands-on workshops - highlighting local know-how in healthy food preparation, wildlife management, and regenerative agriculture. These moments created opportunities for dialogue both among organisations and between them and the community, fostering social cohesion and a shared space for learning. Initiatives such as *Night at the Market* (which combines conviviality with education on a local diet), and the *Therapeutic Garden* (where residents experiment with

syntropic techniques in gardening) illustrate this integration of knowledge-sharing with everyday practice.

The MFN has functioned as a site where technical, scientific, and experiential knowledge could be confronted, layered, and reshaped. Its format and facilitation enabled a shift in epistemic authority, giving space to actors - such as cooks and farmers - who are usually left out of planning processes. This widened the circle of contributors and grounded the transition strategy in practical, lived experience.

At the project level, collaboration between BioTraCes and Mértola's organisations and community unfolded through several key moments. Two moments illustrate this: (i) the first workshop with Mértola, where key elements for transformative change in the territory were jointly identified; and (ii) the co-created work plan, built from collective discussions during and after the focus groups. Informal exchanges, participation in MFN meetings, and the feedback workshop continue to feed this collaborative dynamic, enabling knowledge to circulate between researchers, practitioners, and residents.

Looking ahead, the work plan foresees three experience nurseries (*viveiros de experiência*) in 2026, designed to strengthen community resilience. These are spaces to surface tacit knowledge, experiment with new approaches, and reflect collectively on strategies for regeneration. This process aims to bring lay knowledge to the table on equal footing with technical expertise, recognising it as a legitimate and indispensable element of just governance and co-production.

Impact on Policy and Decision-Making

At the policy level, the testing phase revealed the limits of institutional flexibility. Despite innovative ideas to source food locally and engage cooks and nutritionists in planning public meals, public procurement rules remained unchanged, creating a major barrier to systemic change.

To extend participation and bring decision-making closer to residents, the Municipality adopted a practice of rotating its public meetings across the parishes of Mértola, rather than holding them exclusively in the main village. This approach allowed citizens in more remote areas to engage directly with municipal representatives and created opportunities for the message of regeneration to reach communities that are often less involved in public debate.

In addition to this concern with multiplying the spaces where public issues are discussed, another factor that supported decision-making towards regeneration was the role played by policy intermediaries - particularly ESDIME - which acted as both facilitator and funder. These actors sought creative ways to adapt existing procedures and enable more regenerative procurement practices. While such initiatives did not result in formal rule changes, they encouraged small but significant shifts in institutional behaviour and helped build momentum for longer-term transformation.

Community-Level Changes and Social Perceptions

One of the most notable yet nuanced impacts of the interventions was the shift in community-level perception of biodiversity, land use, and regeneration. It is important to frame this not as an immediate or quantifiable transformation, but as an evolving process—one shaped by exposure, narrative, and participation.

The regenerative strategies led by Terra Sintrópica, Mértola City Council, and other organisations committed with regenerative approach have undeniably elevated Mértola's visibility as a site of experimentation. People from across Portugal and internationally now visit the area to learn about syntropic agriculture and community-based regeneration. Researchers, farmers, and policy actors alike have begun to see Mértola as a reference point.

Yet, within the territory itself, changes in local perception remain gradual. There is a growing awareness among residents of the importance of regenerative practices and of the risks posed by ecological degradation. Community-facing initiatives, such as school programs and participatory events like the "Night at the Market" have helped introduce these ideas into everyday language and practice. The interventions are fostering what could be termed a regenerative imaginary - a shift in how people envision the future of their landscape and livelihoods. The different temporalities in biodiversity literacy are important in this case. Also, the interventions are allowing people to know better about climate change, desertification - in other terms, to know and name the difficulties they are facing as well as the possible alternatives to overcome them.

The full effects of these efforts are not yet measurable. The interventions have laid groundwork, creating the conditions for longer-term cultural change, but the degree to which this will translate into transformed behaviors or policies will only become visible over time. If there is no possibility to state that there was a significant transformation in people's lives, it is certain that there is more awareness, and the vocabulary of regeneration is being ingrained in Mértola's community imagery. It is not possible to affirm how, when, and to what extent the consciousness will lead into an economic transformation in practices. As a very challenging territory dependent on environmentally harsh conditions, it is important to remember that the economic gains are unstable and small, and that economic instability prevents experimentation and limits resilience in the face of potential losses from changing production systems. We are talking about a land where one invests time and resources with no guarantees of sufficient water supply, soil conditions, or temperature stability.

Another subtle but powerful transformation is the disruption of the idea that Mértola's landscape must remain unchanged. This reflects a crack in a dominant lock-in-the belief that the landscape's fragility precludes change. New conversations, partnerships, and strategies are nurturing a different imaginary, one in which Mértola's ecological challenges are not immutable but are open to collective response. The Mértola City Council has played a pivotal role here: beyond leading community calls for reflection, it has actively encouraged and supported the set of regenerative projects taking place in the territory. Alongside ESDIME (funding proposals), ALSUD (educational initiatives), TSA (regenerative projects that reinforce social cohesion), and MBS (research approach), this municipal leadership has contributed to a growing collective understanding of the future challenges the landscape will face. This shared awareness is a crucial starting point for tackling this lock-in that hinders the introduction of new agricultural practices.

Another lock-in being addressed is related to the beginnings of a co-governance culture and the value of community knowledge and participation of individuals and organisations in decision-making. In Portugal, the practice of participation is highly institutionalised and often does not accommodate ordinary citizens. While Mértola may not yet have fully tackled this lock-in - also due to territorial constraints and the dispersion of its population across hundreds of small villages - initiatives like "Night at the Market" represent meaningful investments in social cohesion and food literacy.

An additional persistent lock-in stems from a broader political and cultural mentality that values only scalable, externally designed solutions - typically formulated under national and EU directives that often lack articulation with local realities. While the EU aims to promote green and regenerative policies, many of the funding instruments available to agriculture continue to favor extensive, high-input practices such as tillage. This mismatch generates a significant contradiction: locally tailored solutions - crafted through participatory processes and adapted to Mértola's unique conditions - struggle to secure recognition and support. Their specificity, which should be a strength, becomes a barrier in systems that prioritize standardisation and replicability over place-based knowledge and governance.

The work with other municipalities and Mértola's capacity to attract interest in its regenerative strategies strengthen its internal value and legitimacy. This is particularly relevant in light of the ongoing plan to create an autonomous and healthy food system grounded in the food basin concept, which involves multiple municipalities, actors, and community members. It creates expectations, networks, and collective visions.

This Mértola that gains international recognition - attracting researchers, activists, and policymakers - also reinforces the value of its strategies for local residents. Mértola's participation in intermunicipal partnerships is generating a form of reflective recognition: as neighboring municipalities adopt similar approaches, residents begin to re-evaluate their own local efforts, seeing them not as isolated but as part of a broader regenerative shift.

This local momentum, however, still unfolds within a broader political landscape shaped by a prevailing national mentality that privileges scalable, externally designed solutions - for example, bringing water to dry areas - often without questioning how EU regenerative policies can realistically be implemented on the ground.

In this context, while measurable change may not yet be fully apparent, the interventions have clearly contributed to a shift in local imaginaries. More people are aware of the importance of regeneration, and more conversations are taking place about the future of the territory. This does not yet translate into structural transformation, but it represents an essential precondition: a community that is beginning to see itself - and its landscape - differently.

2.3.7 Discussion

Generally speaking, the political imagination in the Alentejo region has affected the recognition and scalability of Mertola's regenerative strategies. This prevalent imagination has been grounded on discussions on river transposition, adapted irrigation systems and

subsidies improvements to guaranteeing economic activities, no matter how they are effectively connected with territorial needs. It has affected Mértola as policies and strategies developed have been concerned with making livestock and food production economic activities less impactful on the soil and on the water available.

Mértola not only has to confront regional and national imageries that disregard approaches such as syntropic agriculture, organic and local food production, and holistic grazing for pasture, but also faces the challenge of overcoming a prevailing perception that its fragile landscape is doomed - that many species will not survive in the most severe scenarios.

The lesson learnt is that changing mentality takes time, and science-based information is not enough to guarantee the change acceleration that is expected. Cultural change requires not only attention towards the rhythm of community and organisations but also the direct involvement of ordinary citizens in the design of the future expected scenarios; otherwise they will not be internally legitimated. It means that some strategies are crucial for making this change feasible, namely:

1. the ongoing invitation for the community to progressively experiment with new ways of doing and see the advantages for themselves (eg. less poor soil, less problems associated with the livestock size because of the holistic grazing model, the need for fodder purchase reduced during droughts);
2. the creation of opportunities for this experimentation by the public body and local organisations;
3. Mutual learning among those rooted in the land - who recognise one another as credible references for what is possible locally - has helped shape an informal community of practice. What Mértola's strategy has shown us is that this progressive cultural change might start to happen if farmers are stimulated to engage in experimentation. This progressive change and the way it was fostered can be seen in an interviewee's remark:

"What we said was that we knew a few different ways of doing things (grazing) that seemed to be working in semi-arid areas like ours, and the proposal was, 'What if we learned together?' And that's exactly what we started doing: visiting other farmers who had been doing this for longer and then holding workshops with other farmers who had been doing this for a long time and knew a lot about it, and together we learned. And together we made plans for each of them, and together we did pilot projects on each of their farms to see how it works, both this system and the key-line design system" (interviewee 11, our translation).

This testimony illustrates the essence of Mértola's regenerative approach: transformation is not imposed but co-created, through shared learning and experimentation. These collective experiences gradually build confidence, strengthen local networks, and open new pathways for cultural change across the territory.

Building on these shared learning experiences, it becomes clear that Mértola's regenerative efforts still face structural constraints that limit their potential scalability. Without embedding regenerative approaches in agricultural and other high-impact sectors, the agroecological transition remains delayed, and the impact of local experiments risks staying fragmented. A broader commitment from national and regional

economic policies is necessary to align incentives with a nature-positive society and support the transition beyond the local scale.

Collaboration and the More-Than-Human Perspective

Mértola's case demonstrates the importance of experimenting with farming and grazing practices that foster a more balanced relationship between society and nature - one that recognises the agency of non-human beings.

Although syntropic agriculture is not yet dominant in Mértola, its principles can be observed in different initiatives, even when the term itself is not used. Its adoption in Malhadinha Vegetable Garden (Horta da Malhadinha) proved to be a smart way of both fighting against the soil impoverishment and regulating microclimate in a semi-arid region. By combining forestry and food production, syntropic agriculture has become a timely setting at the present time as it is grounded on the perspective of "regeneration by use". As its creator, Ernst Götsch, described, syntropic agriculture gives ["each plant the ideal conditions for its development, placing each one in their just right position in space and time"](#) (Andrade, 2019). This brings us back to a concept dear to syntropy: respect for temporality.

The more-than-human perspective adopted by syntropic agriculture reframes farming as an exercise in collaboration rather than competition. Collaboration here means recognising the co-dependence and productive interaction between plants, animals, insects, fungi and other microorganisms, making use of them towards soil recovery. This approach connects ecological restoration with a pedagogical process, allowing communities to experience regeneration not only as a set of technical solutions but also as a way of cultivating new relational practices.

Syntropy also encompasses an inclusive approach, engaging the community in decision-making processes related to biodiversity management. A lesson learnt from Terra Sintropica's approach has to do with their attention towards the cultural dimension, not only recognising each group's pace for the mentality change but also involving marginalised communities in the planning and implementation of biodiversity regeneration projects - as happened with refugees in the Shelter Land Project. Syntropic agriculture in Mértola contributed to Afghan refugees' self-empowerment but also allowed the regenerative project to benefit from their knowledge and perspectives. Terra Sintropica's concern with fostering the participation of different groups - including the older persons and children as vulnerable groups and refugees as a minority in European context - demonstrated the social relevance of encouraging community-led stewardship towards regenerative practices in the territory.

By positioning regeneration as both an ecological practice and a pedagogical process of recognising diverse knowledges, Mértola highlights that transformative change requires creating spaces where scientific, traditional, intercultural and experiential knowledge interact on equal footing. This plurality of knowledges reinforces the legitimacy of regenerative governance and ensures that biodiversity strategies are socially anchored as well as ecologically sound.

Isolation as a persistent lock-in for regeneration

Despite the many strategies directed toward biodiversity regeneration, **the geographic, social, and economic isolation** experienced by communities in Mértola remains one of the most persistent lock-ins faced in the territory. Isolation - whether physical, infrastructural, or informational - limits not only the flow of regenerative knowledge but also the distribution of its benefits. Some residents are unaware of local innovations, while others are structurally excluded from accessing them. For example, zero-carbon fresh food deliveries in Mértola (Fresh Food on Wheels Project) represent an important environmental achievement, yet they do not reach dispersed or mobility-restricted populations. This reveals a deeper challenge: regenerative measures must not only address ecological systems, but must be consciously designed to foster community integration. Without a clear socio-cultural and economic axis, these initiatives risk reinforcing existing inequalities and overlooking the very populations most vulnerable to ecological collapse. This leads us to understand that territorial or spatial justice must be seen not only in connection with, but as an integral dimension of, social and environmental justice. In territories like Mértola, where mobility and infrastructural access are unevenly distributed, spatial inequality can reinforce ecological vulnerability - making justice in space a precondition for the fair distribution of regenerative benefits.

In Mértola, territorial injustice and the uneven distribution of the fruits of regeneration practices contribute directly to the persistence and the resistance to change. Many individuals who remain geographically isolated do not have access to new scenarios, narratives, or practices of reimagination. This absence of exposure fosters a spiral of exclusion, reinforcing these areas as sites of resistance not due to unwillingness, but due to lack of opportunity. Overcoming this challenge requires more than institutional engagement; it calls for continuous invitations to participate, experiment, and imagine differently.

At the same time, the Mértola experience highlights the importance of integrating local and community knowledge into regenerative processes on equal footing with scientific expertise. Yet, territorial exclusion frequently hinders this integration. Isolated citizens often lack the opportunity to participate in knowledge-sharing spaces, preventing their valuable insights from contributing to broader strategies. This not only limits the potential richness of regeneration initiatives but also creates an epistemic imbalance where only formalised or institutional knowledge is prioritised.

It is important to note that the Mértola case - and its societal partners - demonstrate clear awareness of the importance of integrating local and community knowledge into regeneration efforts. However, their efforts have not yet been sufficient to fully address this issue, which is why we identify it as a persistent lock-in.

Another persistent lock-in relates to the difficulty of integrating ordinary, non-institutionalised citizens into co-governance and participatory processes. Although notable efforts have been made in Mértola to establish participatory forums - which stand as benchmarks when compared to the broader participatory culture in Portugal, largely centred on institutionalised participation - these initiatives have not yet succeeded in systematically involving citizens outside organised structures. . While our fieldwork did not reveal an unmet or explicit demand from these citizens, it remains a central principle of regenerative co-governance to cultivate a participatory culture as a core component of regeneration. Despite important community events, the participation of ordinary citizens

in decision-making remains a work in progress. This dimension of participatory justice must evolve further to ensure the inclusive character of regeneration strategies and the sustainability of their outcomes.

Despite the existence of several forums and participatory spaces, the inclusion of underrepresented and socially marginalised groups - such as Roma and migrant communities - remains limited within Mértola's regenerative strategy.

Territorial injustice further exacerbates this exclusion, especially in the context of environmental vulnerability. These, together with the elderly and isolated populations, are often the groups most exposed to disasters like wildfires or extreme heat, yet they face barriers to accessing water, safe public spaces, or even health assistance. Without integrating these perspectives, regeneration risks being socially detached and unjust. Spatial justice becomes essential: mobility, access to services, and representation are prerequisites for any inclusive transition, and their absence directly interferes with the ability of these groups to engage with and benefit from regenerative change.

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2.4 MRU Case Study: Lithuania

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2.4.1 Short presentation of the case

The Anykščiai dam case study examines one of Lithuania's most emblematic river restoration dilemmas, set within the broader European ambition to reverse biodiversity decline and re-establish free-flowing rivers. Located in the small town of Anykščiai in northeastern Lithuania, the Šventoji River is both an ecological corridor of national importance and a deeply familiar feature of local life. Yet, like many European rivers, it has been altered by the construction of dams. The Anykščiai dam, originally built for hydropower but now functionally obsolete, remains a major barrier to ecological connectivity. It obstructs fish migration, degrades river habitats, and contributes to biodiversity loss. At the same time, the dam has become a visible part of the town's landscape and cultural memory, complicating discussions about its future.

This case sits at the intersection of urgent environmental policy goals and local socio-cultural realities. At the European level, the Water Framework Directive and the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 call for restoring good ecological status in rivers and reconnecting at least 25,000 km of free-flowing waterways. Lithuania's national policies

echo these ambitions, and scientific assessments identify the Anykščiai dam as one of the country's priority barriers for removal due to its ecological impact and limited socio-economic value. However, translating these policy frameworks into local practice is far from straightforward. Earlier efforts to initiate dam removal did not result in a restored river or strong community consensus, reflecting the challenges of aligning ecological imperatives with diverse local perspectives, values, and concerns.

The BIOTraCes project takes up this challenge by investigating how participatory action research (PAR) can support transformative biodiversity governance. Working with societal partners the project explores how inclusive and creative engagement methods can reframe contentious debates into opportunities for dialogue and co-creation. Through stakeholder interviews, media and policy analysis, and experimental participatory practices, the research seeks to understand how residents, authorities, businesses, and cultural actors construct meaning around the river, and how their voices can be included in decision-making processes.

The significance of the Anykščiai case lies in both its ecological and social dimensions. Ecologically, dam removal offers a rare opportunity to restore migratory fish populations and re-establish natural fluvial processes. Socially, the case reveals how histories, identities, and attachments to place shape environmental governance. It demonstrates that biodiversity restoration cannot succeed through technical solutions alone but requires building trust, integrating plural knowledge systems, and creating genuine spaces for shared decision-making. In this sense, the Anykščiai dam is not only a barrier in the river but also a symbol of the broader challenge of reconciling ecological sustainability with community resilience across Europe.

2.4.2 Evaluation of strategies in action

Introduction

The Anykščiai case study examines biodiversity regeneration strategies within a locally specific environmental and social context. It focuses on a small town with an ecologically valuable river, that largely natural in character but shaped by the presence of a dam. The Anykščiai dam has been identified as a national priority for restoration due to its potential to improve fish restore connectivity, improve migration routes and improve conditions of aquatic habitats. Previous discussions about dam removal in 2018 did not gain broad acceptance among local residents, authorities, and political representatives, which halted progress toward river restoration. Within this complex setting, our evaluation examines the strategies developed through collaboration between the research team and societal partners Karolina Gurjazkaitė and Jonas Tertelis, implemented between March 2023 and June 2025. The central strategy aimed to create a space for dialogue among stakeholders, ensuring that diverse perspectives were heard while maintaining a focus on biodiversity protection.

Current strategies in action

We began engaging with the Anykščiai case by exploring local media coverage, historical materials, and other sources to better understand the background. The process then unfolded in three phases: (1) extensive individual interviews with stakeholders from diverse groups, (2) ongoing informal exchanges and regular presence in the community, and (3) a collective event by the dam in April 2025 that brought together insights gathered along the way.

This approach was co-designed through five workshops with societal partners between March 2023 and June 2024. Together, we established a working principle that emphasized shared learning — positioning local stakeholders as holders of essential, experience-based knowledge. This orientation differed from the more traditional, expert-led formats that are common across environmental policy and decision-making contexts.

The community event held on April 26, 2025, by the dam reflected the gradual process of understanding diverse perspectives. It was an open, informal gathering where participants took part in several activities, including (1) anonymous perspective-sharing drawn from earlier interviews, (2) sensory mapping of river experiences, and (3) writing personal reflections and wishes to the river. The event made visible that knowledge about the river extends beyond scientific data — encompassing emotional, sensory, and lived experiences that shape how the river is valued and cared for in community life.

Transformative potential

The strategies tested in the Anykščiai case demonstrated elements of transformative potential in several ways. They encouraged a shift from top-down decision-making toward more community-inclusive and participatory forms of dialogue, giving the community greater power, voice, and responsibility in shaping its environment. This process helped connect environmental policy objectives with local knowledge, values, and lived experience. It created opportunities for residents to share place-based insights and emotional connections to the river, opening what several participants described as “a different kind of conversation” — one that recognised the dam as both an ecological barrier and a cultural landmark.

The activities established a shared space for diverse actors who rarely meet in the same setting. NGO representatives, local residents, business owners, technical experts, environmentalists, and others had the opportunity to exchange perspectives directly and informally. Through this process, community members moved from being observers to active participants in discussions about their living environment, strengthening their sense of ownership, agency, and confidence in contributing to environmental decision-making. The dialogue fostered mutual curiosity, understanding, and respect among stakeholders, creating foundations for more inclusive and collaborative approaches to the river’s future.

The participatory activities revealed that people value the river in similar ways and for similar reasons. In the wish-writing exercise, participants expressed hopes for a “living” river — a vision that united rather than divided perspectives on restoration. The sensory mapping activity illustrated the many ways people relate to the river — through sensory experiences, memory, and daily practice — enriching shared understandings of its ecological and social significance.

Addressing indirect drivers of biodiversity loss

Several indirect drivers of biodiversity loss became visible through the activities and discussions. One recurring theme related to how information about the river is shared and understood locally. The activities revealed that limited awareness and access to clear, trustworthy information about the dam’s ecological effects have weakened people’s ability to engage with biodiversity issues. By creating opportunities for participants to exchange their own experiences and perspectives, including environmental perspectives, in an informal way, the project helped address this gap. Through face-to-face discussions

and the anonymous sharing of interview excerpts, participants could encounter different viewpoints. This format encouraged open reflection and curiosity about the variety of relationships people hold with the river, strengthening awareness and dialogue around ecological change.

In the case of Anykščiai, the dam remains in place even though the ecological impacts of dams are well documented in scientific research. This shows that scientific knowledge alone does not automatically translate into local awareness or collective action. It needs to be communicated in a way that is understandable and builds trust — and in our case, face-to-face communication in an informal setting supported this process. Open dialogue can help build trust and shared understanding — essential steps for addressing these indirect social drivers of biodiversity loss and supporting informed decision-making about the river’s ecological future.

Scalability and replicability

Our engagement in Anykščiai offers several promising directions for strengthening biodiversity governance and community participation. Two complementary pathways stand out:

Horizontal scaling involves applying this engagement approach in other contexts — for example, along different dammed rivers or in other towns. The steps developed in Anykščiai — exploring local media and histories, mapping the social–ecological system and stakeholders, conducting interviews, and progressively opening dialogue — form a clear, adaptable sequence.

Vertical scaling focuses on deepening engagement within the same community. This includes expanding educational activities, integrating biodiversity and dam-related awareness into local institutions, and collaborating with schools, NGOs, and neighborhood groups to build knowledge and long-term capacity for river stewardship.

These ideas align with established frameworks in social innovation literature, such as the “scaling out / scaling up / scaling deep” model (Moore et al. 2015) and related work by Westley & Antadze (2010). Yet, many unknowns remain, especially how the method translates across different political, cultural, or ecological settings. But laying out these possible scaling paths helps frame the next steps without overclaiming results.

Framing of Biodiversity and Local Meanings

The activities invited people to engage with the river in ways that extended beyond formal discussion. Through reflection, writing, and sensory exploration, participants expressed how the river forms part of their everyday lives. They were also introduced to a range of perspectives — including environmental viewpoints — and learned about the issue of change directly from other community members. Some creative elements, such as sensory exercises inspired by theatre, were used not as performance but as a way to make dialogue more human, open, and embodied. This approach encouraged a shift from conventional expert–public interactions toward a space where emotion, memory, and imagination could coexist with scientific perspectives, enriching collective understandings of biodiversity and its local meanings.

Conclusion

The activities invited people to engage with the river in ways that extended beyond formal discussion. Through reflection, writing, and sensory exploration, participants expressed how the river forms part of their everyday lives. They were also introduced to a range of perspectives — including environmental viewpoints — and learned about the issue of change directly from other community members. Some creative elements, such as sensory exercises inspired by theatre, were used not as performance but as a way to make dialogue more human, open, and embodied, forstnering connection.

This approach encouraged a shift from conventional expert–public interactions toward a space where emotion, memory, and imagination could coexist with scientific perspectives, enriching collective understandings of biodiversity and its local meanings. Most importantly, it enabled community members to discuss environmental issues among themselves — to see that the river and its ecosystems matter not only to experts, but to locals as well. Through hearing one another’s arguments, experiences, and emotions, participants could move beyond simply voicing positions to building connections grounded in shared care for the river.

2.4.3 Enablers and disruptors

Attunement and mismatch with broader trends

The biodiversity goals in Anykščiai align strongly with national and European policy directions. Frameworks such as the EU Water Framework Directive, River Basin Management Plans, and the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 provide a solid foundation for restoring rivers and strengthening biodiversity across Europe. Authorities operate within these frameworks, and there is growing potential to enrich them with locally grounded approaches that bring policies to life in specific community contexts. Integrating social, cultural, and experiential dimensions — including local meanings, perceptions, and relationships with the river — can make these frameworks even more effective and meaningful for residents.

Policy efforts typically focus on technical indicators such as restored river kilometers per improved environmental quality indicators. Complementing these measures with community perspectives — rooted in daily experience, memories, and attachment to place — can help bridge ecological goals with the ways people value and interact with their environment. Such connections transform policy implementation into shared stewardship, where success is measured both in ecological outcomes and in community engagement.

Local tourism and recreation businesses already demonstrate how biodiversity and economic activity can complement one another. By building on existing initiatives that showcase the river and its surroundings, future restoration discussions can further integrate nature-based tourism with ecological renewal. This alignment between environmental care, cultural identity, and sustainable livelihoods positions Anykščiai as a promising example of how community and policy can move forward together toward resilient river landscapes.

Enablers and Capacity to Replicate

Several factors enabled meaningful collaboration and engagement. Two societal partners worked together, each contributing distinct strengths: one brought strong technical and environmental expertise, while the other added creative capacity and experience in

community engagement. This interdisciplinary partnership fostered rich discussion and helped link community perspectives with institutional perspectives, making the project more balanced and effective than either could have achieved alone.

Existing informal groups within the community — such as people who use the river for recreation and those involved in local heritage — provided natural entry points for dialogue. These networks made it easier to reach residents and identify others interested in sharing their perspectives. During the April event, participants with diverse views interacted constructively, demonstrating that the community already holds capacity for dialogue and openness to differing opinions.

In Lithuania, a generally strong cultural connection to nature, especially to forests, supports public sensitivity to environmental issues, even where rivers are less central. In Anykščiai, the involvement of local cultural authorities played a practical and trusted role in facilitating introductions and identifying relevant contacts. This collaboration with respected community figures proved essential for building trust and could serve as a model for other contexts where engagement relies on familiarity and personal credibility.

Sustaining and replicating these approaches depends on strengthening local capacity. Training programs, long-term partnerships, and the integration of participatory methods into municipal practices could help maintain momentum beyond the project timeline. By investing in local knowledge, trust, and continuity, similar initiatives can take root elsewhere, linking communities, institutions, and environmental goals in lasting ways.

Disruptors and mitigation capacity

Disruptors can act as catalysts for transformation, revealing tensions and prompting reflection within socio-ecological systems. The capacity to engage with these moments through dialogue, learning, and adaptation determines whether disruption leads to division or constructive change.

A visible disruptor in our case is the ongoing conversation about the river and the dam, which unfolds across multiple levels. Media discussions show a mix of opinions — some in favor of keeping the dam, others supporting its removal. Local media has the power to facilitate informed discussion by reflecting this diversity of perspectives while also giving value to technical and ecological expertise. Public opinion and scientific knowledge are not the same, yet both are important: local voices bring lived experience and social meaning, while technical evidence provides the factual grounding for understanding ecological impacts. When the media highlights both dimensions and explores the reasoning behind them, it can help people see how different perspectives connect and foster a more balanced, informed dialogue. Similar debates have also reached local politics. What could help now is the creation of clearer and better-connected spaces for these conversations to continue — ensuring that discussion, wherever it happens, becomes more inclusive and constructive.

Another possible disruptor could be a broader recognition that the dam itself is one of the main sources of harm to local biodiversity. Many residents and stakeholder groups may still be developing an understanding of the scale of that impact and how far it reaches beyond the immediate area. Building this awareness through school education, public learning initiatives, and creative communication could gradually shift how the dam is perceived — from a familiar structure to a visible part of the ecological challenge.

Public discussions, whether in local meetings or through the media, can also play an important role when they focus on learning rather than blame. Presenting science in ways that connect with local experience and identity can help people see the issue as shared and encourage collective reflection on the river's future.

Influence of governance frameworks

National and EU-level policies set ambitious goals for river restoration and biodiversity protection through mechanisms such as the EU Water Framework Directive, other nature directives, and the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030. However, translating these frameworks into local practice is complex. Municipalities operate within diverse social and political realities that influence how environmental objectives are interpreted, prioritized, and implemented.

Previous efforts to present the issue of dammed rivers to the community became polarized and highly politicized. Many community members perceived these initiatives as representing narrow interests rather than shared goals, which limited trust and engagement. They reported feeling that information was delivered to them rather than co-created with them. Politicians who addressed the issue publicly also struggled to gain support, suggesting that earlier communication approaches left a lasting imprint on local perceptions. These experiences continue to shape how municipal authorities and political actors navigate the topic today.

At the same time, environmental perspectives are not consistently represented in broader local development planning. For example, the vision for the Anykščiai city centre reflects strong cultural, social, and ecological ambitions, yet gives limited attention to questions surrounding the dam. This suggests that while environmental considerations are increasingly present in urban planning, the specific challenges and opportunities linked to river management have not yet been fully integrated into the town's long-term vision.

It is understandable that municipal authorities must balance national environmental goals with local priorities such as social stability, heritage, and alignment with community expectations. Yet there remains limited understanding of how the issue is perceived locally: some stakeholders view the dam as uncontroversial, while others anticipate community opposition to its removal. This uncertainty makes public dialogue a sensitive process, where bold environmental decisions are difficult to advance and incremental measures, such as improving fish passage, are often preferred.

Interviews revealed a wide range of narratives surrounding the dam. Some residents expressed a strong sense of attachment, viewing the dam as a symbol of familiarity, historical continuity, and everyday use of the landscape. In this context, technical arguments about ecological connectivity can appear abstract unless linked to local meanings and experiences. Other participants emphasized the need for clear, trustworthy answers about hydrological, landscape, ecological, and safety aspects, showing confidence in scientific and technical expertise. Common narratives also surfaced — for instance, that ecosystems have adapted to human influence, or that other dams, such as Kavarskas, have greater ecological impact and should be addressed first. These perspectives cannot be addressed solely through administrative or regulatory instruments; they require time, dialogue, preparedness, and sensitivity that extend beyond standard governance procedures.

While our work did not focus directly on municipal administration, it became clear that national and EU biodiversity frameworks must be connected more closely to local realities. Patient involvement, education, and a shared vision for the future are essential components of this process. The challenge reflects procedural complexity, limited communication between governance levels, and practical constraints related to time and resources. Nevertheless, it is evident that translating policy ambitions into local action requires more than formal compliance — it depends on continuity, coordination, and spaces for dialogue across institutional scales.

Together, these dynamics illustrate how governance frameworks both enable and challenge local environmental action — their influence extends beyond policy design, shaping the trust, participation, and dialogue required to translate ambition into tangible ecological outcomes.

2.4.4 Failed and successful practices

Successful Practices

Several practices described earlier (e.g., gradual engagement, mixed formats for participation, and the societal partners' complementary roles) also appear here as "successful practices." This overlap is intentional: the case timeframe is short, and the same elements that enabled progress also proved effective in practice. We chose to move step by step—starting with media analysis, historical sources review, interviews, then small-scale public activities—so that each next action was informed by what we had already learned rather than rushed by external expectations or premature experimentation.

The April 2025 event showed that a gradual process can create space for open and constructive discussion on a sensitive topic. Participants from different community groups joined throughout the day, engaging in activities such as sharing anonymous interview quotes, mapping meaningful places along the river, and writing wishes to the river. These varied formats encouraged participation from people with different comfort levels and viewpoints. The event demonstrated that careful groundwork can turn a potentially divisive issue into an opportunity for shared reflection and dialogue.

Working across different kinds of expertise proved important. Combining environmental science with creative, participatory methods showed that the dam issue is not only about ecology or engineering but also about people's relationships with the river. Looking at it from technical, social, and cultural angles helped us see that different stakeholder groups might have very different understandings about the river management.

The process also helped the team adjust participatory action research (PAR) to real-life river management. For researchers used to working with numbers and data, using participatory and creative tools opened new ways to link facts with people's experiences. This flexibility, mixing structured research with local stories and observations, could be a useful example for others dealing with similar, complex river restoration cases.

Failed or Less Effective Practices

The idea of using theatrical methods was set aside for now rather than abandoned. Early in the process, the team considered applied theatre as a way to explore community

experiences with the river. However, interviews and observations showed that we did not yet understand the local context well enough to use such expressive tools.

Youth participation was limited, mainly because of ethical and procedural requirements for involving minors. Choosing not to proceed under these constraints was the responsible course of action, though it meant that younger voices were underrepresented. The team partly addressed this gap by including insights from educators, cultural workers, and young adults over 18 who were familiar with how younger residents relate to the river.

Critical Gaps and Missed Opportunities

While the early phase focused mainly on collaboration with societal partners, this deliberate choice meant that wider stakeholder engagement was postponed. Broader involvement — especially during planning — will be needed in later stages, but at this point the priority was to build a solid foundation for dialogue rather than expand participation too quickly.

The engagement process did not extend to religious leaders, whose perspectives could be valuable in future initiatives. This remains an area worth exploring, as religious communities often hold influence in shaping values and public attitudes toward nature. Their knowledge systems — rooted in moral and spiritual interpretations of the natural world — can either support or complicate biodiversity efforts, depending on how they are approached.

During the feedback workshop, societal partners reflected on the reach and scope of the intervention. The April event demonstrated that constructive dialogue across diverse perspectives was possible — a key proof of concept for future engagement. Given the project's early phase, the event was intentionally kept small-scale to allow careful observation of interaction dynamics and to refine methods before expanding participation. Future stages may build on this tested format through broader outreach and collaboration with local organizations once readiness and interest grow naturally.

Overall, what may appear as “missed opportunities” were, in practice, deliberate pacing choices. Each step was designed to inform the next, ensuring that engagement grows sustainably rather than reactively.

Lessons and Future Directions

The experience confirms that transformation in biodiversity governance requires working at the pace communities can sustain rather than imposing external timelines. Future interventions must balance the proven success of careful, graduated approaches with the need for broader community inclusion. The lessons learned suggest that effective strategies must be simultaneously patient and proactive, structured yet adaptive, protective of fragile trust while ambitious about expanding participation.

Lesson 1: Process before scale. In contexts shaped by earlier, less successful attempts to engage communities, the order and pace of engagement determine whether dialogue is possible at all. Past efforts around dam removal were often highly political and focused on imposing “correct” solutions rather than understanding what mattered to local people. These top-down approaches, which overlooked the community's values, needs, and lived relationships with rivers, felt alienating and counterproductive.

Our approach sought to do things differently. Before moving to collective discussions, we focused on understanding the local context through a mix of methods—media analysis, individual interviews, and informal conversations. This process allowed us to recognize the diversity of opinions about river biodiversity and to create space for residents to express their perspectives and values freely—helping us see what truly mattered to them.

This sequencing proved essential. By beginning with listening and reflection, rather than public debate, we helped transform a previously divisive issue into one that could be discussed with less tension and greater mutual understanding. True engagement, we found, does not begin with scaling up participation but with careful groundwork that makes participation meaningful. Before expanding the dialogue, it is crucial to understand what matters most to the community—and only then begin working together toward solutions.

Lesson 2: Knowing when (and how) to adapt as a form of success. Some planned activities—such as applied theatre methods or direct youth involvement—were postponed after it became clear that they were not appropriate for the situation and could risk closing down dialogue rather than deepening it. Recognizing these limits early helped avoid missteps and kept the process constructive and relevant to the context.

Instead of pushing for attention or triggering a major public debate, we explored how different approaches and messages resonated with the community. Our intention was to create space for reflection, foster participation, and strengthen local voices—to encourage collective, participatory action rather than rush toward predetermined outcomes.

This flexibility—adapting the pace, language, and tools of engagement—proved just as valuable as introducing new ideas. Adaptability became a form of success in itself, allowing the process to remain open, responsive, and aligned with the evolving dynamics of the community and the discussion.

Lesson 3: Steady and naturally growing participation. Future engagement should build on the connections and approaches developed so far, gradually bringing in new groups, especially young people, educators, and community figures. Working with schools, cultural venues, and local initiatives could provide ongoing ways for people to stay involved beyond single projects.

Lesson 4: From learning to governance. The implementation of national and international environmental and biodiversity goals is closely linked to successful collaboration with local-level actors. Strengthening this connection requires maintaining open communication between policy, research, and community levels. Specialists who understand both the local context and community dynamics can play a key role—helping translate broad environmental objectives into practical, locally meaningful actions.

Lesson 5: With interdisciplinarity to practice. Interdisciplinarity—linking social and psychological sciences, environmental science, and creative disciplines—has proven useful in connecting ecological, social, and cultural aspects of fluvial biodiversity and revealing new perspectives. Such collaboration fosters more innovative approaches to environmental challenges. Each interdisciplinary team combines unique skills, enabling novel ways of understanding and addressing local cases. Yet effective collaboration requires preparation, shared learning, and institutional support. To make interdisciplinarity a working norm rather than an experiment, it should be promoted at all

levels: encouraged at the European level, embedded in national scientific and policy frameworks, and applied on local levels, e.g. via practical guidance or short-term interdisciplinary teams. Embedding such practices across governance layers would build a culture where interdisciplinarity drives innovation in environmental action.

2.4.5 Co-learning

Co-learning as a general principle and its relevance in our case

Co-learning served as one of the core guiding principles of this project. Throughout the project timeline, teams observed one another's methodological choices and progress as they developed their own cases. This exchange fostered mutual reflection, inspiration, and adaptation across disciplines.

For our team in particular, most members came from qualitative research backgrounds. Observing the work of other teams encouraged us to engage more actively with participatory approaches and to experiment with integrating them into our established methods. For instance, inspired by systematic literature reviews, we conducted a media analysis of national discourses surrounding dams. Drawing on reflective practices typical of qualitative inquiry, we approached the process carefully and analytically, taking time to map and understand each next step. We also consulted international experts with experience in researching the social dimensions of dam removal, incorporating insights from their approaches into our own work.

Within our research team, co-learning meant finding ways to bridge different disciplinary perspectives. Environmental scientists, psychologists, and creative practitioners each brought distinct methodological and theoretical orientations that needed to be aligned. We organized several internal workshops to clarify what each method could contribute, identify where approaches might overlap or diverge, and determine how to combine them to support the project's goals. This ongoing and reflective dialogue was essential to creating a truly shared approach rather than a collection of separate methods.

Co-learning also extended beyond the research team to our interactions with local communities. Through interviews and informal conversations, we gained insight into how residents perceive the river—what values, beliefs, and needs are associated with it, and what visions they hold for its future. These exchanges challenged and reshaped our initial assumptions, broadening our understanding of the river's complex, multilayered, and multidimensional meanings. The discussions also created space for reflection among some participants, helping them articulate their relationships with the river in ways that could not have been anticipated at the outset.

Co-learning in the writing process

The feedback workshop with societal partners on August 1, 2025, demonstrated the extent to which collective understanding had deepened over the course of the project. Participants collaboratively analyzed the transformation process, examining both outcomes and shifts in perspective that had emerged through interdisciplinary engagement.

A central point of discussion revolved around the meaning of transformative change. Two complementary perspectives emerged. The environmental societal partner emphasized measurable ecological outcomes—such as projects restoring river connectivity and

generating visible improvements in ecosystem functioning—while the societal partner focusing on social aspects highlighted relational dimensions, including community capacity for dialogue, shared responsibility, and collective action. The exchange revealed that transformation can only be considered successful when these two dimensions—material and relational change—advance together. Ecological restoration without community engagement risks remaining superficial: for long-term sustainability, local actors must be informed, supported, and feel genuine ownership of the process.

The environmental societal partner further stressed that environmental issues need to be placed firmly on local agendas and prioritized through sustained technical, financial, and institutional support. Local communities should be recognized not as passive recipients of environmental policy, but as active contributors to national and European environmental goals. The societal partner focusing on social aspects emphasized that the persistent gap between regional and national governance levels must be addressed to ensure inclusion and coherence in decision-making.

True transformation also requires a shift in perception. People will not act if they do not recognize a problem or see their role in addressing it. Awareness and understanding are therefore preconditions for engagement. Inviting communities to take part in identifying problems and designing solutions cultivates both responsibility and motivation. Environmental change should not be viewed as the task of a few, but as a collective democratic effort—a shared process of caring for and restoring the natural systems that sustain us. When people see ecological restoration as an opportunity to give back to nature, it becomes not merely a policy goal, but a meaningful expression of reciprocity and belonging.

Co-learning in this case study

Throughout fieldwork, co-learning took multiple forms. Interdisciplinary research meetings integrated diverse knowledge systems. Team members brought contrasting yet complementary perspectives—the environmental researcher and the theater director, for example, approached community engagement differently but in mutually reinforcing ways. This interplay fostered understanding between scientific and cultural viewpoints, ensuring that neither was marginalized. It created conditions for authentic problem-solving and the pursuit of common ground, leading to productive and thought-provoking dialogue.

The April 2025 event exemplified co-learning with the broader community. Participants encountered perspectives they had not previously considered. The synthesis of “wishes to the river” expressed a shared vision of a “living river,” a locally co-created concept that conveyed collective aspirations more effectively than technical language.

Stakeholder interviews reflected similar dynamics. Technical experts and residents offered complementary insights: scientists documented biodiversity loss, while older residents described the decline of species and fish abundance through lived experience. Combined, these perspectives provided a more comprehensive and compelling understanding of environmental change.

Youth perspectives remained largely absent due to institutional consent requirements—a missed opportunity for co-learning. Future initiatives could include youth through educational frameworks that enable ethical participation. Discussions also revealed self-exclusionary patterns among some individuals who, having previously felt unsupported

by their community, withdrew from collective efforts. Their absence reduced both the inclusivity of the process and opportunities for mutual learning.

Looking ahead, multi-stakeholder co-learning events could help envision scenarios for the river's future. Participants expressed interest in the involvement of technical experts and access to environmental impact assessments, visualizations, models, projections, and evidence-based information on potential changes affecting the community. Experts, in turn, could benefit from engaging with community members' experiential knowledge to better incorporate local perspectives into decision-making.

The central insight is that the river's future cannot be determined by scientific analysis or community preference alone. Sustainable transformation depends on sustained dialogue between different ways of knowing—a process that, though gradual and sometimes challenging, represents the most transformative outcome of co-learning itself.

2.4.6 Testing of interventions

What was tested and why it matters

This section revisits content from earlier chapters, as the guiding questions for this part of the report overlap substantially with topics already addressed. A similar framing is therefore used to maintain conceptual and stylistic consistency across sections.

In the Anykščiai case, the primary approach tested involved gradual engagement with the topic of river restoration and dam removal—an approach that differed markedly from conventional participatory methods. It emphasized creating conditions for constructive dialogue on a sensitive and complex issue, ensuring that diverse perspectives were expressed, heard, and incorporated into decision-making. Central to this process was enabling residents to participate meaningfully and feel a sense of ownership over outcomes, thereby fostering long-term, sustainable transformation in which environmental benefits are achieved through social and cultural change. In essence, the approach sought to nurture a shared sense of reciprocity toward nature—a willingness within the community to care for and sustain the environment. Such change requires support, understanding, recognition of existing values and meanings, and trust, rather than decisions perceived as externally imposed.

The approach focused on understanding relationships within the community and exploring the values, beliefs, and needs connected to the river. It sought to identify what kinds of change people desired, what they valued most, and how they envisioned the river's future before initiating collective discussions. The work unfolded in three stages: first, individual interviews with residents and stakeholders; second, ongoing informal contact and presence in the community; and finally, a collective event in April 2025 that brought together people from diverse backgrounds to reflect on the river's future.

This case reflects a broader challenge in biodiversity governance: how to facilitate dialogue in contexts where environmental change is necessary, yet intertwined with other deeply held values—historical, cultural, aesthetic, and recreational. These overlapping attachments and interpretations of what is “best” for the environment shape the complexity of transformation processes and highlight the importance of inclusive, trust-based engagement.

Description of the testing process

How it was organized

The testing process was organized around a feedback workshop held on August 1, 2025, involving the research team and both societal partners, Karolina Gurjzkaitė and Jonas Tertelis. This 2,5-hour recorded session served as the main forum for collective reflection on the intervention's effectiveness and impact. The discussion was structured around guiding questions addressing transformative change, stakeholder engagement, knowledge co-production, policy influence, community-level outcomes, and broader transformative potential.

Complementary evidence was drawn from the intervention event held on April 26, 2025, beside the dam, which brought together participants from diverse stakeholder groups. Activities included anonymous sharing of perspectives collected through interviews, sensory mapping of river experiences, and collective writing of "wishes to the river." The event successfully created an inclusive setting where participants shared personal experiences and memories of the river, exchanging opinions, knowledge, and reflections on its past, present, and possible futures. The event provided space for informal, unstructured dialogue—where people could speak freely, listen to others' perspectives, and explore different understandings of what the river means and what its future might hold. This atmosphere encouraged genuine exchange and mutual learning, allowing insights to emerge organically through conversation.

Who participated

The feedback workshop included:

- Research team members: Audra Balundė, Aistė Bakaitytė-Bagdonė, and Goda Kaniušonytė
- Societal partners: Karolina Gurjzkaitė (environmental specialist) and Jonas Tertelis (theatre director)

The broader testing process engaged a wide range of stakeholders interviewed throughout the study, local governance representatives, technical specialists, businesses, NGOs, cultural actors, and unaffiliated residents.

Results of testing across key dimensions

Stakeholder engagement and participatory processes

The intervention and accompanying interviews introduced participatory formats not previously applied in the local context. As observed by the theatre societal partner during the feedback workshop, the process rendered the topic of the river more accessible to a broader spectrum of residents by providing a shared setting in which diverse perspectives could be expressed, acknowledged, and discussed constructively.

The participatory process evolved through iterative reflection and adaptation. Insights from early interviews indicated that some initially planned methods—such as applied theatre—were not well suited to this stage of engagement. The team consequently reoriented its approach toward exploratory, discussion-based formats that encouraged gradual involvement and collective sense-making. This flexibility enabled the process to progress at a pace aligned with local dynamics and capacities.

The April intervention served as a practical test of this approach. Participants contributed a wide range of perspectives and expressed interest and surprise at encountering views from neighbors they had not previously engaged with. The anonymous sharing of interview excerpts during the event provided an opportunity for participants to reflect on alternative viewpoints, fostering openness and mutual understanding.

Knowledge co-production and collaboration

The testing process revealed evidence of knowledge co-production, though not always in anticipated forms. This unpredictability is integral to such processes: outcomes cannot be fully pre-defined but emerge through trust—both within the research team and between researchers and the community. Knowledge co-production, in this sense, is a relational practice grounded in openness, dialogue, and mutual learning.

During the feedback workshop, the environmental societal partner reflected that engagement with community members had reshaped her understanding of how sustainable change occurs. She recognized that lasting environmental transformation must originate within the community itself. The community cannot be excluded from the process; its members require access to clear, reliable information and opportunities to ask questions and engage critically in order to develop trust in environmental initiatives. She observed that residents sought shared ownership of environmental ideas and actions, demonstrating a strong underlying appreciation of nature and a willingness to contribute when their perspectives are acknowledged and valued.

The theatre societal partner described a similar transformation, noting: “I can no longer think about the river without considering the entire ecosystem. This now influences my creative work in other projects.” His reflection underscores that exposure to diverse forms of knowledge—scientific, local, and experiential—can reshape how individuals perceive environmental systems and approach their own professional practice. It illustrates that knowledge co-production extends beyond the exchange of information; it involves internalizing new perspectives that influence how people think, act, and imagine future possibilities.

Despite these insights, important gaps remained in what was tested. Several participants emphasized the need for concrete, localized analyses demonstrating the potential effects of dam removal and other environmental interventions. They expressed interest in clear assessments outlining both benefits and trade-offs—how such actions might influence the ecosystem, water levels, landscape, and public safety. Providing these context-specific projections would not only support informed decision-making but also strengthen trust between experts and communities by ensuring that environmental discussions are grounded in locally relevant evidence. Nevertheless, some community members continued to question whether change was necessary at all, reflecting the persistence of attachment to the current state of the river and differing interpretations of what constitutes improvement.

Impact on policy and decision-making

The intervention did not aim to produce immediate policy change but to generate insights for more effective environmental governance. The findings underscored that constructive dialogue on complex environmental issues is possible when discussions are framed around shared concerns and local meanings. Feedback discussions revealed persistent gaps in representation: environmental perspectives are often underrepresented in local

decision-making processes, which can result in unbalanced or short-term outcomes. Strengthening their inclusion—through both formal mechanisms and informal engagement—could enhance the integration of environmental considerations into local governance.

At a broader scale, the case illustrates a fundamental governance challenge. The environment is increasingly at risk and addressing this requires collective responsibility, political commitment, and concrete action. Yet the key question remains: how can a stronger sense of ownership be cultivated within broader communities, particularly at the local level? Local contexts are shaped by historical, cultural, and social specificities that must be acknowledged and incorporated into governance processes. Sustainable transformation, therefore, is best understood as positive environmental change rooted in transformation within the community—where ecological restoration and social empowerment progress together.

Community-level changes and social perceptions

While no major shifts in community attitudes could yet be observed, the intervention provided valuable space for reflection on environmental issues related to the river and the dam. It offered opportunities for residents—including those who had not previously participated in public discussions—to express their perspectives, experiences, and questions. The process helped bring forward a wider range of voices, particularly those that had remained unheard between more polarized positions. These participants often approached the topic with curiosity rather than fixed opinions, raising questions and exploring uncertainties. Such openness proved valuable for fostering reflection and dialogue within the community.

Through the intervention, participants were able to articulate their own values and views regarding the dam and the river's future, and to recognize the diversity of perspectives within the community. The event also allowed residents to voice concerns and identify the kinds of information and conditions necessary for them to support potential future changes—such as access to trustworthy data, scientific evidence, and clear communication about impacts.

The intervention created a space for participants to discuss and reflect on the river, the dam, biodiversity, restoration opportunities, and the broader meanings attached to this specific site—community events, recreational spaces, daily walks, and memories of kayaking, swimming, or fishing. Moving beyond technical framings, the interviews and the April event invited participants to consider the river as something they are in relationship with. Writing “wishes to the river” and sharing personal memories encouraged emotional and reflective engagement, resonating with how people experience the river in their everyday lives.

The intervention's scope was necessarily limited. As the theatre societal partner observed during the feedback workshop, true transformation implies a depth of change from which “there is no way back”—a process that requires sustained engagement over time. The April event demonstrated that constructive dialogue about the river is possible; however, broader structural and policy transformations demand direct engagement with relevant stakeholders, formal proposals, and long-term commitment.

The testing also revealed hesitations toward environmental discourse. Several participants expressed skepticism about environmental initiatives, citing concerns over

political agendas, frameworks detached from local realities, and doubts about the need for action. These perspectives underscore the challenge of building trust in environmental governance. Such trust depends on transparent communication, competence, and genuine attention to community well-being, supported by clear, evidence-based information.

The April event showed that relational approaches—grounded in place, memory, and everyday experience—can lower barriers to participation and foster discussion. This indicates a transformative potential for governance processes that prioritize inclusion.

Transformative potential

The testing revealed both the possibilities and limitations of change. The April event demonstrated that it is possible to discuss the river from a relational perspective—emphasizing connection, shared meaning, and community experience rather than technical or political framings. Including environmental perspectives proved essential for helping participants become familiar with ecological arguments and ensuring that these views were heard, understood, and supported. The event avoided politicization or imposition; progress was achieved instead through dialogue and relationship-building. Such relational exchanges represent early stages of transformative change, where new understandings and relationships begin to reshape how communities and institutions approach environmental issues.

The feedback workshop indicated that engagement also shifted perspectives within the research team and among societal partners. The environmental societal partner reflected that collaboration with community members had reshaped her approach—reinforcing the view that environmental change is necessary but must enable choice within the community and address a broader spectrum of concerns, such as accessibility, green spaces, and cultural heritage. The theatre societal partner noted that ecological thinking had begun to influence his creative work. These perspective shifts illustrate transformative change as a gradual reorientation of values and practices—change that occurs not through policy reform alone, but through learning, empathy, and reimagining relationships with nature and society.

The intervention was exploratory rather than comprehensive, but it created opportunities for dialogue within one community context. The approach could be adapted to educational settings—both formal and informal—where discussions about rivers and ecosystems may help foster long-term environmental literacy. The methods tested could also inform governance practice by offering ways to engage diverse groups—from local communities to national institutions—in experiential, trust-based dialogue. Such discussions, grounded in human connection rather than bureaucratic procedure or mediated communication, can build empathy, mutual understanding, and recognition of environmental complexity. In governance terms, this signals transformative potential—moving from hierarchical, technocratic decision-making toward participatory, relational, and trust-based processes. For such approaches to be effective, environmental perspectives—ranging from experiential and local to scientific and technical—must be actively included in these dialogues to ensure that ecological knowledge is represented, contextualized, and collectively understood.

A further challenge concerns the limited direct experience many residents have with the river's biodiversity. Apart from anglers and nature enthusiasts, few community members regularly interact with the ecological dimensions of the river. This disconnection can

reduce understanding of environmental issues. Expanding opportunities for residents to experience biodiversity—through community events, educational programs, or creative interventions—could deepen relational engagement, strengthen emotional ties to the river, and foster more supportive attitudes toward environmental stewardship. These experiential processes are crucial components of transformative change, enabling individuals to reconnect with local ecosystems and to translate awareness into sustained care and action.

Reflections on the intervention's transformative potential

Based on the testing process, the intervention demonstrated that structured dialogue about environmental topics can work when conversations focus on relationships and shared experiences. The approach created space for diverse perspectives without requiring immediate consensus or generating conflict.

The transformative elements include:

- **Methodological approach:** The graduated process—moving from individual interviews to collective engagement—offers a model that could be adapted for other contexts. This approach complements expert knowledge by creating space for community perspectives in environmental governance.
- **Relationship transformation:** The intervention may have contributed to evolving relationships between researchers and the community, between different stakeholder groups, and between people and the river itself. While these shifts cannot be measured directly, the process created conditions in which they could begin to develop.
- **Narrative expansion:** By making visible the full spectrum of community perspectives and introducing relational framings of human–river relationships, the intervention expanded imaginative possibilities beyond dichotomic pro/anti-dam positions.
- **Experiential connection:** The testing also revealed that many residents have limited direct experience with the river's biodiversity, which can constrain understanding of ecological issues. Expanding opportunities for people to encounter and experience local ecosystems—through education, events, or creative activities—could further deepen relational engagement, strengthen emotional ties to the river, and foster more supportive attitudes toward environmental stewardship.

The testing also pointed toward areas for future development: building on this approach in other community settings, connecting insights to broader governance processes, and developing the site-specific studies that participants requested.

Lessons and open questions for future considerations

From these observations, several key lessons for transformative biodiversity governance can be drawn:

- **Consider sequencing.** In similar contexts, beginning with context analysis (site visits, media and historical review, stakeholder mapping) and then moving to individual conversations before collective events can help participants feel more confident and prepared for group dialogue.

- **Acknowledge and integrate multiple knowledge systems.** Technical expertise, local observations, emotional connections, and cultural values all contributed to understanding the river in this case. Recognizing and valuing these forms of knowledge strengthens legitimacy and inclusiveness in governance processes.
- **Prioritize process alongside outcomes.** The structure and facilitation of dialogue directly influence who feels able to participate and what perspectives surface. While such spaces do not eliminate disagreement, they clarify its basis and enable constructive exchange.
- **Center personal and relational connections.** Participants engaged most strongly when reflecting on their memories, daily interactions, and hopes for the river's future. Attending to these relational dimensions can foster empathy and motivate collective action.
- **Extend learning beyond discussion.** Creating experiential opportunities for residents to interact with biodiversity—through shared activities and observation—can reinforce awareness and deepen the social foundations for long-term environmental transformation.

Looking ahead, future initiatives could build on this approach by applying it in other community settings, linking locally grounded insights to broader governance processes, and developing the site-specific studies requested by participants. Together, these lessons suggest that transformation in biodiversity governance depends not only on institutional change but also on fostering relationships, dialogue, and lived connections with nature.

Several open questions emerged from the testing:

- **Knowledge integration.** What tools and processes can most effectively translate between scientific assessments of ecological change and community experiences of landscape transformation? Developing such mechanisms is essential for bridging the gap between data-driven environmental governance and lived, place-based understanding. Creating opportunities for communities to generate and share environmental knowledge through direct experiences—such as participatory monitoring, creative activities, or collective observation—could strengthen both ecological awareness and local stewardship.
- **Sustainability.** How can transformative processes be maintained beyond project timeframes when they rely on continuous relationship-building and trust? Sustaining transformation also requires addressing a broader spectrum of community needs—including those of people with disabilities, families, youth, and the elderly—so that environmental initiatives are inclusive and socially embedded. Long-term sustainability depends on creating institutional structures and allocating resources that can support these relational and inclusive processes across temporal, spatial, and governance scales.

The testing showed that structured dialogue about the river is possible when approached through relationship-building and attention to community priorities. Building on this foundation will require sustained effort across multiple timeframes and governance levels. As the theatre societal partner noted, deep change means that “there is no way back.” The intervention succeeded in creating dialogue and testing methods; however,

achieving enduring transformation will depend on long-term engagement, mutual commitment, and institutional support that carries these relational practices forward.

2.4.7 Discussion

Main insights from testing the interventions

The testing process demonstrated that meaningful discussion about the river can serve as a starting point for transformation within the community—strengthening care for the environment and fostering a more inclusive, community-centered approach to environmental problem-solving. Conversations that begin from lived experience and relationships with the river can build understanding, trust, and a shared sense of responsibility for its future.

The testing confirmed that understanding the river requires integrating diverse forms of knowledge. Scientific and environmental perspectives were complemented by local experience, personal memory, and emotional connection to the place. The most productive moments arose when these different ways of knowing met and informed each other. The process worked best when participants saw themselves as contributors in a shared learning space—different kinds of actors exchanging insights and learning together—rather than as experts and audiences divided by roles or hierarchies.

The way conversations were structured also proved decisive. The anonymous sharing of interview excerpts during the April event enabled participants to engage with contrasting views without feeling exposed, while the “wishes to the river” activity encouraged creativity and emotional reflection. The shared idea of a “living river”—which emerged from participants themselves—captured both ecological and social aspirations for the site. These activities demonstrated that connection precedes change: communities are more likely to care for and support environmental transformation when they feel personally and emotionally connected to the river. For transformation to be genuine, people must be willing to see and experience the river differently, not simply accept imposed changes. This willingness depends on familiarity—with the river’s biodiversity, its rhythms, and its living character. Expanding opportunities for residents to experience the river’s ecosystems directly—through shared observation, creative practices, or environmental learning—can deepen understanding, foster attachment, and build the foundation for lasting stewardship.

Aspects that showed promise or traction

The testing process highlighted several elements that proved effective in engaging participants and demonstrated potential for strengthening future environmental governance practices.

Individual interviews as a foundation for collective dialogue. Conducting one-on-one interviews before collective engagement allowed participants to share their perspectives privately and at their own pace. When anonymized excerpts from these interviews were later introduced during the April event, participants could listen to diverse community views without pressure to defend their own positions. This approach revealed the range of knowledge present—scientific, observational, and experiential—and established a constructive basis for open discussion.

Facilitating informal, inclusive discussion spaces. Informal discussion formats allowed multiple forms of knowledge to surface and interact. The April event’s design—combining anonymous interview excerpts with participatory activities such as drawing, writing, and open conversation—enabled engagement without hierarchy or polarization. By bringing together scientific perspectives, local observations, and personal narratives, participants developed a more integrated understanding of the river’s condition and its role in community life.

Supporting technical knowledge with local meaning. Framing discussions through personal memories, everyday relationships, and shared visions for the community’s future made participation more accessible and meaningful. Activities such as place-based storytelling and sensory mapping resonated with how residents already relate to their environment, demonstrating that environmental issues can be explored through culturally familiar and emotionally grounded practices. At the same time, for the future, integrating clear and context-specific technical information—such as visualizations or localized assessments of water levels, biodiversity change, and safety—can enhance these relational approaches. When environmental and technical knowledge is communicated through locally meaningful narratives, it becomes more understandable, trusted, and actionable within the community, strengthening the connection between scientific understanding and lived experience.

Involving trusted and knowledgeable actors. The participation of environmental specialists, local enthusiasts, and in future iterations academics and technical experts can play a crucial role in fostering understanding and care for the environment. Trusted actors, such as environmental specialists, local environmentalists, and community enthusiasts—can help build stronger environmental narratives within local contexts, making these topics more relevant and relatable to residents. Such interpersonal engagement and credibility have proven more effective in raising awareness and building care than data-driven communication alone.

Future direction: fostering direct experience with biodiversity. Although not yet implemented, future initiatives could deepen community connection to the river through direct encounters with its biodiversity—such as guided walks, participatory monitoring, or community-led ecological activities. Experiential engagement of this kind can enhance ecological understanding, cultivate emotional attachment, and strengthen long-term stewardship.

Remaining challenges and areas for further work

Building broader participation. The intervention engaged about 30 participants through interviews and the April event, enabling constructive but limited dialogue. Future work could expand participation by partnering with local organizations, using varied communication channels, and involving community members as multipliers to embed environmental dialogue more widely and foster shared responsibility.

Inclusion of youth. Youth participation was constrained by consent and school coordination requirements, despite their stake in future outcomes. Future initiatives should develop educational partnerships and consent frameworks that enable ethical, meaningful engagement. Early involvement can foster environmental literacy and long-term stewardship.

Need for site-specific technical information. Participants sought concrete, localized evidence on potential outcomes of river restoration—visualizations, models, and projections showing likely changes in water levels, biodiversity, and riverbanks. Providing such information, though resource-intensive, would make discussions more tangible and support informed, evidence-based decisions.

Connecting dialogue to governance. While the April event showed that community discussions can be inclusive and constructive, how they influence formal decisions remains unclear. Stronger mechanisms are needed to connect local dialogue with regional and national policy frameworks.

Balancing dialogue and advocacy. The intervention prioritized dialogue over advocacy, fostering open exploration rather than predefined outcomes. While this built trust, it left questions of environmental action unresolved. Future work could pair participatory dialogue with policy engagement to ensure reflection leads to concrete progress.

Final reflections and messages

The testing process demonstrated that structured, relationship-based dialogue can open meaningful pathways for environmental transformation. When community conversations begin from lived experience and local meaning rather than politicized framings, they foster trust, empathy, and a deeper understanding of differing perspectives within the community. The gradual approach—from individual interviews to collective dialogue—helped participants feel heard and prepared to engage, creating the conditions for openness and reciprocity. This process revealed that connection fosters mutual care, shared responsibility, and ultimately, a greater willingness to support environmental change when people feel personally and emotionally linked to the river.

The process also demonstrated that integrating diverse forms of knowledge—scientific, local, experiential, and emotional—enhances collective understanding and strengthens the legitimacy of environmental decision-making. Informal and inclusive settings enable different actors to engage as collaborators rather than as experts and audiences, fostering dialogue on equal terms.

Future efforts should build on these insights by broadening participation, strengthening the bridge between local dialogue and governance, and expanding opportunities for residents to experience the river's biodiversity firsthand. Sustained, trust-based engagement—supported by transparent information, inclusive methods, and respect for local values—can transform short-term initiatives into enduring frameworks for community stewardship and effective environmental governance. Local environmental actors should play a role in building environmental awareness, relevance, and care within the community, translating complex ecological insights into shared, locally meaningful understanding.

Engagement with transformative principles

The approach engaged with several transformative principles through practice rather than explicit design, illustrating how participatory methods can operationalize pluralization, empowerment, politicization, and embedding.

Pluralizing was achieved through the sequencing of individual interviews and group dialogue, which revealed the diversity of perspectives within the community. This process

demonstrated that environmental understanding does not arise from a single authoritative view but through the interaction of scientific knowledge, lived experience, emotional connection, and cultural meaning.

Empowering emerged from creating spaces where residents—often excluded from formal processes—could share concerns and knowledge on equal footing. Treating participants as knowledge holders rather than research subjects surfaced insights often overlooked by conventional consultation. Empowerment could be further strengthened by amplifying local environmental voices and fostering a collective sense of ownership over the river’s future, supported by growing care and responsibility within the community.

Politicizing occurred partly through the involvement of political actors in the research process and by acknowledging that environmental decisions are inherently political. Supporting politicization with robust technical evidence—through context-specific assessments—and grounding it in community experience can help balance competing priorities and values. However, transforming these dynamics requires institutional change beyond a single community initiative.

Finally, **embedding** was achieved by aligning the process with familiar local practices and conversational forms, showing that dialogue about the river can be both accessible and meaningful when rooted in place. Yet, deeper institutional embedding—linking community dialogue with governance and policy frameworks—will require sustained commitment, time, and multi-level collaboration.

Closing remarks

The Anykščiai case demonstrated that structured, community-based dialogue about local rivers is possible, even when addressing sensitive topics. The process required careful preparation, trust-building, and a thoughtful design that created space for diverse perspectives to be expressed, heard, and exchanged.

The interviews revealed that sound technical preparation is essential to ensure that all community-relevant questions are adequately addressed. Equally important is an approach grounded in genuine respect for local contexts and values—one that emphasizes a willingness to listen, reflect, and acknowledge both environmental concerns and community perspectives.

The intervention created opportunities for dialogue and tested participatory methods that resonated with participants. The continuation of these conversations will depend on community interest, institutional support, and their integration into formal decision-making processes.

The April event demonstrated that inclusive dialogue is achievable and highlighted the importance of experiential knowledge. Strengthening connections with the river and its biodiversity can foster greater environmental awareness, care, and stewardship within the community.

Ultimately, the case underscored that environmental change is inseparable from social transformation. Lasting ecological improvement must be rooted in the community’s willingness to care for the river and to share responsibility for the change process. Building understanding and ownership requires time, trust, and continuity. Although this project alone could not transform governance systems, the methods tested provide a

valuable foundation for those seeking to strengthen dialogue, trust, and collective stewardship of rivers and their ecosystems.

2.4.8 References

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2.5 UBB Case Study: Romania

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2.5.1 Short presentation of the case

The Romanian case study examines how biodiversity conservation can coexist with sustainable rural development in the Sighișoara-Târnava Mare region, one of Romania's largest Natura 2000 areas, covering approximately 85,000 hectares. This landscape boasts remarkable biodiversity, featuring over 1,000 plant species, 55 endangered bird species, and 23 endangered mammal species, including wolves, bears, and wildcats. It also reflects centuries of coexistence between people and nature through traditional farming, grazing, and cultural practices. Today, these high-nature-value farmlands are increasingly threatened by land abandonment, agricultural intensification, depopulation, and economic inequalities that particularly affect marginalized groups such as Roma communities. At the heart of the case study lies the challenge of aligning biodiversity protection with the social and economic realities of rural life. Traditional land management once ensured both ecological and cultural balance, but changes in policy and market structures have weakened these systems. The decline in small-scale farming, the loss of communal herding, and the erosion of traditional knowledge have disrupted ecological processes. At the same time, migration and aging populations have reduced the number of active land stewards. As a result, pastures are overgrown, water resources are drying up, and biodiversity tied to open landscapes is in decline. Research combining participatory workshops (implemented in June 2024) reveals that local people understand nature through relational and emotional experiences rather than technical definitions. They value the landscape for its beauty, productivity, and significance, seeing it as an integral part of their identity. However, their knowledge and perspectives are often excluded from decision-making dominated by top-down policies. Building inclusive governance requires revaluing traditional ecological knowledge and fostering cooperation

among farmers, scientists, NGOs, and policymakers. Several community-led innovations demonstrate potential for transformative change. Efforts to restore hay meadows, protect native species, revive orchards, and reintroduce buffalo grazing have not only enhanced biodiversity but also strengthened local identity and tourism. Education, shared learning networks, and environmental awareness initiatives are proving effective in engaging both adults and children. Yet, obstacles such as climate change, weak policy enforcement, and short-term economic pressures continue to hinder progress. The case study shows that enduring biodiversity regeneration depends not only on ecological restoration but also on revitalizing the human communities that care for nature. Sustainable transformation emerges where conservation supports local livelihoods, respects cultural traditions, and empowers people to act collectively. In these Transylvanian villages, human resilience and ecological renewal are inseparable foundations for a sustainable future.

2.5.2 Evaluation of strategies in action

The ongoing strategies and interventions implemented by LAG/GAL and the UBB team for biodiversity regeneration present various strengths and gaps. These are analyzed under three primary lenses: (1) transformative change potential, (2) the manageability of indirect drivers of biodiversity loss, and (3) enablers of replication and impact reduction attached to disruptors.

1) Transformative change potential: A key aspect discussed during the last workshop (March 12, 2025, hereinafter referred to as W7) was the necessity of transformative change rather than incremental adjustments. This last workshop was part of the broader sequence of qualitative engagements (six workshops) carried out throughout the case study. The insights shared during the online session build directly on earlier meetings held in Apold, Saschiz, Boiu, Biertan, Mălâncrav, and Șoard where participants first articulated local understandings of land-use pressures, biodiversity decline, and opportunities for change. Referencing these earlier workshops helps show that the reflections emerging in March 2025 do not stand alone but represent a cumulative learning process developed over multiple interactions with community members. This framing highlights how perspectives on transformative change have evolved across the complete set of workshops and field dialogues. Against this background, one participant emphasized that “Real transformative change requires greater momentum. If we don’t pick up the pace, it will be difficult to achieve the desired results” (P_W7 anonymized identifier for a participant in Workshop 7). The emphasis is on finding new methods and adapting to novel conditions while maintaining sustainable land use and biodiversity. One example of transformative change cited in the discussion was an effort to restore biodiversity on agricultural land: “When we took over the land, we faced problems... we bought habitat-specific seeds, we brought bales of hay from other areas to introduce native seeds, we practiced grazing according to certain rules” (P_W7). The visible transformation over 10-18 hectares signifies progress, but the time-intensive nature of such interventions raises concerns about scalability and long-term feasibility.

However, a significant barrier to transformative change is the lack of enforcement of existing regulations. As pointed out, “A concrete example of transformation would be the application of already existing legislation ... We have the tools, but they are not put into practice.” (P_W7) Without proper implementation of environmental policies, efforts at biodiversity regeneration remain fragmented and ineffective.

Moreover, cultural and behavioral change is necessary to ensure long-term transformation. The discussion highlighted that mindsets rooted in short-term profit

maximization and economic survival must shift toward long-term ecological sustainability. “The individualistic mentality, focused exclusively on profit, on personal interest, has become the norm... Therefore, any form of collective management of natural resources becomes almost impossible.” (P_W7). Transformative change in biodiversity management thus requires both structural policy changes and a fundamental shift in societal values toward collective responsibility.

2) Manageability of indirect drivers of biodiversity loss

The indirect drivers of biodiversity loss – including economic constraints, land-use changes, and policy misalignment – were among the recurring themes in the discussion. Economic viability remains a core issue, with farmers struggling to balance sustainability with profitability: “Many continue to practice organic farming, even if they no longer have official certification. This shows that it can be done, and the world is starting to understand the benefits” (P_W7). This suggests that while local farmers are willing to adopt environmentally friendly practices, economic pressures often hinder their long-term adherence to these practices.

Another significant challenge is the lack of incentives and support for environmentally sustainable practices. As one participant noted, “If someone wants to benefit from subsidies, they should prove that they have learned about the sustainable use of natural resources” (P_W7). This suggests a possible solution: integrating education and policy incentives to encourage best practices in sustainable agriculture.

Furthermore, the ongoing degradation of ecosystems due to land privatization and resource competition was highlighted: “There are already examples of people appropriating portions of the river stream and conflicts are already starting”. This highlights the pressing need for enhanced land management and governance structures that prevent resource monopolization and environmental degradation.

From the previous workshops in Apold and Saschiz, additional insights emerged. The significance of traditional agricultural landscapes as biodiversity reservoirs was emphasized: “The meadows would be. The forest is very important” (for biodiversity). However, these landscapes are threatened by overgrazing and changes in land use. This shift reduces habitat heterogeneity, impacting biodiversity.

3) Enablers for replication and impact reduction attached to disruptors

In June 2024, the societal partner (GAL Dealurile Târnavelor) organized six on-site workshops in the villages of Apold, Saschiz, Boiu, Biertan, Mălâncrav, and Șoard, where residents discussed local understandings of nature, land-use change, and biodiversity vulnerabilities. An online deliberative workshop complemented these workshops in March 2025, revisiting earlier insights and deepening reflections on the need for transformative change. While the complete set of workshops informs the case study, Deliverable 2.4 places particular emphasis, but not exclusively, on participants from Saschiz and Apold, as these locations provided the most relevant perspectives for intervention testing. Together, these engagements form a continuous qualitative process that grounds our analysis in locally situated experiences and cumulative learning. Through these discussions, participants consistently highlighted not only the need for transformative change but also the practical conditions that either enable or hinder such change on the ground. Replication of successful biodiversity conservation initiatives is critical, but

institutional and structural barriers often impede progress. One identified enabler is the formation of communities of practice, as one participant (March 2025 workshop) pointed out: “We need functional communities of practice. WhatsApp groups, for example, are very effective” (P_W7). These networks facilitate the sharing of knowledge and support between farmers, researchers, and policymakers, enhancing the overall impact of biodiversity regeneration efforts. Another factor contributing to replication potential is education and awareness-building. The importance of early education and hands-on learning experiences was emphasized: “Every school could have a pedagogical garden, where children can learn through practice” (P_W7). Additionally, initiatives like school greenhouses and environmental education projects in rural areas were highlighted as models for fostering environmental stewardship from a young age.

However, the risk of local disengagement remains a challenge. The lack of institutional responsiveness was highlighted: “If someone files a complaint about the destruction of protected land, there must be a prompt and effective response, not just a formality.” (P_W7). Without stronger accountability measures, the effectiveness of replication efforts is compromised.

Disruptors such as climate change and external economic pressures require multi-level governance approaches. The importance of water resources was a recurrent theme: “Water as a resource for food, drinking water, household water, animal watering water” (P_Saschiz). Participants in Saschiz expressed concerns over declining water availability: “30 years ago we used to bathe in the valley, but now we can’t do this anymore because it almost doesn’t flow anymore”. Without effective strategies to protect water resources, local ecosystems and agricultural sustainability remain at risk.

Moreover, wildlife conservation challenges were highlighted. The presence of large carnivores is both a conservation success and a source of conflict: “The bear, the wolf, the jackal... It is very interesting, considering two edges” (explanation: the need for conservation-protection of people). While some view these species as integral to their identity and even as potential attractions for ecotourism, others struggle with livestock predation.

To address the identified gaps, several strategic recommendations emerged from the March 2025 workshop: Strengthening policy implementation: Enforcing existing environmental regulations to protect biodiversity-rich areas; Economic incentives for sustainable practices: Providing financial support to farmers who adopt environmentally friendly methods; Enhancing community engagement and education: Expanding educational programs and community-based knowledge-sharing platforms; Improving institutional accountability/performance: Ensuring that complaints and reports on environmental violations lead to concrete actions; Developing sustainable land-use strategies: Encouraging traditional, nature-friendly agricultural practices to prevent ecosystem degradation; Balancing economic development and nature preservation: Creating models for sustainable tourism and resource management; Leveraging technology for biodiversity monitoring: Using satellite imagery and remote sensing tools to track biodiversity changes in real-time.

2.5.3 Enablers and disruptors

Although the workshop discussions centered on local experiences, they unfolded within a broader governance landscape shaped by national and EU policies. Romania’s Natura

2000 obligations, strategic planning regulations, and national biodiversity strategies provide the overarching framework for conservation (European Commission, 2020). At the EU level, instruments such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) strongly influence farming practices, subsidies, and land-use incentives in the region, shaping both opportunities and constraints for biodiversity-friendly management (Pe'er et al., 2019). These frameworks can support agroecological practices and habitat restoration, but they may also reinforce intensification pressures or administrative burdens that rural communities struggle to navigate. Understanding how these multilevel policies interact with local strategies is therefore relevant for enabling transformative change, as community-led initiatives are most effective when aligned with broader governance structures.

1. The success: on a 10–18-hectare plot, a transformation is visible in both species' richness and ecosystem function after a few years of adaptive management (using local seed mixes, imported hay to introduce native seeds, rotational grazing, and fallow periods). When traditional practices collapse – due to legal restrictions, labor shortages, or poor profitability – the result is often habitat degradation through neglect. Overgrown pastures, the disappearance of livestock breeds (such as the buffalo in many villages), and the accompanying loss of open-land flora and fauna are examples of these failures. Any strategy for regeneration must envisage how to revitalize or substitute the functions of these fading traditional practices.

2. Community attitudes and cultural identity

The workshops underscore that biodiversity is as much a cultural and social phenomenon as an ecological one. Local attitudes towards nature can greatly enable or impede regenerative efforts. In these Transylvanian communities, many natural elements are deeply woven into cultural identity. For instance, the white storks that nest in villages have become beloved symbols of the countryside. In Boiu, several women enthusiastically recounted how “the people love them”, celebrating the storks' return each spring. One resident was overjoyed when storks attempted to build a nest on her small house, saying, “I was so happy.” Stork nests are even used as local landmarks (e.g., “the nest at the bus stop”). This cultural relationship translates into practical protection – villagers guard the nests and view the birds as part of the community. Such cultural pride in a species or landscape is a powerful enabler of regeneration, as it motivates grassroots conservation efforts. It makes biodiversity a source of local esteem rather than an external mandate.

Communities also find identity and economic opportunity in unique local biodiversity. In Apold, a rare carnivorous plant (*Drosera*) was discovered in a marsh, and the recent reintroduction of the “Albăstrelul Transilvan” blue butterfly became a topic of discussion. Locals immediately connected it with future ecotourism: “many tourists will come to see it”. This excitement shows how a well-communicated intervention can capture the public imagination.

3) Attunement and mismatch between local biodiversity agendas and economic interests

The relationship between biodiversity regeneration efforts and economic activities is complex, with both alignments and tensions. Many community members in the study areas express deep concern about the loss of biodiversity due to financial pressures, primarily stemming from agricultural practices and land-use changes. The dominance of

monocultures directly conflicts with the need for diverse landscapes to sustain biodiversity. Economic viability remains a significant driver of decision-making at the local level. While some farmers maintain environmentally friendly practices, others prioritize short-term economic returns over long-term sustainability. One participant noted: "The individualistic mentality, focused exclusively on profit, on personal interest, has become the norm... Therefore, any form of collective management of natural resources becomes almost impossible". This perspective highlights the fundamental mismatch between biodiversity-focused interventions and prevailing economic models.

However, there are also opportunities for alignment. In Apold, discussions revealed an interest in promoting traditional agricultural landscapes that support biodiversity, suggesting that policies promoting agroecology and sustainable grazing could serve as enablers for biodiversity net gain while preserving economic benefits for farmers. In Biertan, discussions emphasized the importance of natural water resources, with particular concern over declining water levels. The drying of rivers and streams due to climate change and land-use changes presents a significant challenge for balancing local biodiversity conservation efforts with agricultural demands. Similarly, in Soard, discussions revealed concerns regarding land-use change and habitat loss. A participant stated: "In the forest, for example, it rained for two weeks in a row. You'd think the soil is now full of water. But if you go into the forest a week later, the ground is cracked. So, there is a great need for water". This highlights a critical issue: deforestation and improper land management exacerbate the effects of climate change, affecting both biodiversity and agricultural productivity. Further, in Mălâncrav, participants emphasized the growing challenge of balancing biodiversity conservation with economic pressures: "People call them ponds... (used for) fishing and swimming... But I think they also serve as a water source for animals". While small artificial water bodies provide some relief for biodiversity, they also underscore the need for economic activities, such as livestock farming, to adopt sustainable water use strategies and prevent depletion.

Another economic factor affecting biodiversity is the increasing pressure for land privatization. In multiple case studies, concerns were raised about the monopolization of natural resources. As a participant pointed out in Soard: "Here, we can see a hillside pasture that, after the first 15 years of abandonment and forest encroachment, likely will never return to its original pasture state". This suggests that while land abandonment may offer some short-term benefits for biodiversity, a lack of proper management can lead to unintended ecological consequences.

The tensions between economic interests and biodiversity regeneration are also evident in forest management. In Soard, participants noted the pressure from private owners to exploit forests for short-term gains: "Foresters are quite receptive, but they still must deal with landowners. Currently, there is no compensation for those trees, though I believe it will be introduced in the forestry code. From my perspective, this represents a loss of timber resources". This demonstrates a key conflict: conservation efforts must be accompanied by financial or policy incentives to make biodiversity-friendly practices economically viable for landowners.

4) Replicability of enablers and broadening impact

Communities of practice have been identified as a key enabler for expanding biodiversity initiatives. A participant emphasized: "We need functional communities of practice. WhatsApp groups, for example, are very effective". Such informal networks facilitate

knowledge exchange and capacity building among farmers, conservationists, and policymakers. Education is another enabler with strong replicability potential. The importance of integrating environmental awareness into school curricula was highlighted: "Every school could have a pedagogical garden, where children can learn through practice". By fostering an early appreciation for biodiversity, communities can cultivate a generation that is more inclined toward sustainable practices. Financial incentives and support mechanisms were also discussed as necessary enablers. One participant noted: "If someone wants to benefit from subsidies, they should prove that they have learned about the sustainable use of natural resources". This approach could incentivize farmers to adopt biodiversity-friendly practices, ensuring long-term impact. In Mălâncrav, the role of natural elements in community identity was underlined: "... examples of nature's elements that are relevant to the local community... Pastures, forests, rivers, orchards". This suggests that leveraging local appreciation for natural landscapes could enhance biodiversity restoration initiatives.

5) Managing disruptors and reducing long-term impact

Several disruptors were identified in the workshops, ranging from climate change to land privatization and economic pressures. A recurrent theme was the decreasing availability of water resources, which threatens both agriculture and biodiversity conservation. As noted in Saschiz: "30 years ago, we used to bathe in the valley, but now we can't because it almost doesn't flow anymore". Addressing such environmental changes requires integrated water management strategies that align with local biodiversity goals. Large carnivores, such as bears and wolves, represent another disruptor. While they are an essential part of the ecosystem, their presence often leads to conflicts with local communities. One participant described the dilemma: "The bear, the wolf, the jackal... It is very interesting, considering two edges". This suggests that while large predators are valued as part of regional biodiversity, their increasing numbers create tensions with farmers and herders. Land management conflicts also pose challenges. The privatization of key natural resources has led to disputes: "There are already examples of people appropriating portions of the river stream and conflicts are already starting". Such conflicts hinder biodiversity conservation efforts and necessitate stronger governance mechanisms.

In Soard, climate change impacts were also noted, particularly regarding soil degradation: "Well, now the rain has changed a lot, the rains of 40, 50 years ago were smaller and soaked the soil, and now they are more violent and run off, washing the soil". This suggests that land erosion resulting from shifting rainfall patterns poses a significant challenge to biodiversity.

2.5.4 Failed and successful practices

Across these diverse but interlinked cases (from the six villages), a clear picture emerges: biodiversity regeneration thrives when human and natural systems are tended together, but falters when either side is neglected. The successful practices – whether it's the return of a rare butterfly, the persistence of buffalo grazing, organic farming, or the celebration of an orchard – all share a common thread: they combine ecological restoration with local social benefits and cultural meaning. Such interventions are locally led or at least locally embraced, and they often require patience. As one practitioner noted, "Our impact is slow. We see it over time, over many years."

Yet, when that impact does come, it tends to be enduring, because it has grown from local roots. For example, the apple orchards of Malâncrav have survived modern pressures in part because the community, with external support, has found new value in them – culturally (through festivals and identity), economically (through products and tourism), and ecologically (as habitat for pollinators). Likewise, Apold’s newfound “blue jewel” (the butterfly) is poised to become a long-term asset precisely because it was introduced hand in hand with community awareness. On the other hand, the failed efforts and ongoing challenges underscore that good intentions alone are not enough. While many of these challenges arise from local socio-ecological dynamics, such as shifting land-use practices, declining traditional knowledge, and changing community motivations, they are also shaped by broader structural forces. Market pressures that favor high-input agriculture, rural depopulation trends, and rigid regulatory frameworks often amplify local vulnerabilities and limit the scope of community-led interventions. Distinguishing between these scales helps clarify why specific barriers persist despite strong local commitment and underscores the need for effective solutions to integrate both community-level initiatives and supportive, wider policies.

Systemic challenges – such as youth migration, the breakdown of traditional knowledge transfer, unfavorable market conditions, or rigid regulations – can undermine regeneration projects if left unaddressed. We saw that when farmers cannot make a living or feel unsupported, they abandon practices vital for biodiversity. When a community’s social fabric frays, nature is left without its stewards. In these Transylvanian villages, people likened fighting for sustainable practices to Don Quixote tilting at windmills: “when you try and try to change deeply rooted mentalities, at some point you get tired... You feel like the windmills are too many and too big”. This vivid metaphor highlights that deeply rooted mindsets are a primary barrier, whether it is locals stuck to harmful habits (such as improper pesticide use) or authorities hindered by one-size-fits-all policies. The fatigue that changes agents feel is real, but the case studies also offer hope: even windmills can be harnessed if enough force is applied in the right direction.

While the workshops brought together a varied group of local actors, the perspectives of certain underrepresented groups were present only partially. Youth, many of whom have migrated, were largely absent from discussions, and their viewpoint on land use and future livelihoods remains underrepresented. Women were frequently present and contributed substantially; however, several participants noted that women’s voices are still not consistently recognized in local decision-making structures. The situation of economically vulnerable households and some Roma families surfaced only through second-hand accounts, indicating gaps in direct representation. These patterns reflect wider social inequalities that also shape who participates in shaping environmental futures. Acknowledging such asymmetries is crucial for interpreting the evidence base and ensuring that biodiversity initiatives do not inadvertently perpetuate local exclusions.

In conclusion, the enabling factors for biodiversity regeneration in these territories include strong community engagement, respect for traditional practices combined with updated knowledge, cultural pride in natural heritage, economic innovations that reward conservation, supportive networks, and responsive governance (when present). When these factors align, small projects can snowball into long-lasting positive change. Conversely, the limiting factors – social disintegration, cultural apathy or fear, economic inequities, and inflexible or absent policies – are influential and often interlocking. A well-documented lesson from the Transylvanian experience is that tackling these limiting

factors requires an integrated approach: ecological goals must be paired with social and economic solutions. As one participant insightfully noted, “human life and nature cannot be seen separately.” The most successful practices created win-win situations for people and ecosystems. By learning from both successes and failures – the orchard that blossoms and the pasture that vanished – practitioners and policymakers can better craft strategies that regenerate biodiversity in a way that local communities can sustain. The future of these landscapes depends not only on conserving nature but also on restoring the human communities and practices that care for nature. The integrative narrative from these case studies is ultimately one of cautious optimism: with knowledge, cooperation, and perseverance, the challenges of the windmills can be turned into engines of ecological and social renewal.

1. Traditional land management: Gains and losses

Many of the villages focus on traditional land-use practices, such as grazing, hay meadow management, and small-scale farming, which have a significant impact on biodiversity. In several communities, reviving or maintaining historic grazing regimes has proven beneficial. For example, participants observed that pastures where hardy water buffalo still graze harbor exceptional biodiversity: “As a rule, wherever buffaloes are grazed, biodiversity increases... traditionally buffaloes were more”. Buffalo grazing creates varied vegetation structures, and sites with buffalo host very strictly protected species. In Malâncrav, locals reported that buffalo are indeed still present, suggesting that continuity of this practice has helped sustain rich pasture ecosystems. Recognizing this, we must help farmers keep buffalo – which means first understanding why they gave up buffalo and addressing those causes. This marks a promising intervention: supporting traditional herding as a modern conservation tool. Where such support exists, it can be considered a successful practice that enables biodiversity regeneration by connecting ecological goals with local husbandry traditions. However, traditional grazing has declined in many areas, often with adverse effects.

Several villages described the loss of communal herding systems due to regulatory and social changes. In Boiu, residents complained that the daily communal herd (locally “ciurda”) of cows no longer goes out, in part because animals were banned from using the main road: “we were told that animals have no business on the county road. It is prohibited by law”. This legal barrier forced remaining farmers to find back roads for their livestock, and such hurdles discourage the practice. Elsewhere, pasture abandonment is a serious issue. In Şoard, participants pointed to a hillside pasture that, after 15 years of being unused, had rapidly overgrown with scrub. Once woody growth passes a threshold, the land is even reclassified as forest. This illustrates a failed outcome: traditional grazing and mowing kept landscapes open and biodiverse for centuries, but when economic and demographic shifts led to abandonment, biodiversity tied to open habitats declined as thickets and eventually forests took over. In Biertan, older residents noted a similar decline in active land use. Terraced hills, once famed for their vineyards, have largely fallen out of cultivation; they still hold aesthetic and historic value, but much of their ecological and productive function has been lost. Thus, loss of traditional management is a recurring challenge in these territories. Crucially, the social dimension underpins these trends. In the workshops, people observed that fewer villagers engage in farming and herding today, especially among the young generation. “At the community level, the number of people who exploit the land has been reduced... there is no one young anymore. That is, whoever could has left... In most of the country, large farms have taken over”, one Biertan participant remarked. This quote captures the

demographic and economic forces driving change: youth out-migrate, smallholders age or quit, and large commercial farms or absentee owners take over land in many regions. The departure of “ciobani adevărați” (true shepherds) is particularly acute – an expert surveying over a hundred wooded pastures could “in 2 years, I only found 5 real shepherds”. With skilled herders disappearing, the knowledge and labor needed to manage grazing for biodiversity also vanish. A participant from Apold highlighted that even when flocks remain, the economics are harsh: “The price for a liter of milk is 60 bani” (approximately 0.12 Euro), which undermines livestock viability. Market failures like this make traditional pastoralism economically unsustainable, explaining why many who “could” have indeed left to seek better livelihoods. Practically, where traditional land management persists or is revived with support, landscapes show resilience and biodiversity re-integrates all elements of nature into a “sort of mini cultural wilderness”

The introduction of planned grazing regimes and restoration seeding on formerly arable land is a notable aspect of the butterfly’s return, serving as a point of pride and a tourism draw. We can consider community support as a crucial ingredient for long-lasting success. Similarly, in Malâncrav the historic apple orchards are a source of identity. Villagers instituted Sărbătoarea Mărului (the Apple Festival) to celebrate their orchard heritage, which one local explicitly cited as an “identity value”. The festival is now the village’s annual celebration, linking cultural tradition with biodiversity. Such events not only reinforce local appreciation for biodiversity but also encourage practices that maintain it – for example, keeping the old orchards pruned and productive for the festival. While these cultural connections can enable conservation, their absence or erosion can hinder it. A recurring theme was the gap between generations and the loss of traditional ecological knowledge. Older residents often possess valuable knowledge of the local environment, but as they pass away or as young people leave, this wisdom risks being lost. In Apold, participants suggested a project for pedagogical schools to interview village elders, precisely to capture and transmit such knowledge. The need for “a meeting between generations” was seen as very important. Without efforts like this, young people may grow up disconnected from the land. Indeed, some have noted that many youths show little interest in farming or forestry, having witnessed their parents’ struggles. Where cultural continuity is disrupted, conservation projects can fail because there is no one to maintain the practices. As one man observed, in some areas from other parts of Romania, entire villages have been abandoned. “In Tulcea, a village was emptied, nobody left”. In such cases, even the best ecological plans on paper are of little value if there is no community to implement or benefit from them.

Another attitudinal challenge is striking a balance between fear and tolerance of wildlife. Traditionally, rural communities have known how to coexist with large carnivores, such as bears and wolves. One participant noted that Romania was recognized as “the most tolerant country towards bears,” and that experienced shepherds still accept predators as part of life, taking measures to protect their livestock. One participant remarked that those who have long lived with wolves “tolerate them and know what to do to minimize risks”. This traditional tolerance has enabled Romania to retain populations of species that have vanished elsewhere in Europe – a conservation success rooted in culture. However, tolerance is wearing thin in some communities as lifestyles change. Several villagers admitted, “We are afraid of bears now and no longer go into the forest to collect mushrooms”. Younger or newer residents lack the familiarity with wildlife that their forebears had, and some incidents amplified fear. This shift toward fear can hinder regeneration: it reduces people’s use of and presence in nature (affecting practices like

foraging that tie them to the land), and it can spur calls to cull wildlife rather than protect them.

The case studies, therefore, highlight that maintaining a cultural acceptance of living alongside nature – whether it's storks on one's rooftop or bears in the woods – is vital. The workshops revealed that communities value open communication and education to strengthen positive attitudes. In Apold, after hearing that even "traditional" farm products can harbor pesticide residues if old practices are misapplied, locals agreed that better information is the answer. A cautionary example was voiced: "Eggs from lovely old ladies at the market had very high pesticide levels, because the poor souls didn't realize the potato powder they used would contaminate the hens." Locals have noted that many villagers believe a lack of money is the primary problem. Still, in reality, "everyone... needs information... A lot can be done without money. If they have the information, money is a tool, not an end in itself". In other words, knowledge and initiative can achieve a great deal even with limited funding. This sentiment suggests that investing in human capital – including education, demonstration of good practices, and intergenerational learning – is a low-cost, high-impact strategy. Communities that have internalized this, fostering learning networks and pride in local nature, seem far better positioned to regenerate biodiversity than those waiting passively for outside funding or top-down instructions.

3) Economic and political factors: Barriers and enablers

While culture provides motivation, economic and political frameworks often determine feasibility. Across the workshops, systemic factors – including markets, policies, and institutions – emerged as either supports for regenerative efforts or as obstacles that frustrate them. On the enabling side, supportive policies and projects have made a difference in certain instances. One example is how scientific research influenced law. In Malâncrav's workshop, the moderator described how the concept of protecting "remarkable trees" was developed over 10 years, and eventually, "now it's a law". This shows that evidence-based advocacy can translate into concrete legal protections, providing a framework to preserve biodiversity (in this case, like ancient oaks or other veteran trees) beyond individual efforts.

The LAG (GAL) and NGOs also play a positive role. In Apold, the GAL repeatedly held meetings to inform residents about the value of their land – to discourage the sales to outside investors. One man noted "Luckily, not many ended up selling land here". By anticipating threats (land grabs, loss of local control) and raising awareness, the GAL may have helped the community retain its land and the possibility to manage it sustainably. This is an example of a preventative intervention with long-lasting benefits: keeping land in the hands of local stewards is essential for any regenerative practice to take root. Economic support can also come from alternative income streams aligned with conservation. Tourism and branding local products are frequently mentioned hopes. The introduction of the rare butterfly is anticipated to draw visitors. At the same time, Malâncrav's apple festival and traditional apple products (like juices or jams made from the old orchard) attract people to the village. Such biodiversity-based businesses or events give conservation a tangible value. Similarly, the growing interest in organic farming provides an economic incentive to farm in a manner that is friendly to wildlife. One participant gave an example: some farmers initially obtained organic certification for better market access, and "many continue ecological practices even after dropping the formal certification". This suggests that once farmers experience the benefits (such as

improved soil health, enhanced product quality, potential price premiums, or personal satisfaction), they often continue with greener practices. However, it also highlights a limitation: the cost of certification was too high for some, leading them to abandon the label even though they continued the practice.

In general, when policies (such as organic subsidies or agri-environment payments) or markets (like consumers paying more for organic products) are supportive, they enable regenerative agriculture. When they are lacking, it falls to the personal conviction of farmers to continue, as seen in this case. Many challenges documented in the workshops relate to economic disadvantages and policy gaps that hinder the implementation of conservation-oriented practices. An example is the low pricing of farm products (as with milk mentioned earlier), which makes it hard for traditional farmers to survive. No matter how much a community values its meadows or herds, if the farm economy is unprofitable, younger generations will not continue in that path. This is a systemic issue that requires higher-level policy intervention (e.g., fair pricing, subsidies, cooperative structures). Otherwise, local regenerative efforts may fail in the long run due to simple economic factors. Another systemic barrier is the existence of fragmented or counterproductive regulations. The case of the forbidden road grazing in Boiu is illustrative: a well-meaning traffic law ended up outlawing a sustainable practice, without providing an alternative.

Participants across communities have voiced concerns that legislation often treats humans and nature as separate entities, rather than promoting their coexistence. As one facilitator put it, "The two (people and nature) cannot be seen separately as, for example, the EU Habitat Directive does". This suggests that some top-down conservation policies may be perceived as out of touch with local realities, which could potentially hinder their effectiveness. A more integrative policy approach, which supports traditional land uses like shepherding or haymaking as part of habitat management, would likely be more successful. In fact, Romania's implementation of EU schemes has sometimes tried this – for instance, by paying HNV farm subsidies to shepherds – but the persistence of comments like the above means gaps remain between paper and practice. Another factor is the influx of external actors and new landowners. The discussions revealed mixed effects of this. On one hand, those "who worked in the West, then came back and bought cheap land" were often the ones with foresight and resources to invest. These individuals can be agents of positive change if they bring sustainable ideas or keep the land from being overly exploited. On the other hand, if land is bought by investors with purely speculative or industrial agriculture intentions, local biodiversity can suffer. Apold's experience was relatively positive – few sold out, and those who did were often informed folks – but the very need for the GAL's awareness campaign shows that market pressures to sell land are intense in rural Transylvania. This economic pressure is a limiting factor, as it can disrupt community cohesion and remove land from the traditional stewardship that has historically favored biodiversity. The presence of "neo-rural" newcomers (city people moving to villages) was also debated. Some saw them as "winners" because "they earn money in the city and come invest it locally", potentially boosting the rural economy. If these newcomers purchase and restore old houses, buy local food, or even start small enterprises, they could indirectly support biodiversity-friendly living. But others noted that many "don't take part in village life, even if they enjoy the rural environment". Thus, the social integration of new stakeholders is crucial when outsiders connect and collaborate with locals, as they can be an asset. When they remain detached, their presence alone does not regenerate the community or landscape.

Finally, the mentioned enabler was the formation of collaborative networks and the establishment of trust. Participants stressed the value of exchanging experience and being “part of a network”. They acknowledged that current society is “very individualistic” and people are afraid to trust each other, but rebuilding trust and cooperation can spark new ideas and solutions.

In practical terms, this means farmer associations, community groups, or partnerships with NGOs can help pool resources and knowledge for conservation. For example, if farmers band together to market a product (such as meadow-raised beef or wildflower honey), they might overcome some economic barriers that each would face individually. The participants referred to this through references to GAL projects and knowledge-sharing meetings. Indeed, one local expert concluded that with the correct information and minimal training, people can achieve significant results. Peer examples of success (like seeing a neighbor profit from eco-tourism or organic cheese) create a demonstration effect that money can’t buy. Thus, a key enabling factor is fostering these networks and disseminating success stories among communities, turning isolated successes into broader movements.

2.5.5 Co-learning

The co-learning process between research partners and societal actors reveals both challenges and opportunities in biodiversity governance. While indirect drivers such as land abandonment, economic constraints, and policy inefficiencies pose significant obstacles, the workshops also identified powerful enablers, including community-driven knowledge exchange, intergenerational learning, and participatory governance approaches. To enhance clarity for readers unfamiliar with the empirical material, it is helpful to note that the qualitative component of the case study consisted of six deliberative workshops conducted in June 2024 across Apold, Saschiz, Boiu, Biertan, Mălâncrav, and Soard, followed by an additional online workshop in March 2025. Quotations from the first six workshops are coded using anonymized identifiers of the form “P_VillageName,” while contributions from the online event are referenced as “PW7,” indicating “Participant in Workshop 7.” This system ensures both transparency and confidentiality while allowing readers to trace insights across events. A detailed analysis of all workshops, along with the full interview transcripts, is openly accessible in one of the UBB team’s contributions (co-authored with the social Partner, the GAL): Reti et al. (2025). Drawing on these cumulative insights, the patterns that emerged across the workshops underline a consistent expectation for governance models that recognize local knowledge and respond to the lived realities of land users.

To create effective biodiversity governance, action plans must integrate local insights, provide economic incentives for sustainable practices, and strengthen participatory decision-making. By fostering genuine co-learning and responsiveness to societal needs, biodiversity strategies can move beyond theoretical frameworks to create tangible, lasting change on the ground.

The co-learning process described in the document was produced through an integrative analysis of discussions from all workshops and field observations documented in the provided files. The co-learning between researchers’ partners on indirect drivers of biodiversity loss was developed by reflecting on the patterns of disruption that emerged across the six villages. Research partners identified: The loss of traditional land management practices, such as the decline in manual hay mowing or buffalo grazing,

which previously supported biodiversity; Economic constraints, such as the drop in milk prices, which force farmers to shift toward unsustainable agricultural practices; and Land abandonment, leading to rapid ecosystem changes.

By analyzing these trends, research partners could identify enablers for biodiversity regeneration, including a) Community-driven knowledge-sharing mechanisms (e.g., WhatsApp groups); b) The role of local ecological knowledge in policy design; c) Recognition of systemic lock-ins, such as bureaucratic delays in conservation policy implementation.

The co-learning between the research partner and the GAL was produced through the exchange of knowledge between local communities and researchers. Many insights in biodiversity governance originate from place-based observations, such as: ► Water shortages in Saschiz, which serve as real-time indicators of environmental change; ► Economic struggles faced by farmers, reinforcing the need for financial incentives tied to conservation; ► Cultural identity and biodiversity, as seen in Saschiz, where the reintroduction of the Transylvanian Blue butterfly sparked local engagement. By engaging directly with GAL, the UBB team could move beyond theoretical aspects.

I. Co-learning on indirect drivers of biodiversity loss between researchers' partners

Patterns of disruption in biodiversity regeneration: One of the main insights from the workshops was the recognition that biodiversity loss is deeply intertwined with socio-economic shifts. In Malâncrav, participants observed that traditional practices, such as manual hay mowing, have almost disappeared: "Nobody mows by hand anymore. That is, very few". Instead, mechanization and demographic changes have led to a decline in labor-intensive, yet biodiversity-friendly, land management practices.

Another major disruption pattern is land abandonment. In several case studies, community members highlighted that when pasture lands are no longer used, they quickly become overgrown, altering local ecosystems. In Șoard, a participant noted: "In the first 15 years of abandonment, the pasture became forested... It will never return to its original pasture state". This reflects a broader trend where abandonment leads to rapid ecological succession, often resulting in biodiversity loss.

In addition to land-use changes, economic constraints also serve as a significant indirect driver of biodiversity loss. In Malâncrav, a participant shared concerns about declining profitability in traditional farming. Such low prices make it unsustainable for farmers to maintain traditional livestock-based landscapes, which have historically supported biodiversity.

Enablers and their potential for scaling up: While disruptions pose significant challenges, several enablers identified in these case studies present opportunities for upscaling biodiversity-friendly practices. A key enabler is community-driven knowledge sharing. One of the successful models discussed was the role of informal learning networks. By fostering direct communication among farmers, conservationists, and policymakers, such platforms can enable real-time problem-solving and support. Another enabler is the integration of traditional ecological knowledge into governance models. In Saschiz, a participant emphasized the value of intergenerational knowledge transfer, suggesting

that younger generations should learn directly from elders before traditional expertise is lost. Without a deliberate effort to retain such knowledge, biodiversity-friendly practices may disappear.

Lock-ins that hinder biodiversity regeneration: Despite the existence of scalable enablers, several persistent obstacles act as lock-ins to biodiversity regeneration. Bureaucratic inefficiencies were frequently cited as a barrier. In Mavlankar, a participant described the slow policy response to environmental concerns: “10 years of working on remarkable trees... and now it’s law”. This demonstrates that while science can inform policy, the lag in implementation significantly weakens the impact of conservation efforts. Additionally, economic lock-ins continue to shape decision-making in ways that are detrimental to biodiversity. Market-driven agricultural intensification has led to the expansion of monoculture. The reliance on monoculture reduces habitat diversity, creating a biodiversity-poor landscape.

At the same time, these local patterns suggest broader, multi-level policy implications. The persistence of bureaucratic and economic lock-ins suggests that local actors cannot overcome these barriers without more substantial alignment between national CAP instruments, regional land-use planning, and local conservation goals. Strengthening cross-scale coordination, particularly between municipalities, LAG structures, and environmental authorities, could accelerate the uptake of regenerative practices that communities already recognize as necessary. Moreover, the insights from these workshops illustrate how local experiences can inform higher-level policy adjustments to reduce administrative burdens and improve incentive structures for biodiversity-friendly farming.

To strengthen the connection between these subsections I and II, it is important to highlight that the analysis of indirect drivers presented above operates at a structural and analytical level, examining how broad socio-economic and institutional mechanisms shape biodiversity outcomes. By contrast, the following subsection shifts to a local and operational level, focusing on how researchers and societal actors engage in concrete co-learning practices within specific communities. This bridging step illustrates how diagnosing systemic pressures (subsection I) lays the groundwork for the collaborative, practice-based interactions (subsection II) required to implement transformative change. In doing so, effective biodiversity governance depends on linking structural understanding with on-the-ground experimentation and shared learning.

II. Co-learning between research partners and societal sectors

Bridging the knowledge gap between researchers and communities: A key insight from the workshops was that successful biodiversity governance requires bidirectional learning – where researchers learn from local communities as much as they share their expertise. In Malâncrav, participants highlighted the need for scientific research to be made more accessible and actionable: “This science is translated into laws... but how far do these laws reach people?” The effectiveness of policy depends on whether local communities are equipped to implement it. Moreover, societal actors often hold crucial place-based knowledge that researchers might overlook. For instance, a participant from Saschiz pointed out: “30 years ago we used to bathe in the valley, but now we can't because it almost doesn't flow anymore”. Local observations like this can serve as critical early-warning indicators of ecological degradation, which researchers should incorporate into biodiversity assessments.

Action plan adjustments for inclusive biodiversity governance: To enhance biodiversity governance, action plans need to shift towards more participatory approaches. One major proposal emerging from the workshops is the need for economic incentives for biodiversity-friendly farming. As noted in Malâncrav, “If someone wants to benefit from subsidies, they should prove that they have learned about the sustainable use of natural resources”. Integrating educational components into financial support mechanisms can ensure that funding fosters long-term ecological and economic sustainability. Additionally, local governance structures should incorporate early-warning systems based on community knowledge. For example, in Şoard, where pasture abandonment was raised as a concern, a proactive monitoring system led by local stakeholders could help detect early signs of habitat degradation and inform timely intervention. Finally, biodiversity action plans should prioritize cultural continuity as a conservation strategy. In Saschiz, participants discussed the potential for ecotourism based on local biodiversity, referring to the recently reintroduced Transylvanian Blue butterfly. By linking biodiversity efforts to local identity and tourism, conservation becomes a source of economic resilience rather than a constraint.

2.5.6 Testing of interventions

Monitoring and evaluation in local events: The Local Action Group (GAL) Dealurile Târnavelor has implemented various initiatives over time to address biodiversity loss through monitoring and evaluation at local events. One of the primary ways GAL has tested interventions is through knowledge-sharing workshops that bring together farmers, researchers, and local stakeholders. To avoid confusion between institutional and community levels of action, it is essential to note that GAL-led interventions are formally coordinated activities, such as workshop organization, project facilitation, and strategic planning. In contrast, community-driven initiatives emerge organically from local actors, based on their own practices, needs, and motivations. Clarifying this distinction helps illustrate how institutional support provides structure and resources, whereas community initiatives reflect bottom-up engagement and lived experience. In many cases, GAL interventions have served as catalysts that strengthen rather than replace locally initiated efforts. This dual dynamic shows how institutional guidance and community agency interact to shape biodiversity-related action.

In Saschiz, workshops have facilitated discussions on traditional land-use practices, agroecology, and biodiversity conservation. Participants assessed the success of past interventions and explored innovative approaches. A participant shared, “We tried to restore the valley with native plants, and in one season, we saw an increase in insect populations and bird species.” This demonstrates that local conservation efforts are yielding tangible results and require continued support and refinement.

In addition, efforts in Malâncrav demonstrated the transformative potential of targeted biodiversity regeneration strategies. A participant explained: “When we took over the land, we faced problems. We had arable land, but our goal was to preserve the pasture networks. We therefore explored various methods to restore biodiversity on arable land. We bought habitat-specific seeds, brought bales of hay from other areas to introduce native seeds, practiced grazing according to certain rules, and let the soil rest, according to a procedure established together with experts”. Over approximately 10-18 hectares, these interventions resulted in visible improvements in both species diversity and ecosystem function. Importantly, these ecological gains also reflect the indirect drivers identified earlier in the analysis. By reactivating land that might otherwise be abandoned, demonstrating affordable practices that alleviate economic pressures, and partially compensating for gaps in policy enforcement, the interventions address the broader

structural challenges shaping local land use. This connection indicates that restoration outcomes are not isolated events but rather emerge from a wider socio-economic and governance context.

Addressing root causes of biodiversity loss: To ensure a just transition, GAL has worked to address the root causes of biodiversity loss through practical, community-driven initiatives: a) Deforestation and land degradation: Conservation projects such as “Achiziționarea de echipamente pentru fabricarea brichetelor din resturi vegetale” (“Purchase of equipment for the manufacture of briquettes from vegetable waste”) promote sustainable land use and waste management. By funding equipment that transforms plant waste into briquettes, GAL is helping to reduce deforestation and encourage responsible resource use (<https://tarnava-mare.ro/bune-practici/proiecte-finantate-prin-sdl-2014-2020/>); b) Agricultural intensification: GAL has promoted traditional and organic farming techniques, supporting projects such as “Diversificarea activității fermei Boian Global Business SRL”, which encourages sustainable agriculture and biodiversity-friendly food production (<https://tarnava-mare.ro/bune-practici/proiecte-finantate-prin-sdl-2014-2020/>). c) Declining traditional knowledge: The cultural establishment in Daneș provides a venue for knowledge-sharing events and workshops that educate locals about sustainable farming, biodiversity conservation, and traditional ecological knowledge (<https://tarnava-mare.ro/bune-practici/proiecte-finantate-prin-sdl-2014-2020/>); d) Overexploitation of resources: GAL has implemented sustainable harvesting guidelines and supported projects such as “Modernizarea exploatației agricole Grădinile Mălâncrav SRL”, which promotes biodiversity-friendly farming practices (<https://tarnava-mare.ro/bune-practici/proiecte-finantate-prin-sdl-2014-2020/>).

Strategic responses to lock-ins and barriers: Despite success, GAL has encountered several challenges:

a) Regulatory constraints: Legal restrictions sometimes hinder traditional farming and grazing practices that support biodiversity conservation.

b) Economic challenges: Many small-scale farmers lack financial incentives to adopt biodiversity-friendly practices.

c) Knowledge gaps: There remains a disconnect between conservation policies and local ecological knowledge.

To address these challenges, GAL has implemented strategic responses:

Economic incentives for conservation: Eco-tourism initiatives, such as the “Înființare Pensiune Turistică Saschiz” project, have linked biodiversity conservation with local economic benefits; Educational outreach and training: The equipping of a cultural establishment in Daneș has created an educational hub for biodiversity awareness, organic farming, and conservation (<https://tarnava-mare.ro/bune-practici/proiecte-finantate-prin-sdl-2014-2020/>).

Moreover, GAL sought to bridge the gap between legislation and practical application. One challenge noted was the ineffective implementation of environmental policies: “A concrete example of transformation would be the implementation of existing legislation. For example, the effective implementation of the grasslands law and pastoral

management, as well as the implementation of the Natura 2000 directives. We have the tools, but they are not being put into practice". Ensuring that legal frameworks align with conservation needs is a critical step toward breaking systemic lock-ins.

Leveraging influence and systemic change: GAL strategically influences conservation policies and land management practices by:

- 1) Being part of participatory research methods to document and integrate traditional ecological knowledge into formal conservation strategies (e.g., Biotraces and the former initiatives).
- 2) Creating pilot projects to showcase the economic and environmental benefits of biodiversity conservation. A notable intervention in Saschiz involved the biodiversity-friendly certification program for local agricultural products, which incentivizes farmers to adopt sustainable practices while providing transparency for consumers. The success of this program has encouraged discussions on scaling similar models to other regions.
- 3) Collaborative thinking with researchers: Collaboration between researchers and societal partners has been essential in refining conservation strategies. Researchers contribute scientific methodologies for data collection and analysis, while societal partners provide local insights and contextual knowledge. A key takeaway from these collaborations is the importance of adaptive management. One researcher in the workshop noted, "Rather than imposing predefined solutions, we need to adapt interventions based on local feedback and environmental changes continuously". This flexible approach has led to more effective and locally relevant conservation strategies.

2.5.7 Discussion

The biodiversity regeneration strategies implemented by the LAG/GAL and UBB team offer insights into conservation efforts at the local level. These initiatives address environmental concerns while navigating economic, social, and policy-related challenges. This discussion critically examines their transformative potential, the role of indirect drivers of biodiversity loss, key enablers for replication, and the broader socio-economic and environmental contexts shaping biodiversity conservation. Consequently, building on the indirect drivers and systemic lock-ins previously identified, such as policy misalignments, socio-economic pressures, and the erosion of traditional stewardship, this section links the discussion of transformative potential to these deeper structural constraints. By doing so, it emphasizes that proposed innovations cannot be understood in isolation but must be situated within the broader socio-ecological dynamics that shape local land-use decisions. This bridging perspective highlights how the institutional path dependencies continue to shape community practices and constrain options for transformative change. At the same time, it highlights how emerging enablers, such as strengthened local governance and collaborative learning processes, can help unlock alternative trajectories. Together, these insights underscore the need for comprehensive strategies that address both surface-level challenges and the underlying mechanisms contributing to biodiversity loss.

Biodiversity conservation increasingly requires transformative change rather than incremental adjustments. The results of the workshops demonstrate promising approaches, but their success depends on whether these efforts can trigger broader systemic shifts. Actual transformative change, as we have seen, involves altering

economic incentives, policy enforcement, and cultural values to promote long-term ecological sustainability.

A significant barrier to transformative change is the weak enforcement of environmental policies. While regulations exist to protect biodiversity, their implementation is often inconsistent. Without proper enforcement, conservation initiatives risk being fragmented and ineffective. Stronger governance mechanisms, combined with community engagement, can help bridge this gap. In evaluating the broader context, it's clear that multi-level governance support is needed. Local action can achieve a great deal, but supportive regional/national frameworks (policies, funding, property rights, etc.) significantly enhance its impact. Likewise, economic and social trends (migration, market changes) will influence how far a local biodiversity strategy can go. The interplay between top-down and bottom-up efforts emerges here: top-down efforts (government policies, EU regulations) set the enabling environment, while bottom-up efforts (community initiatives, LAG, local knowledge) ensure on-the-ground implementation and innovation. The UBB team's academic perspective, combined with the LAG's grassroots base, exemplifies bridging these levels – scientific evidence informing local practice, and local lessons feeding back into broader policy discussions.

Several indirect factors were identified as primarily contributing to biodiversity loss, including economic pressures, land-use changes, and policy misalignment. Addressing these challenges requires an integrated approach that considers both environmental and socio-economic factors. Farmers often struggle to strike a balance between sustainability and profitability. While some continue organic farming practices, others prioritize immediate financial stability, making it challenging to maintain biodiversity-friendly land-use practices. Providing financial incentives, such as subsidies for sustainable farming, can help offset economic constraints. Land privatization and resource monopolization pose further threats to biodiversity. Effective land management policies should prevent overexploitation and ensure equitable distribution of resources. The integration of conservation goals into agricultural and economic policies is crucial for long-term sustainability. Many biodiversity-rich areas are maintained through traditional farming and grazing practices. However, these landscapes face threats from modern agricultural expansion and overgrazing. Conservation strategies should support traditional land-use methods while incorporating sustainable management techniques to preserve habitat heterogeneity.

For biodiversity conservation efforts to be practical on a larger scale, successful initiatives must be replicable and resilient to disruptions such as climate change and economic instability. Climate change remains a significant disruptor of biodiversity. Strategies such as sustainable water management, habitat restoration, and agroecology can enhance ecosystem resilience. Additionally, economic diversification, such as promoting eco-tourism or organic farming, can reduce reliance on resource-intensive industries and provide alternative livelihoods for local communities. Local engagement plays a crucial role in conservation success. Functional communities of practice, such as farmer cooperatives and knowledge-sharing networks, facilitate the exchange of ideas and best practices. These groups help sustain biodiversity initiatives beyond the initial project scope. Environmental education programs, such as school gardens and rural training workshops, build awareness and encourage sustainable practices. Integrating biodiversity education into local curricula fosters long-term ecological stewardship. That is why transformative biodiversity management requires a shift in societal values. Many local economies prioritize short-term profit, making it challenging to implement conservation-

friendly practices. Encouraging a collective mindset that values long-term ecological health over immediate economic gain is essential. Educational initiatives and awareness campaigns can help drive this change.

Conservation efforts do not exist in isolation; they must be integrated with economic and social realities. Aligning biodiversity goals with sustainable development is crucial for long-term success. Biodiversity regeneration must coexist with economic growth. While monoculture farming and land privatization pose threats, sustainable land-use strategies can create a balance. Agroecological methods, such as crop rotation and regenerative grazing, can enhance both productivity and biodiversity conservation. Eco-tourism offers a chance to generate income while promoting environmental conservation. Responsible tourism initiatives can create financial incentives for local communities to protect natural landscapes. Similarly, sustainable resource management – such as responsible forestry and fisheries policies – ensures long-term ecological and economic stability. Strong governance structures are essential for biodiversity conservation. Participatory decision-making, where local stakeholders have a voice in policy and land-use planning, leads to more sustainable outcomes. Incentive programs, such as payments for ecosystem services and conservation grants, can further align economic interests with biodiversity goals.

Transformative change reminds us that isolated projects must connect to more profound societal shifts to truly reverse biodiversity loss. The indirect drivers highlight economic and policy contexts as both obstacles and targets for integration, underscoring that conservation success demands engaging with broader development agendas. The focus on enablers and disruptors highlights the importance of community empowerment, knowledge sharing, and resilience in scaling up positive outcomes and withstanding shocks, such as those posed by climate change. Ultimately, examining the broader socio-economic context reveals that conservation and human development need not be mutually exclusive, with effective governance, targeted incentives, and participatory approaches, they can be mutually reinforcing.

The LAG-UBB co-learning can be seen as a microcosm of global biodiversity efforts, as it faces the same need to balance human needs and ecological integrity, requires patience in changing mindsets, and demands persistence in the face of external pressures. Critically, this co-learning experience contributes to a growing understanding that effective biodiversity regeneration is as much a social challenge as an ecological one. The key themes explored are not just academic concepts; they manifest in day-to-day decisions – a farmer choosing integrated pest management, a town council debating land use, a youth group volunteering for tree planting. By expanding and refining the discussion around these themes, we appreciate that meaningful biodiversity/nature conservation requires transformational thinking, cross-sector collaboration, and a long-term commitment to harmonizing our socio-economic systems with the natural world. The partnership between LAG/GAL and the UBB team, therefore, is relevant not only for the local benefits it produces but also for the lessons and inspiration it offers to other communities striving for a more biodiverse future.

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2.6 UGOT Case Study: Sweden

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2.6.1 Short presentation of the case

The study examines focusing on biodiversity dynamics among private forest owners in three Swedish parishes—Säve, Istorp, and Ambjörnarp.

Geographical and Historical Dimensions

Säve (near Gothenburg) features flat farmland and forested hills shaped by glaciation. Historically dominated by farming, deforestation peaked in the 19th century, followed by regrowth and spruce planting. Today, urban expansion pressures forests, with most residents working outside agriculture. Istorp is characterized by agricultural valleys and forested uplands, once communal grazing lands. Fires and 19th-century land reforms fragmented ownership, leading to conifer plantations. The population has declined since the 19th century, and current employment spans agriculture, construction, and services. Ambjörnarp is predominantly forested, with continuity since the 17th century. Poor soils constrained farming, fostering self-sufficient animal husbandry. Logging accelerated in

the late 19th century, reducing deciduous cover. Population peaked around 1900 but later stabilized at low levels.

Key Actors and Worldviews

Swedish forestry debates pit industry (productive forestry) against conservationists (protection of old-growth forests). Private forest owners—diverse in background and rarely professional foresters—occupy a middle ground, valuing both ecology and practice. Local differences emerge: in Ambjörnarp, biodiversity is tied to forestry practices; in Istorp, to species variation and protection; and in Säve, to informed reasoning. Companies like Sveaskog, Derome, and Skanska integrate biodiversity unevenly, while associations such as Södra promote certification and voluntary conservation. Government actors (Swedish Forest Agency, Environmental Protection Agency, County Boards) enforce legislation and monitor biodiversity, with municipalities playing varying roles—minimal in Istorp/Ambjörnarp but significant in urbanizing Säve. Non-human “actants” such as capercaillie, trees, soils, and topography also shape forest use and conservation debates.

Drivers of Biodiversity Loss

Key direct drivers include: reforestation (conversion of heathlands and open landscapes to conifers); even-aged silviculture (clear-cutting and monocultures, replacing diverse forest structures); and urban expansion (notably in Säve, where housing and logistics displace forests). Indirect drivers stem from industrialization, urbanization, and reinforcement of production forestry.

Cultural and Identity Dynamics

Forest owners emphasize relational values (recreation, heritage, stewardship) over economic returns. Conflicts arise with authorities and industry over management and aesthetics. Gender dynamics show women’s growing yet marginalized role, with networks like Dryaderna providing support. Age influences stewardship, especially succession planning.

Political/Institutional Dynamics

Swedish forestry is locked into even-aged silviculture due to long-standing policies, industrial interests, and infrastructure. This entrenched model shapes both national forestry culture and Sweden’s role in European policy, creating barriers to biodiversity-friendly alternatives.

2.6.2 Evaluation of strategies in action

In the Swedish case study, strategies in action have largely emerged from local practices rather than from explicit and designed interventions. Instead of building on an existing societal partnership or promoting a particular biodiversity innovation, our research sought to explore and analyse forest owners’ own strategies and understandings regarding biodiversity management. Through qualitative face-to-face interviews, walk-along interviews, and a series of workshops held between spring and summer 2025, the case study has examined how private forest owners in southwestern Sweden engage with

biodiversity, and how these engagements reflect both potential enablers and barriers to transformative change.

Although no single practice or initiative clearly qualifies as transformative in an institutional or societal sense, the case study identified several tendencies that may contain the seeds of future change. Some forest owners expressed interest in alternative silvicultural practices, such as continuous-cover forestry or the introduction of more mixed stands, often motivated by concerns over climate change or aesthetic preferences, or species diversity. This was especially explicitly visible in the Ambjörnarp and Istorp workshops, where owners discussed their dissatisfaction with monocultures and clear-cuts, and their aspirations to maintain a more varied and dynamic forest landscape. However, such approaches remain rare in practice. Even owners with opinions in favour of biodiversity often continue to manage their land according to conventional, albeit small-scale, even-aged forestry. This discrepancy illustrates the gap between intentions and structural constraints – including economic market structures, limited advisory support, and current institutional inertia – that continue to favour production-oriented forestry.

The transformative potential of these emerging strategies lies less in their current extent and more in their relational and reflexive dimensions. Many forest owners articulated a deep emotional connection to their land, framed through ideas of intergenerational stewardship and place-based responsibility. These sentiments, while not always expressed in ecological or scientific language, reflect long-term considerations and a concern for continuity, which align well with core principles of biodiversity conservation. Through the workshops, forest owners were able to encounter others with differing or similar views and begin to position their own practices and wishes within a broader spectrum of forest management. This dialogue appeared to stimulate reflection on what biodiversity and alternative forestry might mean in practice and what current limitations and possibilities there are for the individual forest owner.

Forest owners often make autonomous decisions about their forest management, with many choosing to diversify tree species. While this may align with biodiversity goals, it is frequently driven by other motives – such as aesthetic preferences near homes or recreational areas, or practical experiences showing that spruce monocultures, historically common, are ill-suited to certain soils and increasingly vulnerable to drought. As a result, diversification occurs even among owners who do not explicitly frame their practices in ecological terms. However, workshops revealed that current forestry market structures are poorly adapted to support alternative management models (Workshops in Ambjörnarp and Istorp, March 2025). The system is adapted to bulk timber and pulpwood production, making it difficult to sell high-quality wood for crafts or building restoration. In response, some owners – particularly in Istorp – have initiated local collaborations to exchange goods and services, aiming to sustain alternative forestry through mutual support (Workshop in Istorp, March 2025; Interview with 'Maria', May 2024). In Säve, urbanisation itself emerged as a direct driver of biodiversity loss. Many forest owners acknowledged the need for housing and had sold land for development, yet expressed concern that municipal planning prioritised short-term expansion where infrastructure already existed, rather than distributing development more evenly across the area. Workshop participants felt that ecological values in the forest were overlooked and called for more consistent, long-term strategies balancing conservation with growth (Workshop in Säve, March 2025). Across all case study areas, landscape conditions further shaped what forms of forestry were feasible. Steep slopes, wet soils, and

inaccessible areas often remained unmanaged simply because they were impractical to harvest, thereby acting as somewhat unintentional biodiversity refuges.

Despite these examples, the case study also revealed how fragmented ownership, lack of alternative collective infrastructure, and policy uncertainty limit forest owners' capacity to engage in more coordinated or strategic biodiversity initiatives. While forest owners in Sweden have considerable legal freedom to manage their land, their practical agency is often constrained by time, knowledge gaps, available technology and market structures. Many participants expressed confusion or frustration over shifting policy signals and contradictory advice from authorities in a longer time perspective, particularly around biodiversity and acceptable management practices. Some recounted negative experiences with conservation interventions, where external actors were perceived to have intervened without sufficient understanding of local conditions or without adequate compensation (Workshop in Ambjörnarp, March 2025). These experiences contribute to a rather widespread scepticism toward top-down governance and a preference for autonomy in forest decision-making.

The workshop with Dryaderna, the network of female forest owners (Workshop with Dryaderna, March 2025), aimed at examining the specific conditions for female forest owners and analyse whether women face particular challenges when it comes to questions of biodiversity and the potential for transformative change. As this workshop revealed, the primary reason for this network was to provide an arena for knowledge exchange and dissemination between female forest owners in a more open way than allowed for in ordinary settings. According to the participants, the actual forestry conducted by female forest owners do not diverge in any significant way from their male counterparts, although they face certain discrimination with regards to recognition of their knowledge as forest owners. Although previous literature tends to emphasize the higher involvement of female forest owners in nature conservation and environmental values (Bakx et al., 2024; Tiebel et al., 2022), such assumptions have also recently been called into question based on more decisive factors for management directions such as property size (Hansen et al., 2025). Another aspect, that research about female forest owner networks emphasize, is that female forest owners tend to replicate masculine forestry norms (Laszlo Ambjörnsson, 2021).

The project attempted to address some of these constraints by creating horizontal arenas for dialogue through our workshops. The workshop format – based on small-group discussions and supported by visual materials and thematic questions – enabled participants to speak on their own terms, and encouraged those with less formal knowledge to participate, with varied degrees of success. Although no collective strategies or formal innovations were co-produced, the workshops served as arenas where personal knowledge and practical experiences could be exchanged and validated locally. They made the internal diversity of the forest owner group visible – from those focused on production, to those motivated by conservation, recreation, or tradition – and challenged the image of the “typical” forest owner often invoked in public discourse.

Importantly, the case study also recognised the limits of its own influence, where we sought primarily to identify barriers, emerging practices, and supporting local reflexivity. While no direct replication of strategies or scaling of innovations occurred during the study period, the regional stakeholder workshop (Workshop in Gothenburg, August 2025) bridged local insights with higher governance levels, including forest authorities, advisory organisations, and environmental NGOs. This hopefully helped to connect the situated

knowledge and latent potential of private forest owners with broader processes of policy development and institutional adaptation.

2.6.3 Enablers and disruptors

The case study reveals several enablers and disruptors influencing the potential for biodiversity net-gain and transformative change. These emerge from the interaction between the material realities of forest ownership, institutional frameworks, and broader economic structures, rather than from isolated interventions or policies.

One key enabler identified is the freedom of choice in forest management granted to private forest owners under Swedish forest law. This legal autonomy allows owners to pursue biodiversity-enhancing practices if they want, including continuous cover forestry, leaving deadwood, promoting deciduous tree species, and setting aside conservation areas. Some forest owners use this freedom as an opportunity to align forest use with personal values, including long-term stewardship, aesthetic preferences, or ecological interest. However, while this flexibility theoretically enables diverse forest management practices, it functions as an enabler only when owners possess the knowledge, values, resources, and support networks to act on it.

A second enabler is the presence of strong place-based knowledge and long-term ownership, especially in more rural and forest-dominated areas like Ambjörnarp and Istorp. Here, forest owners often manage land that has been in the family for generations, providing a deeper understanding of local ecology and landscape dynamics. In these settings, some landowners resist conventional homogenous forest management and instead develop forest practices better adapted to site conditions. Some emphasize soil improvement through ash spreading or selective harvesting aimed at maintaining ecological structure (Workshops in Istorp and Ambjörnarp, March 2025). These actions are sometimes related to local knowledge and peer-to-peer learning rather than formal extension systems (Workshop in Ambjörnarp, March 2025).

Third, local collaboration and exchange of services have emerged as important enablers, particularly in areas where state or market support is limited. In Istorp, some landowners have developed informal networks to trade timber, services, and knowledge, partly as a means to foster local self-sufficiency (Workshop in Istorp, March 2025). This generates a level of independence and collective capacity that can support biodiversity goals, especially when it enables alternative harvesting methods or the use of non-standard forest products.

However, these enablers are often constrained or undermined by powerful and persistent disruptors. Foremost among these is the market structure for forest products, which remains geared toward pulpwood and bulk timber. This favours large-scale, mechanised, and standardised forest operations. Certification systems such as FSC or PEFC, while designed to ensure sustainability, are experienced by many private owners as too bureaucratic and poorly adapted to small-scale or biodiversity-oriented forestry (Workshop in Ambjörnarp, March 2025). Even owners who wish to produce high-quality timber or manage for ecological values often find that buyers, contractors, and sawmills are uninterested or unequipped to handle such products (Workshops in Ambjörnarp and Istorp, March 2025). This represents a fundamental mismatch between local ambitions and the economic infrastructure of the forestry sector.

Another major disruptor is the dominance of large forest companies and institutional actors, which shape norms and expectations in forestry. Their management models often prioritise clear-cutting, rapid rotation, and homogenous stands, which set the standard for what is seen as “productive” or “modern” forestry. For small and medium-sized private owners, especially those lacking forestry training or advisory support, these models may appear to be the only viable or legitimate options.

Policy inconsistency across time further acts as a disruptor. Owners recall how past state subsidies encouraged practices now considered detrimental to biodiversity, such as spruce planting on unsuitable soils or to suppress deciduous tree growth through herbicide spraying (Workshop in Ambjörnarp, March 2025). Current biodiversity policies, while aiming to reverse these trends, are often met with scepticism because of their shifting nature and perceived lack of grounding in local realities (Workshops in Ambjörnarp and Istorp, and with Dryaderna, March 2025). This generates a credibility gap that limits the transformative potential of top-down strategies.

In more urbanised contexts, such as Säve, a different set of disruptors emerges. Here, urban expansion and real estate speculation are important drivers of biodiversity loss. Forest land is here valued for its development potential rather than its ecological or forest-based functions. Many owners have sold or subdivided land for housing, and forest management is often oriented toward aesthetic or recreational functions rather than long-term biodiversity strategies or conventional forestry. Municipal planning, according to several workshop participants, prioritises development where infrastructure already exists (Workshop in Säve, March 2025), which may reinforce pressures on existing remaining forest patches in those areas. Participants also described local politics as short-term and inconsistent. Despite these challenges, a potential enabler is apparent where some owners in Säve have a multifunctional land use, where forest land serves multiple overlapping purposes: recreation, privacy, informal conservation, and limited timber production primarily for firewood. While not necessarily aligned with formal biodiversity goals, these uses can help maintain heterogeneous forest structures and provide refuges for species.

Regarding the replicability of enablers, the findings suggest that while some practices – like local cooperation – are context-specific, the underlying enabling conditions (e.g. autonomy, embedded knowledge, peer learning) could be supported more broadly through targeted policy and institutional support. For example, advisory systems that further validate and support diverse forest management approaches, rather than focusing on promoting standardised solutions, could help scale local innovations. Likewise, procurement systems that recognise non-standard timber products or more strongly reward ecological outcomes, such as further development of conservation premiums or biodiversity credits if done in non-standard ways, could broaden the impact of small-scale biodiversity efforts.

In terms of addressing disruptors, local actors currently have limited capacity to challenge structural market conditions or institutional forestry norms. Some resist by operating in niche markets or through informal economies, but this does not amount to systemic change. Bridging this gap would require interventions at national or even EU level, such as regulatory reforms, differentiated subsidies, or market incentives for ecosystem services.

The interaction between local and national/EU policy is complex. While EU directives on biodiversity and climate increasingly emphasise ecological restoration and multifunctional

landscapes, they are filtered through national forest policy, which in Sweden remains deeply shaped by the dual goals of production and environmental protection. In practice, production goals dominate, due primarily to historical inertia, and biodiversity strategies tend to be additive rather than transformative. Local actors often experience EU-linked policies – such as the Nature Restoration Law – as top-down and misaligned with on-the-ground conditions, and circumscribing both national and local senses of self-determination. At the same time, national implementation of these policies varies depending on political priorities, which further contributes to uncertainty.

In conclusion, transformative change in Swedish private forestry is currently constrained by a combination of entrenched market structures, institutional inertia, and weak integration between ecological and economic goals. Nonetheless, enablers exist in the form of legal autonomy, local knowledge, peer collaboration, and multifunctional land use. Strengthening these enablers – for example through broader advisory support and market innovation – while actively mitigating the structural disruptors identified above, will be essential to any future strategy for biodiversity regeneration in this context.

2.6.4 Failed and successful practices

Successful Practices

A major success in this case study was the ability to reach a broad and diverse set of private forest owners in three local study areas, without relying primarily on established organisations such as forest companies or associations. Instead, contact was made directly with forest owners, resulting in a wide range of perspectives in both interviews and workshops. This allowed us to explore a spectrum of forest management practices across geographic, economic, and social contexts – from peri-urban areas in Säve to small-scale farming landscapes in Istorp and forest-dominated rural settings in Ambjörnarp.

Another success was the initiation of local dialogues through our workshops, which enabled forest owners to reflect on alternative or diversified forest management practices. These workshops revealed existing practices of variation and adaptation among forest owners and also initiated discussions around collaboration and autonomy, particularly in relation to industrial forestry norms. For instance, in Istorp, existing informal exchange networks between owners – where timber, machinery, and services are traded – appear to offer a foundation for alternative forms of land management. These findings point to a potential for more horizontal and locally grounded forms of organising among forest owners, which could support biodiversity regeneration beyond current certification schemes.

From a research design perspective, the case study succeeded in highlighting that some forest owners often already engage in practices that deviate from the standard industrial model. While certification schemes typically encourage certain set-asides – such as steep slopes or wetlands that are left unmanaged or managed in a limited way – some owners actively experiment with alternative management strategies even on productive land. This includes practices like selective logging and mixed-species planting. Such initiatives, though currently small in scale, offer promising models for increasing structural and species diversity in Swedish forests while responding to both ecological and owner-specific values.

Another important success was the final stakeholder workshop in August 2025, where actors from across the forestry sector – authorities, advisors, industry and NGOs – were brought together (Workshop with stakeholders, Gothenburg, August 2025). That this was achieved within a relatively short project timeframe suggests a strong interest in locally driven, bottom-up perspectives on forestry, and demonstrates the potential to elevate insights from small-scale ownership contexts into broader policy discussions.

Failed or Less Effective Practices

One clear limitation of the study was the difficulty in reaching forest owners who hold strongly negative views on biodiversity or alternative forest management. While the study did include some sceptical voices – which provided particularly valuable interviews – a broader representation of this group would have enriched the analysis of barriers to biodiversity regeneration. For example, we may have benefited from approaching such owners through more familiar channels like forest owner associations (e.g. Södra), which could have lent credibility and increased positive responses to participation.

Similarly, the study faced challenges in engaging with landowners primarily involved in property speculation, particularly in Säve. These owners, who represent a significant portion of the local forest ownership structure, were generally uninterested in participating. Their absence leaves a gap in the analysis, as their actions – such as parcelling or keeping forest land for residential development – constitute an important driver of biodiversity loss in peri-urban areas. Including their perspectives might have revealed further obstacles to landscape-level regeneration.

Finally, the absence of a clear societal partner in the project – such as a municipality or coordinated landowner group – meant that we as researchers had to drive the process independently. This made it difficult to co-develop formal biodiversity strategies or implementation plans. The fragmented nature of forest ownership, where individual actors operate largely autonomously, further constrained the potential for formalised interventions during the project period.

Strategic Gaps and Missed Opportunities

The most significant gap in the study relates to the lack of formal structures for horizontal collaboration among forest owners. While individual practices varied considerably and some networks existed informally, there was little evidence of coordinated collective action to promote biodiversity regeneration, apart from the previously mentioned conservation premium by Södra. Nonetheless, the workshops indicated a potential openness to collaboration, particularly in areas where owners share values or challenges.

Another gap concerns the disconnect between local alternative practices and prevailing market structures. Several owners expressed frustration with timber buyers' focus on bulk pulpwood, which undermines efforts to produce high-quality or niche timber products. These economic structures act as disruptors by making it difficult for owners to pursue diversified strategies, even when motivated to do so.

In terms of knowledge integration, there was limited incorporation of younger or more diverse voices in the study. Forest ownership in Sweden tends to be older and male-dominated, and while some efforts were made to engage other perspectives – such as

female owners or those with mixed-use landscapes – a wider geographical focus would have enabled to further target certain groups of forest owners.

Conclusion and Lessons Learned

This case study shows that private forest owners are already engaging in a range of diverse and context-sensitive management practices, many of which contain elements supportive of biodiversity regeneration. However, these efforts are often individualised, small-scale, and poorly aligned with broader market and policy structures. The most successful practices identified in this study – direct owner engagement, local dialogue creation, and documentation of informal networks – suggest that bottom-up approaches have strong potential if given adequate support.

Conversely, difficulties in reaching sceptical owners or property speculators highlight the importance of credibility, trust, and framing when addressing contested topics like biodiversity. The lack of a formal societal partner limited the potential for strategy co-design, but also made visible the need for future projects that focus explicitly on fostering horizontal organisation and peer-driven learning among forest owners.

Ultimately, the study illustrates both the limitations and the latent potential of fragmented ownership systems. While structural disruptors remain – such as market logics and certification biases – seeds of change exist in the form of local knowledge, alternative values, and emerging collaborative tendencies. A future project could build on these findings by supporting forest owner-driven local networks, improving communication channels between local and national actors, and further challenging the one-size-fits-all orientation of current forest governance models.

2.6.5 Co-learning

Introduction: Co-learning in an exploratory case

In the Swedish case study, co-learning emerged primarily as a research-led process in the absence of an established societal partner. The ambition was not to implement a predefined action plan, but to explore whether an analysis of local bottom-up processes could initiate dialogue and reflection among private forest owners around more biodiversity-friendly forest management. In this context, co-learning was also a way to test the potential for new forms of organisation, shared understanding, and local knowledge about forestry and biodiversity.

Co-learning as a principle and method

The foundation of the case was a large number of qualitative interviews with forest owners in three distinct areas – Säve, Istorp, and Ambjörnarp – which provided empirical insights and served as a basis for workshop development. These interviews revealed the diversity of ownership structures, motivations, and land-use practices, and informed the design of the workshops that followed. Each workshop was planned with the explicit aim to generate open-ended discussions among local actors, without predefined outcomes or expectations.

Rather than seeking consensus, the workshops were designed to allow tensions and disagreements to surface, making it possible to identify both shared concerns and points of friction. The co-learning approach was therefore exploratory and emergent, aimed at revealing latent possibilities for cooperation and critical reflection on prevailing forestry practices. By intentionally including moments of collective synthesis – where group discussions were summarized and reflected upon in plenary – the workshops created spaces for mutual recognition and exchange between forest owners with different perspectives.

Co-learning during the D2.4 preparation

Three main types of co-learning activities were conducted during the preparation of this deliverable: the thematic workshops with forest owners, the targeted workshop with female forest owners (Dryaderna), and the August 2025 stakeholder workshop which brought together actors from civil society, state agencies, and research.

In the Ambjörnarp and Istorp workshops (March 2025), the discussions focused on possibilities and obstacles for more biodiversity-sensitive or alternative forestry, as well as identifying messages that forest owners themselves wanted to transmit to regional stakeholders. These workshops served as both moments of knowledge sharing and sites of reflection on forest management under changing ecological and policy conditions. In Säve (March 2025), where urban pressures are more tangible, the discussion centred on how forest owners relate to urbanisation, property speculation, and ecological values in an increasingly urbanised landscape. This workshop offered insight into how ecological concerns are weighed against economic and social pressures in a semi-urban setting. The workshop with Dryaderna (March 2025) addressed gender-specific challenges among female forest owners, and provided valuable insights into the reasons for organising women-only networks for knowledge sharing among forest owners. Finally, the stakeholder workshop in August 2025 gathered a wider range of actors and created a forum for feedback and strategic dialogue. This was not only a moment of co-learning between researchers and societal actors, but also a way to leverage the findings from the local workshops into a broader institutional setting.

Co-learning dynamics in the case study

The most significant outcome of the co-learning moments was the confirmation that local dialogue around biodiversity is both possible and meaningful. While forest owners differed in their priorities and practices, many shared concerns emerged – such as market limitations, bureaucratic obstacles, and uncertainty around future policy. At the same time, geographical context and degree of forest management activity shaped which challenges were most pressing. The workshops showed that despite these differences, forest owners could engage in constructive conversation and identify opportunities for local collaboration and mutual support.

In Istorp, for example, some participants expressed interest in further developing local exchange systems and reducing their dependence on the conventional mass timber market. These reflections did not result in immediate collective action but demonstrated a latent willingness to explore alternatives, especially among forest owners with limited trust in large-scale actors. Some tensions also emerged, where some participants strongly advocated continuous cover forestry, while others viewed it as economically unviable – especially those with long experience in mechanised forestry (Workshop in Istorp, March 2025). In Ambjörnarp, discussions revealed tensions around how to

manage carbon sequestration: whether through more active silviculture or by allowing natural succession (Workshop in Ambjörnarp, March 2025). These tensions did not resolve into agreement, but they helped clarify the differences among the participants and their different viewpoints.

Importantly, the co-learning moments were not limited to the participants themselves. For the researchers, the workshops revealed further how forest owners formulate problems, identify common points and obstacles, and relate their individual decisions to broader ecological and policy contexts. In this sense, co-learning also served as a means of refining the research team's understanding of transformative potential under highly individualised ownership conditions.

However, the case study also revealed some of the limits of co-learning in this context. Despite efforts to reach a broad spectrum of forest owners, those who were explicitly opposed to biodiversity measures or sceptical of alternative practices were underrepresented in both interviews and workshops. As noted in previous sections, these groups were harder to engage and may have perceived the project as biased. This reduced the range of views in some settings and limited the extent to which co-learning could encompass the full spectrum of tensions in Swedish forestry. Future efforts may need to work more deliberately with trusted intermediaries (e.g. Södra) or with alternative recruitment strategies.

Conclusion: Key insights and future directions

In conclusion, co-learning in the Swedish allowed for the emergence of new understandings among forest owners, created modest spaces for mutual recognition, and surfaced informal practices that could serve as entry points for future action. Although no joint action plans were developed, the workshops functioned as important sites of reflection and pointed to the potential for more bottom-up approaches to biodiversity governance. For researchers, the co-learning approach reinforced the usefulness of open-ended, conversational formats in building and understanding locally grounded knowledge in a wider context. Looking forward, deeper co-learning would require sustained engagement, mechanisms for follow-up, and possibly the emergence of intermediary actors who can stabilise and support informal initiatives. But as an initial step, the workshops and interviews conducted in this case study have laid the groundwork for such future processes and may serve as a model for how to approach highly fragmented actor landscapes in other contexts as well.

2.6.6 Testing of interventions

Introduction: What was tested and why it matters

In our case study, interventions took the form of workshops organised and facilitated by the research team. Unlike other project cases, there was no official societal partner with a mandate to lead the process. Forest owners in the study areas are not collectively organised around biodiversity issues, and this absence strongly shaped our approach. The workshops themselves became the intervention, aiming to create an arena for discussion where forest owners could articulate their views, exchange experiences, and reflect on the challenges of forestry and biodiversity.

Testing in this sense did not mean measuring behavioural changes or producing specific outcomes. Rather, it meant critically assessing whether such researcher-led workshops could function as entry points for dialogue and for surfacing knowledge about opportunities and obstacles to biodiversity-friendly forestry. This is significant because biodiversity loss in private forestry is tied to how markets and institutions enable or constrain alternative actions, and how fragmented groups of owners can be mobilised locally around common concerns to overcome these constraints.

Description of the testing process

The testing was conducted in connection to the three local workshops in the case study areas (Säve, Istorp, and Ambjörnarp), one workshop with the female forest owner network Dryaderna, and complemented by one regional stakeholder workshop. Each local workshop gathered forest owners with diverse backgrounds, motivations, and management strategies. Some were highly production-oriented, others more focused on recreation, aesthetics, or conservation values. The workshops were designed around sets of thematic questions and provided informational material, with the dual purpose of initiating local dialogue and providing material for analytical reflection.

No formal feedback workshop was organised. The main reason for this was the absence of a societal partner who could take responsibility for co-hosting such a process. Instead, the research team itself carried out the evaluation of the workshops. From our perspective, the local workshops worked effectively as interventions given their aims, and the stakeholder workshop served to test the insights generated against a wider governance and policy context. In this way, the process still provided a form of feedback loop, albeit mediated by researchers rather than through a formal societal partner.

Stakeholder engagement and participatory processes

The workshops showed that it is possible to mobilise a broad set of forest owners, even in contexts where they are not organised collectively around biodiversity. This in itself is an important finding: with relatively modest effort, we could bring together individuals with different priorities, values, and levels of forestry activity. Participants generally expressed appreciation for the opportunity to exchange experiences in a neutral setting, something that rarely happens otherwise.

At the same time, the testing also made clear the limitations. The workshops were one-off events, and no structures for sustained participation were created. For interventions to move beyond the exploratory stage, more durable mechanisms would be needed – such as identifying local ambassadors with strong trust and networks, who could take forward discussions and innovations beyond the workshop setting, an insight particularly generated from Workshop 5 (Workshop with stakeholders, Gothenburg, August 2025). The participatory process was thus valuable as a test of what is possible, but it also highlighted limits of long-term engagement when no local organisational structure exists.

Knowledge co-production and collaboration

The most tangible form of co-production that emerged from the workshops concerned the barriers to alternative forestry practices. Discussions revealed, in concrete terms, how existing market structures limit forest owners' options. Many participants noted that while they might be interested in diversifying their forests or producing higher-quality timber, the infrastructure and markets for such outputs are largely absent (Workshops in

Ambjörnarp and Istorp, March 2025). Pulpwood and bulk timber dominate, leaving little incentive for owners to manage forests differently.

Another insight concerned the challenges of inactivity. In Säve, several owners showed little inclination to actively manage their forests, due to lack of time, limited interest or knowledge barriers (Workshop in Säve, March 2025). This raised questions about how biodiversity strategies might address situations where the barrier is primarily not resistance to change but rather disengagement, and a fundamental lack of demonstrable viable options.

From the testing perspective, these discussions were particularly valuable. They provided grounded, practice-based insights that allowed us to better understand the structural barriers and opportunities. They also demonstrated that co-production in this context does not necessarily mean agreement on solutions, but rather the surfacing of critical constraints that need to be addressed if interventions are to gain traction.

Impact on policy and decision-making

Direct policy effects were not expected at this early stage of a transformative change process, and none can be observed yet. However, the stakeholder workshop provided an indirect channel for testing local insights against regional governance structures (Workshop with Stakeholders, Gothenburg, August 2025). Here, several key issues emerged.

First, participants problematised the one-sided nature of forestry advice, which remains heavily oriented toward industrial production, especially since the advisors are often timber buyers as well. This raised the question of whether advisory systems can be diversified to better support alternative forms of forestry. Second, there was broad recognition of the lack of market and infrastructural solutions. Without new outlets for timber products or systems that reward biodiversity-oriented management, local innovations are unlikely to spread. While a few examples exist, as noted in the text above regarding Södra's conservation premium and biodiversity credits, these are still only embryos of the needed development. Third, the discussion highlighted the importance of local innovators and ambassadors. Change requires individuals who not only experiment with new practices but also gain trust among peers, thereby helping to diffuse new ideas and methods.

While it is impossible at this stage to know whether these insights will translate into policy change, the workshop served as a testing ground for framing such issues in a collective arena. The fact that actors from different sides – authorities, industry, advisors and forestry organisations – engaged in this discussion suggests that space exists for further dialogue.

Community-level changes and social perceptions

At the local level, it is not yet possible to say whether the workshops produced changes in perceptions or practices among forest owners. Forestry operates on long timescales, and one-off interventions are unlikely to lead to immediate shifts, or tangible outcomes of such shifts. We can hope that new ideas were planted and that owners began reflecting on biodiversity in ways they had not before, but this cannot be substantiated with evidence at this stage.

Similarly, it is unlikely that any new practices have been adopted as a direct result of the workshops. For such changes to occur, a sequence of interventions would be necessary, ideally combined with support from other actors and institutional/policy incentives. What the testing did demonstrate is that forest owners are willing to discuss these issues and that dialogue can highlight both shared concerns and divergent perspectives. This is an important first step, but it remains limited in scope.

Transformative potential

Taken together, the results suggests that workshops can serve as useful interventions, but also that their transformative potential is limited if they remain isolated and short-term. The main contribution of our interventions was to open up discussion arenas: forest owners came together to discuss biodiversity and alternative forestry, structural barriers were articulated, and regional actors engaged with the findings.

At the same time, the workshops did not and could not resolve the deeper barriers of the system. Market structures, advisory systems, and institutional path dependencies remain strong. Without changes in these areas, even motivated owners will face difficulties in adopting alternative practices. The interventions therefore revealed both opportunities and limits: dialogue is possible, awareness of barriers can be increased, but transformative change requires broader structural shifts.

Future interventions could build on this by:

- Identifying local ambassadors who can sustain engagement and diffuse innovations.
- Creating forums where owners, advisors, and market actors can interact more directly.
- Embedding workshop-style interventions in longer-term processes rather than treating them as one-off events.

Lessons and open questions

The testing process provided important lessons. It showed that unorganised actors can be drawn upon to engage with each other, and that dialogue can surface key structural barriers such as market limitations and one-sided advisory systems. It demonstrated that researcher-led workshops can function as effective interventions when no societal partner exists, and that these can be complemented by broader stakeholder forums to situate findings in a governance context.

At the same time, the process highlighted the limits of such interventions. Without follow-up, sustained organisation, or institutional anchoring, the effects are likely to remain modest. The long timescales of forestry mean that any changes in perception or practice will take time to materialise and cannot be captured in the short term.

The open questions are therefore: how can temporary interventions be scaled up or embedded in more durable structures? How can new markets and infrastructures be developed to support alternative forestry practices? And how can advisory systems be diversified so that biodiversity-oriented approaches receive similar institutional support to industrial forestry?

Our testing suggests that with modest effort, meaningful dialogue can be initiated, and key structural constraints can be brought to the surface. The challenge is to build on these initial steps and connect them to broader processes of change

2.6.7 Discussion

The Swedish case study did not follow the conventional model of testing interventions through formalised feedback workshops with societal partners. Unlike other cases in the consortium, no official societal partner existed in this context, for reasons described in the text above. Private forest owners in southwestern Sweden constitute a highly fragmented actor group, without strong collective representation around biodiversity concerns. This meant that our interventions could not be designed as joint action plans negotiated with partners, but rather as research-led workshops aimed at stimulating dialogue, eliciting perspectives, and assessing barriers and opportunities for more biodiversity-friendly forestry.

From this point of view, the workshops themselves became the intervention. They were not supplementary exercises to test pre-existing strategies, but the primary mechanism through which we sought to engage actors, surface tensions, and experiment with new ways of discussing a diversified forestry. The purpose of testing, therefore, was to evaluate whether such workshops could function as arenas of engagement, what kinds of knowledge and conflicts they revealed, and how they might be improved or scaled up for projects in the future.

Forest owner workshops as interventions

Across the three local workshops in Säve, Istorp, and Ambjörnarp, we succeeded in gathering a surprisingly broad spectrum of forest owners, given that the workshops were aimed at discussing alternative forestry. This was a result we did not take for granted, given that owners are typically addressed individually through industry or state channels. The willingness of owners to come together in a neutral, research-organised arena should itself be seen as an intervention outcome. These meetings created opportunities for exchange that are otherwise largely absent, especially for owners who are neither strongly integrated in the forestry industry nor part of conservation organisations.

The character of the discussions varied across locations. In Säve, close to Gothenburg, the main issue was inactivity: many owners were not actively managing their forests, and findings ways to activate them proved to be a difficult issue which if handled could help counter the challenge of urbanisation. In Istorp, with its stronger agricultural base, the workshop revealed a more collaborative orientation and highlighted local exchange practices that could, in principle, support alternative forms of forestry. In Ambjörnarp, in a more forest-dominated setting, debates revolved around carbon, species choice, and the pressures of industrial demand.

Taken together, these local interventions confirmed both the diversity of ownership contexts and sets of common concerns. At the workshops in Ambjörnarp and Istorp, participants pointed to the dominance of conventional industrial markets, the lack of alternative outlets for timber, and the one-sided character of advisory services that primarily reproduce industrial practices. These insights were not generated by external experts but articulated collectively by the owners themselves once given a forum to do so.

Stakeholder workshop and comparative testing

Workshop 5, with a wider group of stakeholders, was important not only as a continuation of the case study but also as a test of whether the local findings resonated in a broader context. Here, forest owners' perspectives were set against the views of advisory organisations, county administrations, NGOs, and industry representatives. This workshop confirmed that many of the issues raised locally – such as the narrowness of advisory services, the dependence on conventional industrial markets, and the importance of institutional support for experimentation – are widely recognised. Several participants emphasised the importance of local ambassadors and innovators who can demonstrate alternative practices and build legitimacy among peers.

In this sense, the stakeholder workshop functioned as both an evaluation of our earlier interventions and as an intervention in itself. It demonstrated that it is possible to convene diverse actors on short notice and use local perspectives as an entry point for wider debate. While we cannot claim that this has led to any immediate policy change, it helped situate the case study within ongoing regional conversations and opened possible avenues for future collaboration.

Reflections on effects and limitations

The testing phase revealed a number of important dynamics. On the positive side, it showed that dialogue formats of this kind can successfully bring together actors who would not otherwise meet. The workshops also revealed a more complex picture of owners' motivations than is often assumed, demonstrating that there is no single 'private forest owner' perspective but a mosaic of orientations, practices, and constraints.

At the same time, the limitations were clear. Forestry is a long-term activity, and it is not possible to assess within the project period whether perceptions or practices have changed as a result of participation. We can hope that the discussions introduced new ways of thinking for some owners, but we cannot provide evidence of this. More importantly, the workshops showed that willingness to engage with biodiversity is not sufficient if structural barriers remain. Without alternative markets, more diverse advisory systems, and enabling infrastructure, individual owners are unlikely to adopt radically different practices, regardless of personal interest.

Another limitation was representativity. Certain groups – especially property investors and owners strongly opposed to conservation – were underrepresented. This is partly a result of recruitment difficulties and partly of self-selection. While this does not invalidate the findings, it does suggest that interventions of this type may tend to attract the more reflective or willing participants.

Finally, the lack of continuity must be acknowledged. The workshops were one-off events. For transformative potential to be realised, they would need to be followed up, embedded in local structures, and connected to broader institutional frameworks. As they stand, they represent promising interventions, but fragile ones.

Lessons for future interventions

Despite these limits, several lessons emerge. First, relatively modest interventions can mobilise diverse forest owners and create spaces for dialogue that are otherwise lacking. Second, such interventions can help reveal not just individual attitudes but overarching bottlenecks, particularly the structural dependence on conventional wood markets and

the narrow scope of advisory systems connected to this. Third, linking local perspectives to broader governance discussions, as we did in the stakeholder workshop, can amplify their relevance and highlight potential pathways forward.

For future strategies, a number of elements seem crucial. Identifying and supporting local ambassadors with strong community trust could enhance the legitimacy and impact of interventions. Creating follow-up processes that embed workshops into longer-term dialogue would increase their durability. Finally, interventions need to be connected to policy and market reforms if they are to lead to actual changes in practice. Dialogue alone cannot overcome structural barriers.

The fleeting character of intervention through the eyes of the capercaillie

During a daytime nap I awake to a sound. Footsteps approach. Several humans are in the forest. I freeze, hidden on my branch, gazing out across my display ground. The humans draw nearer, speaking their language among themselves. They do not sneak in silence to conceal themselves, but trample and talk as if nothing in the world could frighten them. I relax slightly, yet remain tense. They do not seem threatening. Not yet.

Now I see them clearly, they have entered my display ground. Three humans, still talking. One points toward the surrounding trees and gestures, the others watch. Their voices are loud. One of them points to the tracks of the great animal in the soil beneath them, to the trace of dragged logs and then to the stump. Another holds a wooden stick in one hand and a white block in the other. The stick moves across the block and the human nods.

They begin to move again, now away from me. I relax, but I do not stir. I have learned to be cautious, at least when the frenzy of spring display does not take hold of my body. The humans are farther off now, soon vanishing beyond sight. Will they return? Only time knows.

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2.7 UNICT Case Study: Italy

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2.7.1 Short presentation of the case

Located in inner eastern Sicily, the Simeto River and its Valley constitute a territory of high ecological, cultural, and historical value currently facing profound socio-ecological challenges. Extending over about 4,200 km² and including the fertile Plain of Catania, the valley is shaped by a dense interaction between natural and human systems. Its riverine corridor – fragmented by dams, weirs, and extensive irrigation infrastructure – reveals how biodiversity loss interlaces with industrial agriculture, energy production, and governance fragmentation. This makes the Simeto Valley an exemplary case for studying how local actors understand and address biodiversity decline through innovative, participatory and transformative practices.

Three interdependent pressures define the crisis: (1) the fragmentation of aquatic ecosystems caused by heavy engineering, which disrupts ecological corridors and habitats; (2) the persistence of intensive monoculture farming reliant on agrochemicals and mechanisation, leading to soil depletion and pollution aggravated by drought and wildfires; (3) and the conversion of farmland into industrial-scale photovoltaic fields enabled by the collapse of citrus monoculture and declining land values. Together, these processes reveal a socio-ecological system dominated by extractive dynamics but also animated by civic mobilisation and experimentation.

The case study, grounded in Participatory Action Research, was conducted by the University of Catania in close collaboration with the Participatory Praesidium of the Simeto River Agreement a long-standing civic network uniting municipalities, communities, and associations across the basin. This partnership ensured inclusiveness, co-design, and the translation of research findings into collective action. The study engaged a diverse set of actors, such as farmers (both conventional and alternative), livestock breeders, water authorities and infrastructure managers, multinational energy companies, civil-society organisations, and local institutions. Their interactions shape the ecological and governance dynamics of the Simeto system.

Research activities developed along three interlinked strands:

1. Re-inhabiting the river through historical and ethnographic analysis of dwelling and agroecological practices.
2. Investigating irrigation governance and farmer cooperation around water infrastructures.
3. Mapping the socio-ecological and spatial impacts of industrial photovoltaic expansion through collaborative GIS.

The process fostered sustained co-learning between researchers and local actors, deepening mutual understanding of biodiversity-related challenges and enabling the co-production of actionable knowledge. Participatory outcomes – such as a permanent exhibition and a two-week territorial festival in 2025 – contributed to public debate and institutional dialogue.

Overall, the Simeto Valley case highlights how place-based alliances, civic participation, and plural knowledge systems can sustain more just, democratic, and biodiversity-oriented forms of territorial governance, aligning with BIOTraCes Theory of Transformative Change.

2.7.2 Evaluation of strategies in action

Building on the socio-ecological system (SES) analysis, which revealed both structural constraints and emerging spaces for collaboration, this section presents the locally tested interventions developed through the partnership between the UNICT research team and the Participatory Praesidium of the Simeto River Agreement. These interventions did not arise from a linear plan but from an adaptive process responding to the valley's ecological and institutional dynamics. They translate the analytical insights of the SES into collective experimentation—through mapping, cultural events, and community energy initiatives—that tested how participatory governance can foster biodiversity stewardship and strengthen local capacities for transformative action.

The strategies and interventions implemented through the participatory action research (PAR) process in the Simeto Valley constitute concrete efforts to address the challenge of biodiversity regeneration. As detailed in other sections, the Valley remains exposed to multiple pressures—intensive agriculture, fragmented water management, the broken relationship with the river, and the unregulated expansion of photovoltaic plants. Within this context, ordinary administration does not include explicit biodiversity policies, nor is there a widespread institutional sensitivity to the issue.

One of the main challenges in planning strategies and interventions with the Societal Partner, the Participatory Praesidium, concerns precisely this gap. While environmental and ecological concerns have long been at the centre of the Presidio's activities, the process of placing biodiversity at the core of policy action and embedding it as a transformative value is still an objective to be achieved. This section critically evaluates ongoing strategies along three dimensions: their transformative change potential, their capacity to address indirect drivers of biodiversity loss, and their ability to replicate enabling factors while mitigating disruptors.

Transformative change potential

The strategies observed in the Simeto Valley reveal a persistent tension between niche innovations and consolidated socio-ecological arrangements. On one side, agroecological practices by local farmer-inhabitants, the Simeto Ecomuseum, and the participatory mapping of energy infrastructures provide tangible foundations for transformative change. These evolving practices, though limited in scale, have begun to modify ecological relations and promote biodiversity regeneration by proposing alternative models to extractive paradigms and territorial marginalisation.

However, their transformative potential remains constrained by structural and political limitations. Agroecological initiatives depend on informal networks and interpersonal collaboration, functioning as flexible socio-ecological infrastructures but lacking long-term stability. The continuity of these efforts is undermined by their marginal position within a territory still dominated by intensive agriculture and soil-exploiting practices.

Similarly, the Simeto Ecomuseum, despite its active presence, faces obstacles due to the absence of formal institutional recognition by the Sicilian Region. This uncertainty limits its capacity to consolidate as a transformative territorial actor within the Presidio's broader organisational framework. The same applies to the energy-mapping initiative, which holds high potential for community empowerment and public awareness but requires stronger institutional adoption and durable diffusion mechanisms to ensure continuity beyond the BIOTraCes project timeframe.

Management of indirect drivers of biodiversity loss

A second evaluative dimension concerns the ability of existing strategies to tackle the indirect drivers of biodiversity loss. In the Simeto context, these drivers are primarily socio-economic and political: dependence on global citrus markets, institutional weaknesses in water governance, external energy pressures, and the absence of integrated territorial planning. Through a guided reflection, participants of FG1[1], [1] identified how biodiversity decline stems from historically embedded cultural, economic, and governance dynamics. A first theme concerns waste management, framed as both a cultural and ecological issue. The widespread practice of burning agricultural and household waste reflects deeply rooted habits and limited environmental responsibility, symbolising a persistent disconnection between care and cultivation. A second issue relates to water inequality. Access to irrigation water is fragmented and often privatised, reinforcing hierarchies among producers. Those able to afford private wells benefit from secure access, while small farmers remain vulnerable to droughts and scarcity, perpetuating a cycle that strengthens monocultural dependency. Monoculture itself—particularly citrus farming—was repeatedly described as both a symbol of identity and a driver of ecological fragility, reliant on pesticides and exposed to market volatility. Participants contrasted this with memories of the traditional "Sicilian Garden," a diversified and resilient model now deemed economically obsolete. As one participant stated: "The classic Sicilian garden is the kind that, for those still lucky enough to have one today, saved you a trip to the greengrocer [...] 'I grow my own eggplants'" (FG1). This quotation reveals how the perspective of self-sufficiency was crucial within the communities, and how it was 'materialized' through the agricultural and food biodiversity of the Sicilian garden. Finally, participants noted a deeper cultural disconnection from rural spaces and from the Simeto River, which has become invisible and inaccessible. Urban expansion, land privatisation, and pollution have reinforced this alienation, transforming the river into an absent presence in everyday life. This process was briefly but effectively described by one of the participants: "*What has been lost is a form of connection between the city and the countryside. My grandfather had small plots of land that allowed him to survive. Today you buy cheap pasta.*" This distancing has transformed the countryside into a functional periphery: *'It becomes a periphery that can be used to dump waste, to do whatever one wants with it'* (FG1). These reflections carried on during FG1 demonstrate that the indirect drivers of biodiversity loss are embedded in cultural practices, social inequalities, and economic dependencies.

Addressing them requires not only ecological restoration but also cultural regeneration, equitable access to resources, and the collective re-embedding of ecosystems as shared heritage. These initiatives are largely part of the societal partner action plan through a variety of tools such as environmental education in school or specific financed projects addressing cultural and ecological issues[2] [DP3] . Key examples include the *LIFE SimetoRES* project, which advances blue-green infrastructures and climate-change adaptation or school-based programmes such as Open Science and Students for Simeto, which integrate civic water monitoring with artistic and environmental education. Additionally, the *Biodistretto del Simeto*, though not a funded project, acts as a strategic network that connects farmers, promotes solidarity-based purchasing, and strengthens community participation around sustainable agriculture. Together, these initiatives foster new alliances among schools, farmers, municipalities, and civic groups, consolidating the societal partner's territorial engagement. However, the possibility to manage the indirect drivers strongly lays on the continuity of the territorial and political action, which at the present moment represents a challenge for the societal partner's future planning.

Replication of enablers and reduction of disruptors

The strategies developed within the Presidio's network seek to replicate enabling factors for biodiversity regeneration and foster transformative change, but this process faces both political and practical challenges. From a political perspective, the main gap lies in the limited centrality of biodiversity in local policy agendas. Biodiversity remains perceived largely as a scientific or environmental issue, rather than a political and social priority. This hinders both the replication of enablers and the mitigation of disruptors, as transformative interventions require explicit political framing and institutional support.[4] From a practical and organisational perspective, the Presidio's dependence on project-based funding mechanisms constrains continuity. Its activities rely on the availability of temporary public or private funding calls at multiple scales, producing structural discontinuity. This fragmentation undermines the consolidation of long-term processes such as social-network building, community empowerment, and participatory control over energy-related land transformations[5] [DP6] . Sustained continuity of engagement is essential to consolidate enablers and reduce disruptors. Without stable resources, even the most promising interventions remain vulnerable to interruption, limiting their capacity to trigger systemic and lasting transformations.

Despite these barriers, the case study does reveal meaningful contributions to collective learning and the emergence of a gradual mindset shift. Over the past two decades, a slow but steady cultural reorientation has been taking place: an increasing segment of the community, in particularly younger generations has begun to view the Simeto Valley and its river not as marginal or expendable spaces, but as territories requiring proactive care and protection. This shift has been nurtured through a plurality of collective practices, including mapping activities, rediscovery of local heritage, and participatory explorations, which have supported shared processes of re-learning and re-imagining the territory. While this transformation remains long-term, non-linear, and frequently challenged by persistent socio-cultural constraints, it nonetheless indicates that seeds of change are already rooted in everyday practices and community engagement.

Concluding remarks

The strategies implemented through participatory governance in the Simeto Valley demonstrate significant efforts to integrate biodiversity into territorial practice, yet they remain constrained by limited institutional recognition, funding discontinuity, and entrenched cultural patterns. Their transformative potential lies in fostering community empowerment, reconnecting culture and ecology, and embedding biodiversity in local governance. To enhance replication and impact, it is essential to strengthen institutional commitment, secure long-term support, and politicise biodiversity as a shared and strategic priority. These steps would consolidate the conditions for transformative change within the Valley's socio-ecological system.

2.7.3 Enablers and disruptors

Processes of biodiversity regeneration in the Simeto Valley do not occur in a vacuum but are embedded within a complex social, economic, and political landscape. Local initiatives seeking to integrate biodiversity as both a value and a practice, and to promote non-anthropocentric uses of the territory, face a combination of enabling factors that support their development and disruptive forces that limit their effectiveness or long-term sustainability.

This section analyses these dynamics along four axes: (1) the relationship between the local agenda and economic-sector interests; (2) the capacity to replicate enablers; (3) the ability to contain disruptors; and (4) the influence of national and European policies on local strategies.

Attunement and mismatch between the local agenda and economic interests

The local agenda for biodiversity regeneration is not yet supported by public institutions or local authorities[7] [DP8] . Instead, it is driven by civic networks, associations, and groups of alternative farmers. This agenda revolves around three main practices:

- Agroecological production, including crop diversification and the valorisation of landscape heritage.
- Cultural and ecological reconnection between the river and local communities, through both material interventions and immaterial practices led by the Simeto Ecomuseum.
- Opposition to agricultural desertification caused by the uncontrolled spread of agro-photovoltaic installations.

Although these practices resonate to some extent with broader European strategies for biodiversity regeneration, such as the Farm to Fork Strategy, they remain only partially aligned, as national and transnational policy frameworks continue to prioritise high-impact sectors. This partial mismatch, further discussed in the *Relation with policies* section, shapes how local initiatives interact with dominant economic trajectories.

These objectives frequently collide with the interests of dominant economic sectors. Industrial citrus farming, though in decline, remains the backbone of local production and continues to favour monocultures oriented toward external markets, with severe impacts on biodiversity. Likewise, large energy corporations promote extensive agro-photovoltaic developments on agricultural land, accelerating ecological and social impoverishment. However, a more nuanced picture emerges when considering smaller, locally rooted actors. Informal farmer networks supported by the Participatory Praesidium are

advancing agroecological diversification and short food supply chains that directly strengthen biodiversity. Similarly, Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) are fostering local energy autonomy, aligning energy transition goals with biodiversity regeneration. Thus, while the biodiversity agenda remains marginal relative to globalised economic trajectories, it is substantively expressed through localised practices of smaller actors whose actions embody transformative potential.

Capacity to replicate enablers

Key enabling factors in the Simeto Valley include formal and informal civic networks, the Simeto Ecomuseum, and the emergence of regenerative agriculture. All are closely interlinked with the activities of the Presidio, which engages directly or indirectly through both permanent structures and project-based initiatives. Despite external and internal limitations, the Presidio strategically uses these enablers as launching platforms for new forms of civic participation and territorial co-management. An illustrative example is the Simeto Biodistrict, a network of small organic farmers coordinated with Presidio's support. The Presidio provides organisational and logistical resources to consolidate the Biodistrict and scale up its scope, thus enhancing the territorial reach of agroecological innovation. Similarly, the Ecomuseum and renewable energy communities act as laboratories of community empowerment, strengthening connections among associations, citizens, and local administrations. However, replicating these enablers remains difficult due to limited economic and temporal resources. Expansion depends largely on building alliances with institutions, universities, and external networks capable of providing visibility, funding, and recognition. Without such alliances, the sustainability and scaling-up of enablers remain uncertain.

Capacity to address disruptors

Several disruptive factors hinder the development of regenerative biodiversity strategies: the ecological crisis, farmland abandonment, disconnection from the river, increasing infrastructural control over water and agriculture, the pressure of external energy investors, and the weakness of local institutions. These long-term structural forces render the socio-ecological system fragile and constrain transformative interventions. The Presidio's capacity to counter these disruptors is fragmented. This results from limited financial and human resources, the absence of institutional interlocutors, and the project-based funding model on which it relies. Without stable financial continuity or long-term planning tools, the Presidio struggles to engage disruptors structurally, limiting its ability to pursue durable transformative change.

Relation with policies

A major challenge for the Presidio lies in navigating the European policy framework for biodiversity and ecological transition. This issue was explored during FG2 of 15th March 2025, revealing key tensions between local visions and institutional instruments. The 2015 Simeto River flood illustrates these tensions. The abrupt opening of the Ancipa dam, without prior warning, caused severe damage to local farmers and herders. The Presidio's response—organising a public assembly with farmers, ENEL, and the University of Catania—led to the idea of submitting a LIFE Programme proposal for participatory flood-management solutions. Although the project was reformulated after rejection, shifting its focus toward urban drainage infrastructure, the case revealed the disconnect between the transformative potential of EU programmes and their practical local implementation. A second example is the *Patto di Fiume Simeto* (Simeto River Agreement), inspired by the EU Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC) and the UN

2030 Agenda. The Agreement sought to politicise and embed biodiversity governance through deliberative democracy and local knowledge. It empowered the Presidio to participate directly in the Assembly and Executive Commission, making local communities' constituent actors in territorial policy. However, the absence of regional legislation on participation limited this innovation: the Presidio's representation remained minoritarian, and the intended Laboratory—a space for autonomous operation—never materialised. Despite its recognition as an institutional innovation, the Simeto River Agreement (Patto di Fiume Simeto) remains a fragile experiment, constrained by the lack of enabling legal and financial frameworks. These cases highlight the gap between European directives and local implementation, underscoring the need for institutional structures capable of embedding participatory and bottom-up innovations within long-term governance.

Concluding remarks

The analysis of enablers and disruptors confirms that biodiversity regeneration in the Simeto Valley is a deeply political and contested process. Enablers—rooted in bottom-up networks, agroecological practices, and participatory governance—illustrate pathways of transformative change. Disruptors, however, remain largely structural, driven by global markets, institutional inertia, and concentrated power. Strengthening alliances, ensuring policy coherence, and embedding community-led governance within formal institutional frameworks are essential to consolidating biodiversity as a shared territorial value and advancing the BIOTraCes vision of empowered and plural socio-ecological transformation.

2.7.4 Failed and successful practices

Successful practices[9]

In contrast, several successful or promising practices have emerged, each contributing to biodiversity regeneration and participatory socio-ecological transformation through different intervention domains. The first domain concerns the valorisation of cultural and ecological heritage. The establishment of the Simeto Ecomuseum in 2019 exemplifies how the recovery of collective memory—both material and immaterial—can be intertwined with the revitalisation of local economies and ecosystem care. Through participatory action research conducted by the BIOTraCes UNICT team, traditional techniques such as fishing and livestock raising have been reinterpreted as components of the valley's historical socio-ecological system, reframing biodiversity as a social and cultural relation rather than a purely biological indicator.[10] [DP11] Fieldwork and archival research revealed, in particular, how fishing, today practised only as a recreational activity, with no economic or subsistence purpose, historically constituted a dense relational practice through which local communities engaged with the river, learned its flows, and navigated its seasonal rhythms. River fishing also created a tangible link between the fluvial area and nearby urban centres, where dedicated markets existed specifically for river fish. The gradual disappearance of this practice marks a widening distance between communities and the river, signalling not only cultural loss but also ecological degradation, as fishing has ceased largely due to the declining health of the waters. Similarly, livestock breeding once embodied a continuous relational interplay between humans, animals, and the riverine landscape: herders moved daily in search of water sources, possessed deep knowledge of spontaneous plant

species, and lived for extended periods along the riverbanks in lightweight, temporary shelters built from *Arundo donax*, the typical river cane. These practices, therefore, reveal how biodiversity was historically embedded in everyday life, shaping social worlds as much as ecological ones. Building on this renewed understanding of the valley's socio-ecological past, the collaboration between UNICT researchers and the Ecomuseum has generated new spaces for public engagement and knowledge transmission.

This collaboration culminated in a permanent exhibition inaugurated in May 2025 at the Presidio headquarters in Paternò, presenting archival and ethnographic materials that illustrate human–non-human relationships along the Simeto River since the nineteenth century. The second domain concerns alternative agriculture. New farmers inspired by permaculture and agroecology are pioneering low-cost, small-scale innovations that counteract monocultural dependency. By creating micro-wetlands, reinstating open soil irrigation channels based on the traditional *saje* system, and eliminating pesticide use, these practices regenerate soil health and enhance biodiversity. The cultivation of oranges, olives, and nitrogen-fixing species reactivates the Sicilian Garden model, reconnecting contemporary agriculture to traditional ecological knowledge. Although currently limited in scale, these initiatives demonstrate the transformative potential of relational networks that link farming, biodiversity, and community life, reconstituting the Valley's socio-ecological fabric. The third domain involves scalable bottom-up innovations in the renewable energy sector. Since 2023, three Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) have been established, promoting the democratisation of energy governance through inclusive participation of citizens, associations, enterprises, and institutions. Parallel to this, the participatory mapping of agro-photovoltaic infrastructures, developed within BIOTraCes[12] [SL13], enables collective analysis of how energy projects reshape the Valley's landscapes and livelihoods.

Grassroots organisations and individual participants collaborated in developing a critical and collaborative map of PV infrastructures and their interactions with biodiversity and cultural and archaeological heritage. Between September 2024 and January 2025, several informal meetings and two structured workshops were held to design this mapping process. Participants decided collectively to integrate their local ecological and territorial knowledge into a georeferenced dataset. From January 2025 onwards, multiple rounds of collaborative GIS-based surveys were conducted in the municipalities of Troina and Belpasso, in cooperation with Legambiente Ancipa and Sciarra Viva. These activities exemplified the BIOTraCes principle of embedding participatory governance in research practice, transforming mapping into a tool for community empowerment and evidence-based advocacy.

This process generates shared knowledge and advocacy tools, addressing the absence of participatory mechanisms and weak institutional oversight in land-use planning. By revealing patterns of land expropriation, agricultural crisis, and ecological degradation, the initiative reinforces territorial awareness and strengthens community agency in negotiating the Valley's energy transition. Together, these bottom-up innovations demonstrate how participatory governance can bridge energy, ecology, and democracy, restoring public engagement in environmental decision-making while aligning energy transition goals with biodiversity conservation and local well-being.

Failed practices[14]

Within the Simeto Valley socio-ecological system, several failed practices illustrate the challenges of achieving durable transformative change and embedding participatory governance in biodiversity strategies. A first case concerns the Simeto Ecomuseum[15]

[DP16] , which, despite its strong potential as an institutional and cultural innovator, faces internal challenges in communication and coordination. The Ecomuseum’s structure includes a rich territorial network of antennas—local referents, experts, and nodal points across multiple municipalities—but its communication channels remain fragmented. This weakness is reflected in the irregular frequency and uneven participation in its itineraries and initiatives.

At the same time, the Ecomuseum regularly activates collective processes, such as community mapping, educational workshops, and co-designed territorial itineraries that engage residents in interpreting landscapes, sharing ecological knowledge, and planning forms of river and land stewardship. These practices link cultural heritage with biodiversity restoration by fostering shared learning and reinforcing community responsibility toward the Simeto Valley. Ecomuseum activities prove most successful when they are co-organised through participatory and collective processes[17] [DP18] [2], particularly in collaboration with other local organisations, as demonstrated by the *Facciamo la Valle! Festival* organized as part of the BIOTraCes intervention in late May-early June 2015. By contrast, initiatives promoted autonomously tend to achieve limited outreach and visibility. While these outcomes do not signify failure in absolute terms, they highlight the need to refine internal structures, strengthen community engagement, and consolidate the Ecomuseum’s autonomy and recognition as a territorial actor. A second case of partial failure relates to participatory action research (PAR) with agroecologically inspired farmers. These farmer-inhabitants have developed strong internal bonds, continuously exchanging machinery, skills, and techniques to regenerate land and biodiversity. However, the high cohesion within this network also risks reinforcing a mechanism of self-isolation that separates “the good ones” — that is, young, often educated people practicing agroecology — from “the bad ones,” meaning conventional farmers, who are older and generally belong to more socially vulnerable groups.[19] [20] . As a result, the engagement with “conventional” farmers—those practising intensive or chemical-dependent agriculture—remains limited. Techniques such as permaculture and syntropic cultivation are still perceived as niche, reducing opportunities for cross-learning and pluralisation of knowledge. The absence of sustained bridges between conventional and alternative farmers has thus far prevented wider transformative diffusion across the agricultural system. A third failed practice emerged in the field of participatory mapping, the initiative aimed to engage citizens, associations, and municipalities in collectively mapping the spread of photovoltaic infrastructures and their impacts on the territory. While civic participation was strong, municipal administrations showed limited involvement, rarely assuming ownership of the process. Given that municipalities are directly responsible for authorising photovoltaic and agrivoltaics installations, their absence represents a critical gap. This limited institutional participation weakens the potential for community empowerment and reveals the difficulty of embedding participatory processes within local governance structures.

Concluding remarks

The analysis of failed and successful practices in the Simeto Valley underscores both the fragility and potential of transformative socio-ecological change. Failures highlight the limits of institutional engagement, internal communication, and cross-sectoral collaboration, while successes demonstrate the empowering role of participatory processes, collective learning, and locally grounded innovation. When supported by sustained institutional recognition and adequate resources, these practices can consolidate into replicable enablers of biodiversity regeneration and participatory

governance, advancing the BIOTraCes vision of an embedded, plural, and democratic socio-ecological transformation.

2.7.5 Co-learning

The co-learning experience developed in the Simeto Valley case study represents a central component of the participatory action research (PAR) process promoted by the University of Catania within the BIOTraCes project. This process unfolded through a plurality of moments — partly connected to fieldwork and focus group activities and partly embedded in the collective design and implementation of the *Facciamo la Valle! Festival*.

Throughout the project, co-learning functioned both as a methodological framework and an epistemological horizon grounded in dialogical exchange between scientific, experiential, and community-based knowledge systems. It was conceived not as a consultative exercise but as a transformative process of knowledge co-production, sustained by negotiation of perspectives, collective reflexivity, and shared experimentation in socio-ecological regeneration.

Co-learning process on indirect drivers of biodiversity loss

Co-learning sessions among BIOTraCes research partners facilitated the creation of a shared vocabulary and interpretive framework around the indirect drivers of biodiversity loss. Internal discussions highlighted that these drivers are not purely ecological, but deeply rooted in institutional, cultural, and economic structures that perpetuate extractive territorial models.

In the Simeto River case study, collective reflection revealed how territorial marginalisation, short-term project-based funding, and the absence of institutional coordination weaken connections between public policy, local knowledge, and environmental regeneration. At the same time, the dialogue identified key enablers for transformative change: building trust-based spaces, reactivating ecological memory, and creating collective knowledge devices such as participatory mapping, environmental archives, and place-based artistic practices.

The research team adopted a comparative approach, analysing systemic configurations that either facilitate or constrain biodiversity regeneration. In the Simeto Valley, this involved exploring the river's dual role as an ecological and symbolic infrastructure, and as a contested space between extractive logics (agro-industrial, energy, infrastructural) and bottom-up practices of territorial care. This process fostered collective learning about the interrelations among governance, institutions, and socio-ecological transformation, laying the groundwork for sustained and reflexive co-learning.

Co-learning processes with the Societal Partner

During FG1 and FG2 (see footnote on the section "Management of indirect drivers of biodiversity loss") [21] [DP22], researchers and members of the Participatory Praesidium of the Simeto River Agreement jointly analysed the tensions among social innovation, institutional dynamics, and biodiversity conservation strategies. These encounters produced critical co-learning insights that informed the design of local action plans. The FG1 explored agroecological practices and the relationship between community and rural territory, focusing on biodiversity loss and regeneration in the Simeto Valley. Testimonies emphasised the affective and historical memory tied to the river and traditional agriculture, seen as foundations of local identity and resources for socio-

ecological renewal. Narratives recalled a once-fertile valley where water, land, and biodiversity formed a shared equilibrium, while discussions addressed how economic and political transformations disrupted this balance through intensive agriculture and loss of community autonomy.

Despite these challenges, the group also identified emerging alternative visions, such as the Mediterranean garden model — a non-intensive, poly-cultural paradigm integrating ecological, cultural, and relational dimensions. Agroecological practices and environmental education projects were recognised as niche innovations, fostering collective learning and testing new ways of inhabiting the Valley alongside more-than-human species. The session thus operated as a reflective space to examine indirect drivers of biodiversity loss — economic marginalisation, institutional weakness, and socio-cultural disconnection — while advancing a transformative understanding of community–environment relations.

FG2[23] addressed the interaction between multi-scalar environmental policies (regional, national, and European) and their local implementation in the Simeto context. It examined how the Participatory Praesidium engages with regulatory frameworks and public institutions to pursue sustainability, biodiversity protection, and environmental justice. Participants highlighted a persistent gap between supranational policy frameworks and local operational capacity. Although the Presidio aligns closely with EU Water and Habitat Directives, these frameworks often fail to translate into effective local instruments due to fragmented governance and lack of long-term strategy.

Concrete examples — such as the LIFE Simeto RES project — illustrated both the potential and limits of these collaborations: bureaucratic delays, weak institutional coordination, and insufficient political continuity hindered implementation. The discussion revealed a dual dynamic: strong conceptual alignment with EU biodiversity goals but limited capacity for local translation. This recognition prompted a collective reflection on how to develop adaptive, cross-sectoral governance integrating local knowledge with institutional mechanisms.

Methodologically, the focus group functioned as a strategic dialogue between research and society. Researchers acted as mediators and facilitators, comparing the Simeto River case study with other European contexts. This comparative perspective illuminated institutional lock-ins—rigid procedures, hierarchical knowledge structures, and the separation of environmental and social policies—as major indirect drivers of biodiversity loss. Overall, the dialogue reinforced shared understanding of how policy frameworks can both reproduce and transform ecological crises, directing future collaboration toward multi-level governance and co-designed biodiversity strategies.

Further co-learning and exchange with the Societal Partner

The organisation of the *Facciamo la Valle! Festival* [24] represented a pivotal stage in the co-learning process, integrating research, dissemination, and collective experimentation. Initiated in early 2025 with Participatory Praesidium of the Simeto River Agreement (Presidio Partecipativo), the festival acted as a distributed laboratory of situated learning, where BIOTraCes findings were reinterpreted through local memory and social practice.

Preparation for the festival involved weekly meetings, co-design workshops, and collective reflection sessions with researchers, local actors, artists, and citizens. These interactions explored connections between environmental crises, biodiversity loss, river memory, and civic activism.[25] As a result, a very rich program was built. The "*Facciamo la Valle!*" Festival took place from **26 May to 8 June 2025** and was co-organized with the societal

partner Presidio, in collaboration with local associations and under the patronage of the Municipality of Paternò. The festival main strands of activity were:

- ✓ An ethnographic exhibition featuring fieldwork materials and documents from the local archive.
- ✓ A series of artistic and musical performances.
- ✓ The implementation of ecomuseum itineraries.
- ✓ Seminars and workshops.

More specifically, the detailed programme of activities unfolded as follows:

- ❖ **May 26 - Inauguration of the ethnographic exhibition “Re-stitching the memory”** | Co-organized by the research team and the societal partner the inauguration of the ethnographic exhibition “*Re-stitching the Memory*”. Curated by Accademia Abadir and hosted at the former municipal slaughterhouse of Paternò, the exhibition presented archival materials, maps, and video-interviews documenting the socio-ecological transformations of the Simeto Valley. Drawing on the longstanding process developed by the Presidium, the exhibition highlighted community memory, historical water governance, traditional and alternative agricultural practices, and the collective struggle for environmental justice in the valley.
- ❖ **May 27 and May 30 - School visits to the exhibition** | Organized by the societal partner. These visits reflect the strong educational dimension of the Ecomuseum, which has engaged more than a thousand students in its activities and has promoted community mapping, heritage education, and intergenerational learning across the valley. During these days, several classes participated in activities inspired by projects such as “*La Valle del Simeto in una Cartolina*” further reinforcing the festival’s pedagogical role.
- ❖ **May 30 - Public presentation of the exhibition and a talk on ecomuseology practices with leading experts and local representatives** | Co-organized by the research team and the societal partner. This day hosted the public presentation of the new Ecomuseum of Simeto visual identity, the result of a long community co-design process (“*Forme del Simeto*”) involving schools, citizens, and local associations. The event aligned with the ecomuseum’s trajectory as a civic, cultural, and territorial infrastructure, rooted in twenty years of community mobilization, participatory mapping, and shared planning.
Workshops and discussions enriched the day, situating the exhibition within broader reflections on landscape, justice, and community-based museology.
- ❖ **May 31 - Evening artistic performance** | Organized by the societal partner the performance was part of the festival’s artistic program, which also featured poetic actions and theatre workshops curated by artists such as Alessandra Pescetta, Giovanni Calcagno and the Batarnù company, animating public spaces through collective storytelling and ecological sensibility.

- ❖ **June 1 - Ecomuseum “Water Itinerary”** | Organized by the societal partner these itinerary forms one of the most consolidated routes of the Simeto Ecomuseum, developed through years of community mapping, school projects, and field explorations. The walk retraced key locations of the valley’s historical and contemporary water system, saje, gebbie, irrigation networks, and river crossings, reflecting the ecomuseum’s long-term work on water governance, heritage, and collective territorial knowledge. The itinerary builds on previous educational and participatory activities, reinforcing the waterway as a cultural, ecological, and community anchor of the valley.

- ❖ **June 3 - Workshop with farmers: “Regenerating and Inhabiting the Valley: Techniques and Experiences for a Thriving Territory”** | Held in Contrada Nicolò, Paternò (CT), at *Munnu Farm* and co-organized with: Jennifer Harumi Tanaka, farmer and researcher based in the Simeto Valley and Filip Micoletti (Vallone delle Pezze, RG), educator and expert in permaculture and syntropic agriculture. This workshop, hosted in the heart of the Simeto Valley, explored regenerative agricultural practices as a pathway to healing and revitalising both land and community. Led by Filip Micoletti the session offered both theoretical insights and hands-on experience. Together, we delved into the biodiversity and evolution of ecosystems, the social lives of plants, and the co-evolutionary processes between plants and animals. A central moment of the day was the practical session dedicated to sowing a MUVUCA—a diverse mix of seeds designed to regenerate soil and foster ecosystem resilience. Through this activity, participants gained a deeper understanding of what makes an agricultural system truly sustainable and alive over time. More than just a learning opportunity, the workshop marked an important step toward transformation: envisioning and practicing an agriculture that heals, regenerates, and creates abundance in synergy with nature. Discussions focused on micro-regenerative practices rooted in syntropic principles, tailored to the Simeto Valley’s unique ecological, historical, and cultural context—particularly in response to the growing challenges of climate change. The workshop also served as a moment of connection, aiming to strengthen networks of solidarity among farmers, foster collaboration with experts in regenerative techniques, and promote the sharing and amplification of local knowledge in support of biodiversity.

- ❖ **June 4 (morning) - Walking deep-mapping workshop “Inside the ‘saje’. Exploring Simeto water infrastructure”** | Organized by the research team. The activity took place in *Contrada Buglio* (Santa Maria di Licodia) and was structured in two main phases.

The first phase consisted of a collective exploration, conducted in three small groups, across the area. The walk began at the *Fontana del Cherubino* and at the first springs emerging from beneath the lava mantle, waters that not only feed the Simeto River but also sustain agriculture and livestock in the surrounding area. From these springs, participants followed three parallel routes that traced the local water infrastructures, focusing particularly on the network of *saje* and their intersections with *gebbie* and other distribution systems used for irrigation management. During the walk, participants

collected personal observations, photographs, audio recordings, and objects intended for use in the subsequent workshop session.

The second phase took place nearby and involved a collective sharing of experiences. Participants discussed what they had observed and perceived during the walk, reflecting on how the irrigation infrastructure operates, what kinds of social and ecological relationships it generates, and how these systems shape the landscape. Through this exchange, the group examined the role of water and the river in the valley's agricultural practices, highlighting the deep interconnections between hydrological infrastructures, land use, and everyday forms of territorial life.

❖ **June 4 (afternoon) - Conference: "Interrupted Rivers: Infrastructure, Water Control, and the Continuity of Life"** | Held at *Ex Macello* in Paternò, with researchers and activists working on key BIOTraCes research themes and organized by the research team and the societal partner. The event aimed to explore the complex socio-ecological relationships between river systems and local communities. In particular, it addressed the threats posed by infrastructural developments to biodiversity and life along rivers, while critically examining existing governance models for river management—with a focus on the *Simeto River*.

Francesco Visentin, Associate Professor at the University of Udine, opened the discussion by highlighting how "waterscapes" are shaped by the ongoing accumulation of human interventions—both material and symbolic. His talk, bridging theory and practice, stressed the need for a hydrocentric perspective to reframe rivers not as infrastructures or utilities, but as vital elements of ecosystems and landscapes.

Giuliano Trentini, spokesperson for the Italian Centre for River Restoration (CIRF), focused on the biodiversity crisis and the role of river restoration in risk mitigation and sustainable management. He argued that restoring rivers is not only a technical challenge, but also a cultural and ecological one—calling for a rethinking of the human–river relationship. The static, utilitarian approach to rivers developed in the 20th century is no longer adequate; restoring vitality requires allowing rivers to move and flow—both longitudinally, by removing barriers, and laterally, by permitting natural meandering and expansion. Paolo Gruppuso, researcher at the Rachel Carson Center (Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich), offered a critical reflection on the disciplining of Sicily's most important river through infrastructure and embankments, and how this process has disrupted socio-ecological relations. Advocating for a new "river literacy," he called for a break with dominant narratives of engineered "progress," and a renewed attention to once-central river-based practices such as fishing and herding. These, he argued, could play a key role in reviving the ecological and relational fabric of the Simeto Valley.

The debate continued with a contribution from Dr. Umberto Troja, director of the Simeto River Nature Reserve (RNO Oasi del Simeto), who highlighted the environmental pressures facing the reserve—from industrial development and illegal construction to the challenges of bird conservation and fish migration. He emphasized ongoing efforts to dismantle artificial barriers that prevent the natural movement of aquatic fauna.

Roberto De Pietro (engineer and independent researcher) and Antonino Duchi (biologist and independent researcher) presented a detailed case study of the Passo Martino weir, located within the Simeto River Nature Reserve. Built in the 1980s to serve the nearby industrial zone—but never put into operation—the structure interrupts the river's ecological continuity just 7 kilometres from its mouth, significantly harming aquatic life in an already highly modified watercourse. Drawing from both theoretical insights and case studies at national and international levels, the event made a strong call for concrete action: in particular, the dismantling of the Passo Martino weir to restore the Simeto's ecological connectivity from its mouth to Ponte Barca (Paternò). This aligns with the European Union's goal of restoring at least 25,000 kilometres of free-flowing rivers across Europe by 2030.

- ❖ **June 5 (morning) - Conference: "Energy and Community: Transformations, Conflicts, and Perspectives for the Territory and its People"** | Co-organized with local associations, experts, community members and the project Energy Commons. During the conference the researchers present also a first draft of the critical map of energy infrastructures.

- ❖ **June 5 (afternoon) - Walking workshop in Belpasso: "Energy and Future Perspectives"** | Organized with a local association the workshop served as a space for discussion, collective reasoning, and debate on renewable energy production and its relationship with territory and local communities. Starting from the case of the Simeto Valley—which simultaneously hosts some of Italy's largest photovoltaic plants and several Renewable Energy Communities—the conversation widened to include other Italian contexts. Through laboratory-style activities, scholars active in the national debate, local activists, and representatives of municipal institutions examined the dynamics of the energy transition, focusing on everyday practices, ecosystem exploitation, cooperation, and conflict within places of energy production. The workshop brought into dialogue two contrasting models: on the one hand, large industrial-scale renewable installations, where territories often find themselves caught between energy extraction and the marginalisation of local communities; on the other, Renewable Energy Communities, through which territories can instead become laboratories of virtuous cycles linking self-production, democratic planning, and community-building. Its overarching aim was to identify research directions and programmatic priorities capable of fostering meaningful cooperation among local communities, their organisations, institutions, and academia.

- ❖ **June 7 - Ecomuseum multispecies itinerary: "Lives Along the River: Stories of Eels, Concrete, and Peaches on the Simeto"** | Organized by the research team this itinerary invited participants to reflect on life in and around the Simeto River through two symbolic locations in the valley. The first stop was the Santa Domenica intake, a site along the mid-course of the river where we explored the processes of exploitation and violence the Simeto had endured, driven by a development model that separated humans from nature and viewed the river merely as a resource to be used. At Santa Domenica, we engaged in a conversation with environmental conservation experts who helped us understand what it meant to experience the Simeto from the perspective of non-human life, such as fish and eels—species increasingly threatened by human

management of the river. From Santa Domenica, we moved toward the Bronte area, where we met Samantha Pieraccini. Samantha managed a pistachio grove and a piece of family land where she cultivated fruit trees and vegetable gardens along the riverbank. She shared her experience of farming in the Simeto Valley in the context of a changing climate, discussing her crop choices and adaptation strategies. Together, we reflected on the beauty and challenges of living and farming next to a river that was constantly shifting and transforming.

- ❖ **June 7 (Evening) - Artistic performances** | Organized by the societal partner.
- ❖ **June 8 (Morning) – Historical itinerary** | Organized by the societal partner and led by SiciliaAntica (section Paternò). This itinerary is part of the routes designed by the Simeto Ecomuseum and co-constructed with the local community, in close collaboration with the association SiciliaAntica. Traversing the historical hill of Paternò, the itinerary not only showcases the area's architectural and artistic heritage but also reveals a medieval fabric that has persisted into the present. Along the route, participants encountered stories and historical land uses, including the former neighbourhood that once hosted the river-fish market and housed the families of river fishers, a profession now extinct. The itinerary further highlighted the deep relationship between the city, its inhabitants, and the Simeto River, emerging through the historical layers of churches, civic spaces, and the Norman tower overlooking both the river and the valley.

Re-stitching the Memory

A central element was the exhibition at the former Ex Macello of Paternò, jointly curated by the Presidio, the CNR[3], and other local partners. Combining archival materials, oral histories, and artistic productions, the exhibition created a shared environmental history of the Valley and a dialogic space across generations and knowledge systems.

Re-stitching the Memory ("Ricuciamo la Memoria"), symbolised ecological and social reconnection. Through the collective creation of a large map of the Simeto River, sewn together from archival fragments and community contributions, participants performed an act of transgenerational and more-than-human learning. This participatory artwork made visible the lost interconnections between urban and rural spaces and between human and non-human communities, reframing the territory as a subject of knowledge rather than an object of exploitation.

Conferences, workshops and more

The thematic days dedicated to BIOTraCes research within the festival expanded co-learning opportunities through all the activities mentioned. These events fostered reciprocal learning between scientific knowledge and everyday practices, where researchers improved their in-depth understanding of the context thanks to local actors, and communities acquired analytical tools for collective action. The festival also highlighted the aesthetic and affective dimensions of co-learning, demonstrating that knowledge emerges not only through analysis but also through sensory, artistic, and performative experiences.

Concluding remarks

The co-learning process in the Simeto Valley redefined the role of research in fostering inclusive biodiversity governance. By revealing indirect drivers of biodiversity loss—from institutional fragmentation to cultural disconnection—while activating practices of socio-ecological reconnection, it bridged scientific and local knowledge in a shared learning process. These activities have generated collective reflexivity, empowered the Societal Partner, and provided a methodological model for future BIOTraCes interventions: one based on reciprocity, care, and the reactivation of ecological and cultural memory as drivers of transformative change.

2.7.6 Testing of interventions

The process of testing actions and intervention plans within the Simeto Valley case study represents both a collective learning pathway and a space for critical reflection, involving the research partners and the Societal Partner in a deeply integrated manner. This phase goes beyond evaluating the operational effectiveness of actions: it constitutes a moment of transformative co-evaluation, where field experimentation, participatory monitoring, and the joint restitution of results converge to construct new forms of territorial governance for biodiversity.

Throughout the research, the Societal Partner oriented much of its activity toward identifying and addressing the root causes of biodiversity loss, adopting a systemic perspective that links ecological, social, and institutional dimensions. Among the most significant strategies emerging from this process is the work on Renewable Energy Communities (RECs), conceived as a response to the threats posed by the uncontrolled expansion of industrial-scale agro-photovoltaic plants. These infrastructures—often imposed externally and embedded in extractive energy and land-use logics—pose major risks to biodiversity by transforming rural landscapes and undermining the ecological multifunctionality of soils.

A grassroots mobilisation against industrial-scale agro-photovoltaic plants has stimulated community-based discussion and action groups, which have found in the research team key allies both cognitively and technically. Through shared learning sessions and the creation of analytical tools—such as the participatory mapping of agro-photovoltaic plants—these groups have opened new arenas of debate and critical reflection on the Valley's future. The mapping initiative, one of the most significant pilot actions of the testing process, synthesises the co-production of knowledge between researchers and communities. It will be returned to the Societal Partner and citizens as an operational tool to counter unsustainable energy projects and as a basis for alternative development scenarios grounded in biodiversity and environmental justice.

In parallel, the RECs promoted through a bottom-up, participatory approach by the Societal Partner, in collaboration with citizens, small producers, and researchers, have emerged as socio-technical devices for ecological and social justice. They aim to build an alternative model of energy governance based on inclusion, equity, and participation. The co-design process of the RECs has been transformative not only in its material outcomes—renewable energy generation, emissions reduction, and local autonomy—but also in its pedagogical and community-building dimensions. It has diffused new knowledge, reinforced place-based belonging, and promoted a vision of the territory as a common good.

The testing of actions revealed that the Societal Partner adopts a dual and complementary strategy in confronting institutional barriers and governance lock-ins hindering ecological transition. On one hand, it acts in a reformist and proactive manner through continuous dialogue with local and regional administrations, seeking to establish

collaborative grounds for experimentation. On the other hand, it cultivates resistance and cognitive autonomy, disseminating knowledge and creating public spaces for debate and participatory governance.

Although institutional dialogue remains limited by administrative fragmentation, low deliberative capacity, and a sectoral political culture, it nonetheless operates as a field of transformative learning. Even small-scale initiatives—such as territorial laboratories, environmental education programmes, and rural regeneration projects—help to “stretch” institutional limits, demonstrating the feasibility of grounded alternatives. This incremental approach to transformation, based on the social prototyping of good practices, has been recognised by researchers as a key enabler for overcoming structural and cultural constraints that impede systemic change.

Concurrently, a reflexive civic component of action has consolidated, oriented toward the production of territorial knowledge as transformative power. Through environmental data collection, documentation of landscape transformations, and the valorisation of collective memories related to the Simeto River, the Societal Partner operates at the symbolic and cultural levels, rebuilding the relationship between community and environment. The Simeto Ecomuseum plays an emblematic role in this process: more than a cultural institution, it functions as a social infrastructure for learning and regeneration, translating principles of sustainability, inclusion, and care for the commons into everyday practices. The testing phase has shown that the Societal Partner’s actions go beyond responding to environmental emergencies—they actively redefine governance logics[26] [DP27] and territorial narratives. Through advocacy, participatory research, and artistic and cultural practices, the alliance between community and research has influenced the representation of the Simeto Valley, challenging its image as a marginal space and reframing it as a laboratory of sustainability and social innovation.

The *Facciamo la Valle! Festival* and its related exhibition represented a key moment of symbolic transformation. Through installations, debates, and workshops, the festival staged the historical memory of the river and its connections to everyday life, reinforcing a collective awareness of the Simeto as a living socio-ecological system to be regenerated rather than a neglected margin. In this sense, the festival acted as an extended co-learning device, where research, art, and citizenship intertwined languages and visions, cultivating a new ecology of knowledge and participation.

Finally, the testing phase demonstrated that the relationship between researchers and the Societal Partner constitutes a practice of transformation in itself. The ongoing dialogue between methodological frameworks, local knowledge, and analytical tools has fostered co-production of knowledge, enhancing collective capacities for territorial interpretation and intervention. Activities such as mapping agro-photovoltaic installations, analysing water infrastructures and agricultural practices, and documenting rural landscape evolution illustrate how research–society collaboration generates tangible outcomes—benefiting both scientific inquiry and local governance.

Shared knowledge thus becomes a civic infrastructure, capable of supporting informed and inclusive decision-making. Through continuous dialogue, researchers and the Societal Partner not only produce data and tools but also contribute to building a shared horizon of meaning for the Simeto Valley—one in which biodiversity, socioecological justice, and ecological innovation are recognised as inseparable dimensions of transformative change.

Concluding remarks

The testing of interventions in the Simeto Valley exemplifies the BIOTraCes approach to embedding transformative change through participatory governance. By linking

community initiatives, research experimentation, and institutional dialogue, this phase demonstrated how co-production of knowledge can reconfigure power relations and strengthen local agency. The outcomes—spanning from energy communities to participatory mapping—show that transformation emerges incrementally, through collective learning, shared responsibility, and the integration of biodiversity values into daily territorial practices. The experience positions the Simeto Valley as a living laboratory for just and plural socio-ecological transitions.

2.7.7 Discussion

The participatory strategies and interventions developed in the Simeto Valley constitute a living laboratory of socio-ecological transformation, where biodiversity regeneration is pursued through collective governance and situated experimentation. Across diverse initiatives—agroecological practices, the establishment of an Ecomuseum, renewable energy communities, and participatory mapping—their shared significance lies in the attempt to politicise biodiversity, embedding it within social relations, local identities, and institutional processes. The Societal Partner and its civic networks have gradually transformed the Valley’s marginal condition into a site of reflexive innovation, linking ecological recovery with cultural heritage, energy democracy, and social solidarity. In this context, biodiversity emerges not as an abstract ecological metric but as a relational achievement: the outcome of co-produced knowledge, contested meanings, and everyday practices of care that reconfigure the relationships between communities, ecosystems, and governance structures.

A central insight concerns the transformative potential of these local practices. Initiatives such as agroecology, the Simeto Ecomuseum, and community mapping cultivate alternative socio-ecological imaginaries that challenge extractive paradigms.

Agroecological farmers, for example, enact micro-transformations that reintroduce crop diversity, regenerate soils, and revalue traditional ecological knowledge. The Simeto Ecomuseum operates as a socio-cultural infrastructure that turns collective memory into an instrument of regeneration, framing biodiversity as the interplay between ecological integrity and social relations. These initiatives embody plural ways of valuing and inhabiting nature, opening new spaces for empowerment and experimentation. Yet, their transformative reach remains constrained by the absence of institutional recognition, project-based funding logics, and the dominance of monocultural economies. Despite these constraints, they function as “niches of transformation,” demonstrating how place-based practices can prefigure more just and sustainable governance arrangements.

When viewed through the lens of indirect drivers of biodiversity loss, the Simeto Valley case underscores that ecological degradation is inseparable from socio-economic inequality, institutional fragmentation, and cultural detachment from the territory. Fieldwork and focus groups revealed that destructive practices—waste burning, monocultures, overexploitation of water—stem not only from ignorance but from long-standing political and cultural disconnections. Biodiversity loss, therefore, reflects the erosion of the social and symbolic bonds that once linked communities to their environment. In this sense, the Presidio’s work to restore an ecological pact between people and nature acquires a deeply political meaning. Through participatory processes, educational initiatives, and particularly the collective mapping of energy infrastructures, the Societal Partner reframes the territory as a shared common. These activities nurture

civic responsibility and encourage new understandings of nature as a co-actor within the Valley's socio-ecological system.

The analysis of enablers and disruptors further clarifies the dynamics of change. Enabling factors—such as trust-based networks, civic cooperation, and the revival of ecological memory—have emerged from the long-term engagement fostered by the Presidio. These enable the diffusion of regenerative practices, the consolidation of social alliances, and the co-production of situated knowledge. Disruptive factors, however, remain formidable: globalised agri-food markets, external energy investors, weak institutional capacity, and the volatility of project-based financing. The Societal Partner's ability to sustain enabling conditions in such a context is in itself an act of resilience. By mobilising social capital and forging partnerships with universities, municipalities, and grassroots organisations, the Presidio demonstrates that transformative agency can thrive even under systemic precarity. This empowering dimension—grounded in participation and mutual learning—represents a distinctive contribution to the BIOTraCes approach.

The attunement or mismatch between the Valley's biodiversity agenda and the trajectories of major economic sectors exposes both structural tension and opportunity. Industrial citrus farming and the uncontrolled expansion of agro-photovoltaic installations perpetuate ecological simplification and territorial inequities. Conversely, small-scale farmers, civic associations, and renewable energy communities articulate an alternative model of development that reconciles production with ecological stewardship. The Valley thus epitomises Europe's wider challenge of aligning green transitions with territorial justice. Renewable Energy Communities illustrate how the energy transition can be pluralised and democratised: they reframe energy not as a commodity but as a social right, linking decarbonisation to participation and equity. By contrast, the top-down proliferation of industrial-scale agro-photovoltaic plants exemplifies the risk of reproducing extractive logics under the banner of sustainability.

Within this tension, the collective mapping of photovoltaic plants emerges as a crucial transformative device. More than a technical exercise, it functions as an epistemic and political intervention—making visible the territorial consequences of energy transition and transforming data into democratic agency. Through collaborative cartography, local actors, researchers, and municipalities jointly reconstruct the geography of power, revealing how land-use decisions reflect broader conflicts over biodiversity, livelihoods, and justice. The mapping process thus materialises the project's guiding principles: it politicises environmental knowledge, empowers communities to act, and embeds transformative practice in everyday governance. It stands as a flagship example of how BIOTraCes methodologies—participatory, reflexive, and transdisciplinary—can foster accountable decision-making and strengthen biodiversity governance.

From a policy perspective, the Simeto experience reveals both reinforcement and friction between local innovations and supranational frameworks. The Patto di Fiume Simeto (Simeto River Agreement) remains an advanced institutional experiment inspired by EU directives and the 2030 Agenda, which sought to embed deliberative democracy and socio-ecological justice in territorial governance. However, its potential has been curtailed by the absence of regional legislation on participation, fragmented competences, and limited administrative capacity. Similar dissonances affect the local implementation of European programmes such as LIFE, whose transformative aspirations often falter under procedural rigidity. The Simeto Valley, therefore, illuminates a broader systemic issue: transformative change for biodiversity depends not only on visionary frameworks but on

embedding them within flexible, place-sensitive institutional architectures capable of sustaining bottom-up innovation.

A defining feature of the Simeto Case Study process has been the emergence of co-learning as both a methodological framework and a political act. Through focus groups, workshops, and the Facciamo la Valle! Festival, researchers and citizens co-produced interpretations of ecological crises and their social roots. These encounters blurred hierarchies between scientific and experiential knowledge, creating affective and dialogical spaces where new ecological imaginaries could emerge. The festival's performative act of "re-stitching the river," for instance, transformed research findings into a collective ritual of repair, demonstrating that transformation begins with shared imagination. Co-learning in this sense not only produced knowledge but also reconfigured relationships of trust and reciprocity, embodying the BIOTraCes principles of pluralising perspectives and politicising environmental practice.

Finally, the testing of interventions consolidated these learning dynamics into concrete governance experiments. The co-design of Renewable Energy Communities and the participatory mapping of agrivoltaics plants demonstrated how the co-production of knowledge can evolve into operational capacity. These initiatives reframed governance as an open, iterative process integrating data, memory, and foresight. The Presidio's dual strategy—maintaining dialogue with institutions while cultivating autonomous civic action—proved essential to sustaining transformative momentum under adverse conditions. Cultural infrastructures such as the Simeto Ecomuseum and civic events like the Facciamo la Valle! Festival amplified this process, transforming knowledge exchange into collective empowerment and contributing to embed biodiversity within a renewed sense of shared territorial responsibility.

Concluding remarks

Overall, the Simeto Valley case exemplifies how transformative change for biodiversity can take root through the interplay of social innovation, reflexive governance, and the co-production of knowledge. Its success lies less in measurable ecological outcomes than in its capacity to generate new forms of collective agency, territorial imagination, and socio-ecological solidarity. Despite structural constraints, the Societal Partner and its networks have forged a resilient civic ecology that bridges science, policy, and activism. Their experience demonstrates that biodiversity regeneration is inseparable from questions of justice, recognition, and participation. In this sense, the Simeto Valley does not merely test interventions—it performs transformation, offering a grounded demonstration of how plural, empowering, politicised, and embedded approaches can anchor the Theory of Transformative Change in the lived realities of European territories.

Notes

[1] It is important to clarify that two different focus groups were held on March 15th 2025. The first one (FG1) was focused on the indirect drivers of biodiversity loss while the second one (FG2) was about inconsistencies between regenerative policies across different levels of government and governance. The participants in FG1 and FG2 were primarily, though not exclusively, long-standing members and activists of the societal partner, several of whom also hold responsibilities within the governing board of the Participatory Presidium. All participants affiliated with the Presidio have

played various roles over the past ten years, both within the societal partner and in public institutions, thereby engaging with territorial projects from different institutional positions.

In addition to these participants, the session included the coordinator of a women-only activist collective called *Mamme in Comune*, which has been involved for several years in educational and environmental initiatives and currently collaborates closely with the societal partner in numerous projects. A member of the NESTI cooperative was also present; although recently established, this cooperative works in a close and ongoing partnership with the societal partner. Finally, the group included an external researcher (not affiliated with UNICT) who studies ecomuseums in Southern Italy and was conducting a research period at the Simeto Ecomuseum. The focus group was held at the headquarters of the Participatory Presidium. For this reason, in addition to the core group of participants, other activists from the societal partner joined the discussion during the session. Although they participated mainly in the final part of the activity, they nonetheless contributed several meaningful insights and feedback.

[2] The Simeto Ecomuseum mobilises a variety of collective processes that combine community engagement, territorial knowledge, and participatory planning. These include community-mapping exercises, co-designed with schools, farmers, and local associations to document water systems, rural landscapes, and everyday ecological practices; intergenerational workshops and educational laboratories that bring together children, elders, activists, and researchers to exchange memories and ecological knowledge; and collective territorial itineraries such as *In Viaggio con Violetta*, which activate shared exploration and interpretation of riverine and agricultural spaces.

[3] The CNR (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche) — National Research Council of Italy — is the country's largest public research institution. Founded in 1923, it operates under the Ministry of University and Research and coordinates multidisciplinary scientific activities across national and international programmes. The CNR conducts research, promotes innovation, and supports public administration and industry through applied science and technological development.

2.8 UT Case Study: The Netherlands (Dutch Foodpark case)

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2.8.1 Short presentation of the case

Foodpark Amsterdam is a grassroots organisation that aims to protect an area in the city of Amsterdam (the Lutkemeerpolder) from industrialization. Their approach consists of three interrelated strategies. The first strategy is protest. The movement protests against the plans to develop the area and build warehouses on them through banners and flyers and by using public consultation. The second strategy is to frame a broader narrative. In this narrative, they present the development plans as representing an unsustainable economic worldview that is based a separation between people and nature, overconsumption, and property, and they contrast this with an alternative worldview that conceives of land not as property but as commons and that considers humans as entangled with nature. The third strategy is prefiguring and building an alternative. Specifically, they aim to create a foodpark that will be governed as a commons and that will foster enhanced human nature relationships, and they also prefigure this model of the commons in the inner workings of the grassroots organisation. The case study demonstrates how these different strategies work together to not only protect a specific area, but also build an alternative, commons based, society.

2.8.2 Evaluation of strategies in action

One of the great strengths of Foodpark Amsterdam is that they constantly employ a large variety of strategies. Their strategy can be described as playing on various chessboards, yet these chessboards can be defined in multiple terms.

Firstly, it should be noted that Foodpark Amsterdam often refers to a just transition framework that understands transition as the double movement of stopping the bad and building the alternative. As we described in the summary of this deliverable, they engage in protest, they aim to change the narrative, and they prefigure and build the alternative. On a slide that is often used by Foodpark Amsterdam for internal reflection but also outwardly they outline the following four steps:

1. "Break": Focus on disruption, on opposing plans and complicit institutions, direct action, legal action
2. "Push": Advocacy, seeking better policies from those in authority & institutions
3. "Building the alternative": Imagining Voedselpark Amsterdam addressing the socio-environmental problems in a direct way, experimentation
4. "Grow": connecting & networking, mobilizing for a cause, organizing & campaigning, growing the movement.

Foodpark emerged as a complementary and successor initiative of Save Lutkemeer [Behoud Lutkemeer], the original action group that resisted the coming of a business park in the Lutkemeerpolder. The initiative Save Lutkemeer [Behoud Lutkemeer] had very strong tactics of opposing the building of the business park, as such their focus was on the first step of "break". They engaged in demonstrations, non-violent direct action including civil disobedience. For this purpose, they were also collecting an impressive array of information, uncovering the untransparent web of decisions around the business park, including reports of the corruption.

Foodpark Amsterdam was founded from within Behoud Lutkemeerpolder but adjacent to it and with new people to show that the activism in the Lutkemeerpolder was not only about opposing existing plans but also about providing an alternative vision. In this sense, Foodpark Amsterdam was brought to life to embark on the second step of the model of pushing better policy. They were following the spirit of the famous quote by Buckminster Fuller "You never change things by fighting the existing reality. To change something, build a new model that makes the existing model obsolete." Yet, especially in the periods that Save Lutkemeer [Behoud Lutkemeer] became less active, Foodpark Amsterdam integrated the first step of resistance into their strategies. They generated media attention around the Lutkemeerpolder through media campaigns, regular online posts, and making an effort to get into touch with local press,¹ public events, getting

¹ [Nieuw in Amsterdam-West - De Westkrant](#) – Online news from the larger westside of the city of Amsterdam, Online news concerning the direct neighbourhood of Amsterdam Nieuw West [Amsterdam Nieuw-West | Rodi](#), The streetnewspaper [Z! de Amsterdamse straatkrant](#), the Amsterdam-based daily newspaper [Het Parool - Vrij](#).

engaged in all kinds of public conversations. Moreover, in 2024 Foodpark– together with Save Lutkemeer – organized a campaign that put the main emphasis on protesting against the building plans.

Foodpark Amsterdam’s strategy has also always involved elements of “building the alternative” in multiple ways. Firstly, within their own organization they are prefiguring to some extent commons-based modes of collaboration that allows for democratic participation and decision making.² Foodpark Amsterdam is also involved in ‘building the alternative’ through the launching their first pilot Foodpark in a plot of land recently won through tender. This gives Foodpark Amsterdam the opportunity to prefigure on the ground their vision on collaboration and collective care for land. Simultaneously, they are making sustained efforts of community building, particularly in the neighbourhood of Nieuw-West. To build an alternative economy it is of primary importance that relationships are formed within the neighbourhood and a collective conversation around food and environmental justice is flourishing.

Finally, Foodpark Amsterdam is also involved in growing the initiative, and their community is constantly growing. So far, it has proven to be more difficult to also ‘materially’ grow, in other words, to make more land available for urban agriculture, particularly land that originally was not already reserved for urban agriculture (such as the smaller plot now used for piloting their approach).

Foodpark Amsterdam’s strategies aim to combine the local and concrete (challenging the development plans, building an alternative vision for the Luktemeer) with the broader narrative (challenging political economic paradigms and institutions, developing a commons based alternative society). The following strategies emerged during the PAR research:

1. Organizing protest
 - a. Shaping public discourse through protesting and campaigns
 - b. Media and communication (lots of videos, social, media, visuals)
2. Influencing Policy
 - a. Using opportunities for policy engagement, using speaking time during municipal commission meetings, letters, lobbying

[Onverveerd](#), local television station in Amsterdam [AT5](#), daily Dutch newspaper [NRC - Nieuws, achtergronden en onderzoeksjournalistiek](#),

²Within Foodpark Amsterdam, anybody who has an idea for doing something can in principle go ahead, but they are expected to consult others before execution. This gives everybody a sense of ownership of their own work and freedom and creativity to do what they can do best. At the same time, the consultation ensures broad support and also improvement of plans. As it is basically impossible to pull a bigger initiative on one’s own, the consultation process also ensures that there are always enough people in support of a plan. While there are people that are in charge of the budget (in terms of organizing payments and applying for funds), the budget is also transparent and everybody who would like to do something can make a budget plan. There is one person who makes decisions, however the aim is to come to an agreement.

- b. Developing institutional mechanisms: commoning
- c. Joint Fact Finding
3. Building (local) communities
 - a. Bodily engagement: walks, cooking sessions
 - b. Artistic expression: working with artists
4. Prefiguring the alternative (by giving the right example)

These different strategies are all very contextual as they respond continuously to different opportunities and barriers within the field. This involves the people that have energy to pull initiatives, engaged in political events such as elections, the agenda of the municipality, available funds, and not at least the experience of success and failure. For instance, the overall ambition of Foodpark Amsterdam changed quite a bit from when we joined in early 2023 until now, mid 2025. Foodpark Amsterdam started with the ambition to turn a 43 hectares plot within the Lutkemeerpolder into a commons-governed food park. Yet by now, almost half of this territory is under construction. Nonetheless, they continue to struggle for all remaining hectares. Besides, they made and won a tender submission for a smaller adjacent plot of land of 9,5 hectares (zoned for urban agriculture). The aim is to use this small plot as a pilot and show on a smaller scale how different entrepreneurs (ranging from food foresters to urban farmers, to herbalists, and cooks) who need land can cooperate and share the land as a commons in the neighbourhood.

Fitting with Foodpark Amsterdam's flexibility to continuously and creatively respond to changing political circumstances, also in our collaboration with Foodpark Amsterdam we have adapted a more flexible way of working. Instead of having one plan to follow through, we worked in short half-year cycles, updating what will be important upcoming events and opportunities and how we could collaborate for this purpose. Such an approach required an initial period of getting to know each other, so Foodpark Amsterdam was getting a sense of what kind of questions we were interested in and vice versa. In this process we learned that we could most effectively support their aims through organizing workshops and collaborating with artists, circulating the story of Foodpark Amsterdam, making connections with other researchers. Therefore, we worked together primarily on these terrains. As such, we contributed most significantly to further articulating and promoting the transformative change potential of the initiative to address the indirect drivers of biodiversity loss. Ideally, this would have contributed to replicating enablers of biodiversity and reduce the impact of biodiversity disruptors, particularly here the expansion of the business park on the land. Yet, this remains questionable as so far there are no signs that the building activities within the Lutkemeerpolder will stop.

2.8.3 Enablers and disruptors

In the case of Foodpark Amsterdam, the enablers and disrupters concern very local circumstances, that is circumstances that mostly concern municipal politics.

Enablers

There is a growing movement that embraces key aspects about which Foodpark Amsterdam also stands for: an alternative economic vision, a social justice outlook, a perspective that also centres ecological flourishing, that does not view agriculture as separate from biodiversity.

The appeal of the ideas Foodpark stands for can be deduced from the number of times they are invited to speak on public occasions (e.g., Pakhuis de Zwijger, as well-known cultural meeting place in the centre of Amsterdam), take part in expert and public conversations (e.g., on the topic of women and food), and are sought out by researchers and educators as a fieldtrip destination and the continuous support they manage to mobilize.

Moreover, there are vibrant networks active on these various frontlines, ranging from commons coalitions to (urban) agroecological networks. Within a cosmopolitan city like Amsterdam, there is plenty of opportunity for these different ideas to cross-fertilize and support each other, become integrated in the curricula of local educational institutions ranging from primary schools to universities. This demonstrates the strategy of FPA to connect the concrete case of the Lutkemeerpolder to the wider social and political context (see 6.2). At the same time, in its specificity the Lutkemeerpolder serves as a concrete example where the enablers and disruptors to biodiversity regeneration become very clear. For instance, it also inspired the national agroecological network to think about alternative models of landownership. There is no shortage of people that would like to work in this sector and also plenty of potential customers. A further impact of the increasing support of the ideas Foodpark stands for is also that it can reach policy circles, leading to ambitious policy plans.

Whether these enabling factors will ultimately lead to the spreading of Foodpark Amsterdam and whether the different volunteers will ultimately take these ideas to other work and initiatives in which they are also involved, remains to be seen.

While there are no designated subsidies for the kind of work they do, Foodpark has been able to access various funds, ranging from donations from private people, funds given out by companies (Lush, Patagonia), and funds that stimulate grassroot initiatives with a commons agenda (Stichting Doen, Community Wealth Building). These funds allow Foodpark Amsterdam to keep on going, by allowing them to pay two members one day a week, have some budget for hiring external expertise on a project basis (e.g. a landscape architect) and for occasionally printing a flyer, buying sunflower seeds, or other material costs for their campaigns.

Disruptors

The main disruptors are economic interests over ecological ones. This becomes most visible in the companies that aim to settle within the Lutkemeerpolder. Their business in themselves relies on extractive industries and unsustainable practices. Besides, they managed to be so successful at this that they see the need to expand their businesses, building on what Foodpark Amsterdam did not fail to bring to attention – the last fertile soil of the city. The municipality, whose *raison d'être* is to act on the public good of its citizens is prone to stand at the side of the disruptors for regenerative farming. The reasons for this are multiple:

1. Thinking in terms of old models of the economy is still dominant. For instance, an increased industrial territory is often thought to be automatically good for the economy and job opportunities. Yet, the number of jobs that will be created in the business park and how this contributes to the economic well-being of the residents of Amsterdam (which should be the primary focus of the municipality of Amsterdam) remains unclear. Foodpark Amsterdam activists, for instance, point to the fact that urban logistics and distribution is becoming highly automated and that actually does not offer a lot of jobs, now and especially in the future. Moreover, by removing requirements concerning what kind of businesses can settle in the area (which was previously the case) the municipality has little available tools to stir this process. The worry of Foodpark Amsterdam is then that mostly (multi)national enterprises will settle there. This thinking in terms of old economy does also not recognize the economic potential of a foodpark. For instance, on a third of a hectare, the adjacent Community Supported Agriculture initiative Pluk is capable of providing weekly vegetables for almost 100 households employing three farmers. While small-scale organic farming can hardly economically compete as a producer of food for large supermarket chains, the cooperative model of community supported agriculture provides a robust alternative economic model, where harvesters commit to a season of produce by paying the fee upfront at the beginning of the season according to a model of social pricing. This is quite significant economic activity that very tangibly adds to the economic well-being of the local residents.
2. The municipality understands renting out land as a lucrative business to manage the municipal budget. It can charge higher land prices if renting out land to industry than to agriculture. Since, within a municipal context, there is a shortage in terms of financial resources, extra income for the municipality is always welcome.
3. The municipality wants to come across as an institution of reliable governance [betrouwbare overheid] that does not simply overturn the plans of previous administration.
4. The municipality may be faced with compensation claims from companies that have reserved a plot in case it retracts the possibility of establishing a business park there.

So far, Foodpark Amsterdam has not managed to structurally dismantle these disruptors. There are signs that the idea of alternative economies are becoming more popular within circles of the municipality (policy, research, plans and events for a communal economy). At the same time, the step of translating them into laws and regulations that will actually support bringing land into a common governance structure seems to be still far away.

(Mis)match with EU policy

Currently there are no EU policy frameworks that can be effectively evoked within the context. One of the tricky aspects of this is that the opportunities and disruptors are so locally specific. Some policies that would support Foodpark Amsterdam, on a European, national and municipal level would do so because they support green and civic initiatives. A good example is the 2022 ministerial decision to make soil and water leading factors in spatial decision about where and what to build³. However, these policies have not been able to reverse industrialization as most of the building permits had been already granted. More generally, these green policies run the risk of being ineffective without further institutional and legal changes. Some people see new opportunities in the new [De Omgevingswet](#), the Dutch Environment and Planning Act that is handled since 2024 or in the initiatives around the Right to Challenge⁴.

It is difficult to evaluate whether the inability to reverse industrialization is a matter of policy or of political will. The alderman [in Dutch wethouder] of spatial planning [in Dutch Ruimtelijke Ordening] - roughly the municipal equivalent of a minister on the national level - in theory, has the power to reverse decisions that have been made. One reason for this that we have seen is that the municipality wants to come across as a trustworthy government [in Dutch betrouwbare overheid]. This means, that there is strong pressure for current aldermen to not overturn decisions and deals that have been made. In the case of the Lutkemeerpolder, these are decisions that have started in the 1980s and that were tweaked and changed throughout the 2000s.

This seemingly absence of political will is striking because since 2022, Amsterdam has a GreenLeft Mayor, and a governing coalition that includes GreenLeft, the Labor Party and the Liberals D66. All these parties support green politics and social causes, combined with supporting local entrepreneurs and job opportunities, all of which is part of the Foodpark Amsterdam plan. Nonetheless, Foodpark Amsterdam is often dismissed as too small, and thus too irrelevant to make a real impact.

³ *Kabinet maakt water en bodem sturend bij ruimtelijke keuzes.* (2022, November 25). [Nieuwsbericht]. Rijksoverheid; Ministerie van Algemene Zaken. <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/actueel/nieuws/2022/11/25/kabinet-maakt-water-en-bodem-sturend-bij-ruimtelijke-keuzes>.

⁴ *Right to Challenge.* Rijksoverheid: Kenniscentrum Voor Beleid En Regelgeving. Retrieved November 20, 2025, from <https://www.kcbr.nl/ontwikkelen-beleid-en-regelgeving/beleidskompas/3-wat-zijn-opties-om-het-doel-te-realiseren/31-beleidsinstrumenten/juridisch/recht-challenge>.

2.8.4 Failed and successful practices

In the case of Foodpark Amsterdam, it is difficult to isolate their different strategies and assess them in terms of failure or success. Often, they inform their learning and the next steps, and ultimately all strategies, taken together, are mobilized towards advancing their project. Moreover, our research and collaboration process does not fit well with a linear and instrumental evaluative approach that would separate strategies into specific actions that can be evaluated as successful or unsuccessful. As indicated above and also in chapter 4 of D2.5, the strategies of FPA are better seen as a continuous process or struggle. Moreover, they are all interconnected and they fit with FPA's long-term vision. Even if a strategy might temporarily appear as a failure, this offers opportunities for learning and reframing. At the same time, the limited timeframe of the project does not allow for an appropriate reflection and discussion of success and failure.

Yet, FPA has managed to build a large network of ambassadors and supporters who are good at disseminating their story and ambitious further. They also have an active volunteer base and despite financial pressures, they have been effective in motivating people to join and support a common cause. Another important strategy has been that of persistence and making their case in various ways. This has contributed to achieving a shift in thinking in the municipality, for instance in terms of more actively supporting the idea of commons and commoning as an alternative economic practice. A tangible result of this success is that Foodpark Amsterdam has won the public tender procedure.

So far, the initiative has not managed yet to stop the building activities and reclaim (part of) the land that is now destined to become an industrial area. Some of the parcels have been built now, but for other slots the building process goes extremely slow. While the reasons for this are unclear, one may be tempted to speculate that some of the campaign of Foodpark Amsterdam was effective in exposing this site as an undesirable building area. The initiative has been also less successful in engaging committed younger people for extended periods of time, particularly from the nearby Nieuw West neighbourhood. However, this cannot be seen as a specific failure for Foodpark Amsterdam, as young urbanites from cosmopolitan cities are more generally difficult to involve in activities perceived as non-urban or involving knowledge and skills that are currently lost from urban environments. This was visible in a speculative workshop Listening to the Soil (W02, see table 2), organised in collaboration with a local international school and involving young people⁵.

2.8.5 Co-learning

Throughout the research process, researchers have been involved in fieldwork and actively took part in regular monthly meetings of Foodpark Amsterdam. We have also held meetings together to co-organize workshops and other activities. As such, co-learning happened primarily through working together (some illustrative examples are

⁵ A discussion of the workshop is included Baibarac-Duignan, C., & van den Eijnden, T. (2025). Designing for Transitions Through Co-created Artistic Methods: Gluing Affective "Rurban" Encounters. *World Futures Review*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/19467567251330153>.

provided below). Besides this ongoing process, we are currently organizing more formalized feedback workshops with research partners and societal partners to reflect upon the project results and the co-learning that has taken place.

Some of the collaborations between Foodpark Amsterdam and the University of Twente research team have had a highly reflexive dimension linked to co-learning. One example is the Postgrowth Symposium co-organised by the research partners with Foodpark Amsterdam. This was a crucial moment in the project in terms of co-learning opportunities (see chapter 4 of D2.5). It brought together academics and practitioners that share the common cause pursued by Foodpark to reflect more broadly on biodiversity in the context of urban agriculture and the role of collaborations between researchers, civic organisations, and the municipality.

Another moment of co-learning was the participation of one Foodpark member in all the consortium discussions of the second consortium. This provided the Foodpark member a clearer idea regarding how we work within the BIOTraCes project, but also the BIOTraCes researchers could learn from her knowledge on land commoning ideas and experiences.

Moreover, one Foodpark member and University of Twente researcher co-authored a conference presentation together that the Foodpark member presented at the conference Regenerating the Commons (2025). The core idea of paper built on the researcher's insights from her fieldwork, which she formulated and then discussed and refined with the Foodpark Amsterdam member. The topic the presentation addressed was about co-learning in the context of commoning - something we referred to as 'commons literacy'.

Some other activities and instances of co-learning were more about generating academic reflection and output (e.g., societal partner joining consortium meetings, co-organizing a symposium, and co-authoring a conference presentation); while some were more artistic (e.g., the co-production of a narrative for the International Architecture Biennale Rotterdam, co-coordinating an artistic residency). These collaborative actions helped to concretize and articulate some of our ideas.

Sometimes, also, members of Foodpark Amsterdam invite us to teaching and public speaking occasions to which they have been invited. This gives us the opportunity to think together about how we would like to present our ideas, often also complementing each other. An example for this is a recent talk one of the Foodpark members provided at a cultural venue in which Foodpark was presented as an example of 'the regenerative city'. During this talk, the Foodpark Amsterdam member was talking about the activities of the foodpark, while the researcher offered a short reflection on how the activities of foodpark may be understood as regenerative. This provided new insights and reflections for both sides.

2.8.6 Testing of interventions

Feedback workshops with research partners and societal partners are currently being organised to deepen discussion regarding the locally tested interventions. The ongoing activities of Foodpark Amsterdam towards realising an agroecological commons are a critical component in addressing root causes of biodiversity loss (e.g., associated with urbanisation and industrialisation of land previously used for agriculture). A form of ‘peer review’ has been conducted throughout the project, involving mostly one-to-one conversations. The Postgrowth Symposium was a way to formalise this time of ongoing monitoring and reflection, as it brought different researchers engaging with Foodpark Amsterdam together to discuss the case (for more about the symposium, see chapter 4.2 of D2.5).

As mentioned previously: our collaboration with Foodpark Amsterdam was very integrated. We made great efforts to work as a continuation of their ongoing efforts and make our contributions also relevant to their aims. From this perspective, a framework of ‘testing’ and ‘interventions’ is a bit alien to our efforts. Moreover, rather than separate concrete interventions that can be tested and evaluated, the strategies of FPA are better described as a continuous process or struggle.

Nonetheless, we can talk in terms of our contributions to the initiative of Foodpark Amsterdam. Indeed, perhaps our intervention can be best understood as an affirmation of promising approaches we could observe were at the core of the initiative Foodpark Amsterdam.

As can be seen in Table 2, our collaboration involved various workshops that aimed at bringing in artistic and creative reflections. These contributions have generally been embraced by Foodpark Amsterdam. What’s more, as in the case of the Ceramic workshops (W06), and the Speculative Monitoring workshop (W09), we were actually building on collaborations Foodpark Amsterdam has already established before or independent of our participation. These workshops, for most of the part, we co-organised with core members of Foodpark Amsterdam and were about engaging the larger community around Foodpark Amsterdam.

Table 2 Overview of Workshops

Number, Name & Date	Organizers	Participants	Description
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Deliverable 2.4 – Locally tested interventions

<p>W01:</p> <p>Social Ecological Systems mapping with FoodparkAmsterdam</p> <p>28 June, 2023, at de Waag Futurelab</p>	<p>UT researcher</p>	<p>6 FPA members</p>	<p>During this workshop, in a three-step procedure, we mapped with our societal partner the Social Ecological System around FoodparkAmsterdam. Starting from the individual network and connections, we were further circling into issues of conflict, power, synergies and open questions and concluded with a formulation of challenges and potentials. During this workshop the key themes were identified, which included problematizing real estate development and its financial logic, community building and creating an appealing narrative for Foodpark Amsterdam</p>
<p>W02:</p> <p>Listening to the Soil, June 2023, at the Boterbloem in the Lutkemeerpolder</p>	<p>UT researcher & external artist with some assistance of Foodpark.</p>	<p>Around 40 15-16 year old students from local (public) international school</p>	<p>The aim of the workshop was to stimulate deeper engagement with nature and imagination around alternative human-nature relationships through making speculative listening tools. For this purpose, we used white canvases and coloured pens for brainstorming; discarded and leftover crafting materials and electronics for making the tools. With this the pupils made speculative listening tools capturing more-than human needs in ways that could be experienced through human senses. Analysis of the workshop may be found in Baibarac-Duignan, C., & van den Eijnden, T. (2025). Designing for Transitions Through Co-created Artistic Methods: Gluing Affective “Rurban” Encounters. World Futures</p>

			Review, 0(0). https://doi.org/10.1177/19467567251330153 .
<p>W03:</p> <p>Land Lease and Food Initiatives, 27 Oktober, 2023, Urban farm Noord-Oogst</p>	<p>Foodpark member & Foundation for Urban Agriculture, UT researcher involved as report maker</p>	<p>15 participants, including civic servants, urban farmers, artists, etc.</p>	<p>The starting point of the conversation was a widely shared feeling that there is much motivation for urban agriculture, exemplified by still unrealized projects such as Foodpark Amsterdam. However, there are structural financial, legal and fiscal barriers that prevent such projects from being realized with difficulty, if at all. The goal of the workshop was to better identify these barriers, but also to gather strategies and courses of action for how we can collectively deal with these barriers and what the possibilities are for rearranging land ownership.</p>
<p>W04:</p> <p>Postgrowth Cities workshop on collaboration, 9th February 2024, at the Boterbloem in the Luttekemeerpolder</p>	<p>UT researcher, external researcher and FPA</p>	<p>2 X 25 participants, mostly researchers, 1 FPA member</p>	<p>During the <u>Postgrowth Cities Symposium</u> (see chapter 4.2), we also conducted a workshop with the aim of the workshop was to bring policymakers, researchers, commoners and urban agriculture practitioners together to reflect on the relations and collaborations between researchers, civic organisations, and the municipality. These questions do not just bring us together around Foodpark Amsterdam, but also resonate more widely with the broader field of urban agriculture. While generally, there is a lot of enthusiasm for these collaborations, it is also worthwhile examining how they take shape, what are good practices and where we</p>

			<p>need to improve our ways of working together to make them more equitable, impactful and generative. The aim of the workshop was twofold: to formulate general principles that can help us to make collaboration agreements and strategize about concrete actions we could take in the present.</p>
<p>W05: Spatial planning for Food within Urban Development, 21 June, 2024, urban farm NoordOogst</p>	<p>Foundation for urban agriculture, municipality of Amsterdam, UT researcher</p>	<p>Around 15 participants including architects, planners, civic servants, researchers</p>	<p>For a healthy, sustainable and resilient city, it is crucial that the food cycle is given space in new neighbourhoods. How can this be organized in the planning process? And what does this require from residents (networks) in adopting gardens and other communal outdoor spaces? We take the case of the area development for Havenstad and NoordOogst as an example</p>
<p>W06: Ceramic Workshops, March-July 2024, at New metropolis, Bouwput, & de Boterbloem</p>	<p>External artist, Waag Futurelab, FPA, UT researcher</p>	<p>About 5-25 participants per workshop, mostly residents and clay lovers of Amsterdam</p>	<p>There were 8 clay workshops taking place between March and July 2024 in different locations in Nieuw West, including the Lutkemeerpolder. This happened as part of an artistic residency between FPA and Waag Futurelab. All workshops involved clay from the Lutkemeerpolder. In some workshops the focus was on harvesting the wild clay and cleansing it in others the focus was on making objects. Different artistic exercises were employed for this and inspiration was taken from ancient ceramic art from the Asia Minor region. This also provoked reflections on how ceramic art and clay</p>

			connects us to the land, plants, and food. Results include an artistic catalogue, a short documentary on “The Gold of Amsterdam” and an open air exhibition.
<p>W07:</p> <p>Toolmaking to Reimagine Food Futures, 14 June 2024, at de Boterbloem</p>	<p>UT Researchers, RurbanFutures Collective, FPA</p>	<p>10 participants</p>	<p>In this workshop, we aimed to explore and reimagine ‘rurban’ food futures for the neighbourhood of Nieuw West through toolmaking at the present site of FoodparkAmsterdam. The workshop was an experimental format, conceived as a low-threshold mode of engagement with the site at Lutkemeerpolder by making it accessible to participants from groups outside the academic or artistic realms. Tools allow us to work the land, harvest and prepare food. They connect soil and seeds, skills and knowledge, humans and nature.</p>
<p>W08:</p> <p>Bioblitz, June 2024, in de Lutkemeerpolder, cancelled due to lack of available volunteer ecologists</p>	<p>UT Researchers & FPA</p>	<p>n.a.</p>	<p>Through biologically surveying the site where the Foodpark is presently located, we will make visible the biodiversity value of the land and explore potential futures where various species thrive. The aim of the workshop was to bring to the fore the biodiversity specific to this land and to explore potential tensions between how biodiversity is normally conceived (e.g., as unique and/or protected species) and everyday / mundane illustrations of biodiversity of a land under threat of redevelopment for lack of biodiversity significance.</p>

			While in the end we had sufficient citizen participants that were eager to participate, we did not manage to find enough ecological experts that would have been able to instruct the citizens and bring the tools for proper examination.
W09: Speculative Monitoring Workshop, 24 July, 2024 at de Boterbloem	UT researcher, FPA Amsterdam, External curators	20 artists, curators, and activists from Open Call: de Appel Curatorial Programme Summer School - de Appel Amsterdam	In this workshop, we speculatively monitored the life of the polder above and below the surface of soil, water, and empirical reality. We did this by imaging what the polder smells, feels, and looks like for different moments in time that slip through current monitoring practices. In doing so, we wanted to expand our attention to biodiversity beyond limiting notions of biodiversity that dominate in the present and think about other ways of conceiving the richness of the living world. By bringing together different speculative accounts on what biodiversity might be, we wanted to open up a conversation about what biodiversity would mean if we conceived of it as a potentiality rather than a reality. And lastly, what are the implications in terms of landownership, if we look at land as potentialities for life rather than a measurable reality?
W10: Toward a desirable land	UT researcher, FPA, Foundation for urban	25 participants, including urban farmers	The workshop was conducted during the Day of Urban Agriculture in Amsterdam organized by the Association

<p>policy:</p> <p>Visions and routes for collaboration, 4 December 2024, at urban farm NoordOogst</p>	<p>agriculture</p>	<p>and municipal employees</p>	<p>of urban agriculture in Amsterdam. Approximately 25 people were anticipating in the workshop, among which two core members of FoodparkAmsterdam, and one researcher, one student who are also involved in the case. Among their participants were urban farmers (among which at least one who is currently collaborating with FoodparkAmsterdam):</p> <p>Leading questions were: What are the desirable visions for the future of land policy? Is land a resource, or should it be considered a commons, meaning that the land is unsellable? What are the challenges and opportunities from the perspective of officials and council members as we move toward desirable land policy? And how can we collaborate effectively at the interface of research, policy and civic engagement? This workshop is "hands-on": we started with big ideas and then worked toward concrete proposals for collaboration. The workshop provided different insights on vision on land and principles of collaboration.</p>
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Moreover, providing a narrative for the video for the International Architecture Biennale Rotterdam can be seen as further connecting the learning from Foodpark Amsterdam to a more general theoretical level (see chapter 5 of D2.5). The film and the narrative offer a reflection on Foodpark Amsterdam in the context of architecture and shows that architecture cannot be understood as isolated from the environment where it is situated.

What all of our contributions to the case of Foodpark Amsterdam have in common is that their focus is on highlighting the social, ecological, and cultural aspects of biodiversity. This is particularly relevant, as there is more and more recognition that – what used to

be different departments and sectors – really need to work together for addressing complex problems like biodiversity loss.

2.8.7 Discussion

In this report we have discussed and reflected upon the strategies employed by Foodpark Amsterdam to advance their commons-based vision of urban agriculture and alternative economies. We have identified strategies that break, push, build and alternative and grow a movement around the local initiative. These strategies are being developed and employed in parallel and despite what may be perceived as failures along the way, taken together they have been promoting the cause and approach of Foodpark Amsterdam among the activist, practitioners and academic community. Moreover, their ideas and vision have started to shape more support from the inside of the Municipality of Amsterdam for the commons and the alternative economic practices commoning implies.

Moving on from the strategies employed by FPA, we have identified some key enablers and disruptors. The main enablers include the various related initiatives that share aspirations for an alternative economy, social justice and ecological flourishing. Together they are shaping a movement at the forefront of which is Foodpark Amsterdam. On the other hand, the reliance on volunteer support represents a potential limitation and weak point in this process. While financial pressures of everyday life in a mainstream economy represents a risk from the volunteer perspective, economic factors can also be observed as wider disruptors. Key is the prevalence of economic interests over ecological ones, which are visible in the industrialization process of the area and arguably could also limit the extent of engagement of the younger inhabitants of the neighbourhood in the initiative.

2.9 WUR Case Study: The Netherlands (Nature Inclusive Building)

Authors: Roel During, Zoë van Eldik, Amy Wortel, Rosalie van Dam

2.9.1 Short presentation of the case

The planning, design and construction of new houses and neighbourhoods has a significant impact on nature. Over the past decade, approximately 280 square kilometres have been converted into human habitats, coinciding with a corresponding decline in agricultural and natural areas. The sector is rightly considered high impact. In response to its problematic relationship with nature, efforts have been made to incorporate more nature into human living environments. These innovation programmes are referred to as part of the “nature inclusive agenda.”

The system tasked with building around one million homes in the coming decade is highly complex, involving a multitude of actors, legislation and political disputes. As a result, it is difficult to change. The power to initiate or resist change is distributed across a wide public private network. The aim of this case study is to uncover the structures and

mechanisms that either block or enable innovations that could improve the sector's relationship with nature.

This case study focuses on one such nature inclusive innovation programme, Natuur voor Elkaar [Nature for Each Other], hosted by the Province of Overijssel. In parallel, it examines an innovative citizens' initiative called De Beuk, which aims to establish an ecovillage and eco community on the outskirts of Wageningen. The research methods applied are rooted in action research. By engaging directly with the bio innovative enterprise and collaborating with the citizens of De Beuk and provincial officers, researchers encountered the challenging path of marginalisation, blockage and leverage.

Biodiversity loss is indirectly driven by a narrow view of nature, understood merely as species and habitats, whose decline is assumed to be compensable by converting agricultural land into new nature reserves. This approach backfires in politics and public opinion, as the public tends to sympathise with farmers. Nature is often blamed for the sector's current stagnation. The deterioration of nature is countered by an increasingly strict set of regulations. Ironically, these same regulations now hinder the success of bio innovations. Innovations emerging from new human–nature relationships are seen as potentially harmful to the forms of nature that existing protection frameworks recognise and safeguard. The regulatory and permitting system remains unyielding.

The case study reveals that innovation within the sector is primarily driven by goals of efficiency and the adoption of biomaterials. Ideological and moral innovations, however, do not fit within the sector's systemic boundaries. Although nature inclusive building is widely recognised, it is still difficult to realise and often remains more words than practice.

2.9.2 Evaluation of strategies in action

Below, we present the interventions and strategies identified in our case study and discuss them in relation to:

1. their potential for transformative change
2. the manageability of indirect drivers of biodiversity loss
3. their capacity to foster plural perspectives
4. the empowerment of vulnerable and underrepresented groups
5. gender balance within the biodiversity governance agenda
6. concerns related to environmental justice

De Beuk

De Beuk has been established as a cooperative endeavour of five standalone initiatives, seeking to engage in the development of De Dorschkamp. This site, formerly a hospital and forest station, lies just outside the city and adjacent to a large nature reserve. A new allotment plan prepared by the municipality of Wageningen allows for the construction of 120 houses. The municipality supports De Beuk's plans under the Collective Private Commissioning policy. However, because the allotment plan has been altered, the site

cannot yet be developed. It requires multiple permits, one of the most difficult being the nature permit, which falls under provincial responsibility. At the outset, De Beuk's strategy was to address challenges by drawing on their own experience and their extensive network of specialists both within and outside the sector.

Internally, De Beuk faces the challenge of reaching agreement on ambitions and overall plans, given the heterogeneity of the five groups involved. Initially conceived as an ecovillage, the idea evolved into an eco community. Within this eco community, the ecovillage (built environment) remains central, but other elements are also included, such as community childcare, shared land stewardship, and educational, celebratory or spiritual activities (lifestyle). Members are united in their commitment to circular biobased materials, adapting to the natural environment, and adjusting their lifestyles away from consumerism and its associated housing trajectory. Yet operationalising these lifestyle choices reveals differences in preference, and participation in activities is not mandatory. To manage this diversity, De Beuk adopted an internal strategy that provides space for individual and group variation, financial equity, common spaces, and inclusive activities aimed at people with less access to living with nature—such as young people, singles, and those without property. Activities also accommodate elderly members with limited mobility. A gender balance has emerged naturally among members.

Members of De Beuk clearly wish to minimise their ecological footprint: no cars next to houses (or no cars at all), no private gardens, off grid and self supportive living. This ideology of a like minded group conflicts with municipal policy, which requires neighbourhoods to represent diverse social groups. In response, De Beuk began cooperating with the Wageningen social housing institute, enabling them to adopt important social aims of the local administration.

It soon became clear that De Beuk must solve hundreds of problems and underpin numerous technical and ecological choices. BIOTraCes supported them by organising a workshop on power in networks, offering new insights into cooperation and strengthening agency. One example is De Beuk's coalition building with other ecovillages to increase lobbying power.

Externally, a major barrier is land acquisition. The Didam Arrest, a Supreme Court ruling, requires public procurement of government property through open competition. Exemptions are possible but demand extensive preparation and carry risks. This forces De Beuk to compete with investors and developers. Their dilemma is clear: building trust with landowners such as the State Forestry Agency and investor Smink requires transparency, but openness risks losing the competition, as their nature positive ideas could be appropriated by others.

Their willingness to adapt lifestyles offers no advantage in procurement, even though their aspirations address biodiversity loss in ways mainstream developers do not. Their plan meets all legal sustainability standards and goes beyond them, aiming to integrate housing into nature. To achieve this, they keep their plan discreet while strengthening trust with landowners.

The WR team studied the Didam Arrest and explored avenues for negotiation. If De Beuk can significantly contribute to the policy aims of the landowner, the ruling might be bypassed. Such contributions could include contracts requiring residents to abstain from car use, avoid fences, and adopt practices that enhance species richness. Similar bypasses have succeeded elsewhere, for example in contracts mandating social housing.

However, landowners remain focused on maximising revenue and insist on open competition. To secure nature permits, they commissioned a master plan from an architectural firm that incorporates nature inclusion.

In consultation with WR, De Beuk developed a follow up strategy to strengthen their bargaining position. They formalised a 'gebiedscoöperatie' [area cooperation] to manage biodiversity across the terrain, enabling land acquisition as a cooperative entity. The strategy also involves engaging the innovation department of the State Forestry Organisation, which works on nature inclusion in housing development. Although formally invited only after acquisition to ensure objectivity, this plan has already fostered relations between De Beuk and the department through workshops with sectoral institutes.

Another external barrier is nitrogen deposition from construction. The province announced that no permits will be issued within 500 metres of Natura 2000 areas. Initially this seemed a showstopper, dismaying members. The WR team, having studied the policy, explained that landowners now face a problem that De Beuk could help solve. This improved their competitive position. Strategically, De Beuk is exploring pilot status, aiming for a 70% reduction in nitrogen emissions and, more importantly, recognition of a new nature typology: human inclusive nature. Together with GEN NL, the Dutch ecovillage alliance, they presented this idea on 4 October 2025 at a Cooplink symposium on collective housing.

The WR team used a more than human method, employing character cards to advocate human inclusive nature. Developed by Jay Marisca Gietzelt (2024) and adapted by WR, the cards invited participants to adopt the perspective of native species and landscapes, considering how coexistence with humans might be possible. This exercise tested the concept of human inclusive nature within a wider network not usually addressed by the sector. Should this new typology be adopted in housing and nature policy, it would represent a game changer and a significant transformation of the sector. The near future will reveal whether this becomes reality.

Natuur voor Elkaar

The programme *Natuur voor Elkaar*, executed by the province of Overijssel, deliberately aims to transform the urbanisation sector by adopting principles of nature inclusion (see also Chapter 3 in D2.5). The programme strongly believes that good examples can serve as a compass for the sector to become more nature inclusive.

Their strategy is composed of four elements:

- Stimulating the process "from thinking to action"
- Disseminating actionable knowledge
- Building diverse networks and facilitating cooperation
- Providing resources for innovative actions

An example of how principles are disseminated within the network is the Recipe for Edges project. In this initiative, spatial arrangements and provisions for the inclusion of nature in new residential areas are sketched by a landscape architect and discussed within the network. It is intended as inspiration for architects, municipal officers and project developers.

At the end of their first programming period, confronted with an anti nature atmosphere in public policy, the programme realised that “nature” alone was not sufficiently appealing. A new narrative was required. Their strategy shifted to emphasise nature for the benefit of people, for example, nature for health or for deprived communities living in environments without green structures. This can be seen as a survival strategy in a policy environment hostile to nature.

Part of this new narrative was the recognition that the programme should not focus solely on elites, as this risked gentrification. In their second period, they redirected their strategy to include low access groups in society. This was achieved by initiating and discussing good examples. One such example is ‘Straatboeren’ [Street farmers], an initiative that supports residents in social housing to improve biodiversity in their gardens. Social housing neighbourhoods, often characterised by low socio economic status and grey, tiled gardens, are particularly vulnerable to climate change impacts such as heat waves. Straatboeren works with housing organisations to create greener, climate resilient gardens. These gardens mitigate the negative effects of heat and weather extremes, while contributing to liveability, health and well being (Snep et al., 2023).

Even small improvements in biodiversity, such as in four square metre gardens, can have significant impacts, providing food and habitat connections for insects and birds (Delahay et al., 2023). Beyond construction, the initiative supports maintenance, teaching residents how to care for plants and manage water use. The project also has strong social elements: neighbours share sprouts, organise planting days, and help each other in communal gardens. An app allows residents to exchange experiences, tips and questions, strengthening neighbourhood networks and helping to combat loneliness.

The adverse attitude towards nature in national and provincial politics has created controversy. Commercial actors within the network demand rules and standards for nature inclusion to ensure a level playing field. While inclusion can benefit them reputationally, they resist additional costs that might raise house prices in the free market. The programme sees no possibility of meeting this request, pointing to the political climate that seeks to reduce regulations—especially those favouring nature.

One innovative action supported by the programme is the ranking of nature inclusion with numerical scores, enabling benchmarking and collective learning. This initiative has already been adopted by several municipalities.

When considering the overall cases of De Beuk and Natuur voor Elkaar, there are no interventions to date that can be regarded as having produced transformative change. However, innovations emerging from the margins of the sector do carry the potential to influence it. De Beuk may contribute to transformation if their new typology of nature—where humans are seen as integral to nature and prepared to adapt their lifestyles to support its flourishing, is recognised within policies and by the sector. For this to occur, the sector would need to open up to new perspectives on human–nature relationships. So far, there are no indications of such a shift.

The provincial programme Natuur voor Elkaar operates as an innovation initiative. With its focus on nature inclusion and its deployment through a public–private partnership, its objectives are primarily transitional rather than transformative. It does not seek to alter the power configuration of the sector or to expand citizen agency.

Deliverable 2.4 – Locally tested interventions

The reasons for this limited transformative impact are outlined in Table 3 below, which reviews several elements of transformative change.

Table 3. Overview of findings regarding transformative change in the work of the societal partners De Beuk and Natuur voor Elkaar

Elements of TC	De Beuk	Natuur voor Elkaar
Transformative change potential	Creating opening of the system with radical new typology of nature positivity: high potential for fundamental change in views about interrelations of humans and nature. Additional potential for other innovations from outside the sector	High potential for a moderate change in the sector to become nature inclusive.
Manageability of indirect drivers	Addresses the indirect drivers by proposing economic equity for De Beuk members, nature positive building techniques, nature positive lifestyle adjustments and different nature typology, but mostly on a voluntary basis. Living according to their standards cannot easily become part of formal institutions and governance.	Leaving the underlying drivers of biodiversity loss mostly unaddressed.
Fostering plural perspectives	De Beuk adopted an internal strategy to manage its diversity, creating space for individual and group differences, ensuring financial equity, and providing common areas and inclusive activities.	The programme's strategy focuses on persuasive examples and guiding principles, which leans towards consensus-seeking rather than actively fostering plural perspectives. They do want to reach further than 'the usual suspects'.
Empowerment of vulnerable groups	This has been adopted to a limited extend in their strategy by incorporating some space for newcomers that have acquired a status but is not the core of their strategy. Other vulnerable groups like children, women and elderly are well represented.	Indirect empowerment of those deprived of nature in their daily living environment (working for them and not with them)
Gender balance in biodiversity governance agenda	The building and construction sector is absolutely dominated by men. In De Beuk there is gender balance, women are well represented in the lead.	The building and construction sector is absolutely dominated by men. Women may be more active in innovations because they are more open towards potentially deeper relations

		with nature. This for instance is shown by the huge population Anders Wonen that wishes to live closer to nature, consisting for more than 80% of women (see chapter 7 in D2.5).
Environmental justice	<p>The Beuk contributes to environmental justice by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organizing themselves as a landscape cooperation that provides a legal entity wherein members can make equitable contributions. This makes living with nature more accessible to people with less financial means (distributional justice) 2. Making decisions sociocratically. This allows all members of the Beuk to voice their opinion until consensus is reached (participatory justice) 3. Making space for different, albeit nature positive, values to coexist in communal areas. All members can organize activities that vary from practical 'planting trees together' to spiritual 'healing trees together' (recognitional justice). <p>These aspects of environmental justice are not evident in the mainstream building sector.</p>	<p>The Straatboeren project is aiming at environmental justice. Social housing itself is a contribution to distributional justice, providing lower income households with adequate housing. Greener gardens can increase distributional justice further, as the services that they provide in terms of climate adaptation and well-being, are likely to make social housing neighbourhoods wealthier (Snep et al., 2023).</p>

2.9.3 Enablers and disruptors

In the work of both societal partners, several key enablers can be identified.

For De Beuk, the most significant enabler is their extensive network, which includes individuals with strong professional standing and specialised expertise. Support from the municipality and the province has also been crucial, particularly in funding a feasibility study. Notably, many of *De Beuk's* enablers, such as Cooplink and the Global Ecovillage Network (GEN), operate outside the conventional building sector, offering alternative perspectives and resources.

For Natuur voor Elkaar, the strength of their network is equally vital. It brings together individuals and organisations willing to challenge conventional norms. National-level opinion leaders, including CEOs of major construction firms such as Heijmans, act as influential enablers. Each progressive step towards nature inclusion within the network generates momentum for further innovation, reinforcing the programme's transformative potential.

Despite these enabling factors, the path towards bio-innovation remains fraught with challenges. Key issues include:

- **Mismatch between local biodiversity agendas and broader economic interests:** Efforts to regenerate biodiversity often conflict with prevailing trends in economic development, creating tension between ecological goals and sectoral priorities.
- **The capacity to replicate enablers:** Societal partners struggle to scale up successful strategies and extend their impact across wider territories.
- **Managing disruptors and mitigating long-term effects:** Sustaining progress requires the ability to respond to and neutralise disruptive forces—whether political, economic or social.
- **Influence of higher-level policy frameworks:** Local regeneration policies and action plans may be strengthened, undermined or delayed by national legislation or European directives—even those aimed at environmental protection.

The following sections address these key issues in more detail.

Mismatch between the local agenda on biodiversity regeneration and economic sectors' interests and trends

A possible mismatch between the agenda on biodiversity regeneration and economic sectors can take the shape of a lock-in, or of negative feedback. The sector may deploy a strategy of black boxing to elude responsibility. The mismatch may take various shapes. We will discuss them in a more general perspective to shed a light on the sector.

Rising Housing Costs, Stress and Scarcity of Time for Nature

Construction in the Netherlands is lagging. One million homes must be built, at a rate of 130,000 per year. Nature is partly blamed for delays. Building is expensive, and the houses that are completed are therefore costly (CBS, 2025). Young families struggle to find housing, and without two incomes financing is difficult (CBS, 2025). The result is a lifestyle dominated by stress and lack of free time (Roeters, Vlasblom & de Voogd-Hamelink, 2018). Leisure is reduced to passive rest in front of television or social media, leaving little time to enjoy nature. Being busy even carries prestige—commercials often open with “I have a busy schedule, and so...”. This is a lock-in that *De Beuk* seeks to overcome.

Densifying Cities, Nature Disappearing from Daily Life

New construction focuses on densification of existing urban fabric. As a result, urban nature deteriorates. Provinces in the Randstad aim for around 90% of new housing within existing urban areas, accompanied by green zones outside cities (e.g. Utrecht's *Green Grows Along* programme). This process gradually removes nature from citizens' daily lives. Visiting nature becomes a leisure activity, often crowded, reducing the quality of the experience. People increasingly substitute weekend nature visits with short holidays, unintentionally raising their ecological footprint.

Urbanisation and Project Development

Relationships between projects and nature are barely acknowledged in policy phases. The *Concept National Spatial Policy Document* (BZK, 2025) provides for one million homes without clear assessment of ecological effects. Where links are made, they focus on nitrogen emissions during construction or car use affecting Natura 2000 areas. Large projects are prioritised to meet housing deficits, while nature is treated as a detail to minimise. Small-scale, well-integrated projects are possible but often blocked by the

“business case”—a black box determining how far developers will go in adopting nature-inclusive practices.

Housing for a Materialistic Lifestyle

The housing sector is embedded in a broader discourse of economic growth. Neoliberal thinking centres on consumption (see sustainability lecture by Kees Klomp). Influencers and advertising encourage buying, shaping a standardised view of the space families need to store and display possessions. Housing is designed for consumerist lifestyles: large houses with expensive goods confer status. Construction assumes a housing career where people move towards larger, more costly homes, and most follow this trajectory.

Nature Deteriorating, Shifting Baselines

Bird and insect populations have declined dramatically over the past thirty years (Vugteveen & van Hinsberg, 2017). Younger generations, unfamiliar with past richness, accept current impoverishment as normal. This is the lock-in of shifting baselines. Behaviour also shifts baselines: unsustainable actions confer social status—travelling far, buying gold, eating large amounts of meat, maintaining perfect gardens. Living in balance with nature lowers rather than raises status.

Meaning and Nature

There is extensive knowledge about human–nature relationships, yet little of it is reflected in policy or actions of powerful actors. This concerns not only nature as environment but also its influence on health and well-being. Numerous books explore these themes, such as *Nature as a Source* (Verstegen, 2025), *Nature’s Mirror* (Schouten, 2025), *The Rebellion of Nature* (Blom, 2017) and *An Ecological Theology for the Future* (Keasberry, 2024). This abundance of literature creates restlessness, yet daily pressures prevent deeper engagement.

Bottom-Up Housing Experiments

Initiatives to live closer to nature or in a nature-positive way are proliferating. Collective approaches, such as eco-communities, offer advantages by enabling larger scales of living with nature. They also respond to rising loneliness among Dutch citizens (*Een tegen Eenzaamheid*, n.a.). Addressing loneliness while living in balance with nature is a potential leverage point. Connecting these initiatives through civil society could strengthen their impact.

Health and Nature

Knowledge of the relationship between health and nature is expanding, leading to new initiatives. This includes awareness of microorganisms as well as mental and physical well-being (van den Berg, 2024; Health Council of the Netherlands & Advisory Council for Spatial Planning, Nature and the Environment, 2004). Urban planning increasingly addresses heat stress, stimulating greening of cities. Yet this often conflicts with densification, and the net result is deterioration of urban greenery.

Capacity of replicating the enablers, broadening their impact in the territory

In the case of De Beuk, replication of enablers is currently weak. The initiative is not positioned to scale or reproduce its biodiversity innovations independently. For efforts such as De Beuk to be replicated more broadly, a supportive innovation policy is required, one that empowers initiatives emerging from the margins or outside the conventional building sector. A notable replicable innovation contributed by De Beuk is the new nature typology of *human-inclusive nature*. The Dutch Eco-Village Network acts as the thought leader of this typology, which aims to make it easier for future nature-positive communities to obtain building permits.

By contrast, *Natuur voor Elkaar* demonstrates a clearer capacity for replication. An example is the *Recipe for Margins* project, which promotes architectural innovation by reserving space for nature before housing developments are mapped out. The programme has the resources and institutional support to drive such innovations within the sector.

However, its replicability is not without limitations. The programme operates within a defined mandate and depends heavily on the willingness of network partners to adopt non-standard approaches. This reliance on persuasion and soft influence, rather than regulatory authority, constrains its ability to scale. While the potential is evident, the programme risks overstressing its boundaries and must navigate carefully to sustain momentum.

Capacity of dealing with disruptors and reducing their long-term impact

De Beuk is currently struggling to deal with disruptors in its process, largely due to financial disadvantage. A long-term scheme they plan to contribute to is the ecovillage fund initiated by the Dutch Ecovillage Network (GEN-NL). Existing ecovillages contribute to this fund once their mortgages are repaid, enabling future ecovillages to access financing more easily and at better interest rates. However, as most Dutch ecovillages are relatively new, this remains a long-term strategy with no immediate benefit for De Beuk.

By contrast, the programme *Natuur voor Elkaar* focuses on establishing good practices. Its strategy centres on positive examples that can inspire and be replicated. The programme does not directly address disruptors. In theory, disruptors could be confronted with positive examples of biodiversity balanced with housing development, but such a shift would require a change in strategy. This could jeopardise the programme's existence, as the sector might resist and withdraw cooperation. Its current theory of change is therefore firmly rooted in inspiration and persuasion.

How policies work out for regeneration

The extent to which local policies, strategies and action plans on regeneration may be reinforced, weakened or delayed by national policies or European directives, even those focused on environmental issues, will be discussed below. The policy landscape is extremely complex. One might argue that public policies themselves contain both direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss, many of which originate at European level.

- Nature is a domain in itself, and, from a policy perspective, is almost exclusively focused on nature in nature reserves
- Nature recovery and nature management are confined to nature as we know it has been, which leads to a focus on recovery and not to the uncertain and unknown outcomes of co-evolution of human activities and natural development (this could be a potential outcome of nature positivity)
- In The Netherlands, nature has been brought under the jurisdiction of the province, while schemes for the building sector originate from national level. This causes the problem that provinces might have to deal with a problem created on national level that is caused by planning new residential areas in ecologically unfortunate places. An instruction by letter has been issued by the minister of Infra saying that water and soil should be leading (Harbers & Heijnen, 2022), but altogether this is far from fixed.
- Damage to nature by human activities is perceived as unavoidable and must be compensated by extending existing or realising new nature reserves⁶
- Compensation is achieved by converting agricultural land into nature reserves, a practice that generates controversy and fosters negative attitudes towards nature protection.

⁶ https://repository.officiële-overheidspublicaties.nl/CVDR/CVDR37969/1/html/CVDR37969_1.html

- Private commercial partners and public organisations, including local and national political bodies, profit from the practice as it stands; likewise, nature management organisations benefit from the enlargement of their estates.
- Profits are highest if cheap agricultural terrain (9.3 Euro per square metre (Kadaster, 2025) is reshaped in costly residential (767 Euro per square meter, CBS (2025) and most of the profit occurs due the change of land use in the environmental plan
- Almost all problems in the housing sector are translated into building agendas for new neighbourhoods, rather than into better use of the existing housing stock.
- The entanglement of public and private partners in the sector is widely regarded as valuable cooperation (and there is truth in this), but it also produces an opaque system of relations that is closed to innovations from outside.
- The common agreement to keep house prices within certain limits is achieved through a high level of standardisation.
- Standardisation has the disadvantage that citizens who wish to live in or with nature are not addressed. In practice, only wealthy individuals can afford housing in or near nature.
- Regulation of the building sector is very high, due to national and European frameworks. This complexity creates a boundary of inclusion for those able to cope with it, but a threshold for newcomers or innovators. Coping requires resources for legal officers who can navigate the procedures.
- Innovation policies are embedded in public–private structures (such as the so-called top-sector policy), based on the belief that co-investment supports adoption. However, the policy fails to embrace transformative innovations, as the sector resists them to safeguard profit lines.
- The stance towards nature, and the focus on human–nature negativity, originates in national policies of the 1980s and 1990s. These were taken up in European policies and have since rebounded, undermining public support for decisive biodiversity measures. Public support for nature in general, however, remains strong.
- Market regulation is embedded in European policies and directives. The baseline is to maintain a level playing field and create transparency. The drawback is the opaqueness of the public–private cooperative system, essentially corporatism.

Altogether, there is not enough room and support for biodiversity innovations that have the potential to change the sector. Problems of biodiversity loss migrate from national planning schemes to the local level, under the assumption that if the right choices are made and designs are nature-inclusive, the effects of a new plan on biodiversity will be negligible. Nitrogen problems have been undervalued for centuries, as has habitat loss in the agricultural landscape. As a result, due to a shortage of workforce and the reduction in permits issued, the sector is no longer able to perform as it should. There is not enough space within environmental norms to add to existing problems. This is a perfect timing for transformative change.

2.9.4 Failed and successful practices

Success and Failure: Too Early to Judge

For De Beuk as well as for Natuur voor Elkaar, it is too early to determine success or failure. Much depends on the perspective from which one judges. Does the programme in Overijssel fulfil its promises, and should it therefore be seen as a success? From a BIOTraCes perspective, success would mean transforming the sector—contributing to pluralisation, empowering innovative actors, politicising debates and embedding practices within broader socio-ecological systems. We combine different views and reflect on success and failure from an outsider’s perspective, considering the realisation of aims, transformative change and environmental justice.

De Beuk

The story of De Beuk shows that they are struggling to realise their aims. A major obstacle is land acquisition. Regulations, limited financing opportunities and their commitment to equity create difficulties. Regulations such as the Didam Arrest, which prescribes mandatory public procurement, do not work in their favour. The upcoming tender process by the State Forestry Agency will likely be executed in two steps: first limiting candidates based on feasibility studies, experience and financial position—placing De Beuk at a disadvantage. Nitrogen restrictions have also become an obstacle due to provincial regulation. One might argue that, because the province seeks to strengthen nature protection, experiments in nature positivity cannot be attempted.

Internal controversies further complicate land acquisition. Some members favour a fully cooperative model, excluding speculation or personal profit after realisation. Others prefer personal land ownership. This division risks becoming a breaking point in their cooperation, representing a failure to put part of their ideology into practice. No solution has yet been found.

On a broader level, De Beuk includes members who have worked in Africa and elsewhere, drawing inspiration from practices of living in natural environments. This has led to a holistic ideology within a linear Dutch context. Frictions arise when worldviews clash (e.g. holistic practices versus strict protocols), but the group also provides a safe space for plural values to coexist. Members wish to engage with refugees currently living in De Dorschkamp, but the refugee centre's management forbids contact. Nevertheless, De Beuk has reserved space for newcomers with residence permits in their development plan.

A step beyond their current experiment would be to allow citizens with migrant backgrounds—bringing different human–nature relationships—to conduct their own experiments in balancing humans and nature according to their traditions or worldviews. It is striking that the system fails to recognise this potential. Dutch society is rich in diverse perspectives on nature, yet this remains unacknowledged and unused as a source of innovation.

The area De Beuk wishes to purchase is currently used to house refugees. Their plan reserves space for some refugees with permits who wish to remain in this temporary neighbourhood. This represents a small step towards environmental justice in biodiversity action. At system level, however, environmental justice from the perspective of cultural heterogeneity remains unexplored. This is both a failure and a missed opportunity. The system also fails to address the wishes of many people who would prefer smaller houses and closer contact with nature (see chapter 7 in D2.5). Instead, it assumes a standard housing trajectory—from renting to a large detached family home.

At system level, a lock-in is created by the combination of limited target groups (based on an imagined “average Dutch citizen”) and the complexity of regulatory frameworks and permits. Innovative groups must dedicate years of spare time to project development, facing numerous obstacles because the system is not open to alternative human–nature relations. Forced to compete with regular developers, ambitions to live in harmony with nature are no advantage. Those with jobs and families face severe time constraints, while the system's complexity effectively excludes people with limited time or lower education, blocking pluralisation.

De Beuk initially sought a privileged position in land acquisition by building trust with landowners and offering a plan most beneficial for natural values. This seemed logical, as the surrounding land remains under the State Forestry Department (SBB), who would be their neighbours. However, SBB refuses to expropriate De Dorschkamp in a one-to-one contract, citing the Didam Arrest and their need to achieve the highest possible market price due to budget shortfalls.

Because De Beuk relied on trust, any intervention from the Wageningen team risked undermining this. The team therefore acted with the utmost caution. Gradually, as this strategy proved ineffective, De Beuk shifted towards a more procedure-oriented approach.

Natuur voor Elkaar

Natuur voor Elkaar has been successful in community building, which is expressed in several ways. Firstly, through active digital networks such as a lively WhatsApp group that sustains informal dialogue. Secondly, via the annual conference organised by the programme, which quickly sells out and attracts around 400 participants, providing space for exchange of ideas and networking. Finally, there is an active community of practice around nature-inclusive building, where experiences and examples from the field are shared, supporting networking and peer-to-peer learning.

From this network, strong collaborations have been established with partners such as Odin and Stichting Oversticht, alongside new alliances in the health domain. Within current political currents, where parties in power do not prioritise nature, Natuur voor Elkaar demonstrates resilience. Their adaptive strategy includes shifting focus towards the relationship between health and nature. The fact that the programme continues to exist in this climate reflects its dynamic approach.

Concerning failed practices, external actors expect objectives to be translated into policy demands. The organisation refrains from doing so, raising the question of whether this represents an inability to act or a deliberate choice to avoid over-politicisation. Another failed practice is the lack of diversity in the network. Although goals have been articulated and development is ongoing, the group remains socially and demographically homogeneous.

Recent organisational developments have altered the programme's character. While embedding within institutions ensures continuity, its innovative and transformative dimension has diminished. The programme now functions more as a facilitator than as a collaborative governmental experiment, raising doubts about its capacity to drive systemic change.

2.9.5 Co-learning

As discussed above, both societal partners have established strong networks as part of their strategy. These networks serve as knowledge resources and platforms. A good example is De Beuk inviting the collective housing experiment De Warren from Amsterdam to WR for an exchange of experiences. Numerous interactions took place between the societal partner, its network and the WR team. Each obstacle encountered—such as the Didam Arrest or the nitrogen restrictions—was turned into a learning moment. Learning also occurred within De Beuk's network, even in cases where the societal partner was not directly involved. Knowledge transfer between WR, De Beuk and the programme Natuur voor Elkaar was intensive, often mediated by student assignments from Academic Consultancy Training (ACT). Workshops organised by WR (ANNEX II) provided opportunities for reflection and knowledge exchange. Members of De Beuk noted that they were so occupied with the practicalities of realising their plan that they lacked time to reflect. The same applied to Natuur voor Elkaar. The interactive workshops helped both partners step back from immediate concerns and gain perspective, which proved crucial in shaping their strategies.

When challenges arose, such as the 'Didam Arrest' or nitrogen restrictions, De Beuk was eager to understand the fundamentals of these issues and how to address them. WR was able to draw on actionable knowledge from its own network. Conversely, WR gained valuable insights for the BIOTraCes research. One of the most important lessons was how regulations and relationships with nature converged in the case, revealing that values and behaviours, often kept outside the housing sector, are highly relevant when aiming for a positive relationship with nature. De Beuk demonstrated how social, technical and ecological aspects of housing can be integrated, showing WR that separating the social from the physical act of building is shortsighted. Their plans

illustrated that a positive relationship with nature is possible, provided lifestyle adjustments are made.

For WR, another key lesson concerned group dynamics, which proved central to success or failure. Members of *De Beuk* invested significant time in workshops with dedicated tasks. Their group dynamics were based on self-organisation rather than anarchism, and learning occurred at a professional level, with solutions tailored and implementable. Differences between groups—for example, between younger and older members—remained visible, particularly in the patience shown in discussions.

Learning also emerged from a critical dilemma within *De Beuk*. Some members hold a transcendental view of nature, seeing it as a worldview requiring internalisation rather than proof. For them, facts such as species counts are less relevant; instead, they emphasise lived experience, such as the belief that healthy vegetables require healthy soil regardless of chemical standards. Others recognised the necessity of traditional ecological impact assessments to obtain permits, requiring evidence that protected species and habitats would not be harmed. Students working on ecological assignments encountered this controversy. As the dilemma cannot be resolved purely through facts, it required negotiation and discussion among members. They learned to manage these differences by taking time to deliberate and reach solutions.

For *Natuur voor Elkaar*, the concept of transformative change proved inspiring. Participation in a European project highlighted the range of options available for programme development. WR learned from the provincial partner how sensitive their work is to language. The *Natuur voor Elkaar* network provided numerous learning opportunities, as members were eager to share and absorb information across the planning and building process. This revealed the complexity of the sector and the many relationships between actors. Interestingly, there was a clear need for formal arrangements and regulations to maintain a level playing field. Common questions addressed to the programme include: “When are we doing well enough?” and “What constitutes a satisfactory level of nature inclusion?” No definitive answers exist. However, WR and BIOTraCes observed that such questions are less pressing when the focus shifts towards nature positivity.

2.9.6 Testing of interventions

An intervention aims at changing the system of relationships constituting the sector, to change business as usual. It can be about working methods, about power, about exclusion and so on. A strategy is a choice from a spectrum of possibilities of actions to be taken to achieve a specific goal. A strategy must be viewed from the perspective of innovation; An intervention should be seen as action and reaction between innovation and system. A strategy is maximally focused on a goal; an intervention can also be aimed at creating space or a favourable condition for change.

We looked at interventions, actions and strategies that the biodiversity innovations have and also what BIOTraCes contributes. There is not really a single intervention that stands out, but rather a process that was navigated. For *De Beuk* quite some difficulties presented themselves in alternation. The knowledge of WR was often called upon.

De Beuk primarily wants a different way of dealing with nature for the place where they wanted to live. In doing so, they run into a sector that works against this, because it is not in line with how the sector is organized and how the sector thinks. As such it is a secondary goal is to influence the sector, in which there is more of a strategy than that *De Beuk* can be seen as an intervention. For *Natuur voor elkaar*, it is slightly different. Here the emphasis is more on making the sector nature-inclusive and then the entire program can be seen as an intervention. Here too, it is mainly a situation of gradually developing and putting strategies into practice. The interventions we discuss are therefore usually not aimed at a total change in the sector, but at achieving their goal. The process our societal partners went through can primarily be characterized as a learning and navigating experience. Despite this characterization we will discuss testing

the innovative actions. First, we will dive into the story of De Beuk, secondly in that of Natuur voor Elkaar.

De Beuk

At the local level, De Beuk has succeeded in persuading most of the Wageningen council that their ideas for an ecovillage and eco-community would be suitable for the site. This has not been achieved through argument alone; earlier versions of the plan had already stalled at provincial level. For the municipality, the site requires careful consideration in relation to the adjacent Natura 2000 areas. The council is open to De Beuk's proposal at an abstract level and is even assisting them in securing funding for a feasibility study, which will help strengthen their position with landowners. However, the municipality does not go further. It could have purchased the land under its legal preference provision and commissioned it through its Collective Private Commissioning (CPO) policy, but this was deemed an unacceptable financial risk. Another option would have been to change the zoning plan so that only an ecovillage could be built there. A precedent exists in another municipality, but such a process would be lengthy, requiring changes to the environmental vision, the environmental plan and its regulatory framework, with no guarantee of standing up in court in the event of a formal protest.

The landowner, the State Forestry Department (SBB), although itself a national nature management organisation, is not receptive to *De Beuk's* ideas. Facing financial difficulties and budget cuts, it is primarily interested in achieving the highest possible market price. On the other hand, following a network meeting involving SBB's innovation division, colleagues expressed strong support for the plans, and subsequent appointments were scheduled.

Confronted with nitrogen challenges, De Beuk adjusted its sector intervention, though not its biodiversity innovation, by introducing a new nature typology, which they call *human-inclusive nature*. This intervention is still at an early stage and requires further development. The next step is to gain support from innovative actors in collective housing, followed by a formal request for pilot status. This will be submitted to the provincial governor or, if unsuccessful, directly to the minister. BIOTraCes has been asked to assist in developing the typology and to join the delegation to the governor. This, however, lies in the future, and there is nothing concrete to test yet.

Overall, responses from public and semi-public actors in the sector have been positive, while reactions from private actors are not yet visible. The most promising intervention with transformative potential is the concept of a novel nature typology in which humans are integrated, under the condition of nature positivity.

Natuur voor Elkaar

The programme Natuur voor Elkaar has been under development for several years. In its early phase, the focus was on activating and building a network or community, within which new forms of cooperation also emerged. Joint storytelling on nature-inclusive building and the Natuur voor Elkaar community is now seen as the next step. In this context, WR organised a workshop and exchange on ownership and shared awareness, centred on developing a collective narrative about nature-inclusive building. In later feedback, participants noted that this positively influenced cooperation, marking the beginning of a shared story and a sense of ownership, although this remains a work in progress.

When considering how the programme's ideas and plans are being transferred to the wider sector, it is clear that actors within the network are enthusiastic about including nature in new neighbourhoods. However, this enthusiasm is largely confined to those directly involved.

Each year, the province organises the symposium Congres Natuurlijk [Symposium Naturally]. In recent years, attendance has exceeded 400 participants, with waiting lists required. WR has been observing, discussing and reflecting on changes in thinking and

working practices for three consecutive years through workshops on obstacles and leverage points, the role of actors in the sector and power relations in transformative change, and on human–nature relations (e.g. *Mens in de natuur, natuur in de mens* / People in Nature and Nature in People). These workshops have tested how theories resonate with sector representatives and how discourse on these topics is evolving. While indicative, further research is needed to understand how institutions are, or are not, being taken along in the process of innovation.

New innovative practices are indeed being realised, though their influence and disruptive potential remain open to debate. Change is gradual and has not yet reached the mainstream of the sector. Private partners are willing to integrate nature more fully into their plans but call for binding regulation to ensure a level playing field. It is expected that governmental actors will eventually follow, though this will take time. At present, the request is directed at provincial authorities, but it must also be addressed at national level. The issue therefore needs to migrate from provincial to national politics.

These developments reflect a transitional process of experimenting with spatial configurations and technical adaptations that allow nature to enter human habitats. A further question is whether innovators within the network will continue their efforts once the programme ends. On this point, BIOTraCes cannot yet provide an answer, it will only become clear in the near future.

2.9.7 Discussion

Introduction of a New Nature Type

The most notable intervention introduced by De Beuk is a new nature type in which humans co-exist with nature. This typology is intended to take its place alongside existing categories used to mitigate and compensate for the impacts of construction on natural areas. It is too early to draw conclusions about the acceptance of this conceptual innovation, which would imply a fundamental shift in the urbanisation sector.

So far, De Beuk’s plans to create a habitat where humans and nature can co-develop run counter to regulations based on the assumption that human presence always has a negative impact on nature. Such impacts are considered inherent and unavoidable, and can only be mitigated or compensated. This highlights an important insight: prevailing images of nature are framed in terms of restoration, how nature is, has been, or can be, rather than how it might evolve in experimental settings alongside humans. At present, no innovation policy or framework exists to support human–nature relationship experiments, which represents a barrier to exploring the outcomes of a nature-positive society.

The new nature type developed by De Beuk clearly has transformative potential. Its implications could be far-reaching, opening new avenues for collective living experiments that bring people closer to nature. However, integrating this concept into policy could also have unforeseen effects. An *ex ante* policy evaluation would therefore be required. At present, there are no signs of acceptance.

Persisting Tensions, Barriers and Structural Forces

It may be tempting to highlight barriers that could be resolved to transform the sector into a nature-positive one. However, this would not fully reflect the praxis observed. The challenges are manifold and arise from multiple directions: time, finance, permits, complexity, know-how, institutional culture, incoherent policies between national and local levels, assumptions about human–nature relations, lack of frameworks to foster nature-positive lifestyles, a profit-driven sector with high margins, perceptions that including nature reduces profits, and the pressing societal issue of housing shortages—particularly for young people, which drives demand for standardised, large-scale housing

projects. The reliance on generic target groups also fails to engage meaningfully with nature.

These tensions coincide with biodiversity innovations such as *Natuur voor Elkaar* and *De Beuk*. Addressing them may begin with human–nature relationship innovations that encourage nature-positive lifestyles. Such approaches represent disruptive innovations—ones the sector itself would not generate. They emerge from groups operating at the margins, motivated not by profit but by values, and willing to make sacrifices to live closer to, and more harmoniously with, nature.

Dilemma of Nature Positivity

As shown above, the case of *De Beuk* is marked by normative frictions. One such friction concerns the location chosen for their plans. The site forms part of the distinctive landscape of the Wageningse Es, a garden-like patchwork once used for tobacco cultivation, and is embedded within Natura 2000 forest. Ideally, such an area would not be transformed into a residential zone.

Our discussion of *De Beuk*'s plans has been framed through action research. This does not mean that all researchers are committed to living there themselves. *De Beuk* is neither more nor less than an innovation that challenges the sector. Examining the sector through the lens of *De Beuk* provides valuable insights into its dynamics. At the same time, we have also considered *De Beuk* from the system perspective of the sector itself.

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3 – Overall Conclusions (CES - about all cases)

Building on the process described above, the conclusions presented here result from a comprehensive approach that combined dialogue between consortium partners and their societal counterparts (through focus groups, feedback workshops, and other qualitative-based approaches) with an internal co-learning process among research partners (intervention and cross-case analysis workshops). This multi-layered co-evaluation enabled the identification of common features and emerging trends, despite the diversity of contexts. These core lessons were further reinforced through collective discussions during the consortium workshop held in Hungary (May 2025) and subsequent group reflections.

As Deliverable 2.4 aims to document and reflect on locally tested interventions, the following section synthesises these lessons learned across cases, focusing on three dimensions: recurring trends, observed shortcomings, and inspiring or innovative strategies.

3.1 Common Trends Across Cases

Across case studies, the first consistent trend observed was the recurrent occupation of participatory spaces by dominant actors and familiar stakeholders. This dynamic - largely driven by time constraints, cultural barriers, geographical isolation, and the absence of targeted engagement strategies - has left out some of those most affected by environmental vulnerability, such as migrant families, Roma populations, elderly residents, and women without prior organisation, on the margins of biodiversity governance processes.

A second major trend was the persistent **gap between policy objectives and implementation**. Although many case strategies were formally aligned with national and EU objectives related to biodiversity regeneration (e.g. Farm to Fork, European Green Deal, EU forest strategy for 2030, EU Urban Agenda on Climate Adaptation), researchers repeatedly encountered procedural or administrative blockages to tackling environmental impacts and fostering biodiversity regeneration. These included procurement regulations limiting opportunities for local sourcing, alongside bureaucratic rigidity and institutional inertia. As a result, many interventions struggled to scale or become institutionalised.

Building on this policy–implementation gap, a third trend highlights the **recurring procedural obstacles** that reflect deeper systemic issues and obstruct the scaling and integration of local initiatives. Greater awareness among policy makers of how everyday barriers affect the scalability of biodiversity regenerative initiatives is urgently needed. The cases analysed reveal a persistent gap between major policies in key sectors and locally rooted strategies for biodiversity regeneration. These broad policy frameworks related to high-impact sectors often adopt a one-size-fits-all approach that overlooks contextual diversity and may, in some geographical areas, promote environmentally harmful practices. While regenerative policies have the potential to inspire innovative local initiatives, the lack of formal guidance and verification mechanisms within national or EU frameworks can hinder the scalability of such efforts. Strengthening political support for context-sensitive local strategies - especially those aligned with European climate goals - is therefore essential.

Furthermore, the fragmentation between ecological and social goals emerged as another recurring tendency. In several cases, it proved difficult to integrate biodiversity goals with pressing social needs. Some projects risked drifting toward either overly technical environmental measures or abstract social empowerment narratives, without successfully bridging the two. However, it is important to note that the challenge is not merely about integration. Structural lock-ins persist where dominant sectors - such as agriculture, forestry, urbanisation, and aquatic resources, to name but a few - continue to operate according to their own agendas and rhythms. Rather than adapting to the principles of ecological regeneration, these sectors often reshape the regenerative agenda to serve pre-existing institutional or economic priorities. This results in the rhetorical appropriation of biodiversity language without substantive changes to practice.

For example, funding criteria in programs like the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) continue to prioritize large-scale operations with the ability to absorb risk, thereby sidelining experimental or community-based initiatives that operate with different timeframes and objectives.

It is therefore crucial that Member States and national policy-makers take a proactive role in stimulating new financing systems that recognise and reward qualitative contributions to regeneration. Without this, public support mechanisms will continue to reinforce conventional, high-input, scalable models at the expense of transformative local practices. The persistence of these structural barriers not only limits innovation but also reproduces socio-economic and ecological inequalities, undermining the objectives of regenerative transition.

Taken together, these cross-case trends reveal that the obstacles to transformation are not merely operational or sectoral, but systemic. They expose the fragility of regenerative efforts when institutional support, recognition, and time are lacking. It is within this context that the main shortcomings identified across cases must be understood — not as isolated failures, but as expressions of the broader structural conditions shaping the possibilities for change.

3.2 Key Shortcomings and Limitations

Across cases, several limitations revealed how deeply entrenched institutional and cultural patterns continue to shape the conditions under which regenerative governance unfolds. Although not all cases reflected this tendency, a shared pattern emerged: the **persistence of rigid administrative logics and accountability systems** that privilege efficiency and economic performance over collaboration, learning, and care for ecological and social relations. This institutional culture often constrained experimentation, particularly when local initiatives sought to introduce forms of decision-making or economic organisation that fell outside conventional policy frameworks.

Decision-making processes in public institutions also remain largely centralised and opaque. While policies increasingly invoke participation and co-production, the space for these practices to influence real decisions remains narrow. In many contexts, procedures for consultation coexist with limited downward accountability and little capacity to integrate community-led initiatives into longer-term strategies. As a result, **regeneration tends to be treated as a technical agenda rather than a political and relational process**, leaving little room for collective agency.

A recurrent limitation concerns participation itself. Despite numerous efforts to broaden involvement, the terms of **engagement often reproduced existing hierarchies**. Explanations based solely on resource or time constraints obscure the deeper problem of recognition: the reluctance or inability of institutions to acknowledge underrepresented actors as legitimate co-authors of change. This lack of recognition undermines trust and weakens the transformative potential of local strategies, especially when engagement is confined to short project cycles rather than sustained collaboration.

The **social dimensions of biodiversity governance remain similarly underdeveloped**. Environmental goals are frequently pursued in isolation from issues of inequality, power, and representation. Without addressing these dimensions, regenerative practices risk reproducing exclusionary dynamics instead of challenging the social, political, and cultural lock-ins that sustain ecological degradation.

Gender and intersectionality remain marginal in both analysis and practice. In several cases, gender was perceived as an external requirement linked to EU agendas rather than as a locally relevant concern. Women's and minorities' contributions to biodiversity regeneration were often undervalued, and intersectional perspectives were seldom applied to examine how social inequalities shape environmental impacts. Besides, the persistent lack of gender-sensitive data further undermines visibility and accountability, limiting the integration of gender equity and justice goals within regenerative strategies, as required by the ERA R&I framework.

Community-led initiatives, though recognised as essential for transformative governance, remain fragile. Their heavy dependence on project-based funding and voluntary work limits their capacity to consolidate and scale. This fragility exposes the broader absence of stable institutional frameworks capable of sustaining experimentation over time. Researchers also expressed concern about their limited ability to influence systemic change in isolation, underscoring the need for collective advocacy, alliance-building, and the strengthening of interfaces between research, policy, and practice.

Overall, these shortcomings highlight that transformative potential cannot be separated from institutional reform and cultural change. Without deeper shifts in how legitimacy, expertise, and participation are conceived, regeneration risks remaining a peripheral discourse rather than a shared project.

3.3 Innovative and Inspiring Strategies

Despite the structural constraints identified above, several strategies across cases illustrated how transformative practice can begin to take root even within restrictive governance contexts. While the scale and maturity of these experiences vary, they demonstrate that change is possible through incremental, relational, and context-sensitive processes that rebuild trust, expand collaboration, and reframe how knowledge and value are produced.

One of the most significant tendencies was the emergence of **co-governance arrangements** that sought to distribute responsibility and decision-making more evenly among institutions, civil-society organisations, and community actors. These partnerships, though fragile, have begun to question established hierarchies through the introduction of shared agendas and accountability mechanisms. They illustrate an

ongoing cultural shift towards more horizontal, trust-based, and dialogical approaches to public action.

A second area of innovation concerns **creative and inclusive forms of engagement**. Multiple cases highlighted the value of creative engagement strategies - such as participatory festivals, school gardens, artistic workshops, or cross-generational exchanges - to open space for alternative imaginaries and symbolic shifts. These actions were not only instrumental but discursive: they helped reframe regeneration as a shared, meaningful, and locally rooted goal. In this sense, participatory formats moved beyond consultation to collective meaning-making by using narrative, artistic, or experiential methods to dialogue with groups that are often distant from formal institutions. Such approaches have proven valuable not only for expanding participation, but also for recognising diverse ways of knowing and feeling about ecological change.

Strengthening social cohesion and collective learning emerged as a concern in the majority of the cases, proving to be a key element for mindset change. Many initiatives treated cohesion not merely as a by-product of participation but as a precondition for systemic change. Processes that cultivate trust, mutual recognition, and care — from neighbourhood dialogues to intergenerational learning — were seen as vital for embedding regeneration within local cultures and imaginaries.

Translocal collaboration and mutual learning networks have also shown potential. Connections between territories facing similar challenges have supported the exchange of practices, co-design of strategies, and emergence of solidarity-based alliances that transcend administrative boundaries. These horizontal linkages are helping to transform isolated experiments into shared processes of learning and advocacy.

Discussions during the consortium process also brought forward the **proposal of a basic income** as an enabler of inclusive participation reflected a growing recognition that time and material stability are prerequisites for equitable engagement. Although not implemented, the idea revealed a broader political awareness of the need to address indirect drivers of biodiversity loss, such as economic precarity and systemic exclusion. The idea reflected a growing awareness that regeneration requires not only ecological and technical innovation but also new social contracts that value time, care, and civic contribution.

Finally, many partners reflected on their own evolving roles as **transformative researchers**. The growing awareness of research as an active and situated practice — one that blends facilitation, co-learning, and strategic engagement — has deepened the project's collective understanding of how knowledge can serve as a vehicle for systemic change.

Taken together, these strategies point to an emerging landscape of experimentation in regenerative governance. They may not yet represent consolidated transformations, but they embody essential movements: from control to collaboration, from extraction to care, and from isolated action to shared responsibility.

3.4 Reflections on Testing as Transformation

The workshop Development and Testing of Interventions, in Hungary, during Biotraces Consortium Meeting, along with its follow-up reflections reinforced a central insight of

Deliverable 2.4 – Locally tested interventions

Deliverable 2.4: intervention is not a fixed action, but a living, relational, and evolving process. What was tested in each case was not merely a method or a tool, but a possibility - a different way of relating to land, policy, knowledge, and one another. The limits encountered in these processes - of scale, inclusion, and political complexity - are not signs of failure, but reflections of the reality of working within complex and unequal systems.

Ultimately, the discussions validated the importance of grounded, iterative, and politically conscious experimentation as the foundation for systemic transformation. While none of the strategies offered a ready-made solution to biodiversity loss, each revealed a fragment of a broader mosaic: the cultural, procedural, and institutional conditions necessary for a just and plural transition toward nature-positive societies.